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Synthesis report on Agroecological Value Chains in North Africa

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Full form
%	Percentage
°C	Degrees Celsius
AE	Agroecology / agroecological
AE VCs	Agroecological value chains
AEP	Agroecological practices
AMAD	Mauritanian Association for Self-Development
ANPMA	National Agency for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Morocco
ANSADE	National Agency for Statistics and Demographic and Economic Analysis, Mauritania
AVC	Agri-food value chains
CARI	Centre D'Actions et de Realisations Internationales
CC	Climatic Change
CCA	Agricultural Advisory Centre, Morocco
CIHEAM-IAMM	International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies - Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Montpellier
CRDA	Regional Agricultural Development Commission, Tunisia
CREAD	Centre De Recherche en Economie Appliquee pour le Developpement
DA	Algerian Dinar
DPA	Provincial Directorate of Agriculture, Morocco
DRA	Regional Directorate of Agriculture, Morocco
ECODEV	NGO School of Local Development in Mauritania
EIG	Economic Interest Groupings
ENAM	Ecole Nationale D'agriculture de Meknes
ENSAA	National School of Agriculture of Algiers
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FNRDA	National Fund for Agricultural Regulation and Development, Algeria
GAP	Good Agricultural Practices
GDP	Gross domestic product
GRDR	Research and Achievements Group for Rural Development
GRET	Research and Technology Exchange Group, Mauritania
h	Hours

Ha	Hectare is equivalent to 10,000m ²
HLPE	High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition
ICA	International Cooperative Alliance
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development
INAT	Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie
IT	Information Technology
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
Km	Kilometres
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
LL	Living Lab
MAD	Moroccan Dirham
MAEPSP	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Promotion of Productive Sectors, Mauritania
MALR	Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation, Egypt
MAP	Medicinal and aromatic plants
MASA	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, Mauritania
MDR	Ministry of Rural Development, Mauritania
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
ml	Millilitres
mm	Millimetres
MPI	Multidimensional Poverty Indices
MRU	Mauritanian currency, (Mauritanian ouguiya)
MSMEs	Micro, small, and medium enterprises
NA	North Africa/ North African
NADP	National Agricultural Development Plan, Mauritania
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NOO	National Office of Oil, Tunisia
ONCA	National Office of Agricultural Advisory, Morocco
ONSSA	National Office for Food Safety, Morocco
OPA	Professional Agricultural Organizations
PA2-SCAPP	Second Action Plan (2021-2025) of the Strategy for Accelerated Growth and Shared Prosperity, Mauritania
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PGI	Protected Geographical Indications
PGS	Participatory Guarantee System

PNDAR	National Agricultural and Rural Development Plan, Algeria
PNO	National Olive Oil Plan, Algeria
Q	Quintal; unit of mass usually defined as 100 base units, such as kilograms
REB	Responsible Environmental Behaviour
RGPH	Global population and housing census, Mauritania
RIAM	Network of Agroecological Initiatives in Morocco
RIM	Islamic Republic of Mauritania
SA	Social Acceptability
SADS	Sustainable Agricultural Development Strategy, Egypt
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SDOQ	Distinctive Signs of Origin and Quality, Morocco
SIAM	International Agricultural Show in Morocco
SMDZ	Skoura M'Daz, Boulemane, Morocco
SOR	Stimulus Organism Response model
ToR	Terms of Reference
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
UAA	Utilised agricultural land
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UTAP	Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fishing
VBFC	Values-based food chains
VBSC	Value-Based Supply Chain
VC	Value Chain
WTP	Willingness To Pay

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been developed as part of the NATAE project (Fostering Agroecology Transition in North Africa through Multi-Actor Evaluation and Networking), a four-year initiative (2022-2026) aimed at advancing the agroecological transition in North Africa. It falls specifically under Work Package 3:

- Task 3.2, which focuses on evaluating and strengthening the integration of agroecological value chains. This task is led by the Project Coordinator, the CIHEAM-IAMM, under the Work Package Leader, the UTH, in collaboration with each of the Living Lab Leaders including the CARI, CREAD, GRDR, ENAM, and INAT, and one external expert from Egypt.
- Task 3.1, which focuses on consumers behaviour, perceptions of agroecology and Willingness to Pay for agroecological products in the region. This task is led by UTH, the WP3 leader, based on data collection from other project partners in each country: CREAD (Algeria), INAT (Tunisia), CIHEAM-IAMM (Egypt), GRDR (Mauritania) and IAV (Morocco).
- Task 3.3, on the social acceptability of agroecological practices combinations. This task is led by an international team of Egyptian expert under the coordination of project coordinator, the CIHEAM-IAMM. Under this task so far, after the selection of the team of experts, a methodological framework was prepared for 5 out of the 7 LLs in four countries: Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco and Tunisia. For Algeria, a PhD is being carried on in the two Algerian LLs. Training sessions on the social acceptability methodology are currently being conducted for the Living Labs¹. Fieldwork is underway, and findings will be released in a follow-up report, slated for November 2025.
- Under Task 3.4 "Value Chain Impact Assessment", so far, a modelling module has been created and the needed quantitative data have also been collected. The work is ongoing to perform value chain impact assessment. However, there is no available results yet.

This report offers a detailed presentation of currently available results of WP3, "Evaluating and fostering the integration of agroecology in multi-scale food systems" regarding task 3.1, "Consumer demand assessment and strengthening" 3.2, "Evaluating and strengthening the integration of AE value chains" and presents the methodology developed for task 3.3, "Assessing social acceptability of AEP combination by producers and producer networks". Conducted over seven Living Labs (LLs) in Algeria, Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco, and Tunisia, the study captures the diversity of agroecosystems, local dynamics, and socio-economic settings in the region and focus on the

¹¹ Egypt in September 2024, Mauritania and Tunisia in February 2025, and Morocco planned for April 2025. For Algeria, a Phd candidate will be handling the social acceptability component.

productions and products that are most beneficial to the producers of the project LLs. It presents a thorough examination of the present and potential of agroecological value chains (AE VCs) in North Africa, including the consumers perspective and is structured as follows: (i) value chain analysis (part 1), (ii) consumer behaviour study (part 2), and (iii) the methodology for the evaluation of social acceptability of agroecological practices combinations (part 3). Social acceptability is core to the future of agroecology, informing on the perceptions and attitude of producers towards agroecological practices. Results from LLs specific surveys will be presented in another deliverable “Second survey results from farm and stakeholder surveys” (T4.7, November 2025).

This overall study seeks to help agroecological transitions to move forward by means of a deeper knowledge of the enabling and limiting elements affecting producers, markets, communities and consumers. The work is based on both comprehensive qualitative fieldwork and quantitative surveys to explore how small-scale producers participate in markets, what challenges they face (qualitative analysis) and how consumers view agroecological products (quantitative analysis). It further sets the stage for examining the social acceptability of the agroecological transitions (qualitative questionnaires), which remain an ongoing research agenda. Fieldwork is underway, and findings will be released in a follow-up report, slated for November 2025. This report will integrate and combine the different findings that are presented in the following pages.

Regarding the results, the value chain analysis reveals that agroecological practices are finding their way into diverse territories and value chains, in particular olive oil, dates, medicinal and aromatic plants, cereals, tomatoes, onions, mint and turnips. Many producers know of more sustainable agricultural practices and, in some cases, thrust them into application but structural and economic barriers limit their ability to fully transition. The majority of small-scale farmers do not have direct market access and are not part of strong collective organizations, such as cooperatives. Where cooperatives exist, they tend to be weak or dormant. However, there are encouraging signs of organized groups, especially amongst women producers in MAP value chains, where social and economic impacts are already visible.

Producers' ability to profit from added-value markets is further reduced due to residence insecurity and limited access to certifying systems affordable for local production. Few people know about alternatives like Participatory Guarantee Systems (PGS), which provide a more community-based approach to quality assurance. In some territories, traditional knowledge and agroecological practices are being implemented, but these are not always enshrined in public policy or extension services.

Regarding the behaviour and preferences of consumers, people are generally open to agroecological products, especially those perceived to be healthier or linked to local traditions, according to the results. However, awareness of what “agroecology” means is low and price is a key determinant when making purchasing decisions. Consumers often depend on trust in purchasing

food, especially local markets and souks, where face-to-face relationships matter more than formal labels. Such a trust system works for very small-scale and very short food supply chains; however, this system of trust does not help producers reach broader or more formal markets.

Both value chain studies and consumer behaviour surveys in the five North African countries reveal common problems in the recognition and implementation of agroecological practices. At the same time, however, the great potential and prospects for the development of agroecological food systems are also evident, resulting from the growing awareness of consumers about sustainability and environmental protection.

Although the women's projects in MAPs show encouraging examples of local organization, the value chains for dates, olive oil and medicinal plants in Algeria show significant dependence on intermediaries and weak cooperative structures. In the case of Egypt, consumers show a growing interest in agroecological practices and a general desire to purchase such products despite their low awareness of the benefits. Producers, especially in the case of tomatoes and MAPs, have significant constraints and limitations related to market access and high dependence on inputs.

Small-scale onion and turnip producers in Mauritania suffer from market isolation and inadequate infrastructure. Mauritanian consumers in turn show a growing interest in agroecological practices and especially those with a higher level of education and a satisfactory income are willing to pay more money to purchase them. Although land fragmentation and poor coordination among producers is a constrain for producers, value chains for olive oil, onions, mint and MAP in Morocco show more agroecological potential as a result of traditional methods and strong cultural ties to local foods.

This is in line with consumer needs in the country, where consumers are increasingly interested in agroecological and locally produced foods. Although consumer demand for local and quality products is growing, Tunisia's cereal and olive oil chains reflect comparable problems with low-value markets.

In conclusion, the results indicate that agroecological value chains are feasible in North Africa and first signs of their emerging are noticeable, but require further assistance. These include strengthening producer organizations, improving access to knowledge and technical support, building trust-based market systems, and recognizing women's contributions. In parallel, consumer education and policy incentives are needed to increase demand and support for agroecological products.

Although knowledge of agroecological methods and certification is still poor, people in all North African nations trust locally produced, familiar food products. More than official eco-labels, trust, tradition and price sensitivity still influence purchasing choices.

PART 1

Transversal and country analysis of potential agroecological value chains in North Africa

CIHEAM IAMM (Coordination), in collaboration with CARI, CREAD, GRDR, ENAM, and INAT

PART 1. TRANSVERSAL AND COUNTRY ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL AGROECOLOGICAL VALUE CHAINS IN NORTH AFRICA

Part 1 Summary

This deliverable of the NATAE project represents an overall analysis on the capacity of engaging in agroecological value chains in seven territories distributed in five countries in North Africa. It was developed by the project coordinator – task leader and local partners in Algeria, Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco and Tunisia. Two value chains were selected per territory dates, olive oil, medicinal and aromatic plants, tomatoes, onions, turnips, and mint. Primary data collection and analysis were performed in accordance to questionnaires and an outline provided by the task leader, after which the transversal analysis was developed. Chapters 1 and 2 provide a general background on agroecological value chains in literature, explanation of the methodology, and an overview of the context in North African countries' agricultural profiles and key drivers. Chapter 3 consists of the transversal analysis which synthesises the main results observed from the different value chains analysed in the seven territories. This analysis first presents general observations on land tenure and socio-economic conditions observed and then is divided between upstream provisions and primary production trends to downstream characteristics of logistics, processing and market access in addition to observations on collective action, enabling environment, and gender dynamics. This chapter finally describes the main barriers and opportunities to the construction of agroecological value chains in the territories and the overall transversal potential for their emergence. Finally, Chapters 4 to 10 include the detailed reports of every analysed territory and value chain in the study as provided by the local partners.

In brief, main observations show multiple dynamics, challenges and emerging opportunities that could help shape the future of transition towards more agroecological food systems in the region. First, a clear predominance of vertical rather than horizontal linkages exist between actors, highlighting an overall underdeveloped collective action at primary production which could hold important benefits in consolidating effort, reducing cost, and improving bargaining power of producers through bodies as cooperatives. Yet, although collective collaboration remains limited, certain women-centric initiatives are seen to provide interesting solutions and to integrate women in leadership roles. These include efforts in facilitating access resources, value addition, markets, and in some cases to land which raises interest given women's weak access to property rights generally over North Africa mainly due to legislative gaps and socio-cultural norms. Such dynamics are demonstrated in the medicinal and aromatic plants, highlighting the potential of such a value chain on

the socio-economic level and in local short circuits. Despite such successes and despite the importance of women in the agrifood value chains in the majority of countries, their most common roles remain as low-skilled labour force lacking leadership of decision-making powers. Probably a direct result of underdeveloped horizontal collaboration is the fact that generally, small producers are seen to rely heavily on intermediaries in their seeking of market access. The dominance of middlemen often results in producers selling entire harvests at fixed prices below market value undermining profitability in return for guaranteed sales and in some cases, access to working capital and inputs. Only few exceptions exist where short circuit production to consumption exists and are based on trust for the available, but rather limited, quantities. In fact, direct producer-consumer exchange points exist around North Africa such as in weekly *souks* and open markets but are yet to provide adequate scale as they are unable to accommodate large production volumes; therefore, providing only a partial sales venue. In such short circuit arenas, certification is not seen to bring in any particular added value given the trust-based system of local consumption. However, even in the case of larger expanded markets, primary producers today showcase varying levels of understanding of the benefits that formal certification could bring and remain for the most part unaffordable by the majority of small producers. An interesting alternative of the Participatory Guarantee System exists which, even if currently not recognized by the state, mobilizes various local producers and consumers in its application therefore bringing a 'community' factor to the approach of possible certification.

Overall, the development of agroecological value chains in North Africa should be considered as requiring a systemic and multi-actor approach. Essential elements that could strongly contribute to their emergence include the enhancing of information and awareness-building to producers and consumers in order to simultaneously drive demand and supply, equipping producers with knowledge, skills and means in sustainable practices, and reinforcing self-organization capacities to push for consolidation of efforts and resources and therefore attaining a better ownership of the agroecological transition especially for small producers. Creating an enabling environment that prioritizes women and gender equity, especially in policy and credit, is equally essential is building potential agroecological local food systems while benefiting from indigenous production methods and preserving local culinary heritage.

Chapter 1

Introduction and Context

Iciar Pavez and Rita Jalkh (CIHEAM-IAMM)

Chapter 1. Introduction and Context

1.1 Overview of agroecology and agroecological value chain analysis in literature

Agroecology is a holistic, multidisciplinary, and multidimensional concept that integrates the entire food system from farm to fork through environmental, ecological, and social interactions (Requier-Desjardins, Boughamoura & Lemaître-Curri, 2024). It is represented in the fourth level of the agroecological transition (Gliessman and Rosemeyer, 2007), in which producers and consumers are connected. This concept extends beyond the farm, encompassing agroecological value chains, local value chains including organic agriculture aimed at both national and export markets.

Several principles of agroecology are critical to value chains, as outlined by the HLPE (High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition) and FAO (2018). These include connectivity (strengthening trust and proximity between producers and consumers through fair trade), justice (ensuring fair livelihoods for all actors, especially smallholder farmers), participation (promoting decentralized governance and local management), diversification (encouraging income diversification for financial independence), co-creation (fostering collaboration between farmers and experts for local innovation), and social values and diets (supporting food systems that respect cultural traditions, promote equity, and provide healthy, culturally appropriate diets) (Requier-Desjardins et al., 2024).

The adoption of agroecological principles varies among actors in a value chain (Charry et al., 2023). For example, at the production level, agroecological practices such as recycling and input reduction, soil health improvement, biodiversity enhancement, and the integration of crops and livestock are emphasized (Bezner et al. 2022). These practices can contribute to nutrient cycling, reduced reliance on external inputs, and enhanced ecosystem services (Van der Ploeg et al., 2019; Lefèvre et al 2020). The choice of cultivars in agroecological systems can prioritize genetic resistance and adaptation to local conditions (Lefèvre et al 2020).

Literature identifies different types of agroecological value chains for products recognized as agroecological. These often involve short supply chains (2 to 3 intermediaries), even in export markets (Loconto et al., 2018). Nested market networks (Information-rich, Diversified market networks; Interactive and Sociocultural market networks), facilitated by intermediaries ensuring the recognition of agroecological value (Loconto et al. 2018). In the same vein, the Values-based food chains (VBFCs) and medium-scale values-based food chains (VBFCs) as mechanisms for the creation of conditions for scaling up agroecological production by bringing together like-minded partners along the supply chain, grounded in shared non-economic values such as small-scale and agroecological production systems (Van der Ploeg et al., 2019). Participatory Guarantee Systems (PGS) represent

an innovative certification approach in short value chains, involving a network of farmers, experts, and consumers (Matt, 2023; Loconto et al. 2018; Bottazzi & Boillat, 2021; Bezner et al., 2021). Requier-Desjardins (*et al.*, 2024) characterized 88 agroecology projects in North Africa, in diverse ecosystems (mountains, oases, and peri-urban areas), focusing on local, national and organic export-oriented value chains, among these projects, they describe a specific PGS project in Morocco.

Various agroecological value chain analyses conducted in different Agroecological Living Landscapes (ALL) of CGIAR's Agroecology Initiative, that analyse 10 value chains in subregions from 6 countries, and thus capture a wide range of political, agroecological, socioeconomic and cultural conditions: a dairy value chain in Burkina Faso; a groundnut value chain in India; mango and green leafy vegetables value chains in Kenya (Charry et al., 2023); Green leafy vegetables and African leafy vegetables such as African nightshade, amaranth, cowpea, among others produced in Kenya for both commercial (local and international markets) and subsistence purposes have recently gained popularity because of their significance in terms of nutritional and food security, income generation, and medicinal value (Onyango et al., 2023).

Swinnen, Ronchi, and Reardon (2024) focus on the role of agrifood value chains (AVCs) in enabling climate-smart agricultural practices. They argue that despite the fragmented nature of the farm sector, AVCs present opportunities to address challenges farmers face in accessing technologies, management practices, and financial resources for climate adaptation. AVC firms, motivated by their business needs, have inherent incentives to encourage climate-smart practices, such as offering loans for irrigation or working with farmers to reduce water usage, among other practices. The authors highlight the importance of the often-overlooked role of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), especially in the Global South. The authors stress the importance of domestic markets, as most agricultural output in the Global South is sold locally, and suggest that policies should account for the structure and incentives within AVCs to promote climate-smart agriculture.

These studies highlight several challenges that the agroecological value chains face. These include complying with food value chain specifications, such as marketing standards and regulations (Lefèvre et al., 2020), managing pests and diseases without relying on chemical pesticides (Onyango et al., 2023), and overcoming obstacles in market access, logistics, and consumer awareness (Loconto et al., 2018). Additionally, producers may struggle with higher production costs not matched by price increases and the expenses related to organic certification (Charry et al., 2023; Loconto et al., 2018; van Zutphen et al., 2022; Matt, (2023).

However, there are also opportunities within agroecological value chains. The integration of livestock and crop systems can improve nutrient cycling and reduce reliance on external inputs (Charry et al., 2023). Advancements in technologies and practices can add value to agroecological products, while market development, policy support, and a focus on nutrition-sensitive value chains can expand

opportunities for agroecological products. Moreover, these value chains can promote social equity, empower small-scale farmers, and improve food security and nutrition (Onyango et al., 2023), and leveraging a broader toolkit of AVC firms, such as private standards, resource provision contracts, and price premiums, to support climate goals (Swinnen et al., 2024).

A critical role for science and innovation exists in creating affordable smart technologies and fostering collaboration between research institutions and AVC firms. Policy incentives that enable private sector investment, regulate for climate accountability, and repurpose agricultural subsidies to support climate resilience in agriculture (Swinnen et al., 2024), improving market access and development, developing alternative marketing channels, enhancing logistics and consumer awareness, and providing financial resources (Loconto et al., 2018). Requier-Desjardins et al. (2024) conclude that in North Africa, agroecological transitions are occurring across various agrosystems, with collective action supporting diverse agroecology practices at territorial and value chain levels. Civil society organizations play a key role in addressing social aspects like equity and recognizing family farming in the implementation of agroecology.

1.2 Agriculture in the environmental, social and economic profiles in North Africa

North Africa constitutes a major food producer both at global and especially as regional scale given the diversity of agrosystems and climates. The importance of agricultural production is generally reflected by the contribution to national Gross Domestic Product (GDPs) and employment percentages of its various countries. With varying levels between countries, these usually surpasses those of the European Union². Agriculture's GDP contributions ranged from 10% to 15% between 2017 and 2022 and employment levels between 14% and 35% for each of Algeria, Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco and Tunisia according to FAO's Statistical World Book (2022). Main productions registered in the region usually include cash crops such as cotton and tomatoes from Egypt, cereal productions as wheat and barley supplying almost 60% of Northwest Africa from Morocco, olive oil to global (mainly European) exports mainly originating from Morocco and Tunisia, and others (Belmahi *et al.*, 2023, FAOSTAT, EUAGRI, 2025, CAPMAS, 2021). In fact, the agricultural sector was reported to increase significantly in North Africa between the years 1999 and 2019 registering an increase of 80% in agricultural output and a growth of US\$110 billion in 2019, making it Africa's second most significant agricultural region (ISS African Futures, 2023). Multiple reasons have influenced such growth period including, but not limited to, policy reform, international cooperation efforts, initiatives combating desertification, introduction of technologies and investments in the sector and its infrastructure. Yet, family small-scale farming is still highly predominant in North Africa. Even if their contribution is low in industrial crops, they produce up to 80% of the production of certain annual and perennial crops

² Records on average reaching 1.6% of GDP

and take up to 75 to 85% of agricultural land holdings (Marzin *et al.*, 2017; Requier-Desjardins *et al.*, 2024).

Yet, despite this growth, the region today faces serious challenges especially at the environmental and socio-economic aspects. North Africa is a region characterized by a dominance of arid and semi-arid climate, low levels of precipitation and high temperatures. In addition, the region registers a limited surface area of arable land compared to other parts of the world, and the proportion is particularly small in countries such as Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia representing less than 3.5% of the total area. Rainfed farming therefore predominates in the region with the exception of Egypt where irrigated agriculture is mostly adopted given the Nile River supply (Abdelhedi and Zouari, 2018). The difficult environmental conditions of North Africa have been greatly exacerbated by climate change and climatic shocks recently leading to some severe episodes of drought, water scarcity, soil salinization and desertification (UNCCD, 2024, IPCC, 2019). The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) in fact were alerted to home 12 out of the 17 countries globally labelled as facing “extremely high” water stress by the World Resources Institute in 2019 and linking that scarcity to a contribution to conflict and migration (WRI, 2019). In fact, the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) declared in 2024 that there is a 75% decline of water availability on the MENA region since the 1950s (UNCCD, 2024). With a majority of rainfed cultivations found in the region, such environmental conditions have only worsened and producers find themselves under growing disparities. In addition, unsustainable farming practices and conventional intensive production continue to this day and add to the growing long-term sustainability threats in the region and especially at the environmental, social and economic challenges. Examples range from the over-use of chemical inputs especially since the 1960s with the onset of the Green Revolution (significantly in countries as Egypt), to other more common issues such as the overexploitation of groundwater and unsustainable use of water resources, monoculture conventional farming that decrease biodiversity and soil fertility, to deforestation and overgrazing that increase land degradation. In fact, desertification and soil degradation remain today a serious problem in many North African countries (Ziadat *et al.*, 2022). At the same time, North Africa today is an import-dependent region which faces growing threats of food insecurity amongst a social context characterized by a rapid population growth and high levels of poverty. The population almost tripled within the last 6 decades in the MENA region with a corresponding increase in food dependency from 10% to 40% of kilocalories within almost the same period of time (Le Mouël *et al.*, 2023). The largest dependency so far in the region constitutes on cereals and staple foods. Significant wheat imports are registered for almost all countries in North Africa to meet domestic needs, sourced from various countries as Ukraine, Russia, France and Italy; and with Egypt being in fact the largest wheat importer in the world. It is therefore of no surprise that global instabilities such as the conflict in Ukraine has had implications on the food systems of such

food- and wheat-dependent states, reflected by increasing food prices, affecting access to inputs, and affecting local production capabilities (Ben Hassen and El Bilali, 2024).

In parallel, overall poverty generally, and rural poverty specifically persist in North African countries. According to the latest Multidimensional Poverty Indices (MPI)³ in 2024, registered rates range between a minimum of 1% and 1.4% national averages in Tunisia and Algeria, increasing to 5.2% and 6.4% in Egypt and Morocco, and a reaching up to 58.4% in Mauritania. However, what is certain is that poverty disparities are not the same in urban versus rural regions around North Africa. In fact, rural poverty almost doubles that of their urban counterparts, and sometimes more, with the most vulnerable groups being women, the landless, and agricultural workers⁴. In addition, women in North Africa play an important but unofficial role in agriculture. Their role remains today mostly informal and not in any leadership or decision-making positions but is limited to unskilled manual work related to cultivation, harvesting and post-harvest processing mostly. Figures show that, regionally, the percentage of women as labour force in the sector increased from 26% to 32% between the years 1990 and 2018, attaining a proportion of 40% women employed in agriculture in North Africa in 2017 compared to less than 30% for men (Benabdallah *et al.*, 2020). In the latest statistics, Morocco and Mauritania rank first in women employment in the agricultural sector (49.9% and 30.6%), followed by Egypt (19.5%) and Tunisia (10.4%), and with the least proportions registered in Algeria (3.4%). Despite having registered employment in the sector of agriculture, women in North Africa usually attain significantly less employment in other sectors such as the industry. With the exception of Algeria and Tunisia, other North African countries registered two to three times less the proportion of women employment in industrial sectors compared to agriculture. In fact, the work of women in North Africa like many around the world but particularly in the MENA, are regarded to have domestic caretaking responsibilities for their households, making quantification of their workload and workforce quite difficult (Bouzidi *et al.*, 2011). This becomes especially true for agricultural families where women could partake in farming activities directly and/or indirectly without any formal registration of that work nor any form of remuneration. With additional layers of cultural and societal norms, women in North Africa are still marginalized when it comes to their official integration in the agricultural economic cycle. This issue remains particularly clear in women's access to land right, where to this day, the majority of women in the region cannot own lands directly (refer to section 3.1.1 on land tenure). Given such conditions, being a woman in North Africa could be even looked at as “[...] *doubly marginalized by belonging to two vulnerable groups: that of rural women and that of agricultural workers*” (Amri and Amri, 2003). Indeed, the most recent Gender Gap Index of 2024 continues to rank

³ Multidimensional poverty is an indicator of the World Bank. It takes the measure of the multiple deprivations in terms of education, health, living and employment conditions. For more information, refer to:

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/poverty/brief/multidimensional-poverty-measure>

⁴ MPI registered in urban versus rural areas reached the following rates in each of Algeria (0.6% v. 2.6%), Egypt (3.4% v. 6.3%), Mauritania (28.5% v. 84.9%), Morocco (1.4% v. 14.3%), and Tunisia (0.5% v. 1.9%).

the MENA as last among all other regions with a gender parity score attaining 61.7% compared to 68.4% for Sub-Saharan Africa, 74.8% for North America, and 75% for Europe⁵.

Within a context of high vulnerability at the environmental, social and economic aspects, political initiatives in North African countries have been noticed attempting to introduce efforts around agricultural and environmental sustainability, water conservation, introduction of climate objectives, and combat desertification, and others. However, these are seen not to directly or significantly entail the improvement of the position of women and marginalized groups. To date, national food security objectives tend to remain at the forefront of political priorities, and the translation to action seems to revolve around the increase in production and yield in a rather intensive manner as compared to more agroecological principles⁶.

Table 1: Some indicators on social, economic and demographic profiles of countries in North Africa under this study.

Indicator	Algeria	Egypt	Mauritania	Morocco	Tunisia
Share of agriculture in GDP (2020)	14.2%	11.5%	14.9*	12.2%	11.7%
Percentage of the labour force active in the agricultural sector (2020)	10%	21%	29.5%*	33%	14%
Agricultural arable land in 2018 (million hectares)	7.5	2.9	0.45	7.5	2.6
Percentage of irrigated land out of total agricultural land	3.2% (2017)	100%	0.1%	4.6% (2011)	3.9% (2013)
Rural population in 2020 (in millions)	11.5	58.6	2.1**	13.5	3.6
Percentage of the rural population out of the total population (2020)	26%	57%	42%**	36%	30%
Employment in agriculture, female (% of female employment)	3.4%	19.5%	30.6%	49.9%	10.4%
Employment in industry, female (% of female employment)	23%	8%	10%	14%	32%

*2022, **2023. Source: Bessaoud *et al.*, 2019 complemented by data from the World Bank's Development Indicators for Mauritania and for employment in agriculture and industry for females.

⁵ Global Gender Gap Indices reported in 2024 for Algeria 0.612, Egypt 0.629, Morocco 0.628, and Tunisia 0.668.

⁶ For more information, refer to D6.2: Analysis of agroecological perspectives in North African intersectoral public policies. A review of trends, strengths and weaknesses, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/12770882>

1.3 Key drivers for transitioning to agroecological practices and agroecological value chains in North Africa

Multiple factors could be considered when discussing a drive to the transition to agroecological value chains in North Africa. These relate to environmental sustainability, economic resilience, social equity, cultural preservation and others. For environmental sustainability, the overall degradation of natural resources such as desertification and soil erosion, water availability, and loss of biodiversity are some of the main drivers to which agroecology could help potentially alleviate in contexts such as in North Africa. For that, and as the NATAE project progresses in its development of understanding of agroecology in multiple North African agroecosystems, a preliminary study conducted by Requier-Desjardins (*et al.*, 2024) identified both the existence and adoption of practices found in North Africa consisting of crop diversification, agroforestry, and integrated crop-livestock systems in efforts to combat desertification and soil erosion. Certain practices were also identified within irrigated plains in North Africa specifically in Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia, and entailed practices to improve soil fertility, improve agricultural production output, and eco-system services (Ameur *et al.*, 2020). In most situations, the supportive action of international cooperation projects was core to the adoption of renewed agroecological practices, though they were often locally based on traditional knowledge. Outside the realm of direct on-farm practices, economic resilience and social equity are integral in the transition to agroecological value chains as a social movement. Important pilot evidence can be found in literature linking agroecological practices with a tangible increase in productivity and yield when adopted, and thus in the improving of income to farmers and enhancing their economic viability and livelihoods (Romero Antonio *et al.*, 2025; Souissi *et al.*, 2024). In Tunisia for example, the majority (90%) of farmers additionally successfully accepted and adopted agroecological practices into their farms when an adapted form of assistance was received; marking a successful instance where change was stimulated (Souissi *et al.*, 2024). Being a multi-dimensional process, agroecology therefore gives an important place to social principles and this includes social equity and social justice which are important to consider in the context of North Africa (refer to section 2.1.1). In that regard, the use of local knowledge and participatory approaches mobilize creation of place-based knowledge that integrates the participation of local players. Collective efforts and local organisations therefore foster that principle of collaboration and open the opportunity to address social challenges of a certain territory, potentially linking to the roles of minorities, gender, and others, and their access to resources and position in the economic cycle and ultimately their empowerment. In fact, the self-organisation capability of farming communities is regarded as a basis for the establishment of an agroecological food system especially in countries such as North Africa and the Middle East. Self-organisation is considered to particularly regard small farmers as the centre of food system transformations especially in situations that lack or have weak public policy support especially by their consideration

as means of “spreading of ideas and practices outside the conventional” (Goetz and Hussein, 2023). Self organization capacities and participatory governance structures are considered as a main, but not sole, factor that places small producers at their centre, providing the ability to engage in decision-making and networking, and therefore in potentially guide an autonomous ownership for directing a trajectory towards agroecological transitions of local food systems (Goetz and Hussein, 2023). In turn, such grassroots approaches in line with agroecology’s social principles, equally align with the preservation of a locality’s ways and culture. Agroecology indeed calls for the re-emergence of indigenous practices and the co-creation of local knowledge systems has been seen as essential in being integrated into more ‘modern’ applications and scientific knowledge (Utter *et al.*, 2021). Yet, although elements of such components are able to be identified in North Africa (such as collective efforts in cooperatives, traditional production, indigenous ways), it should be understood that a larger enabling environment is as important to foster adoption. The enabling environment for example could entail the public policy and institutional landscapes, property rights, access to credit, civil society engagement, and others.

1.4 Objectives

The main objective of this first study (task 3.2) concerning the identification of levers and potential policy measures to foster AE transitions in the LL areas is to develop a comprehensive conceptual framework for analysing agroecological value chains (AE VCs) in North Africa, with a particular focus on small-scale producers and small-to-medium trading and processing enterprises. The framework mobilized under this specific study aims to explore ways to enhance the value of agroecological products through diverse market channels. As primary producers are at the basis of the agricultural sector overall and in structuring potential agroecological value chains, this research seeks to deepen the understanding of their capacity to engage in value chains that add value to their products through agroecological practices. A key aspect of this analysis is examining the relationships between producers and other actors within the value chain, assessing whether these relationships reinforce agroecological principles and improve market access for small-scale producers. By doing so, the task aims to identify strategies that support the integration and sustainability of agroecological value chains in North Africa. In specific, this task focused on analysing multiple factors around value chains with specific focus on market access and accessibility, drivers and constraints. It also highlighted, when possible, modes of governance (collaborative or not), the distribution of the resulting benefits (equitability); autonomy/independence (financially, seeds, etc.); the know-how in place (cultural aspect); resilience (income diversity); and social performance (example: inclusion of women, people with disabilities, etc.).

This synthesis analysis helps in answering the research questions identified at the early stages of the study task, including:

- What are the producers market strategies? What are the barriers and drivers related to their inclusion in the markets?
- Are agroecological principles a key motivation for the various participants in the value chain?
- What are the main priority value chains onto which development efforts could focus so as to guarantee their economic, environmental and social sustainability, in line with the main principles of agroecology?
- To what extent do these value chains enable or hinder the integration of added-value agroecological products?

Finally, a separate chapter is dedicated for each distinct report formulated by the leaders of each of the Living Labs (Chapters 4 to 10).

Chapter 2

Methodology

Rita Jalkh and Iciar Pavez (CIHEAM-IAMM)

Chapter 2. Methodology

2.1 Overview of the methodology

This section recapitulates the methodology applied under this study for Task T3.1. A full methodological framework has been detailed in a prior document produced under Milestone 3: Adopting surveys methodologies, and was submitted in August 2023.

To build a holistic conceptual framework, we constructed a methodology and semi-structured interview guidelines, drawing on several theoretical concepts. Bolwig et al., (2010) value chain model with a focus on upgrading strategies to enhance the participation of small producers' and marginalized actors to access markets through inclusive value chains. This approach considers financial rewards, poverty reduction, gender equality, and environmental sustainability. Gereffi (2015) provides insights into how various factors influence participation in global value chains, particularly for smallholder producers, and identifies conditions for improving opportunities for disadvantaged actors along the value chain. The analysis addresses value chain mapping, including the supply chain, institutional environment, end-markets, market access, and producer constraints. Additionally, we incorporated the social-ecological systems concept by Folke, Carl, Olsson et al. (2005), focus on adaptive governance, highlighting the importance of social capital, networks, leadership, and trust. These factors support learning, innovation, and resilience in the face of external challenges. They also emphasize the role of bridging organizations in enhancing social capital and governance capacity, and stress the need to understand both external forces and the ability of actors to adapt, particularly in agroecological markets.

We also explored and took some elements from the Value-Based Supply Chain (VBSC) concept, which aims to support mid-scale family farms that are too large for direct marketing but too small to compete in commodity markets. VBSCs involve partnerships among producers, processors, distributors, retailers, and food service operators, all sharing environmental, economic, and social values. The development of VBSCs is shaped by factors such as access to capital, regulations, business acumen, and infrastructure (Hardesty et al., 2014).

Key to our framework was the "value-creating ecology" concept, an alternative to traditional value chains that emphasizes interconnectedness, collaboration, and knowledge sharing. It advocates for regions to understand their role in the global creative ecology and recognize their interdependencies with other environmental elements. This approach is essential for identifying sustainable market opportunities and stresses the importance of institutional arrangements that foster communication and trust to overcome structural and organizational challenges (Hearn et al., 2007).

The methodology was based mostly on a qualitative analysis approach, with some quantitative elements analysed whenever possible. The approach also focused on including analysis of the

economic, social, and environmental dimensions of the value chains whenever possible. It was based on the selection of two value chains per living lab territory, in a participative approach with the living lab leaders and living labs steering committees (boards). It was followed by an in-depth qualitative analysis through a set of semi-structured questionnaires of main actors in the value chains along with supportive data collection methods such as focus groups, and supported through a series of internal workshops and discussion sessions with the LL leaders for follow-up and guidance. The questionnaires and focus group discussions mainly aimed to develop a qualitative analysis following a standard template that was produced and which focused on providing a visual mapping of the value chains, an in-depth characterisation, and an assessment of agroecological potential around the different territories.

Table 2: List of Living Labs participating in the study with their corresponding agrosystem and partner leading the task

Agroecological system	Living Lab	Living Lab Leader
Irrigated valley	Egypt: Luxor LL	CIHEAM-IAMM
Cereal plains	Tunisia: Siliana LL	INAT
Oasis and peri-oasis	Algeria: Laghouat LL	CARI
Mountains	Morocco: Boulmane LL	ENA-Meknes
Peri-urban	Mauritania: Riyadh, PK 17 LL	GRDR
	Morocco: Meknès LL	ENA-Meknes

Figure 1: Geographic distribution of Living Labs (in green, study sites) and Replication Labs (in brown, other project tasks) in the NATAE project

2.1.1 Value chain selection

One of the first steps taken in the task was to arrive at a participatory selection of value chains to analyse under each of the territories studied. The selection of value chains was mainly based rather on those that were found to hold an agroecological potential and interest for local development (whether on the economic, social, and/or environmental components) rather than being based solely on their size of production and economic importance. Additionally, the value chain approach adopted by the NATAE project should be discussed and justified. Although agroecological principles call for a food systems approach and systemic interventions, it would be particularly difficult for a project to efficiently study and analyse all aspects of an entire food system, especially in a regional project as NATAE which extend at multiple countries. By adopting an analysis dedicated to individual value chains, the project will be able to provide practical observations tailored for each specific context. This could, on one hand, provide targeted measures that could have a tangible impact on each specific value chain and its interactions and, on another hand, extend these findings to reflect the larger food systems environment in which it is found. In its ability to identify specific results, a value chain analysis could better highlight gaps and align them with actions that could extend over to multiple actors, at first, at then be used to capitalize on the methodologies, experiences and first results on a larger scale.

In NATAE, the value chain selection step was accomplished by the development of a short questionnaire (Appendix A) which each LL leader was requested to fill and discuss with the task leader. This short questionnaire included three main questions revolving around the nomination and justification of suitable value chains. The reasoning which structured the short and targeted questionnaire revolved around the ranking of value chains of interest and questioning the reasons behind their proposition and a description of their current markets to get a better understanding of their market dynamics and distances. Another question inquired on whether forms of certification or reputable product exist in the territory, whether formal or informal. That question was aimed at getting a clearer picture of whether structured forms of certification exist and applied by which actors (primary producers or others) or whether products hold a reputation which is not transposed in an official certification but rather possibly to culture or a form of trust with consumers. The third question requested the Living lab leaders to nominate two value chains to include in the analysis of their territory, and the reason behind their selection. Bilateral meetings were next organized with each of the Living Labs in August 2023 which aimed to discuss the responses on the nomination of the value chains per territory. These meetings were also used to explain the overall methodology of the task, including an explanation of the development of the different questionnaires to be used with the different value chain actors. Finally, Living Lab leaders were instructed to discuss the results of the selected value chains with each of the Living Lab boards in order to receive a final validation from the local actors that represent the territory per LL.

In brief, the selected value chains per Living Lab consisted of:

- Laghouat LL (Algeria): Aromatic and medicinal plants and tomatoes
- Tizi Ouzou LL (Algeria): Olive Oil and aromatic and medicinal plants
- El-Boghdady Luxor LL (Egypt): Tomatoes and aromatic and medicinal plants
- PK17 LL (Mauritania): Onions bulb and Turnip
- Skoura Boulemane LL (Morocco): Olive Oil and Aromatic and medicinal plants
- Ait- Othman Meknès LL (Morocco): Onions and Mint
- Siliana LL (Tunisia): Cereals and Olive Oil

2.1.2 Analysis framework

- **Development of data collection tools**

Since value chains include a diversity of actors involved in the different stages from upstream production to downstream players until the final consumer, several distinct semi-structured questionnaires were developed to incorporate collecting the maximum possible scope of relevant information from the economic, social, and environmental perspectives. These included but were not limited to sections on general overview of activities (production and/or processing, employment, etc.), marketing (channels, certification, etc.), supply (inputs), governance and organisation (collective action), and challenges and opportunities. Separate questionnaires were developed for five main value chain actors including:

1. Primary producers (Appendix B)
2. Intermediaries – middlemen (Appendix C)
3. Wholesalers – wholesale markets (Appendix D)
4. Retailers (Appendix E)
5. Processing facilities (Appendix F)

Being semi-structured, the questionnaires were based on both closed and open-ended questions which provided the Living Lab leader with flexibility in their interviews with the different actors thus to openly share their knowledge and express their opinions. With further discussion with each of the LL leaders, the questionnaires were discussed and adapted for each territory given the context and applicability of certain questions. This included either the addition or omission of certain questions, and/or their adaptation. Additionally, Living Lab leaders were instructed to complement the information they collect with focus group discussions to fill any gaps in information and compare

findings for further validation between individual and group responses. No specific guide was provided for focus group discussions and it was left at the liberty of Living Labs to decide on the scope of questions to apply along with the organization. Yet, recommendations were given to include a diversity of invitees to represent the diversity of actors involved in the different value chains. It should be noted that the methodology was adapted by the Living Labs depending on the applicability and context per each territory.

- **Sampling**

Sampling of participants to partake in the interviews was based on a qualitative and participatory approach. This means that the identification and selection of interviewees from the different stages of the value chain was led by the Living Lab leader and, when possible, in collaboration with the Living Lab board depending on the diversity, willingness, and context of each territory. Certain recommendations were shared with the Living Lab leaders, such as for example including primary producers who are willing (or are currently) engaged in shifting to agroecological farming practices, who are located within the borders of the living labs and who are active in producing and entering products to the market. For downstream actors, the Living Labs were requested to identify them as per their knowledge of the territory and/or coupled with a rolling basis from referrals provided by the producers themselves. As per the sample size, it was determined depending on the size of the producer pool and market in each case. What was priorities was rather to have a sample that provides a representativity of the different profiles of actors found in the territory; especially at the level of primary producers. Such profile criteria could include for example the size of production (small, medium, large scale), type of production (traditional, industrial, etc.), legal structure (individual, cooperative, private enterprise, etc.), and others. In general, around 15 to 20 participants were recommended at the level of primary producers, and a flexible number of participants representing other actors depending on their number and significance in the value chain. In total, 175 primary producers were interviewed from the seven studied territories. A multitude of other value chain actors, a total of 92, were interviewed according to their number, importance and presence, and position in the value chain functioning in each territory. The categories of interviewed players ranged between two to three and up to six varying per territory and type, including intermediaries and collectors, wholesalers, retailers, processors, cooperatives, input suppliers and seed companies, exporters, governmental development offices, and regulatory bodies. Details per Living Lab can be found in the table below:

Table 3: Sampling of producers and value chain stakeholders interviewed per Living Lab territory under the study

Living Lab	Total number of interviewed producers	Total number of interviewed value chain actors (non-producers)
Algeria: Laghouat LL	30	15
Algeria: Tizi-Ouzou LL	26	12
Egypt: El-Boghdady Luxor LL	20	8
Mauritania: PK17	30	16
Morocco: Skoura Boulemane LL	28	15
Morocco: Ait-Otman Meknès LL	10	16
Tunisia: Siliana LL	31	10
TOTAL	175	92

- **Data collection and analysis**

The structure for data collection through the questionnaires and their analysis was based on highlighting three major components: i) the mapping of the studied value chain (visual representation of the various stages, actors, their linkages and activities that exist) in the form of a diagram, ii) providing a characterisation and diagnosis of the value chain (economic and non-economic assessment with focus on socio-economic conditions of small producers), and finally iii) providing an overall performance of agroecological aspects (with specific questions in the surveys highlighted as contributing to this understanding). Activities performed under this task were conducted in respect to the ethics procedures identified in the project.

- **Internal workshops**

Two main internal workshops were organized to discuss the progress of each Living Lab in their data collection and analysis. The workshops were collective and included presentations prepared by each LL team to discuss their progress and results, along with the provision of comments and guidance on next steps to perform. The first workshop took place online on 24 June 2024 (for Tizi Ouzou Algeria, Boulemane Morocco, and Siliana Tunisia), and on 10 July 2024 (for PK-17 Mauritania and Meknes Morocco). The second workshop took place on a hybrid basis (physically and online) in Montpellier at the CIHEAM-IAMM on 2 October 2024 in couple with another activity that was organized during that same period for WP2. As for Luxor, Egypt, a first follow-up meeting took place on 9 October 2024

and was followed by a field mission by a representative of the task leader from 27 October to 3 November 2024. This mission aimed to accompany the field team and expert in the conducting of focus groups (with producers and local stakeholders), conduct interviews with local stakeholders, and structuring of the report.

- **Formulation of Living Lab reports**

In order to standardize the formulation of the reports per Living Lab territory maintaining the same sequence of ideas and analysis, a template was structured by the team leader and shared/discussed with the Living Lab leaders for guidance. It was based on three main sections, including:

- General introduction and overview: contextual information of the territory and selected value chain, including an explanation of the methodology and selection of studied value chains
- Value chain mapping: a visual representation of the value chain in the form of a diagram that details the main actors from producer to consumer, main processes, their linkages, etc.
- Characterisation and diagnosis: including description of findings and results with focus on producer and production characteristics, market dynamics, certification, collective action and short circuit/consumer contact, motivations, barriers and opportunities, governance and decision-making power dynamics, interactions, and finally, the diagnosis and potential of agroecological value chains.

The outline was developed including a recapitulation of instructions along with each section indicating where the information can be found in the questionnaires. The template was normally also to complemented by information known to the Living Lab leaders regarding from their experience locally regarding the context or through those collected from focus groups (if any), and/or through other tasks they conducted under NATAE. The review of formulation and finalization of these individual reports was conducted bilaterally with each working team during which comments and recommendations were shared. Individual reports were used finally as the main input in the development of the transversal analysis, observations and conclusions.

- **Task timeline**

Step	Date
1) Development and discussion of methodology with LL leaders	By end July 2023
2) Participatory nomination, discussion and selection of value chains	Between August 2023 and March 2024
3) Launch of producer questionnaires	May 2024 the latest
4) Bilateral follow-up meetings on first results	May/June 2024
5) Launch other stakeholder surveys based on their identification in Step 1 (ex. Wholesalers, processors, etc.)	June/July 2024
6) First workshop for LLs	June/July 2024

7) Production of 1 st report draft (following outline produced by CIHEAM IAMM)	September 2024
8) Organization of a workshop for LLs to present and discuss reports	October 2024
9) Second drafts to be produced by LLs	End September 2024
10) Finalization of LL reports	October 2024 – January 2025
11) Production of deliverable draft	January/February 2025
12) Finalisation and submission of final deliverable by WP leader	March 2025

2.2 Description of analysed value chains in the study framework

Under the scope of this study, 14 value chains were analysed from seven Living Labs (two per LL) from five countries in North Africa. These are summarized in table (3) found in section 2.2.1 (Methodology). This section discusses the reasons behind the selection of these value chains as based on the participatory approach and discussions conducted with each of the Living Lab leaders and final validation by the Living Labs boards. It should be noted that the selection of the value chains was based on multiple factors and were discussed collectively with the Living Labs. Value chains were not prioritized according to their production sizes or economic importance, but rather on their potential to transition and possible incorporation of agroecological practices and with respect to its principles along the different stages whether economically, environmentally, and/or socially.

2.2.1 Algeria: Laghouat Living Lab (Oasis and peri-oasis)

Selected value chains: dates and olive oil.

Dates is a typical product of the Laghouat oasis and peri-oasis agrosystem. The date palm is a main crop for which an augmented dynamic has been noticed to be introduced in recent years. This engagement has reflected a development in the sector, and especially since it constitutes a typical short-circuit in mostly local market and consumption. As for the olive oil sector, it constitutes an emerging niche economy in Laghouat and is also considered a typical oasis cultivation now. This is especially following a state-supported program for the development of olive cultivation in Laghouat in the year 2000s which have significantly and widely introduced the tree. One of the main advantages is that olive trees are adapted to the climate in the meaning that they do not consumer much water. For that, a spread in its cultivation is noticeable. In addition, olive mills have been established in recent years with olive oil from Laghouat having obtained recognition and prizes in global competitions. This means that reputation is growing and that could be seen in the local, regional and national markets of the oil that currently exist.

2.2.2 Algeria: Tizi-Ouzou Living Lab (Mountains)

Selected value chains: olive oil and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs).

Olive production and olive oil extraction in Tizi Ouzou are family and even community-based activities. This raises interest to the benefit brought to the community and especially small producers in this activity, especially since the market of olive oil from Tizi Ouzou is diverse from local, to regional, national and even international in the case of one of the olive oil mills that exist in the territory. In addition to being a family scale activity, olive production provides an important role for women in the process and is a production described as 'mastered' by local producers. The MAPs value chain was also selected for its local interest, possible integration of women in the production cycle who already have access to markets. In addition, the selection of MAPs was conducted from the perspective of interest in maintaining the same value chains in both Living Labs of the same agrosystem; thus in comparison with the Boulemane-Skoura Living Lab in Morocco.

2.2.3 Egypt: Luxor Living Lab (Irrigated valley)

Selected value chains: tomatoes and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs).

Tomato production plays an important role in Upper Egypt regions such as Luxor. Its importance in production comes after sugar-cane and cereals; two value chains of highest economic position and are highly regulated by the state. Tomato is a winter-based crop which compensates for producing off-season for other regions such as lower Egypt between January and May when demand is high. Most fresh tomatoes are consumed around Egypt with no major export, whether locally, regionally and nationally depending on the phases of the season. The practice of sun-drying has recently emerged as a low-cost solution to utilize excess produce that would otherwise go to waste, with successes in a growing export (in bulk not in oil) rather than local or national market since the product is not common in the cuisine. Additionally, several sundrying stations have been established in Luxor and are managed by different actors such as associations, governmental development offices, and private investors. Sun-drying of tomatoes is also a very interesting sector which provides employment for women as the process is based on a women workforce. As for MAPs, Luxor is also one of the major producers in Upper Egypt. MAPs are consumed either fresh for the local and national market or are linked to processing into essential oils or cosmetics with industry producers around Egypt. Yet, its production is evident in the area, especially for products such as hibiscus, peppermint and basil, and are considered as important cash crops which also include women employment opportunities. Both tomato and MAPs producers in Luxor have common challenges and follow similar dynamics in production and market-access, which makes it interesting to study.

2.2.4 Mauritania: PK-17 Living Lab (Peri-urban)

Selected value chains: onions (bulb) and turnips.

These two value chains were selected in this territory given their high production and local consumption. Onions are significantly consumed and enter in almost every meal. In addition to being

well adapted to the existing soil type, the onion value chain is well established and organized, and is also well advocated receiving support when it comes to the review of imports (competition from imported onions). A market for agroecological market also exists in the territory although it serves mostly expatriates, yet local production and consumption was highly boosted through political interest during the COVID episode. As for turnips, they are also highly produced in areas like the PK-17, with production extending throughout the entire year, and are considerably consumed. This value chain is interesting since the production of seeds takes place on-site, production cycles are short which provides more important income, and faces less competition from imported products. Finally, the interest in this analysis is augmented by the fact that certain agroecological practices have been successfully introduced and are being promoted through efforts of development organizations linked to international cooperation programs.

2.2.5 Morocco: Boulemane-Skoura Living Lab (Mountains)

Selected value chains: olive oil and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs).

Olive oil production is an important sector in the mountains of Skoura. It is a common practice applied with an important level of knowhow and skills by local producers, especially during the different stages of oil milling and extraction. Locally produced olive oil is also mostly consumed either regionally or nationally which reflects the extent of its production relevance and markets. As for the MAPs, it is considered as a very promising sector with high added value. This is especially true given the basis of this production being women who are attempting at organizing themselves in cooperatives, and having a majority of local to national consumption. This sector holds additional interest and possible innovation in it being introduced potentially coupled with the olive production in family farms, with women members of a household attempting to develop their cultivating by shifting from wild-picking to the domestication of MAPs cultured in between olive groves. Main MAPs considered include rosemary, sage and saffron amongst others.

2.2.6 Morocco: Meknes-Ait Othmane Living Lab (Peri-urban)

Selected value chains: onions and mint (specific MAPs product).

Onions were selected in the Meknes site as it was found to be a dominant and family-based culture which requires integration into an agroecological transition since certain management practices remain borrowed from intensive agriculture. Yet, producers in the area already utilize traditional storage techniques for onions which fall into the principles of environmentally-friendly and heritage thus adding value and interest to this value chain and especially given the peri-urban location of the site. It constitutes one of the main cash crops present in the 'Douar' of Ait Othmane territory and is cultivated on small areas (1 to 2 hectares) in rotation with cereals and market gardens. However, the production is less integrated into national and international production circuits like the large producers

in the area, and suffers from the pressure of drought. As for mint production, the position of the Ait Othmane Douar in the peri-urban area of the metropolis of Meknes favours it to meet the consumption of city dwellers of aromatic plants generally and in mint particularly. Producers have almost converted their production system by adopting a strategy of crop diversification and adaptation to drought and local market opportunities. Mint cultivation generates significant income but poses problems of trust related to the traceability of this crop by city dwellers and their concern to the applied practices such as source of irrigation waters. Yet, mint is a recognized and newly introduced culture which is progressively positioning itself on the new needs of urban centres.

2.2.7 Tunisia: Siliana Living Lab (Cereal plains)

Selected value chains: cereals and olive oil.

Cereals and olive oil are one of the two major productions in the governorate of Siliana. Both value chains fall under governmental regulations by the Office of Cereals and the Office of Oils. Cereal production is considered as a flagship product with mostly regional markets and the culture is a characteristic of the delegation of the Living Lab representing major actors in the governorate of Siliana. As for olive oil, it constitutes a growing sector which already has markets extending on local, regional, national and international scale; as is the case with olive oil from Tunisia. It is seen to take up an increasing position at the level of agricultural holdings. This is mainly due to an orientation towards olive growing to mitigate the financial risks generated by cereal growing, mainly during years of drought. So, olive oil is being noticed to enter into the future plans of the majority of producers, including cereal growers wishing to develop their activities. The selection was also based on having these two value chains prone to a potential for agro-ecological integration and given that they are the most important crops in the territory.

Table 4: List of selected value chains per Living Lab

Agrosystem	LL	LL Leader	LL Selected Value Chains
Irrigated valley	Egypt: El-Boghdady Luxor LL	CIHEAM-IAMM	Tomatoes Aromatic and medicinal plants
Cereal plains	Tunisia: Siliana LL	INAT	Cereals Olive Oil
Oasis and peri-oasis	Algeria: Laghouat LL	CARI	Dates Olive oil
Mountains	Morocco: Skoura Boulemane LL	ENA-Meknes	Olive Oil Aromatic and medicinal plants
	Algeria: Tizi-Ouzou LL	CREAD	Olive Oil Aromatic and medicinal plants

Peri-urban	Mauritania: PK17 LL	GRDR	Onions bulbs Turnip
	Morocco: Ait-Othman Meknès LL	ENA-Meknes	Onions Mint

Chapter 3

Key Findings and analysis

Rita Jalkh and Iciar Pavez (CIHEAM-IAMM)

Chapter 3. Key Findings and analysis

3.1 General characteristics

3.1.1 Land tenure

When observing different countries in North Africa, what can be seen is a basis of cultivation linking humans to land. Accessing land is not homogeneous, and multiple dynamics can be noted. In countries such as in Morocco, many lands fall under collective management by ethnic communities (referred to as tribes) linked to the Ministry of Interior. In the case of Meknes specifically, five hectare plots were associated with every family lineage. Such a system, providing collective ethnic communities with a legal personality, is believed to protect lands against the influx of private investors. Additionally, women in Morocco did not have any direct access or inheritance to lands, and their access was made possible only through family ties allocating harvest shares or through minor children. That was the situation only until recently in 2019 with the introduction of the Law 62-17. This law now allows women to participate in the management of collective lands without them being subject to transfer or sell the plots. Yet, with the process of shifting into this new adoption, the dominant practice of farming remains revolved around men with low allocations to women to this date. A similar system of land access solidarity can be found in some territories in Algeria, such as in Tizi-Ouzou. It is based on a system called “Thadjmaat” which attempts to solve conflicts in land access and in providing access to lands by owners who reside outside the territory or the country, including women who normally are not authorized to own land. On another hand, in the majority of cases in countries as Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia, many producers tend to be independent managers of their own plots, whether as owners (mostly) or as tenants renting. Despite being thought as a form of better guarantee for control over the land, such ownerships are not free from challenges. Land access remains a problem especially in areas of strong land fragmentation such as in Luxor, Egypt, where farmers on average own less than 1 hectare; a situation which has greatly limited production and diversification, and has stimulated the reclamation of desert land to compensate. In exceptional cases such as that of PK-17, the land allocated is normally made available by the state and the regional authority as a result of efforts in local development and encouragement for agricultural facilitation especially for retired military personnel. Yet, that does not stop unauthorized occupation of some plots whose occupants, known as “Gazra” maintain however some level of authorization over land use for agricultural activities only.

3.1.2 Socio-economic conditions

When observing conditions of producers socio-economically, multiple common observations emerge from the different countries. The first and foremost observation would be at the level of an aging farming population. Most producers in the Living Lab territories are middle-aged or older while youth

participation is limited in the sector. In places like Algeria specifically, the average age of producers is relatively high being over 55 years for Tizi Ouzou and over 60 years for Laghouat. In Mauritania and Morocco, a significant proportion of producers (over 30%) are over 55 years old, and in Tunisia, an average age range between 40 to 60 dominates. Poverty and low education are other major challenges especially in rural areas such as in Luxor (Egypt, almost 50%) and Siliana (Tunisia, 24.7%), surpassing the national averages of poverty, along with such problems persisting strongly in the remaining Living Labs. Therefore, in possible efforts to secure alternative income sources, it can be noticed that the many of the territories report on small producers reverting to diversifying their activities for economic support. Examples extend from working as seasonal workers or daily labor in neighbouring farms as in Luxor (Egypt), or even being employed in part-time or seasonal basis in non-agricultural activities such as with local businesses or trade, or as individual jobs as in construction or transportation. This issue is particularly evident in Laghouat where over half of all interviewed producers reported working in non-agricultural due to economic challenges. As for education, and even though illiteracy is on a decline globally, low levels of education remain more or less existing in rural agricultural settings. For almost all Living Labs (except Skoura), levels of education seem to be low at attained primary education mostly. These reports were very clear in territories such as Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria, but particularly high in Mauritania (43% with no formal education), and also generally high in Laghouat (Laoubi *et al.*, 2011) and Luxor (Aboulnaga *et al.*, 2017). It seems that the only territory where secondary education is attained higher than the others is in Skoura (Morocco) at about 45% of farmers. Yet, what can be deduced is that access to education and agricultural training is low and require stronger attention towards the trajectory of transition, starting by the building of literacy, knowhow and capacities of primary producers. Finally, the agricultural production systems and value chain dynamics around the majority of the countries in North Africa remain a male-dominated sector with a male majority of workforce and decision-makers. Women participation in the economic cycle remains rather informal and based on manual activities or home-based work. Even in cases where women are involved, they mostly are as informal (sometimes formal) labour participants rather than in leadership positions, even if they belong to initiatives designed for local development purposes. The situation is exacerbated by low access to land and resources, finance and credit, education, and general more conservative cultural and social landscape in rural North African sites. Yet, the medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) value chain have emerged as a potential arena proven to have successfully provided women with leadership and decision-based roles. This was particularly noticed in the cases of Skoura (Morocco) and Tizi-Ouzou (Algeria) with the involvement of women in cooperatives and their management.

3.2 Observations of the status of value chains in North Africa

This section is based on the findings observed at the level of the different value chains that were selected and analysed from the seven Living Labs located around five countries in North Africa. The

analysis is structured following the major stages corresponding to the value chains from upstream production to downstream consumer markets. It also attempts to provide an insight to the socio-economic and environmental conditions whenever possible, along with the characteristics of the enabling environment which influence of the value chain performance, and gender.

It should be noted that the observations for input provision and farming practices mentioned in this report should be considered in complement with the results coming out of Work Packages 2 and 4 of the NATAE project and should not be considered as standalone results. Certain deliverables in WP2 and WP4 have specific objectives in terms of characterising farming practices in the territories of the Living Labs and therefore go in more details in issues such as the farm typologies and their agroecological analysis. These for example include the Deliverables D2.1, D2.2, D4.2, and D4.3.

3.2.1 Trends in upstream provisions and primary production

Normally, since the territories are distributed amongst a diversity of different agrosystems, then the observations also differed in the dynamics and modes of operation applied. With regards to input provision, different dynamics were equally observed across the region.

3.2.1.1 *Input provision and seed use*

In general, input provision involve mostly seeds, fertilizers and pesticides, and irrigation water/systems for those applying irrigated farming. In most cases, what can be seen is that the needed inputs for cultivation are usually purchased by producers. The sources for these inputs vary but are mostly provided by local suppliers who in turn procure these inputs from either import or in certain cases are produced locally. What is certain however, is the reliance of producers on these suppliers for access to inputs, in which many cases could be limiting in their selection and thus decision.

It was observed in multiple territories that access to good quality seeds and inputs is rather difficult. This is the case especially in Skoura (Morocco) especially for olive varieties, Siliana (Tunisia) for cereals, and Luxor (Egypt) for tomatoes. In fact, almost all seeds used in tomato cultivation in Egypt come from imported hybrid varieties and local varieties are almost inexistent. In cases where tomatoes are destined for processing (sun-drying mostly) and thus export, inputs and seeds are sometimes provided by the drying station directly to the producers in an attempt to facilitate and standardize production, thus maintaining quality and compliance to the norms requested by the concerned international markets. The lack of interest in the use of any local seeds and varieties in such cases pose a serious problem in the protection of local varieties from ultimate disappearance, and their use which in many cases would be more adapted and resistant to local conditions, climate and disease. But it is worth mentioning that local seeds and varieties are still being used in some cultivations around different agrosystems such as MAPs in Luxor and Skoura, and in the case of

Laghouat and Ait Othmane. Except the case of Luxor for MAPs which are purchased from local and reliable nurseries, the remaining cases where local seeds are used remain in relatively small-scale and specific contexts. In Laghouat for example, palm date seeds are auto-produced or procured from neighboring farms from offshoots of healthy mother palm trees and olive oil seedlings were distributed by the state under a national program in the year 2000s. As for the other territories, seeds are mostly purchased locally or not at all such as in the case of foraging for MAPs in Tizi-Ouzou and Skoura.

One of the major observations noted relates to the use of chemical inputs, especially fertilizers, which is still widespread with beliefs of boosting yield and quality of end products. This is evidently noted in the cases of cereal production in Tunisia, onion in Morocco, and for the majority of cultivations in Egypt. This therefore creates an increasing reliance on suppliers knowing that the high prices of such inputs create in fact a limiting factor and a major challenge for production. Even in cases where sectors are regulated by the state, such as for cereals and olive oil in Siliana (Tunisia), reliance remains strong on chemical inputs and suppliers. For that, some subsidies were introduced to attempt to support their purchase; actions that go counterintuitive to agroecological transition. Yet, the dependence on such inputs remain very strong, so much so that producers in certain cases are indebted to suppliers throughout the production season. Such cases can be seen in Luxor (Egypt) and in Ait Othmane (Morocco) where an advance payment for inputs is provided by the producers, and the payment is completed after harvest. In other cases, the high prices and scarcity of such inputs has pushed some producers to avoid their use completely and/or secure alternative practices. For example, organic alternatives as manure and compost could be noted in cases as Skoura and Tizi-Ouzou mainly due to the inaccessibility to the chemical counterparts. Other producers in Skoura, Ait Othmane and Tizi Ouzou have instead opted completely from using chemical inputs mainly due to their high price. In cases as Laghouat, both organic manure from local sources and chemical fertilizers and pesticides from imported sources are used. In the case of Mauritania, given that the PK-17 is a development project-based allocation lands, NGOs play an important role in raising the awareness and capacity building of producers, and that includes shifting to more agroecological practices such as avoiding the use of chemical inputs. Despite such interventions, whether in Mauritania or in the majority of other countries where international cooperation efforts and civil society organisations exist, the most common and dominant form of agricultural production today in fact remains conventional; and that means reliance on chemical inputs. In addition, it should be considered that even if producers were stimulated and acknowledged the need to shift to organic input alternatives, they remain quite limited in their access today. This is due to their high price and unavailability in the common supply market. Therefore, there is a general consensus for the need of making alternative agroecological inputs more accessible and especially in rural territories and for small producers. Another major reflection that should be mentioned at this stage is questioning whether producers would revert to the

(re)use of chemical inputs if their financial situation allows it, and adopting alternative agroecological practices out of conviction rather than obligation.

3.2.1.2 *Characteristics in primary production habits*

When it comes to primary production habits of the analysed value chains in the territories of the project's Living Lab, multiple observations emerge as important from a value chain perspective⁷. These start with the issue of access to land and land sizes. In fact, access and availability to land differs greatly between one territory and another; an issue linked to land tenurship (section 3.1.1). What can be noticed is that most producers involved in the studies value chains cultivate on a relatively small scale, mainly less than 5 hectares. Land fragmentation emerges as one of the major issues in the case of Luxor for example. Only some large farms are noticed in the case of cereal cultivation in Siliana, Tunisia, that can reach surface areas of up to 15 to 50 hectares. Most importantly, it is evident that a diverse array of practices are applied. In many cases, these mix both those that are conventional with those that are more agroecological mainly derived from ancestral techniques. The main understanding that emerges behind these trends is shaped by the producers' necessity, mainly due to the need to reduce costs or due to limitations in resources or soil fertility issues. It is noticed that in the cases where little to no chemical inputs are used, this is due to their inaccessibility by the producers and mainly due to their high prices. This is evident in multiple territories such as in Skoura (Morocco), and in Tizi Ouzou and Laghouat (Algeria). In these territories, producers are more prone (or pushed) to apply organic composting and fertilizers and even rely on practices such as intercropping and livestock integration such as in the oases and peri-oasis agrosystem in Laghouat (Algeria). Yet, the use of chemical inputs remains a dominant form of production evident in the majority of territories due to the belief in their impact on improved yields and quality of end-product. This fact could be logically transcended to the entire North Africa region, with rising input prices is well noted in the majority of countries.

From the agroecological practices mentioned in the country reports, the common practice of water-saving techniques emerges, normally due to the common factor of growing water and precipitation limitations in the region. The adoption of the practice of drip irrigation is thus noticed in arid and semi-arid climates such as in Luxor, Tunisia and Laghouat, whereas rainfed cultivation has been adopted altogether in an attempt to reduce water use. In Tunisia for example, minimum tillage and cover crops are sometimes adopted in efforts to combat soil erosion and help retain soil moisture. Association of multiple cultivations together and intercropping is another form of practice that has been noticed for the analysed value chains especially in Siliana (Tunisia, for cereals, olives, fodder crops, legumes

⁷ Please refer to Deliverable D4.2 for a full typology of farms in the Living Labs for a larger understanding of farming practices in each territory, knowing that these do not necessarily link directly to the value chains studied in this document. In addition, Milestone 5 provides a deeper outlook on identified agroecological practices and some combinations of interest. These are available on the NATAE project's open access Zenodo community at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/101084647/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

and vegetable crops, and fruit trees), in Laghouat (Algeria, in a multi-tiered cultivation alternating palm dates that help create a micro-climate to support the cultivation of olives, fruit trees, medicinal plants and others), in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria, for olive intercropping with legumes and cereals), and in Skoura Boulemane (Morocco, for olive intercropping with MAPs even if in small quantities relatively). For others, it is the application of organic fertilizers that apply and especially at the level of small producers in Algeria, Mauritania, Morocco, and Tunisia. As noted, their application in most parts comes mainly as a result of in-access to the more expensive chemical counterparts. Therefore, smallholders revert to either the purchase of organic manure and compost or to the introduction of livestock for natural fertilization. It is only in certain cases where producers are exposed to organisations and agencies involved in development through international cooperation efforts where practices transitioning to agroecology can be noticed as a result of external interventions, such as in some of Mauritania's PK-17 plots for example. In other cases, such as in Luxor (Egypt), a successful shift in practices was noticed as being driven by the market itself, especially the international export market. In such cases, mainly for tomato cultivation destined for sun-drying, it is the processors (drying stations), that need to comply to specific standards to be able to export their product. Accordingly, they in turn provide in the required inputs and standardize farming practices. Generally speaking, mechanization also remains more or less low, especially at the level of small producers.

3.2.2 Downstream value chains characteristics

3.2.2.1 *Logistics, distribution and overall infrastructure*

When it comes to discussing the available infrastructure for channelling primary production harvests from farm to the market, the observations tend to be more or less similar in the context of North African countries. Results show that the overall infrastructure conditions, and particularly for transportation and logistics, is mostly weak and challenging whereby producers find it difficult to access proper storage facilities, face high levels of post-harvest losses, and do not have the proper means of transportation to access wanted markets. High transportation costs appear to be a serious problem especially for small-scale producers who lack the means to secure accessing of their productions to outlets. This was mentioned explicitly for example in the cases of Living Labs in Morocco stating about 15 to 20% of selling prices represent transportation costs due to the distances to processing centres and urban markets. In places such as in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), extremely high transportation costs were even reported for women engaging in MAPs production reaching up to 50% of production costs even over small distances of 2 to 3 kilometres. The limited number, accessibility, condition, and unaffordable cost of storage and logistics facilities pose similar challenges as reported in the majority of territories. Other than being at a mostly unaffordable price making it inaccessible especially to small farmers, infrastructure conditions, amongst other reasons, are also shown to cause major losses in

food. Food loss⁸ is reported to reach as high as 25 to 30% in crops as dates and olives (Living Lab reports) despite being due to a multitude of factors including but not only to post-harvest infrastructure. Particularly high levels of food loss are reported for tomatoes in Egypt that could reach up to over 45 to 47% of farm production along the different stages of the value chain but mainly during post-harvest, on-farm, wholesale, and retail (FAO, 2021). Reported reasons for losses in the majority of living labs include production causes such as climatic and environmental conditions, harvest techniques, labour shortages, pests and diseases. Yet, these percentages could be considerably reduced if better conditions in post-harvest, storage, logistics, and infrastructure quality were to be improved. This is also further proven when investigating the official levels of food loss reported by the FAO's Food Loss and Waste Database⁹ for the countries analysed in this report (Figure 2). Certain stages of value chain stages are shown to cause significant quantity of food losses of all categories to which storage is included along with post-harvest, wholesale, and retail. This shows that on-farm losses are not in fact comparable to the post-harvest and downstream stages of the value chains where products pass through and for which the majority of food is lost or wasted. Interestingly but not surprisingly, households are also to be considered as important contributors to food waste. According to the FAO's Food Loss and Waste Database, the region of North Africa wasted between 9 and 16% of foods at household level between the years 2000 and 2022, as compared to a global average of 11 to 27%. These levels are comparable between North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa, and are ultimately less than the levels registered for North America (between 15 to 30%) but higher than those reported for Europe (7 to 12%) over the same period of time.

⁸ Not to be confused with food waste. Food loss and waste are defined in the State of Food and Agriculture (SOFA, 2019) as: Food loss: the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, excluding retail, food service providers and consumers. Food waste: the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by retailers, food services and consumers.

⁹ Available online at <https://www.fao.org/platform-food-loss-waste/flw-data/en>

Figure 2: Food loss reported in the study countries for Algeria, Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco and Tunisia between 2000 and 2022 along the different stages of the supply chain. Source: FAO Food loss and waste database.

3.2.2.2 Market access

Market access is a key stage of any value chain as it links producers with the ultimate outlet of sales to end consumers, whether directly or indirectly, and thus the generating of income. If there is no market opportunities, it would be very difficult to stimulate any change or shifts in production practices and in building any synergies for a transition within different players. Therefore, market circuits and chains are a driver for any producer and it would be essential to consider channels that are suitable for small producers who are under threat of not being able to compete in a growing globalized market nor meet its ever-growing competitive norms (Hazell and Wood, 2007). This section will discuss the different elements observed in accessing markets across the studied territories in North Africa.

3.2.2.2.1 Subsistence farming vs. market-oriented production

When discussing market and market access, it is important first to realize that market-oriented cultivations are not a priority for many territories in North Africa. Many small producers in fact cultivate

to sustain their own household consumption; referred to as subsistence farming or auto-consumption. Any harvest quantities in surplus are then directed towards the market to generate income. Such is the case for example for small-scale producers in Morocco, Algeria and some in Tunisia. In Ait Othmane (peri-urban) and Skoura (mountains), 20 to 40% of the harvest is directed to the farming households for onions, olives/olive oil and MAPs. Similarly, producers in Algeria's Tizi Ouzou mountains prioritize self-consumption and access to market operations is reported to emerge only recently. As for the Laghouat territory in an oasis agrosystem, as multi-tiered production is common, vegetable intercropping with fruit trees and date palms is destined for auto-consumption along with livestock products that are integrated in the production cycle. Even for important crops such as cereals in Tunisia, 38% of producers are reported to maintain a part of their harvest for household or family use. Yet, production generally remains destined for market sales and income generation. This is the case also for Luxor (Egypt) and PK-17 (Mauritania) where producers operate mainly to sell their products as part of the territories' habits and/or proximity to markets. It is therefore in such market-oriented contexts where accessibility to suitable market channels should be truly considered. Market access is expectedly a key aspect in shaping the motivation of producers around any possible transition or shift in primary production practices with a promised sales and generated income in return.

3.2.2.2.2 *Diversity of marketing channels and role of intermediaries*

When accessing markets, multiple channels and methods are seen around the different territories in North Africa. This comes out as a result of the local context they are placed in, including their agrosystem, distance from markets, and capabilities of producers to secure means of logistics and marketing. In general, what can be seen is that producers and particularly those of small-scale have limited means. The different channels that can be observed for the value chains included in this study, with the exception of those regulated by the state, are onsite farm sales, direct sales to family/personal circles and periodic local markets as weekly *souks*, through intermediaries to wholesalers and retailers, through cooperatives and finally through speciality shops. Although those might not be representative of the entirety of value chain dynamics existing across North Africa, such site specific trends are interesting to analyse especially when it comes to the understanding of local proximity to markets and short circuits. Regarding direct contact between end consumers, it was noticed that there exist some local markets such as weekly *souks* that provide a direct outlet to local consumers as in Morocco or periodic fairs and exhibitions as in Algeria's Tizi Ouzou case. Yet, these venues are not enough in providing sufficient and recurrent sales quantities and farmers are therefore obliged to secure alternative routes for the sale of the remainder of their production. For market-oriented producers, direct contact between producers and end-consumers therefore exists but is rather not as adopted or developed as when compared to other channels. In many territories, producers revert to depend on intermediaries (collectors, traders, middlemen, etc.) who are able to handle logistics and

transportation of their products and in bulk. The dominance of such intermediaries is particularly evident in territories such as Luxor (Egypt), Ait Othmane and Skoura (Morocco) and PK-17 (Mauritania), noting that minimal intervention of intermediaries was reported in the two Living Labs in Algeria. Sales to intermediaries occur in the majority of cases through on-farm sale where the price is fixed. In some cases such as in Luxor, prices could even be fixed prior to the farming cycle. In the case of Luxor also, some intermediaries are even seen to provide producers with a working capital and inputs at the start of each cultivation season in return for guaranteed sales at a pre-fixed price and promise of completing the payment after harvest. It is obvious how in such cases, decision making and mostly negotiation power tends to lay with the intermediaries. It is therefore not a surprise how sales to intermediaries have lower prices than the average market price and thus attain significantly less profit to the primary producer. This issue is exacerbated by the low access to market information of primary producers. Price differences could be as much as 45% less, as reported for example in the case of olive oil in Laghouat (Algeria). Yet, intermediaries in such cases would be responsible of tasks as packaging, managing orders, logistics and transportation and others. This relieves the producers of such responsibilities, workload and time. It mainly due to such facilitations that producers rely on intermediaries. In terms of workload and reach, producers do not have, in many times, the required expertise in branding and conformity to market requirements in addition to the needed means of storage, logistics, transportation and distribution especially reaching rather inaccessible markets. The inaccessibility to markets and facilitations provided by intermediaries do not however depend on distances from those markets. As noticed in Ait Othmane, despite the small producers being localised in a peri-urban environment near the city of Meknes, their main channel would still be to deal with intermediaries. The reported reasons for that were the inability of the financially unstable producers to deal directly with wholesalers, who in fact remain in direct contact with intermediaries for the procurement of products. On another hand, other benefits to working with intermediaries is that they mostly purchase products in bulk and therefore relieve producers from entire marketable volumes. With a recurrent relationship with intermediaries, producers therefore ensure sales and thus secure a certain financial stability over time even though it is in most cases based on verbal commitments rather than written contracts. However, the most serious disadvantage to producers in dealing with intermediaries would be the large compromise made to the cut of potential profit they could otherwise attain, reducing their negotiation power and direct consumer relationships that could translate into premium opportunities. Transparency is another aspect that is rather weak in such forms of business relationships that separate producers from market information. For now, wholesale markets remain in control of prices and coupled with intermediaries seem to be concentrating the core dynamics of major value chains in North Africa. A typical example of that would be in Egypt where some of the largest wholesale markets in the region exist¹⁰.

¹⁰ Such as Al-Obour market in eastern Cairo, Egypt: <http://www.oboormarket.org.eg/Default.aspx>

3.2.2.2.3 *Local short circuits and export dynamics*

Marketing at local scale over relatively short distances is observed in the majority of Living Labs in one way or another. Even in more commercial contexts, such as in Luxor, Siliana, Skoura, local markets are still prioritised. In Egypt, tomatoes in their fresh form are mostly consumed either locally or nationally depending on the production season. Luxor being a winter-producing region given its arid climate, provides local markets and simultaneously diverts production towards the capital during the latter's off-season. The inverse becomes true in summer. For Skoura in Boulemane, producers market their products locally whether through traditional farmers markets, direct farm sales or through cooperatives and distribution remains within the local region even for olive oil, unlike the other regions in Morocco where export dominates. As for Skoura's MAPs, revolving mainly around women engagement, efforts in market access is provided through collective action as with the case of the local women cooperative. Similarly in Ait Othmane, the small-scale producers being located in proximity to the urban center of Meknes perform on-farm sales or, through intermediaries and traders, have their produce distributed locally. As for Siliana, both the cereal and olive oil value chains are state regulated and are subject to the Offices of cereals and oil, and therefore the markets and prices are stabilized, with produce passing through certified collectors unto processors and the market. In Mauritania's PK-17, also being in close proximity to the capital, local sales prevail in different form. These include on-farm sales, through intermediaries and through speciality markets, where the products remain within the local scale. Yet, true short but micro circuits are more obvious in some territories compared to others. This is especially true for the case of Algeria. In Laghouat, both the traditional palm dates value chain and the newer emerging olive oil value chains follow typical local short circuits with minimal interference from intermediaries. In fact, the entirety of products are sold either through personal and social networks, via direct transmission to family members or delivery to consumers, on-farm, or to local speciality shops, with olive oil sales also passing through local mills. As for Tizi Ouzou, the small quantities and family-oriented aspect to productions make it interesting to explore the existing trends even if they do not enter a true market dynamic. In fact, it is reported that producers do not actually engage in extensive marketing efforts, and that products such as olive oil in the area is in such high demand that it is provided through family connections and directly to the local community. In cases where producers are interested in accessing markets, it is mostly done locally also through inter-personal connections. Similarly, MAPs produced in Tizi Ouzou remain within the local markets, and that is noticed for all sizes of producers. In addition to social circles, marketing channels also include speciality shops, online sales and periodic events also passing through collectivities as with cooperatives and development initiatives especially in support to women as the case in Skoura for MAPs.

On another hand, some value chains are seen to be oriented more towards international export markets. This is especially evident in the sun-dried tomatoes of Luxor (Egypt) and olive oil of Siliana

(Tunisia). In the case of Luxor, fresh tomatoes get mainly marketed and consumed within the country, but it is their sun-dried form that gets exported, and Egypt generally and Luxor specifically is one of the major producers of tomatoes. Following harvest, tomatoes pass through a sun-drying process in drying stations after which they get exported. Almost all sun-dried tomatoes get exported in bulk as base product without any oil preservation or packaging in jars since the product is not a common commodity in the local or national cuisine. Export in such cases is mostly handled by the drying station themselves. Certain processed MAPs also get exported after being processed into essential oils. As for Siliana, olive oil is generally known to be of high quality around Tunisia and in a main export industry reaching in 2022 “824 million USD, representing 38% of food export revenues and 3.6% of the country's total exports” (Living Lab report). Connections to the international markets go through either cooperatives or private exporters for its selling, mainly in bulk, under international brands that get mostly blended. Being a state regulated value chain, olive oil production in Tunisia is subjected to the National Office of Oil which, other than supporting inputs subsidies, also invests in developing Tunisian olive oil exports mainly through quality improvement and promotion. Olive oil in Tunisia however faces serious fluctuations in price and threatens the stability of economic return to producers, and especially during the past five years. This is due to multiple factors, including but not limited to, climatic factors affecting yield and productivity, increased production costs, susceptibility to global price fluctuations given that Tunisian olive oil is sold in bulk rather than packaged or branded, and export policies and quota adaptations especially to European markets that affect national supply (Zaied and Zouabi, 2016, Arfaoui *et al.*, 2022). At this stage, two main questions could be raised. The first relates to how agroecological transition could be better fostered or developed in contexts of state-controlled value chains as those of cereals and olive oil in Tunisia; a country that has developed a national strategy for ecological transition but that also has increased subsidies to chemical inputs and is a major exporter of certain commodities. In fact, the second question relates to that very dilemma between export-oriented cultivations and sustainable agroecological practices. With agroecology calling for innovative local markets and short circuits with practices minimizing impact on ecosystems while maintaining social consideration as for livelihoods and tradition, such principles contradict with export prioritization. Besides, multiple countries in North Africa today still include strong focus and large objectives on export targets within their policies, such as Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia. Yet, it is also argued that countries rely on export to generate hard currency for their economic viability and purchasing powers. Several publications discuss and argue for the different sides of this paradox such as those by Altieri A.M. (2009), Korthals M. (2001), and Prost L. (*et al.*, 2023). Therefore, what would be an acceptable trade-off, and by which actors should it be stimulated, advocated and followed through?

3.2.2.3 *Processing, value addition and certification*

From the different value chains analysed in this study, products are seen to pass through more or less conventional processing routes as expected. Olives undergo pressing to extract olive oil, cereals undergo milling for flour, MAPs undergo drying and essential oil distillation, dates are graded (dried in some cases as in Tizi Ouzou but not in Laghouat) and stored, and tomatoes destined for export are sun-dried. Many produce are also sold in their fresh form without going through any major form of processing, and these include onions, mint, tomatoes, Laghouat dates and some MAPs. Therefore, no major form of transformation is seen to place in the majority of territories at the level of the farm or one step downstream of the value chain. This is because, for example, in the case of Siliana (Tunisia), the value chains of cereals and olive oil are regulated by the state through the Office of Cereals and the Office of Oils. For those value chains, producers link directly to certified collectors or collection point for the sale and provision of their producers. For other value chains, produce is mostly sold onsite and/or to intermediaries instead who in turn supplied wholesalers and other actors downstream. For olive oil, after milling and extraction takes place at mills, producers then recuperate the product for which they then either keep a quantity for self-consumption or is sold off directly to end consumers or in bulk. Interestingly in Algeria, hot-extracted olive oil is preferred by consumers as the common taste compared to cold extracted or extra virgin olive oil; thus showcasing a national consumption preference instead of flavor and nutrient preservation which should be taken in account.

Regarding onsite processing at the level of producers, financial capacities play a major role along with knowhow. In Meknes (Morocco) for example, onions were stored following ancestral preservation techniques¹¹ to ensure extended shelf-life over the period of several months and therefore the gradual supply of the market and sales at optimum prices. Yet, an initial investment is required and is sometimes not within the capabilities of many producers. In the case of MAPs, some producers in Skoura (Morocco) and Tizi Ouzou (Algeria) do through minimal processing at the farm or at cooperatives such as drying and packaging. In these cases, the formal grouping of the mostly women actors help consolidate efforts and resources that facilitate its achievement and downstream supply to the market.

What is also noticed in certain cases is that value addition can be innate and take the form of a good reputation of local products within the surrounding communities. This is particularly evident in the two sites assessed in Algeria where especially dates and olive oil have not only a high local demand, but follow short circuits characterized by a strong consumer which is trust built around the reputation and quality of local varieties and tradition. In fact, this is true for such value chains without any certification introduced. Therefore, certification is not always to be considered as a measure of value addition nor

¹¹ This tradition consists of layering straws and onions to ensure aeration over a raised stone bed covered by plastic sheeting.

a means of accessing markets and especially in similar contexts. On the contrary, rural and local consumers are seen to actively seek such local products and are perceived to hold a high quality and belief that their production methods are more natural and valued. Even for MAPs in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), this dynamic facilitated the organization into cooperatives and women groups that supply the market, even in low quantities, but without any need to seek regulatory channels or certification. In Skoura (Morocco) on another hand, even though olive oil also has a strong reputation with high local demand, producers are well aware of available certifications such as the SDOQ (Distinctive Sign of Origin and Quality). Morocco is a country also where agroecological certification exists and is structured around community engagement, such as the PGS (Participatory Guarantee System), but which is informal and not recognized by the state. Ultimately, despite being aware of the benefit that could be potentially brought upon by certification in enhanced marketability, certification remains expensive and not achievable by all. This is also true for other territories such as for producers from Siliana (Tunisia) and Meknes (Morocco) where producers despite understanding the value of certification, do not tend towards its adoption. Their reasoning revolved mainly around its high price and given their conviction that it does not produce higher economic return because there is no form of distinction or differentiation downstream to fetch higher prices as the value chains are state-run and products end up, whether conventional or agroecological, at the same collection and processing centres. Moreover, producers in many territories are also noticed not to have an advanced level of awareness and knowledge when it comes to certification while some have minimal understanding of what certification venue exist, whether those provided by national or international bodies. These are the cases of Luxor (Egypt) and PK-17 (Mauritania). The latter however reports on an informal certification adopted for a specialized end market in attempts to build transparency and traceability, but for foreign target consumer base residing in the city rather than the local population, for whom the products remain unaffordable. Interestingly for Luxor (Egypt), even though producers are not engaging with certification adoption, cases of shifts in farming practices were reported as stimulated by processors, specifically sundrying stations. In these cases, it is the export market requirements that helped introduce this shift when drying stations, in efforts to comply with these requirements, were able to standardize production practices at farm level and in cooperation with primary producers directly. Ultimately, the challenges in certification remain many. They can be summarized as i) being costly and inaccessible for most producers especially when supplied in the majority of times by international bodies, ii) lacking in information and awareness at the level of producers to properly understand feasibility, benefits and even whether it is appropriate or not, iii) differentiation is not clearly distinguishing conventional products from those produced under agroecological practices in downstream channels, and iv) having existing short circuit value chains rely rather on consumer trust whereby making certification not a necessary means of added-value creation in certain territories such as in Laghouat and Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), for example.

Finally, what can be brought forward in this section is that alternative and unconventional routes for value addition could be considered, whether for these value chains in specific when possible, or more generally. These for example could relate to processing techniques that are based on local traditions and knowhow which fall in line with culinary heritage. In the Middle East and North Africa, a specific term in fact exists that directly links to a larger social concept revolving around tradition, indigenous products and ancestral production techniques; especially for food. This term is called “*Beldi*” (pronunciation for Maghreb countries; also known as “Baladi” around the Middle East). The word linguistically even means “country” or “my country” and can therefore be seen to link directly with the origin of products along with a sense of belonging or hometown and homemade (Graf, 2016). In some ways, the term would be similar to that of *terroir products* in their place-based anchoring and shaping along with a larger social inclusion and cooperation aspect to it (Jalkh *et al.*, 2020). Multiple scientific publications discuss this concept and generally describe the importance to culture of heritage. An excerpt from Lucas (2023) mentions that “*beldi refers precisely to an immediate valorization of what it is locally produced as something inherently good and healthy. Indeed, one of the most expressive contemporary uses of the word beldi is precisely the one that converts it synonymous with biological and, accordingly, biological as synonymous with healthy*”. In fact, *beldi* products extend beyond primary production and in fact it encompasses larger food consumption practices, processing and habits to which women directly engage. In Morocco for example, *beldi* products are considered by the population as those grown, produced and processed locally and which have an innate value and characterizable organoleptic qualities and are more trusted as opposed to foreign or imported products; yet not correlating or implying to any higher or lesser quality or value between the two but rather a preference. Examples of typical *beldi* products in Morocco would be cumin, chicken, butter, fruits, vegetables, and many others. In addition, *beldi* directly reflects to a quality linked to a place and which naturally to food, cooking and homemade processing, links directly to women. A particular example of interest in this case would be *Beldi Couscous*¹² which is “hand-made and nowadays, if at all, produced in rural areas, was associated with hard work and patience [...]” (Graf, 2016). Therefore, it would be not only interesting, but essential to find ways of linking value addition, local recognition, and therefore short circuit innovative markets of agroecological value chains adapted to local tastes and with social concepts related to food that already exist.

3.2.3 Status of collective action

When looking if producers organise amongst themselves, the situation quickly becomes clear that in the studied territories in fact, producers tend to follow a more vertical path than horizontal. This means that producers act more individually in their efforts to produce and follow their products downstream

¹² Couscous as a term could refer to both the steamed dish with sauce and vegetables and to the raw grain product, usually made from durum wheat (Graf, 2016).

to the market (individually or through intermediaries), and rarely do group together or organize, whether formally such as in cooperatives or informally. As per the Living Labs reports, it becomes clear that for example in Luxor (Egypt), although the number of cooperatives exceed 5,500 around the country, the sector remains weak due to mainly bureaucracy and weak service provision. The majority of producers in Luxor currently do not seem to be encouraged to join cooperatives. Yet, a few forms of 'Rabita' were reported, and which refer to a formal union of producers together which similarly aims to facilitate access to finances and resources, consolidate efforts of producers engaging in similar cultivations and improve their negotiation power when it comes to collective sales and marketing. Yet, this form of grouping does not seem to be very commonly adopted but is recognized by local state development offices. Similarly in Tunisia's Siliana, vertical market relationships dominate for the two value chains expectedly because they are regulated by the state, and despite that cooperative exist in the country, producer collective associations remain underdeveloped. In Mauritania's PK-17, formal associations are not reported to be present significantly (except for one military veteran's cooperative) and producers have generally a limited awareness and understanding of the benefits of collective action. However, some producers are reported to cooperate informally in attempts to reduce costs, but cooperation remains limited in that territory. This can also be noticed generally in Morocco and Algeria, and the only exception are in fact women-led initiatives and cooperatives in the two territories for the MAPs value chains. As described in the Living labs reports, women play a central role in these value chains and in leadership positions. In Skoura (Morocco), a group of women producers were able to get together and form a cooperative which has shown signs of successes when it comes to consolidating efforts, improving access to resources and information, and ultimately in marketing, socio-economic conditions and networking with external stakeholders for the development of their work. In Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), it is a women association that in fact provides this assistance to the women engaged in the MAPs sector, and they consist a significant number of the cooperative's membership. Other forms of cooperation were also noted in Algeria generally, as the "Thajmaât" values (which is a form of village assembly based on solidarity, cooperation, and shared responsibility aiming for local governance, conflict resolution and community affairs), and the "Twiza" system which is a form of collaborative labor exchange that helps organize harvests and optimize labor access for small producers. Some publications exist on the conditions of cooperative sectors in North Africa (Develtere *et al.*, 2008, El Nour, 2025, Hamamouche *et al.*, 2023). Despite the fact that cooperatives have a diverse dynamic across North African countries, the fact remain that also many challenges still exist around their governance, efficacy, and overall management in reaching capacities in meeting the principles of cooperation as defined by the International Cooperative Alliance (ICA)¹³. These can be described as political and regulatory constraints,

¹³ Seven principles of cooperation are defined by the ICA including: 1) Voluntary and Open Membership, 2) Democratic Member Control, 3) Member Economic Participation, 4) Autonomy and Independence, 5)

economic and financial limitations, socio-cultural specificities, and internal capabilities. Yet, the benefits and successes of the cooperative system are far from unknown (Grace, 2014). Therefore, collective action is one of the pathways that need to be improved in the territories specially to increase consolidation of efforts and access to resources and finances, increase bargaining power in downstream marketing and sales especially facing intermediaries, develop market access, improve accessibility to information and capacity building, advocacy, and risk management. Ultimately, these benefits would be normally expected to reflect on building better conditions and livelihoods, and especially with significant potential for women.

3.2.4 Enabling environment and policy implications

By inspecting the partner reports and when linking to other findings generated in the project, a better picture can be drawn around the enabling environment and policy implications that take part in the Living Labs territories¹⁴. Other than direct players in the value chains, an important role is played by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international cooperation initiatives. Through local partners such as development organisations and research institutions, donors have been a major resource in efforts to integrate concepts of sustainable practices and agroecological principles. Such efforts take shape mainly in the form of research and/or development programs and projects and provide resources as the financial, knowhow and capacity building fronts, and even sometimes in the elaboration and development of related policies. Such dynamics can also be seen reported by the majority of Living Labs, whether directly in their value chain analyses reports or indirectly in other publications. Yet, what remains clear is that governmental bodies whether through the elaborated policies or through direct action, lack in intervening in shifting practices locally. In the majority of countries, public policies have been elaborated to include elements of sustainable cultivation, resource management, and concern for the environment, climate change and biodiversity. Yet, in practice, programs, their monitoring, implementation and translation to direct action remains rather vague. In fact, some paradoxes remain between on one hand prioritizing food security with efforts to increase food production whether in allocated space (land reclamation) or with techniques and resources (as water efficiency and yield), and on another hand, balancing these issues with subsidies in chemical inputs, export objectives, unclear protection or provision of agroecological tools, and financing. Even when having national strategies exist, these are not found to be adapted today locally to distinct territories and their specificities. In fact, the majority of Living Labs seem to recommend a better engagement and intervention by state authorities to improve the support to especially small

Education, Training, and Information, 6) Cooperation among Cooperatives, and 7) Concern for Community, described on the ICA website: <https://ica.coop/en/cooperatives/cooperative-identity>

¹⁴ Specifically in reference to Deliverable D6.2: Analysis of agroecological perspectives in North African intersectoral public policies. A review of trends, strengths and weaknesses, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/12770882>

producers mainly when it comes to access to finance and credit, market improvement, accessibility to resources and information, and overall capacity building.

3.2.5 Gender Dynamics

Looking at the role of women in the functioning of the analysed value chains in the various territories around North Africa, some common observations with pockets of successes emerge. The general most common observation would be that the participation of women mostly takes the form of manual labour and is limited when it comes to decision power, leadership and even access to resources. As noted in the section discussing land tenure (section 3.1.1), land rights have a complex dynamic with respect to women. They are shaped by not only legal frameworks and inheritance rights but a multitude of culture and customs, social factors and religious influence. In fact, even if North African countries recognize women's right to inherit land following introduction of family codes, and even in contexts that are more progressive regarding women's rights such as in Tunisia (Hurch, 2017), the practice still does not reflect that fact. Today, customary and patriarchal social norms still pressure women to renounce their shares to male relatives in return to shared profits generated from these lands. Such customs are highly influenced by the Islamic Sharia law where women normally inherit half the share of men. Statistics on women land ownership in North Africa are quite limited and the World Bank's Gender Data Portal¹⁵ does not show any information for North African countries, except for Mauritania. The portal's most recent map shows that women between the ages of 15 and 49 as sole land owners represent less than 2% in Mauritania. An article from the Middle East Institute published in 2020 mentioned that women represent only around 5%, 4.4%, 6.4% of all landholders in Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia; respectively (Kandeel, 2020).

As for certain value chains, we see that there is an evident participation of women, but it mostly takes the form of low-skill labour force rather than any leadership role. This is particularly true for the tomato production and sundrying in Egypt where women take on labour-intensive activities, representing 20 to 30% of the workforce, as in planting and harvesting, sorting, and post-harvest and sun-drying processing. Women also participate as workforce in the olive value chains in Skoura (Morocco), Siliana (Tunisia) and Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), but also in low-skill manual or seasonal labour related to harvesting and sorting. In Mauritania's PK-17, the number of women as primary producers are also marginal and are seen to be, if involved at all, in informal groups or subsistence farming. The participation of women is also actually specific to certain crops. While their participation in the production cycle is rare or inexistent in cereals (Siliana, Tunisia) and generally in Meknes (Morocco), the MAPs value chains in Skoura (Morocco) and Tizi Ouzou (Algeria) seem to be centred around women. In fact, women in these two value chains have successfully organized themselves in collective groups and their leadership in the economic cycle is strong. In Skoura (Morocco), women-

¹⁵ Available at: <https://genderdata.worldbank.org/en/home>

led cooperatives are emerging and formalize the participation of women. Certain successes can be attributed to their accessing of resources, information, and markets, and ultimately socio-economic inclusion and autonomy. Similarly in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria), the majority of cooperative members engaging in MAPs are women and are involved in production and processing into end products whether fresh produce, dried or processed into essential oils. Women organisations such as 'Tharwa n Yakouren' in fact provide essential support to women in this territory through capacity building, knowhow, and market access. Despite the interesting and promising venue such cooperatives and collective groups provide, women generally remain rather marginalized when it comes to formal decision making and management roles, and remains under-recognized both socially and institutionally. Women in the majority of cases also lack the formality that has otherwise been achieved in Skoura and Tizi Ouzou. Their participation remains highly informal among a male-dominated sector even if their participation is central whether in the production cycle or in supportive roles such as household and family farming activities. Women still face serious barriers when it comes to access to lands, finances, and information, and in the little cases where they do, cultural and traditional social norms commonly intervene and add an additional layer of restriction. Policy focus on women is also highly lacking and efforts in enhancing the rights and empowerment tools for women around North Africa remains highly under-prioritized and underachieved. This is why initiatives such as women-led cooperatives, which have shown important signs of success, should be considered as effective structures to provide women with a venue for their economic participation, formal grouping and governance, and socio-economic empowerment and especially for women-centric value chains such as MAPs or other traditional culinary heritage processes.

3.3 Barriers and opportunities across value chains

Based on our conceptual framework, which examines how various factors influence the participation of smallholder producers in sustainable value chains (mainly Gereffi, 2015; Hearn et al., 2007; Bolwig et al., 2010), the findings regarding barriers across value chains are derived from a transversal mapping of key chain segments outlined in the LL reports. These segments include: Seeds and inputs, Primary production, Processing, Logistics, Services (finance, technology, and others), Market, Consumer and Policy. We then present the identified opportunities. We primarily focus on value chains that are comparable across countries, such as MAPs (Egypt, El-Boghdady Luxor, Morocco, Skoura Boulemane, Algeria - Tizi-Ouzou); Olive oil (Tunisia, Siliana, Algeria - Laghouat, Morocco, Skoura Boulemane, Algeria - Tizi-Ouzou); and Vegetables (Morocco - Ait-Othmane Meknès, Mauritania, Egypt, El-Boghdady Luxor).

Barriers across LLs: MAPS

Seeds and Inputs: In the event of a drought, seedling production declines, causing prices to rise. This affects both seedlings produced by growers for sale, leading to lower yields, and the extraction of oils and collection of aromatic and medicinal plants (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

MAP producers encounter difficulties in accessing inputs and face organizational constraints that restrict profitability, often only covering production costs. While there is an increasing demand for agroecological products, high production costs and dependency on intermediaries impact their competitiveness, particularly in urban markets where agroecology is more highly valued (Morocco).

Primary production: Subsistence farming and restricted access to local markets are caused by limited access to land and undivided land ownership. Farmland's frequent division into small plots makes mechanization and efficient farm management difficult. Women are particularly impacted, as land ownership is passed down through generations to men, excluding women from ownership rights (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

The working conditions and health hazards involved in harvesting and extracting vegetable oils by hand are considered to be challenging by some producers of MAPs. The shortage of labor and the lack of interest among young people in agricultural work are also noted (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Soils and lands in desert areas require significant investments to ensure proper irrigation and maintain soil fertility (Egypt). Insufficient profitability, often limited to covering their production costs (Morocco, Skoura Boulemane)

Processing: Equipment manufacturers have entered the market offering expensive and inefficient oil and essential oil extraction machinery. Due to the growing demand for distillates, many manufacturers have not fully mastered the production process, resulting in essential oils that fail to meet standards and satisfy customers (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Despite reducing overhead costs, storing in domestic spaces may not offer the optimal conditions for preserving quality, particularly for dried plants, essential oils, and floral waters (Morocco, Skoura Boulemane).

Services (finance, technology, other): Unskilled trainers in the production of MAPs and the extraction of oils and their derivatives, are emerging as the demand grows, resulting in substandard products and insufficient support for producers (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Low access to credit is further limited and exacerbates the financial constraints, hindering farmers' ability to invest and adopt new techniques. There is a lack of access to training and technology. (Egypt). Producer needs at the local level are not being met by public services due to limited responsiveness. There is a lack of access to financial support (Morocco, Skoura Boulemane).

Logistics: Production costs are largely influenced by the isolation of the main production area for these aromatic and medicinal plants, which is located at the lowest altitude in Yakouren and involves

very high transport costs. This issue has been brought to the attention of small-scale women producers. Due to limited public transit access, they frequently turn to informal transporters to transport their products to retailers, usually located 2 to 3 km from their plots (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Because of the high cost and irregularity of transportation, the logistics of getting products to markets remains a barrier. Marketing aromatic and medicinal plant products is heavily dependent on logistics, which directly impacts product quality and availability (Morocco). Retailers, especially small-scale ones, frequently utilize their own vehicles for transportation, which allows for flexibility but limits distribution capacity. Sharing storage or micro-warehouses with proper conservation technologies can be explored by cooperatives and producers to improve product quality. Additionally, high transport costs, irregularity, and rising fuel prices remain significant barriers (Morocco).

Policy: While women are active in the MAP value chain, particularly in harvesting and processing (sorting and preparing for sun drying), they still face significant barriers to land ownership, credit, and decision-making positions (Egypt). Complex procedures related to certification requirements constitute operational and cost barriers for farmers (Egypt). Policy gaps at the local level and limited responsiveness to specific product needs are caused by the governance framework responsible for agricultural policy development. In addition, most professional agricultural organizations and cooperatives do not operate effectively. Producers' collective ability to tackle challenges like market access and sustainability is limited by inefficiencies in some cooperatives (Morocco, Skoura Boulemane).

As an opportunity emerging from policies, aromatic and medicinal plants are now permitted on forest land (Law No. 23-21, 2023), which makes up over 50% of the LL territory. Individuals or organizations can get licenses to use public forest land for activities like cultivating these plants, setting up nurseries for forestry or aromatic plants, and developing barren land with plantations (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

Market: The informal and disorganized nature of each segment of the MAP value chain in the living lab area is a barrier to overcome (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Farmers have limited access to market information, such as demand trends, and consumer preferences, which increases their dependence on intermediaries and exacerbates the power imbalance (Egypt). The lack of knowledge about modern marketing channels, such as e-commerce or social media, affects farmers' market access and direct consumer relations (Egypt). Local and weekly markets are particularly competitive for producers and retailers of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP). Retailers in Skoura compete against not only local vendors but also intermediaries from cities such as Fez and Marrakech, who acquire products in bulk at low prices and sell them at substantial margins after packaging (Morocco). The producers are concerned about being able to compete effectively against products from intensive agriculture, which have lower production costs. Accessing their products is difficult for local

consumers due to their low purchasing power (Morocco). The high costs of certification for small producers are a concern for economic feasibility. However, many believe the initial investment could be profitable in the long term, particularly with increased profit margins in export markets (Morocco).

Opportunities: The legal recognition of the aromatic and medicinal plants industry opens new opportunities for its development, particularly in improving the organization of farmers through cooperatives, with a special focus on women (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Specialized shops in the living lab area, a tourist spot along a national road, also present a marketing opportunity (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Investments in supply chain logistics, such as packaging, cold chain facilities, or drying infrastructure, could enhance product quality during transit and boost export potential (Egypt). Additionally, the growing demand for natural and organic products presents an opportunity to expand value-added processing facilities (Egypt), while the local conditions in Luxor offer favourable resources for sun-drying without substantial investment (Egypt). The role of women in labour-intensive activities such as sun-drying is also a crucial element for economic participation (Egypt). Encouraging collective initiatives, like the 'Rabita' approach, could strengthen the industry further (Egypt).

While producers face competition from intensive agriculture, they remain optimistic about the growing demand for natural products. Cooperatives play a vital role in improving market position and facilitating direct consumer sales (Morocco). However, improvements in training, funding, and logistics are necessary for enhanced profitability. Targeted marketing, better infrastructure, and financial support such as micro-credits could further support producers in strengthening their market presence (Morocco). The demand for natural and organic products presents promising growth prospects, making it essential to create ongoing, tailored training programs for producers. Additionally, exploring shared storage or micro-warehouses with proper conservation technologies could help improve product quality and address current economic challenges (Morocco).

Table 5: Barriers across LLs: MAPs

	Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou	Egypt, Luxor	Morocco, Skoura Boulemane
Seeds and inputs	Drought reduces seedling production, raising prices and lowering yields for both seedlings and the extraction of oils and collection of aromatic and medicinal plants.	Producers, who heavily on tomato cultivation, use intensive techniques.	input access constraints
Primary production	Limited access to land and undivided land ownership. Farmland is often fragmented into small plots	Significant investments are necessary to ensure irrigation and soil fertility in desert lands	Insufficient profitability, often limited to covering their production costs.

Processing	Inefficient and costly vegetable oil and essential oil extraction equipment.	MAPs could be processed locally, including drying (onsite rather than in units) and distillation equipment, even though drying units are more focused on the tomato value chain	MAP product quality is linked with processes and storage. Storage in domestic spaces helps reduce overhead costs but may not provide the ideal conditions for preserving quality, especially for dried plants, essential oils, and floral waters.
Logistics	Transport costs account for at least 50% of production costs. Informal transporters.		The logistics of transporting products to markets remains a barrier, because of the high cost and irregularity of transport.
Services (finance, technology, other)	Unskilled trainers in the production of MAPs and the extraction of oils and their derivatives.	Low access to credit is further limited and exacerbates the financial constraints and hinders farmers' ability to invest and adopt new techniques Weak access to training and technology	Limit responsiveness of public services to specific producer needs at the local level. Lack of access to financial support.
Market	Lack of product certification.	Limited market information for farmers. The drying station usually hires farmers to standardize cultivation practices and inputs for export markets. For local markets, they typically negotiate with traders and collectors to obtain wholesale markets, and the price is typically determined before planting. Dependence on intermediaries and exacerbated power imbalance.	Dependence on intermediaries for MAP marketing. Difficult access to urban markets Product quality and availability are undermined due of transport problems.
Consumer		Farmers lack knowledge about modern marketing channels, such as e-commerce or social media, which worsens market access and direct consumer relations.	Urban consumers are more sensitive to agro-ecological MAPS, Local consumer often have low purchasing power.
Policy		Limited women's access to land ownership, credit, and decision-making positions. Farmers also face policy or operational barriers,	There are policy gaps at the local level

		such as those related to the complex procedures related to certification requirements	
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Barriers across LLs: Olive Oil

Inputs: The producers of the LL Tizi-Ouzou, Algeria, face several challenges, however, inputs are not considered a constraint because most producers prioritize agroecology, thereby minimizing their reliance on synthetic chemicals. Fertilizers are often sourced locally, including animal manure and compost (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). This is not the case for the LL Laghouat, where access to inputs is considered a barrier. The high prices of packaging (glass) and animal manure, along with the lack of availability of inputs and packaging, pose significant challenges for producers in Laghouat. (Algeria, Langhouat). The olive sector of Skoura M'Daz faces several significant challenges related to access to inputs, as well as structural and organizational constraints. Producers face difficulties in obtaining quality inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and plant protection products. High-yielding olive varieties are often difficult to acquire. Input costs are prohibitive for many farmers. Organic plant protection products that could improve crop health are very expensive and often exceed producers' budgets, limiting their ability to adopt sustainable cultivation practices (Morocco).

Primary production: The expansion of olive plantations is hindered by the limited availability of agricultural land, making it difficult to increase production despite rising demand. Similarly, the water issue remains critical, particularly during the first two years of olive tree planting. During this period, young trees require regular irrigation to establish strong and resilient root systems. Climatic fluctuations, especially prolonged droughts and increased fire risks, also pose a serious threat to olive groves (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Limited access to land is another barrier in Tunisia, where only 40% of farmers are landowners (Tunisia). Drip irrigation is widely used on all farms in Laghouat and El Assafia due to the scarcity of water in these areas. This method allows for efficient water usage, reducing waste. However, despite its economic benefits, many farmers struggle to control the appropriate water doses for olive trees. This is because there has been little state guidance on the use of this new irrigation system, introduced in the 2000s, which can negatively affect crop health and yields (Algeria, Laghouat).

Despite of the significant contributions of women in olive farming, harvesting, processing and marketing, their involvement is often undervalued in formal decision-making. Nonetheless, they are essential to the farm's workforce, overseeing daily operations and providing crucial support during the harvest period (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

The shortage of agricultural workers due to preferences for other sectors is a major challenge for producers in Laghouat. The workforce is mostly from Saharan regions or northern Algeria, and the

insufficiency of skilled labor for specialized tasks such as pruning, harvesting, and processing contributes to the high labor costs for producers (Algeria, Laghouat).

Processing: Barriers in processing are common across the three studied living labs. The processing units of some producers are small, and due to the limited scale of their operations, most are not actively engaged in extensive commercialization. This was not identified as a barrier in the report (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). In the case of Laghouat, barriers to processing include a lack of qualified labor (Algeria, Laghouat). The absence of modern processing equipment and facilities, as well as insufficient presses and storage, limits both production capacity and the quality of the final product (Morocco). Only farmers with the necessary financial resources can access processing directly (Tunisia).

Services (finance, technology, others): Modern technologies like irrigation management systems and mechanized harvesting are restricted due to a lack of technical training. Additionally, there is insufficient institutional and financial support, with a notable absence of subsidies and low-interest loans to facilitate growth and development (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Minimal state support has been given for the use of the new irrigation system, even though it has been installed for several years (Algeria, Laghouat). Farmer dependence within the value chain is caused by financial barriers. There is a significant shortage of resources, along with high production costs (labour and inputs being perceived as excessively expensive) as the main barriers reported at the production level. The absence of adequate storage facilities results in substantial losses, estimated to range from 15% to 25% of total production (Morocco).

Market: Commercial activities are often limited for small family-owned farms, which, unlike large investors with stronger financial solvency and better social and economic networks, face significant barriers in accessing public funding and technical support. This disparity restricts their ability to modernize production methods and expand their businesses (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Power imbalances exist due to the small number of wholesalers, leading to an oligopsonistic market (Algeria, Laghouat). Marketing products is a challenge for Algerian producers because intermediaries demand high quality while offering prices below the product's value, influenced by the quantities sold. This issue is particularly evident in oil mills, which seek to certify and export their products (Algeria, Laghouat).

Verbal and informal contracts create risks, as prices and quantities are not agreed upon in advance, and orders can be cancelled. Agreements are often informal and vary by buyer. Negotiations are typically satisfactory, but producers with heavy workloads may accept any price. Direct sales to consumers are easier than working with intermediaries. Retailers face challenges, including high rental costs, poor logistics, few wholesalers dominating the market (close to an oligopsony), and

limited storage, which affect market balance and product management. These issues also apply to the palm dates value chain (Algeria, Laghouat).

The olive oil value chain in Tunisia faces several challenges, including dispersed governance and decision-making power across smallholder farmers, cooperatives, and private sector actors. Despite increasing government support and international recognition, issues persist with market access, quality control, and power imbalances between small producers and larger players in the value chain (Tunisia).

In Tunisia, farmers avoid the costs of gathering, transporting, and processing olives by selling standing crops, though this limits their ability to capture more value. Another option is selling olives at oil presses, where farmers bear collection costs but avoid storage and marketing costs, losing control over the final product. Larger-scale growers with financial autonomy sell directly to consumers, covering transportation and processing costs, but this option is less accessible to smaller producers (Tunisia).

Producers are often dependent on intermediaries for the sale of their olives, which can lead to transparency and fairness issues in transactions. This dependence reduces their bargaining power and makes them vulnerable to price fluctuations imposed by intermediaries. Limited access to broader markets prevents them from selling their products at competitive prices (Morocco).

The cost of transportation can be as high as 20% of the selling price due to the distance to reach processing centres or urban markets. This cost, often borne by producers, becomes a barrier to profitability, especially for small farmers who lack access to efficient transport infrastructure. Additionally, the absence of adequate storage facilities results in considerable losses, estimated to range from 15% to 25% of total production (Morocco).

Consumers and direct sales: Olive oil consumption is primarily urban, as rural inhabitants often produce their own oil. In some regions, consumption remains limited, particularly in areas where cheaper alternative oils are preferred. While olive oil is widely consumed in certain areas, it has not yet become fully integrated into the eating habits of the city of Laghouat (Algeria, Laghouat).

Farmers are not inclined to adopt certifications because organic and agroecological (AE) products are not differentiated in the market. As a result, there are no premium prices to encourage farmers to change their agricultural practices. Currently, selling prices in the conventional market are quite attractive, so there is little incentive to adopt certifications (Tunisia).

Around 80% of producers recognize the benefits of joining cooperatives or other collective organizations, such as improved bargaining power and better sector organization. They also see it as a way to meet market requirements, such as certifications. However, 20% remain cautious due to

past unfulfilled promises by cooperatives and concerns about losing control over production. As a result, they prefer independence despite market challenges (Morocco).

Certifications require not only rigorous agricultural practices but also technical and financial support that many local producers lack. The costs of audits and follow-up to obtain these certifications represent a significant barrier, especially for small farmers (Morocco).

Policy: The Algerian government has implemented specific policies to encourage olive cultivation, including financial support for establishing new olive groves, subsidies for irrigation systems, and funding for technical training programs for producers. However, the eligibility criteria for many of these programs often favor larger operations, making it difficult for smaller producers to compete on an equal footing (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). According to the report, the Algerian state could play a role by organizing the logistics of the value chain, supporting producers through subsidies or training, and providing financial aid to improve storage infrastructure. Additionally, introducing commercial regulations aimed at regulating the activities of wholesalers and reducing oligopsony practices would be beneficial. Finally, targeted support for consumers with modest purchasing power could facilitate access to these products and encourage their consumption (Algeria, Langhouat).

Regarding land access, only 40% of olive growers in Tunisia are landowners. In Tunisia, the olive oil value chain is managed by the National Office of Oil (NOO), which holds a monopolistic status. The NOO intervenes in market regulation and export development (most of the national production is destined for export), promoting the quality of Tunisian oil, although none of it is certified as organic, for a non-differentiated market. To remain competitive in the international olive oil commodity market, the NOO distributes subsidized fertilizers and phytosanitary inputs (up to 20%) in Tunisia. There is a paradox between a public policy promoting agroecological (AE) practices on one hand, and on the other hand subsidizing chemical inputs. Although the subsidization of chemical inputs primarily concerns the strategic cereal sector, this policy also affects the olive oil value chain (Tunisia).

At the national level, Morocco's Law 25-06 for Distinctive Signs of Origin and Quality (SDOQ) and the "Morocco" label for olive oil provide official recognition that enhances market value, prices, and distribution access. Organic certification, governed by Law 39-12, is mostly adopted by export-oriented producers. In the Skoura region, however, there is no formal or informal certification for olive oil; its reputation for quality is the only form of recognition (Morocco).

In Skoura there is a high complexity of the institutional framework, with public structures, producer organizations, and external actors. The Agricultural Advisory Centre (CCA) is the main public institution offering technical advice, but the Provincial Directorate of Agriculture (DPA) in Missouri can cause delays due to its distance. Several Professional Agricultural Organizations (OPAs/cooperatives) exist, but few are functional, limiting their ability to support producers. The lack

of active NGOs or development agents in Skoura further reduces available resources and support for local initiatives (Morocco).

Opportunities: In Tizi-Ouzou, the growing number of modern oil mills (with some producers also having on-site processing units) has significantly reduced labor time and increased production efficiency, in contrast to the traditional method of extracting olive oil by hand, which required considerable effort (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

The increasing demand for oil produced through traditional methods, free from chemicals, presents a significant opportunity. More consumers are seeking healthy, natural food products as they become increasingly aware of the harmful effects of conventional products on health. This trend benefits producers who adopt environmentally sustainable agricultural practices that also protect human health (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

Although some Algerian growers interviewed say marketing is declining due to a lack of sales outlets and the inconsistent availability of intermediaries, most of the interviewed olive growers in Algeria report growth in their business activity. This is primarily due to the diversification of marketing channels, especially sales via social networks, which help expand outlets and attract new customers. This trend is also related to the profitability of the activity and the increase in production from one year to the next (Algeria, Langhouat).

Tunisian olive oil is increasingly recognized in the international market, which could provide farmers with opportunities to benefit from the country's growing reputation. Other opportunities include informal relationships among the surveyed farmers, such as mutual assistance during planting (soil preparation, borrowing farm equipment, etc.). A reorientation of policy to promote agroecology (AE) and enhance positioning in differentiated markets would help reduce vulnerability to the volatility of commodity markets (Tunisia).

All olive oil producers try to convince their customers that their product is of high quality. They emphasize the exceptional characteristics of their oil, such as its rich taste and distinctive aromas, and claim that it offers significant nutritional benefits. At the same time, they stress that their production is environmentally friendly, with no chemical inputs. Some producers also highlight that they consume their own olive oil. This self-consumption demonstrates their confidence in the quality of their product and creates a genuine connection between the producer and the consumer (Algeria, Langhouat).

The olive oil value chain in Skoura Boulemane is considered to have significant development potential. By integrating agroecological practices and enhancing the value of olive oil through quality labels, producers could not only increase their yields but also improve their competitiveness in the national market. To achieve this, efforts must be made to strengthen organizational structures,

including the creation and support of cooperatives that can facilitate access to inputs, markets, and training necessary for the modernization of production techniques (Morocco).

Producers in Skoura agree that obtaining a quality label, such as SDOQ or organic certification, would increase selling prices, improve sector organization, and help access new markets. However, they emphasize the need for government support, including grants and training, to make certification processes sustainable and enhance the sector's competitiveness (Morocco).

Table 6: Barriers across LL: Olive Oil

	Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou	Algeria, Laghouat	Tunisia, Siliana	Morocco, Skoura Boulemane
Seeds and inputs	Most producers prioritize agroecological thereby minimizing the reliance on synthetic chemicals. Fertilizers are often sourced locally, including animal manure and compost	High prices of packaging (glass) and animal manure. Lack of availability.	Very high prices and unavailability of inputs especially for the small farmers without financial support	Producers face difficulties in obtaining quality inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and plant protection products. High-yielding olive varieties are often difficult to acquire. Input costs are prohibitive for many farmers. Organic plant protection products that could improve crop health are very expensive and often exceed producers' budgets, limiting their ability to adopt sustainable cultivation practices
Primary production	Restricted availability of agricultural land. Water issue remains critical Young trees require regular irrigation Women's labour in production is undervalued in formal decision-making	Many farmers do not control of drip irrigation systems for appropriate water doses for olive trees. Scarce agricultural workers.	Restricted access to land. Only 40% of farmers are owners.	
Processing	The extraction of olive oil was once done by hand, requiring hard work, the growing number of modern oil mills now significantly	Lack of qualified labour for specialized tasks like pruning, harvesting, and processing adds to	Only farmers with financial capacities can access directly to processing	Lack of modern infrastructure for processing and marketing olive oil is also a brake on their

	<p>reduces labour time and increases production efficiency.</p> <p>Women's labour in processing is undervalued in formal decision-making</p>	<p>the high labour costs for producers.</p>		<p>development. For example, the lack of suitable presses and storage facilities limits production capacity and quality of the final product.</p>
Logistics		<p>Poor logistics organization. limited storage</p>	<p>High transportation costs make small farmers more prone to dealing with middlemen</p>	<p>Cost of transportation can be as much as 20% of the selling price, due to the distance to reach processing centres or urban markets.</p>
Services (finance, technology, others)	<p>Limited access to modern technologies: Irrigation management systems; mechanized harvesting. Limited technical training. Absence of adequate institutional and financial support. Lack of subsidies, low-interest loans.</p>	<p>Little support from the state on the use of this new irrigation system installed since years</p>	<p>Limited access (sometimes impossibility) to financing the activity</p>	<p>lack of adequate storage facilities results in considerable losses, estimated at between 15% and 25% of total production.</p>
Market	<p>Small family-owned farms, unlike large investors who benefit from stronger financial solvency and better social and economic networks, small-scale producers often face significant barriers in accessing public funding and technical support. This disparity limits their ability to modernize production methods and expand commercial activities.</p> <p>Women's labour in marketing is undervalued in formal decision-making</p>	<p>Power imbalance. Few numbers of wholesaler close to a oligopsony market Verbal and informal contracts create risks, as prices and quantities are not agreed upon in advance, and orders can be cancelled.</p>	<p>There is no product differentiation. Price volatility result in farmer profit vulnerability. Sale of Standing Crops; Sale of Olives Gathered at Oil Presses; Sale of Oil to Final Consumers</p>	<p>Limited access to broader markets, which prevents them from selling their products at competitive prices. producers are often dependent on intermediaries for the sale of their olives, which can lead to transparency and fairness issues in transactions. This dependence reduces their bargaining power and makes them vulnerable to price fluctuations imposed by intermediaries.</p>
Consumers and direct sales		<p>Olive oil consumers are mostly urban, because in rural</p>	<p>AE or differentiated product is not</p>	<p>Larger-scale growers with financial</p>

		<p>areas, the inhabitants often produce their own oil. Consumption is still limited in some regions, especially in areas where alternative oils, often cheaper, are preferred. Although olive oil is a product widely consumed in some environments, it is not yet fully rooted in all the eating habits of the city of Laghouat.</p>	<p>recognized by consumers</p> <p>Direct oil sales to consumer is mainly chosen by large-scale growers with financial autonomy and established customer bases.</p> <p>Farmers' unwillingness to adopt certifications is explained by the fact that they see no benefit in it, since the products are not acknowledged recognized ion the market</p>	<p>autonomy sell directly to consumers, covering transportation and processing costs, but this option is less accessible to smaller producers.</p>
Policy	<p>The Algerian government has implemented policies to promote olive cultivation, including financial support for new groves, irrigation subsidies, and technical training. However, the eligibility criteria often favour larger operations, making it difficult for smaller producers to compete fairly.</p>		<p>The national office of oil, which has a monopolistic status. all the farmers surveyed belong to the regional agricultural and Fisheries Union, which is a syndicate organization enabling them to access the subsidies and support provided by the government.</p>	

Barriers across LL: Vegetables (Onions and Turnip, Tomatoes)

Inputs: Tomato production in Egypt relies on importing hybrid seeds and using chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Egypt). Onion seeds are often imported from the Netherlands. Twenty-five percent of farmers buy seeds from local markets, but these sources are often unreliable and anonymous. Forty percent of farmers produce their own seeds and seedlings, while thirty-five percent purchase seedlings from local and nearby nurseries. However, farmers cannot always control the quality, authenticity, or genetic potential of the seeds they cultivate, including their origins (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès). The excessive use of chemical inputs can lead to long-term soil degradation (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès).

Primary production: The dominance of smallholder farms, where many producers own less than 0.42 hectares, leads them to rely heavily on tomato cultivation. Producers use intensive techniques, such as crop rotation, to maximize land use and increase productivity. Some have expanded by reclaiming desert lands, but this requires significant investments in irrigation and soil fertility (Egypt). Farm size is also a barrier affecting onion yields, making farmers less competitive compared to the large estates in the Saïs plain. Family farms barely exceed three hectares, with an average size of only about 2 hectares (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès).

Water scarcity, inefficient water use (such as flood irrigation), high infrastructure costs, and reliance on middlemen limit small-scale farmers' economic potential. Fragmented land ownership, lack of technical knowledge, and the environmental burden of reclaimed desert lands further hinder the adoption of sustainable farming practices and agroecological methods (Egypt).

As a highly water-intensive crop, the sustainability of tomato cultivation is threatened by frequent and ongoing droughts. Irrigation costs have risen due to higher temperatures and increased energy prices (especially gas), leading to a noticeable reduction in areas dedicated to onion cultivation. Intensive irrigation, especially in peri-urban production areas, places pressure on groundwater resources, which is becoming an increasing problem in the Sahel region (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès).

Seasonal agricultural workers face difficult working conditions, often without social protection or security, while working hard for low wages. Many producers live in poverty or are highly dependent on agricultural yields for their livelihoods (Mauritania, PK17).

Processing: Farmers struggle with financial limitations and cannot afford to delay selling their produce due to urgent debt repayment obligations, even though drying onions requires significant labour and infrastructure (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès).

Logistics: The lack of access to transportation, distribution, storage, and infrastructure is preventing access to markets (Egypt). Independent producers and retired military personnel use personal cars or rented taxis to transport onions to markets and shops, while the Nouakchott region uses a bus to harvest the crops of project beneficiaries. Access difficulties prevent the sale of 64% of harvests, which are unable to be sold due to transportation costs that range from 10% to 20% of the sale price. (Mauritania, PK17).

Services (finance, technology, others): The lack of access to essential services such as finance, technology, and training, as well as limited access to credit and market information, is a challenge for farmers. These barriers hinder their ability to improve productivity and market reach, making it difficult for them to expand or adopt new technologies. Additionally, limited market access further compounds the challenges they face (Egypt). Small onion producers have limited access to financing and credit,

which hinders their ability to invest in better irrigation infrastructure, quality seeds, and modern agricultural equipment (Mauritania, PK17).

Market: Producers rely heavily on middlemen for inputs and market access, which limits their ability to improve economic returns (Egypt). There is no law regulating the sale of onions in the market (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès). Consumption needs of nearby urban metropolitan areas, in the village of Ait Othmane, almost all farmers opt for on-site sales, eliminating the need for post-harvest transport. Intermediaries and wholesalers manage the transport but also maximize their profits by lowering prices. The financial weakness of producers diminishes their competitiveness against large-scale onion producers. They begin production by taking on debt, with varying levels depending on the farm, and must repay these debts by the end of the season. This financial pressure forces them to make deals with intermediaries even before the product reaches maturity. This practice, known as "vente par Hsira" (or carpet sale), means transactions are conducted directly in the field, before harvest. Lack of a strong cooperative organization exposes them even more to the pressures of intermediaries and wholesalers (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès).

There is a high price volatility affecting onion producers due to strong competition, seasonal variations, and demand fluctuations. This makes profitability uncertain and reduces the incentives to invest in production (Mauritania, PK17). Turnips are sold fresh by producers: 36% of the products are sold on-site, 41% are sold directly to retailers, grocers, restaurateurs, and shopkeepers, and 23% are taken to markets and sold to wholesalers (in cases of overproduction to avoid the risk of spoilage) and retailers. Products sold on-site are purchased by producer-merchants and intermediaries (Mauritania, PK17).

Consumer and direct sales: Significant barriers persist due to the absence of certification and the use of middlemen for pricing and resources (Egypt). Direct sales at the field are the least economically advantageous method. While it eliminates transportation costs, it also lowers profit margins as products are sold at very low prices, preventing the producer from earning a fair return. This approach, however, may be used during periods of overproduction to avoid the risk of loss (Mauritania, PK17).

Policy: Conventional, input-intensive farming models are still preferred by the current policy frameworks, with subsidies and incentives that are more suitable for large-scale, export-oriented industrial agriculture than smallholder-based farming (Egypt).

Opportunities:

There is significant opportunity to create high-value products for export, especially as sun-dried tomatoes are uncommon in local cuisine (Egypt). The growth potential, driven by the rising demand for organic products, presents smallholder farmers with sustainable income opportunities, particularly through sun-drying stations. Agroecological practices, encouraged by export demand, alongside

producer collectives, can help reduce costs and improve negotiating power. Training programs can further promote sustainable farming practices (Egypt).

The role of women presents an important opportunity for economic participation in both value chains, particularly in Luxor, where women largely contribute to processing and sun-drying activities (Egypt). Collective models such as cooperatives or the 'Rabita' model should also be encouraged to pool resources, share knowledge, and enhance bargaining power with buyers (Egypt). Luxor's agricultural development aligns with Egypt's goals of boosting productivity and export-oriented agriculture. Partnerships with processors could enhance farmers' profits, but without external support such as subsidies, capacity building, and improved market access, transitioning to agroecological value chains remains challenging (Egypt).

The local geo-climatic conditions in Luxor provide the necessary resources and favorable conditions for high-quality sun-drying, with minimal investment required (Egypt).

In Mauritania, the government could play a key role by implementing policies and programs to support local onion production, reduce onion imports and taxes on agricultural inputs, and promote food self-sufficiency initiatives. Training initiatives to improve farmers' skills in onion cultivation techniques, farm management, and market access could enhance production efficiency and competitiveness in the markets (Mauritania, PK17).

Table 7: Barriers across LL: Vegetables (Onions and Turnip, Tomatoes)

	Tomatoes (Egypt)	Onions and turnip (Mauritania)	Onions (Morocco, Ait-Othmane Meknès)
Seeds and inputs provision	Importing hybrid seeds, such as tomatoes, and using chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Egypt).	Excessive use of chemical inputs contributes to long-term soil degradation, particularly in the Sahel region.	Imported seeds (often from the Netherlands). Local markets of seeds are often unreliable quality.
Primary production	High levels of poverty and low investment power of producers. Fragmented land ownership and limited technical knowledge about sustainable farming practices make it difficult for producers to scale operations or adopt agroecological methods. Inefficient water use (such as flood irrigation)	Difficult working conditions, often without social protection or security, hard and poorly paid. Many producers living in poverty. Intensive irrigation in peri-urban areas puts pressure on groundwater resources.	Highly water-intensive. Irrigation costs High energy price. Decreased cultivated areas Low yields. Small farms (2 hectares average).
Processing			Drying onions requires significant labor and infrastructure (Traditional dryers).

Logistics	Inadequate access for transportation/distribution, storage and infrastructure to access markets	64% of harvest cannot be sold due to access difficulties.	High cost of transports influences the choice of marketing
Services (finance, technology, other)	Weak access to training and technology. Low financing and credit access. Limited access of farmers to market information.	Small onion and turnip producers have limited access to financing and credit, which hinders their ability to invest in better irrigation infrastructure, quality seeds, and modern agricultural equipment.	Financial weakness of producers diminishes their competitiveness. Lack of state subsidies or the complexity of procedures.
Market	Limited market access. Producers rely heavily on middlemen for inputs and market access, which limits their ability to improve economic returns.	Onion producers in Nouakchott face price fluctuations due to competition. Turnips, 36% are sold on-site to merchants and intermediaries.	Consumption in nearby urban areas. Most farmers opt for on-site sales, eliminating the need for post-harvest transport. The intermediaries and wholesalers handle the transport, but lower the prices.
Consumer and direct sales	Lack of certification, and the reliance on middlemen for pricing and resources remain significant barriers.		Lack of a strong cooperative organization make farmers vulnerable to intermediaries and wholesalers.
Policy	Current policy frameworks continue to favour conventional, input-intensive farming models, with subsidies and incentives more aligned with large-scale industrial agriculture than with the smallholder-based	Agricultural policies aimed at improving productivity and competitiveness in agriculture.	No law regulates the sale of products in the market.

3.4 Transversal Potential of Emerging Agroecological Value Chains in North Africa

Following the 10 Elements of Agroecology by FAO (2018), we identified the agroecological practices applied within the studied value chains. These elements are: Diversity, Synergies, Efficiency, Co-creation and sharing of knowledge, Human and social values, Culture and food traditions; Responsible governance and Circular and solidarity economy. First, we present the main description of each element, followed by an overview of the key agroecological practices identified in the living labs.

Diversity: Agroecological diversification seeks for improving the ecosystem services like pollination and soil health by improving the species and genetic variety, while minimizing erosion and improving nutrient cycling. It promotes resilience to climate change, supports sustainability, and creates new market opportunities (FAO, 2018).

The reports show a number of practices: Crop rotation that incorporates MAPs to maintain soil fertility, manage pests, and optimize water usage (Egypt, Luxor). Turnip crop rotation with legumes to enrich

the soil with nitrogen, using cover crops to prevent soil erosion and increase soil fertility (Mauritania, PK17). The application of livestock manure to improve soil fertility, crop rotation, and fallow land in onion cultivation (Morocco, Ait Othmane). Cereal farming systems that benefit from cereal residues after threshing, using them for feeding and grazing livestock, mulching, and applying manure as a soil improver to help maintain soil health (Tunisia, Siliana).

Synergies: focus on creating diversified systems that include combined crops, livestock, aquatic animals, and trees, while sustainably managing soil, water, and farm resources (FAO, 2018).

Olive oil producers and those cultivating MAPs use intercropping with fruit trees, cereals, and legumes to improve soil fertility and protect against erosion (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). Intercropping is common among olive producers due to limited land access. Other practices include crop rotation, composting, and the use of organic inputs. In Algeria (Tizi-Ouzou), beekeeping is combined with olive cultivation. It was found that some producers incorporate indigenous crops in synergy with cereals, as well as the interaction of cereals with other agricultural activities, particularly legumes, livestock, forage crops, and fruit trees (mainly olive and almond trees) (Tunisia, Siliana). Onion intercropping, such as with olive trees, is practiced in Morocco (Ait Othmane). In turnip cultivation, intercropped legumes like beans and peas fix nitrogen in the soil, reducing the need for chemical fertilizers. Additionally, lettuce and radishes planted between rows of turnips help reduce weeds. The integration of fruit trees or windbreaks is also practiced (Mauritania, PK17).

MAPs are integrated into agroforestry systems, often in association with fig and olive trees, and exclusively use organic fertilizers (manure) (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Most MAPs are harvested from wild plants, primarily by women (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). Date farming practices include rational water resource management, crop associations and rotations, integration of agriculture-livestock systems, biological control of diseases, and the co-creation and sharing of knowledge. Oasis systems have a three-tiered organization, consisting of date palms, fruit trees, and market garden crops. Agroforestry in date cultivation combines date palms with other trees such as citrus, olive, and pomegranate, as well as medicinal plants. Goat herding is integrated to control weeds in older date palm groves (Algeria, Laghouat). The onion value chain shares cropping spaces with other vegetables like tomatoes, potatoes, lettuce, and carrots. It plays a crucial role in urban and peri-urban agriculture, food security, and local economic dynamics. Synergies with other value chains diversify farmers' incomes and promote sustainable agricultural practices (Mauritania, PK17).

Efficiency: Refers to moving away from systems that rely heavily on inputs to those driven by knowledge, the use of natural resources (e.g., solar energy), recycling, and fostering diversity. The desired outcome is lower costs, reduced environmental impact, and improved financial well-being for producers (FAO, 2018). Innovative sun-drying processes minimize energy costs (Egypt, Luxor). Some farmers, including small producers within the Turnip Value Chain, have adopted irrigation systems

like drip irrigation (Mauritania, PK17). Onions are a cash crop with good profitability when irrigation is well managed and yields are optimized (Mauritania, PK17). Smaller farms implement agroecological practices such as composting, intercropping, and integrated pest management to produce at low cost and stabilize the yields of their rain-fed agriculture (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). The MAPs value chain can diversify farmers' income sources and contribute to domestic economic growth and export markets (Egypt, Luxor). Small-scale producers capitalize on the growing demand for organic and healthy products by marketing spices and aromatic plants (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Skoura olive oil is renowned for its exceptional quality and is produced using traditional cultivation and pressing techniques adapted to local climatic conditions. Olive oil production is a pillar of the local economy and contributes to the preservation of cultural practices (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). Onion cultivation uses irrigation systems such as rain and drip irrigation to minimize water waste, while mint cultivation primarily relies on manual weeding and harvesting (Morocco, Ait Othmane).

Co-creation and Sharing of Knowledge: This process generates solutions based on both traditional and scientific practices to address specific contexts. It involves farmers' expertise in biodiversity, management, and markets. Sharing innovations, developing farmers' skills, and encouraging collective and inclusive participation, especially for women and youth, are greatly supported by education and training (FAO, 2018). The MAPs value chain can lead to greater autonomy for women involved in production, training, and marketing (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). The State has integrated MAPs into research programs, particularly those with socio-economic impacts. A new law on the management of forest estates, promulgated in 2023, paves the way for the planting of aromatic and medicinal plants (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). The MAPs value chain in Skoura is based on collaboration between producers, mainly organized as cooperatives, which facilitate the sharing of resources and knowledge. These collective structures allow producers to strengthen their market position and access short channels that promote direct sales to consumers (Morocco, Skoura M'daz).

Human and Social Values: Promotes gender and intergenerational inclusion, tackles inequalities, strengthens autonomy and adaptive capacities, empowering communities, and enabling individuals to actively drive change (FAO, 2018). Cultivating MAPs provides livelihood opportunities for many rural communities, particularly smallholder farmers. It is a labor-intensive sector that creates employment across the value chain, from cultivation and harvesting to processing and marketing. The sector empowers marginalized groups, including women, who often play key roles in production and value-added processing (Egypt, Luxor). MAPs play an important role in local development, especially in terms of women's participation. Women play a central role in the harvesting of wild plants, using environmentally friendly techniques. The development of women's cooperatives is a promising way to strengthen the economic empowerment of women gatherers (Morocco, Skoura M'daz).

The organization of olive oil production in Kabylie is still inspired by the values of “thajmaât,” a traditional institution deeply rooted in the local culture. The “thajmaât” system is built around the principles of solidarity, cooperation, and shared responsibility, often in the context of agricultural activities such as harvesting, irrigation, or the maintenance of shared resources. It is anchored in social values that promote mutual aid, collective action, and community support (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Within the MAPs value chain, the role of women-led organizations in promoting local heritage products through various activities, including fairs, exhibitions, and development or research projects, such as the Association of Women "Tharwa Yakouren," is a key driver for inclusiveness (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou).

The number of informal relationships among the farmers was identified, including seed donations or sales (mainly during scarcity periods), mutual assistance during sowing (such as soil preparation, borrowing farm equipment, etc.), and support with harvesting and transporting cereals to collection centres (Tunisia, Siliana). Traditional knowledge of mint’s value chain, including practices like drying, syrup production, and essence extraction, is still widely used. Mint cultivation continues to bypass intermediaries and wholesalers, with producers favouring direct sales at local weekly markets. Promotional initiatives, backed by a well-organized group of producers, have the potential to be both unique and promising (Morocco, Ait Othmane). Consumers' preferences for agroecological products are mainly driven by the perception of better quality, environmental friendliness and increased food safety (Morocco, Skoura M'daz).

Culture and food traditions: Promoting healthy diets and preserving cultural food traditions, genetic diversity in food for vital nutrients, cultural identity, landscapes, and traditional knowledge (FAO, 2018). For example, MAPs are key ingredients in condiments and sauces, reflecting a deep cultural connection to the land, where food and health are intertwined. MAPs are ingrained in local habits as kitchen products, traditional remedies, treatments, and for aesthetic uses by women. Local know-how is passed on, especially through women (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou), and MAPs symbolize the cultural identity of the region. They have been used for generations for their medicinal and culinary virtues (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). Olive oil production contributes to the preservation of cultural practices (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). In the Kabylie region, it is a symbol of local heritage, significantly contributing to the region's cultural and economic identity. Olive oil mills dating back to the Roman era are found in the region. The olive tree is so sacred that, until recently, olive trees were considered a separate part of inheritance distribution, separate from the division of land (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). The value chains studied are an essential part of the population's diet, whether as a staple food or a strong cultural anchor.

Responsible governance: Transparency, accountability, and inclusivity encourage the adoption of agroecological practices by farmers. Land and natural resource governance are crucial, as many rural populations depend on ecosystem services and biodiversity but face challenges from insecure access

(FAO, 2018). Governance among producers is predominantly informal, with smallholder farmers making individual decisions regarding their production processes. Producers in these value chains lack formal cooperatives or associations that could provide collective bargaining power or shared resources. Encouraging collective action through cooperatives and farmer groups is recommended to consolidate efforts, augment negotiation power, and reduce dependence on middlemen. Reforms are needed in service provision and management (Egypt, Luxor).

Circular and solidarity economy: Reducing negative externalities and promoting the efficient use of natural resources through fair, locally-driven solutions, equitable, and sustainable markets. Strengthening food supply chains (e.g., short supply chains) can boost smallholder incomes (FAO, 2018).

Repurposing by-products, such as olive residues, as organic fertilizers or animal feed reinforces the circular approach of production systems (Algeria, Tizi-Ouzou). Waste from MAPs and olive residue production can be repurposed for animal feed or compost (Morocco, Skoura M'daz).

For olive oil and MAPs, there is a need to create and strengthen local markets for agroecological products, as well as improve infrastructure for processing, storage, and marketing to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices and ensure long-term economic viability (Morocco, Skoura M'daz). The MAPs value chain remains primarily oriented toward the national market due to a lack of suitable structures for direct exports (Morocco, Skoura M'daz).

The date value chain is shaped by small-scale farming, traditional cultivation methods, and limited mechanization. Key actors include farmers, local intermediaries, and small traders, with a dominant reliance on short supply circuits. Crop residues are used as mulch in addition to manure and compost. However, the absence of certification and geographical indication labels restricts competitiveness (Algeria, Laghouat).

Recommendations

To foster the potential of agroecology by creating conditions that enable it to thrive and make a positive impact, studies emphasize the importance of co-creating and sharing knowledge to enhance capabilities, alongside fostering responsible governance and inclusive participation. Key actions include strengthening entrepreneurial skills through research and development, using demonstration sites to showcase transferable practices. Cooperatives and professional organizations may play a crucial role in knowledge sharing, improving production techniques, and securing financing, while training farmers in agroecological practices and innovative processing techniques enhances both product quality and cooperation. Encouraging collective action through cooperatives and farmer groups is recommended to consolidate efforts, amplify negotiating power, and reduce dependence on middlemen. Additionally, supporting community development, especially for women in rural areas

who are often excluded from key legal rights such as land ownership, improves livelihoods and encourages shared resource management. Creating legal frameworks and supporting local policies will promote sustainable practices, while financial support will facilitate the adoption of agroecological techniques. Integrating circular economy principles, such as minimizing inputs and recycling, can help reduce costs and environmental impact. Furthermore, solidarity networks and mutual support systems, like Participatory Guarantee Systems (PGS), are considered important for improving market access, reducing the influence of middlemen, and fostering sustainable value chains.

Chapter 4

Value chain analysis report for the Laghouat Living Lab (Algeria) *Dates and Olive Oil*

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Chapter 4. Value chain analysis report for the Laghouat Living Lab (Algeria) – Dates and Olive Oil

Summary

This study explores the value chains of dates and olive oil in Laghouat, focusing on their characteristics, key actors, and commercial dynamics. Both sectors are deeply rooted in local traditions and hold economic potential, yet they face structural and operational challenges that hinder their development and competitiveness.

The date value chain is shaped by small-scale farming, traditional cultivation methods, and limited mechanization. Key actors include farmers, local intermediaries, and small traders, with a dominant reliance on direct sales. Despite the strong consumer preference for local varieties like Bentkebala and Tadala, production has declined due to labor shortages, particularly in harvesting and pollination. Soil degradation and limited access to organic fertilizers further constrain yields.

The olive oil value chain is relatively new, developed through state-supported irrigation programs. However, many producers lack the technical expertise required for optimal irrigation and tree pruning, reducing productivity. The sector involves small and medium-sized farmers, local oil mills, and retailers, yet market access remains limited due to the absence of certification and branding.

Both value chains depend on short supply circuits, ensuring profitability but limiting market expansion. The absence of certification and geographical indication labels restricts competitiveness, although lessons from Morocco show that certified products achieve better market positioning.

Key findings indicate that improving technical skills, increasing access to organic fertilizers, and encouraging certification could enhance both sectors. Additionally, strengthening coordination among farmers, traders, and policymakers is essential to optimize market opportunities.

Our research shows that targeted interventions in production, processing, and marketing strategies could significantly improve the efficiency, sustainability, and profitability of the date and olive oil value chains in Laghouat.

4.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

The Laghouat region is located 400 km south of the capital, Algiers. It is located at a latitude of 33°48' north and a longitude of 02°35' east, with an average altitude of 752 meters. (C.D.F, 2016)

The Laghouat living lab, located in the Oued M'Zi valley in the wilaya of Laghouat, 400 km south of Algiers, includes the municipalities of Laghouat and El Assafia, which represent 11% of the wilaya's UAA.

The local agricultural system is characterized by a dominance of small family farms (70% are less than 5 ha) practicing diversified agriculture.

Following the survey carried out among 34 farmers in the living lab as part of task T4.2 of the NATAE project, we were able to identify 4 main types of farms:

Table 8: Types of farms in the living lab of Laghouat, Algeria

Type of operation	Description
Breeding	This type represents cattle herders of various sizes, raising mainly sheep and cattle, but also goats, horses, and camels. Farms typically have more than 50 head of cattle. Animal production is market-oriented; meat and dairy products being sold in local markets. Farms are medium to large and often grow crops for fodder and market sale (accounting for 50% of their land). The farms often incorporate trees and a small proportion of them practice intercropping. Non-farm income is scarce.
Arboriculture and date palms	This type consists of small farms of less than 2 ha of fruit trees (mainly date palms, olives, figs and other fruit trees). Non-agricultural activities are omnipresent in these types of farms (permanent or casual employment). Farmers are younger than in other types of farms. Intercropping is often practiced (sometimes with vegetables for self-consumption). Exceptionally, farms also own livestock.
Diversified	These farms vary in size, and all include field crops (cereals) and trees. They may also have livestock and market gardening, but these production systems account for only a small share of income. When farmers have smaller plots, market gardening becomes proportionately a more important source of income.

Type of operation	Description
Market gardening	On these farms, vegetable crops occupy the majority of the land and are the main source of income. Non-agricultural activities are rare. They generally do not own large livestock. Date palms are often grown.

Source: NATAE project

We can see that most farms practice a diversity of crops, integrating fruit trees (including date palm), fodder crops, market gardening, and livestock, with related specialties. Several farmers also have a non-agricultural activity.

The main production systems differ between the two municipalities of the living lab. Laghouat favours field crops (20.2%) and fruit growing, including olive groves, which are experiencing significant development with the recent installation of an oil mill to meet the local demand for quality olive oil. The municipality of El Assafia focuses on field crops (31.6%) and market gardening (29.6%).

Most farms are irrigated: the irrigated UAA in the communes of Laghouat and El Assafia is very large and represents 97% and 100% respectively of the total UAA. Irrigation is mainly gravity (45-48%) and is supplemented by sprinkler (21-28%) and drip irrigation (25-34%).

Figure 3: Study Area Map in Laghouat, Algeria

Many agricultural practices, on the different farms, can be described as agroecological. Thus, the territorial diagnosis of the living lab highlighted practices related to the rational management of water resources, crop association and rotations, integration of agriculture and livestock, biological control of diseases, co-creation and sharing of knowledge, etc.

4.2 Selection of Value Chains

Two value chains were selected for the study: the date sector and the olive oil sector.

This choice was made following a discussion with the representative committee and with the T3.2 officials.

While the date value chain was unanimously chosen for its economic and cultural importance in an oasis agrosystem, the representative committee hesitated for the 2nd value chain between the olive oil sector and sheep meat.

The sheep meat sector represents many farmers in the wilaya and several actors are involved in this sector: breeders, slaughterers, nomads, etc

However, the final choice fell on olive oil in view of its importance on the market, the growing surface area of olive cultivation, and the recent dynamism of this sector with the establishment of a new oil mill in the wilaya.

4.2.1 Date sector

Phoeniculture, or the cultivation of the date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*), occupies a strategic place in Algerian agriculture, due to its economic, social and environmental importance. It is a key pillar of agricultural development, particularly in the Saharan regions, where it provides livelihoods for thousands of farmers and is a major contributor to the country's agri-food exports.

Since independence, the national area devoted to phoeniculture has expanded remarkably, quadruply. This growth is largely due to public policies to support agriculture, particularly through the National Agricultural and Rural Development Plan (PNDR) and the National Fund for Agricultural Regulation and Development (FNRDA), which have promoted the intensification and modernization of palm groves. Between 2000 and 2018, the number of date palms increased from 11.9 million to 18.93 million, thus recording a growth of 60%, of which 85% are productive, offering just over 1.2 million tons of dates, all varieties combined (including 54% of the Deglet Nour variety, 42% produced in Biskra) (PASA project report, 2021).

In the living lab, phoeniculture represents 66 ha in Laghouat and 70 ha in El Assafia, and it marks the viable southern limit of this crop in Algeria.

As in the rest of the country, post-independence modernization has profoundly restructured the oasis system in the living lab: the traditional oasis of Laghouat has fragmented under urban pressure, while modern palm groves have emerged on the outskirts of the city, benefiting from agricultural support programs and the development of new irrigated perimeters. These new palm groves combine technological innovations and traditional agroecological practices.

It seemed interesting to the representative committee to study this value chain in view of its very important cultural character and this dynamic context.

It seemed interesting to the representative committee to study this value chain in this dynamic context.

4.2.2 Olive oil sector

Algeria is one of the main producers of olive oil in the Mediterranean, with an estimated olive heritage of more than 500,000 hectares and an annual production varying between 80,000 and 120,000 tons of olive oil (MADR, 2021), depending on climatic conditions. The main olive-growing regions are:

- Kabylie (Tizi Ouzou, Béjaïa, Bouira, Boumerdès)
- Centre and East (Médéa, Aïn Defla, Sétif, Bordj Bou Arréridj)
- West and Highlands (Tlemcen, Mascara, Saïda, Naâma)

Olive growing in Algeria is mainly based on local varieties adapted to climatic conditions, such as Chemlal, Sigoise and Azeradj, known for their richness in polyphenols and their taste quality.

In the wilaya of Laghouat, the Algerian state has set up several initiatives to support the olive oil value chain, with a particular focus on the production sector. The Intensification of Olive Cultivation Program is one of these initiatives: it aims to expand the areas reserved for olive growing. Thus, for the period 2010-2014, the area planted with olive trees was estimated at 5,000 hectares per year, with an average density of 400 trees per hectare.

Forest conservation plans to achieve the projected targets of 25,000 hectares planted with olive trees. This intensification program covers all the municipalities of the wilaya and aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Combating desertification in a highly exposed region.
- Fixation of fragile soils, limiting their degradation.
- Reduction of erosion induced by the sirocco, a hot and arid wind that regularly affects the Highlands and Saharan areas.

Support for irrigation systems to encourage this production has been launched since the 2000s among producers; by financing the installation of drip irrigation systems, allowing for more efficient water management in a region where this resource is limited. These systems reduce waste and optimize water supply for olive groves. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development plans to strengthen olive oil production by planting one million olive trees, while modernizing and structuring the sector. The objective is also to promote the central role of the olive tree in national agriculture, in particular by improving yields and developing processing infrastructure.

The surface area of olive trees has increased sharply in recent years in the living lab, and the olive oil sector is growing with the recent establishment of an oil mill in Laghouat.

However, despite these initiatives, the olive sector in Laghouat is facing specific constraints (lack of mechanization for harvesting, quasi-monopoly situation in processing with few pressing units), evolves in a restrictive climatic context (154.35 mm of annual rainfall, temperatures of 3.86°C to 33.46°C) and faces critical overexploitation of water resources: The difference between potential volumes (3.3 and 1.8 million m³) and mobilized volumes (26.31 and 6.38 million m³) threatens the sustainability of the model.

In this context of recent development of olive groves in Laghouat, we thought it would be interesting to study this new value chain.

4.3 Methodology

The approach adopted for this study was based on several steps:

- i. Presentation of the study to the stakeholders concerned: a first phase consisted of informing the stakeholders about the objectives and approach of the project. This presentation made it possible to raise awareness among the actors of the value chain of the challenges of the study and to encourage their involvement. A workshop was organized within the El Argoub association as part of the NATAE project. The main objective was to present the T3.2 activity as well as the objectives of the work, thus making it easier to identify resource persons in order to launch the survey.
- ii. Exploratory surveys: surveys were conducted using the semi-structured questionnaires proposed by the leaders of task T3.2 of the NATAE project. These investigations involved more than 30 olive oil and date producers (sometimes confused, see explanation below), as well as a dozen retailers (specialized stores, supermarkets), two olive oil processors and a date exporter. This data collection took place between May and June 2024 within the Living Lab and aimed to identify the characteristics of the date and olive oil value chains, to assess the agroecological potential of these products and to understand the perception of stakeholders towards agroecology.

In addition to surveys, observation was used as a tool for in-depth analysis. This method has made it possible to explore and refine the data collected, thus providing a better understanding of the dynamics at play within the value chain.

- iii. Data analysis: the data analysis was done by Excel software.

4.3.1 Orientation of the agricultural holdings surveyed

As we saw in the introduction, the farms in the living lab are mostly diversified, combining various productions. Fruit trees are often integrated into other production and livestock activities. Our survey panel reflects this diversity of farms:

The size of the farms surveyed varies, with small farms with an UAA of no more than 5 hectares, medium-sized farms with an UAA of between 5 and 10 hectares, and large farms with an UAA of more than 10 hectares. Most farms were medium-sized, with a dominance of arboriculture and cereal crops such as alfalfa, barley and wheat.

We have distinguished three main orientations of the farms surveyed:

Arboriculture: Growers who specialize in arboriculture use several types of trees, including table grapes, figs, pears, and olives. They also include food vegetable crops for self-consumption. Olive oil is marketed during the autumn period. In addition, these producers grow alfalfa, which they can market year-round to farmers. By diversifying their agricultural activities, they ensure their financial autonomy while strengthening the resilience of their farms to market fluctuations.

Goat farming and arboriculture: these producers are characterized by their dairy goat farming activity, producing milk, pasteurized milk and cheese. These products are mainly intended for self-consumption for most of the respondents. Some of them sell their cheeses to regional restaurants, particularly in Algiers. Goats are not freely accessible on the farm, but can be released on certain plots after harvest. These producers also include trees such as olive, date palm, fig, pear and vine. Market gardening is also present, although the quantities are limited, mainly for self-consumption, with the possibility of sale in case of excess production (lettuce, eggplant, pepper, carrot).

Dairy/sheep farming and mixed farming (including cereals): dairy cattle farming is the main activity of this type of producer, while sheep farming is intended for fattening. They also grow forages, such as alfalfa and barley, as well as other straw cereals, including soft wheat and corn. In addition, they integrate fruit trees and olive trees into their farms. These farmers devote themselves mainly to agricultural activity.

Figure 4: Agricultural characteristics of the agricultural holdings surveyed in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterization

Farmers in Laghouat and El Assafia, who practice diversified agriculture as we have seen, often combine date palms and olive trees on their farms. In this report, we propose to present in a first section the general characteristics of the farms growing these products (olive oil and dates), before making a separate presentation of the two value chains. In the 1st part, we present the general characteristics of producers, the workforce and the land tenure status of the farms, without distinguishing between date palms and olive trees.

Similarly, the conclusion will be generic to both olive oils and dates.

4.4.1 General characteristics of date and olive oil production

4.4.1.1 General characteristics of producers

The majority of producers have a higher or secondary education (about 95% of producers). A small proportion of them have a primary education or no formal education. This percentage does not reflect the illiteracy rate at the Laghouat level, as this rate varies from one commune to another, reaching an average rate of 39%, according to Laoubi et al. (2017). The closer you get to the commune of Laghouat, the less illiteracy is present. This is due to the proximity of schools and educational facilities, facilitating access to education. In contrast, more remote areas, such as Hassi R'Mel and Aflou, have a higher illiteracy rate, likely due to the distance from the prefecture's main municipality and lack of direct access to schools.

The average age of farmers is 61 years, and the start of agricultural activity varies between 8 and 20 years depending on the profile of the farmers.

The survey reveals that 52% of the producers surveyed are pluriactive and work in other non-agricultural activities, which are more remunerative than agricultural activity, which allows them to make investments in their farms. Only 21% of farmers are solely engaged in agricultural activity, while 27% of producers are retirees.

Figure 5: Socio-economic characteristics of producers in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.1.2 General characteristics of the workforce

Owner-operators often rely on outside labour, either permanent or seasonal, for farming operations.

The permanent outdoor workforce ranges from 1 to 3 people, responsible for essential tasks such as technical management, weeding, irrigation, and applying manure or compost. The head of the farm, the owner of the farm, is responsible for making decisions (sale, planting). Payment for permanent labour is done monthly on most farms, while others opt for hourly payment.

On the other hand, the seasonal external workforce consists of 1 to 10 people, mainly hired during periods of high activity: pruning and harvesting for olive trees and pollination and harvesting for dates. The average age of workers is 36 years. However, the limited presence of family labour (2%) highlights an increased dependence on external workers, particularly during the collection period. Payment for seasonal labor is made by the hour or according to the quantity collected.

4.4.1.3 Land tenure status of farms

The survey reveals that producers (of date palms, olive trees, or palm and olive trees) have 85% private title deeds. The rest of the farmers cultivate their land as tenants, free of charge, or arranged by heirs.

Figure 6. Land tenure status of producers in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.1.4 Producers' membership in farmer groups

Most producers (63%) do not belong to farmers' groups. Some explain this by the heavy workload and the lack of time to participate in the meetings of these structures. This low structuring of farmers into associations and cooperatives can also be explained by other factors. At the historical and institutional level, the country's socialist heritage, characterized by state dirigisme and administrative bureaucracy, hinders collective initiatives. Practical constraints, in particular the heavy workload of volunteers, limit their availability. The organizational fragility of the existing structures (associations and cooperatives), characterized by the lack of qualified financial and human resources, as well as the low professionalization of some of the senior managers of these organizations, reduces their effectiveness and attractiveness.

Nevertheless, 37% of farmers have structured themselves into associations, cooperatives or collective organizations to boost exchanges.

In addition, all farmers maintain an active informal collaboration, regularly exchanging on agricultural practices (harvesting, diseases, etc.), sharing resources and advice, thus demonstrating a potential for cooperation that could be better structured with a more favourable institutional environment.

Figure 7. Producers' membership in farmer groups in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.2 Value Chain 1 (Dates)

4.4.2.1 Introduction of the Value Chain

Area of holdings

The area dedicated to phoeniculture in the wilaya of Laghouat is about 192 hectares, home to nearly 28,556 date palms. The annual production of dates is estimated at 12,789 quintals, with about 8,506 palms of the Deglet Nour summer variety, renowned for its superior quality

The area devoted to date palms in the living lab varies from 0.3 to 4 hectares per farm. The cultivation of date palm is, as we saw in the introduction, experiencing a relatively recent dynamic of reintroduction thanks to the State's incentive policy. This policy combines the free distribution of seedlings (date palms) and support for crop protection through the provision of free biopesticides against Boufaroua (date bunch mites) or subsidized chemical inputs (mainly fertilizers). These efforts are aimed at revitalizing date production and promoting agricultural development in the region.

Agricultural calendar

The date production season starts in August/September and continues until February, depending on the variety. For example, for the Deglet Noor variety, ripening begins from September, while other landraces can ripen as early as August.

Yields

Date yields can range from 0.4 tons to 50 tons per hectare or an average of 100 kg/date palm, depending on several factors, including the variety of the date, the density of palms per hectare and climatic conditions.

Date production experiences losses of between 5 and 30% each year, depending on climatic conditions (summer or autumn rains, early cold) and diseases. The major problem for producers is acariosis, locally called Boufaroua, which is a mite that spins filaments on the bunches of dates causing their deterioration.

Inputs

Farmers source date palm seedlings from other farmers in Laghouat or Biskra, while some farmers grow their own seedlings on the farm. These plants are not certified; These are discharges from mother palms, produced on their farms. Producers, who have small areas, prepare their own date palm seedlings by creating nurseries from offshoots taken from healthy and productive mother palms. These rejects, aged between 3 and 5 years and weighing between 10 and 25 kg, are carefully selected and separated using sharp tools.

As far as manure is concerned, farmers call on breeders from Laghouat or Djelfa.

For pesticides and fertilizers, they buy them at a point of sale located in Laghouat.

Table 9: Sourcing inputs for date production in Laghouat, Algeria

<i>Type of Input</i>	<i>Spring</i>	<i>Origin</i>
Date palm plants	Farmers in Laghouat/Biskra	Premises
Animal manure	Breeder in Laghouat/ Djelfa	Premises
Pesticides	Point of sale in Laghouat	Imported
Fertilizer	Point of sale in Laghouat	Imported

Commercialization

The marketing of dates follows a marked seasonal trend. Marketed volumes peak immediately after harvest, usually between October and December, when fresh dates are plentiful and demand is particularly high.

As the year progresses, marketing gradually decreases. Smaller volumes continue to be sold outside the harvest season thanks to advanced storage techniques, including the use of refrigerators and cold rooms. This infrastructure makes it possible to preserve the quality of the dates in the long term. Traders take advantage of this to store a significant part of their production in order to meet the high demand that occurs during specific periods such as the month of Ramadan (more details in the following paragraphs).

The quantities of dates marketed vary from producer to producer, typically between 60% and 90% of their total harvest. This variation can be influenced by several factors, such as self-consumption, the size of the farm, the quantity produced, and the quality of the products. The quantities not marketed

are mainly intended for the producers' own consumption and donations, whether to relatives, friends or associations. In addition, low-quality dates are also used as goat food.

4.4.2.2 Value Stream Mapping

Regarding the dates marketed, there are two types of distribution chains:

- (i) The producer can sell his standing production to a retailer, who then sells it on the local market
- (ii) He can store his production on the farm, in the form of branches or in plastic crates. Then he packages it or not, depending on consumer demand, and then he sells it at the farm, delivers to the home, or also sells to retailers. Some producers export their production to Qatar.

Figure 8. Mapping the date sector in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

We can therefore see that the sale of dates is essentially done through short circuits, with a maximum of one intermediary between the producer and the consumer in the case of sales on the local market or in shops.

Figure 9. Date marketing channels (responses by surveyed producers) in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Figure 10. Photograph of date palm branches wrapped in kraft paper for sale in Laghouat, Algeria

(©Moulai Moulai, farmer from Laghouat)

4.4.2.2.1 Details on the points of sale

Direct sales at the farm and in the networks of friends and neighbours

35% of the producers surveyed sell their dates to friends and neighbours, or directly from the farm.

Of these, about 14% deliver the dates to consumers' homes, located about 20 to 30 km from their farms, using their personal vans.

And 21% prefer direct sales at the farm (including standing sales), where consumers and intermediaries go directly to harvest their date branches. They bring their plastic crates and take crates provided by the producers, which they then return. Sometimes, producers prepare the date branches in a room to preserve their quality in the event of a drop in temperature.

Several producers tell us that they prefer direct sales to consumers because it allows them to discuss and get their opinions on the production of this campaign. This makes growers proud and motivated by their harvest. It should be remembered that in Laghouat the market is essentially local, between friends and neighbours, and that the sale of dates is part of a social moment of exchange around this product with a strong cultural value.

Sale at markets and in specialist shops

In addition to direct sales and network sales, some producers also sell their dates at markets and in specialist shops, with an average of 5 cases of dates per year.

There are also two shops specialising in the marketing of dates in Laghouat: one, established in 2019, focuses on the sale of dates and their by-products. The other, created in 2018, is dedicated to local products as a whole. These traders buy the dates directly from the producers of Laghouat. However, as the quantities available from Laghouat are very limited due to the small size of the local farms, these traders also obtain dates from the town of Biskra (about 350 km away) to ensure the smooth running of their commercial activity. In particular, they work with five large farms in the Biskra region, store the dates in cold rooms to preserve their quality, and then put them up for sale.

Figure 11. Shop specialising in the sale of dates in Laghouat: branches and boxes of dates in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Marketing in supermarkets

Dates are generally not marketed in supermarkets (due to the limited quantities put on sale by producers), except during the harvest season when there is a surplus of production. During this period, merchants can offer only a few cases of their production.

Only producers who sell to supermarkets or specialist shops are aware of the marketing regulations.

4.4.2.2.2 Date Storage

As we have seen, most dates are marketed and consumed immediately after harvest, between October and December. However, part of the production can be stored so that it can be consumed over the long term and at times when demand is high, such as the month of Ramadan.

Not all varieties of dates can be stored and preserved for a long time. A distinction is made between:

- Varieties to be consumed quickly: these dates, often fresher or rich in moisture, should be consumed within two weeks. They deteriorate quickly if not stored properly. Most producers (about 80%), due to the small amount of production, cannot afford to invest in cold rooms and are therefore forced to store their dates in refrigerators at home. This storage method makes it possible to prolong the freshness of the dates and minimize losses, especially for the most fragile varieties.

- Varieties that are more resistant to storage, such as Deglet Noor, Bentkbala, Tadhaf, can be stored for more than a year without deteriorating. However, even for these varieties, many growers choose to use refrigerators to manage their small production quantities. This practice helps maintain controlled temperature and humidity, reducing the risk of degradation due to pest infestations, mold, or unwanted fermentation. According to the Good Practice Guide developed by CRSTRA, cold storage is recommended to preserve the quality of dates over long periods of time. The use of this storage method is suitable for most producers due to the limited quantities produced. However, some of them want to build cold rooms in order to better control storage conditions. They confirm that the humidity of the dates is well controlled, thus guaranteeing better conservation. In addition, 20% of producers confirm that limited financial resources prevent them from building cold rooms.

4.4.2.2.3 Date prices

According to the survey results, more than half of the respondents (52%) believe that the determination of date prices is mainly done by the producers themselves. In addition, 22% of respondents indicated that pricing is based on local and national market pricing. Finally, 14% of respondents set prices through a network of producers.

Most of the producers surveyed set the price of dates by taking into account the market price or by calculating the costs of production. These costs include the cost of labour, the application of fertilizers, the treatment of diseases and pests, and the packaging of dates.

Others also take into consideration the quality and size of the dates when setting the price. This can vary according to these two criteria; For example, low-quality dates may be sold for a lower price compared to other good quality dates.

Figure 12. The price of dates in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.2.2.4 Processed products

Specialist shops, supermarkets and the Laghouat market offer processed date products for sale. However, they are not produced in Laghouat and come from other cities. Among these products, we distinguish date syrup, sugar, coffee, chocolate spread, date paste.

Some producers in Laghouat can process part of their production themselves, but do not market it, it is for the purpose of self-consumption.

Figure 13. By-products of dates marketed in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.2.2.5 Producers' motivation

Profitability

Most producers (73%) consider the marketing of dates to be profitable, mainly through the direct sale of this product, which allows farmers to sell at a suitable price. The price of dates, especially for the Deglet Nour variety, is competitive, with reduced costs and a climate suitable for this crop. This profitability can also be explained by the mastery of the technical itinerary by these producers, thanks to their membership of networks of exchange between farmers (associations, meetings, training, extension days). In addition, there is a leading farmer in Laghouat who masters the management of production and the associated issues. The latter is known for his curiosity and his research on the date palm in the Laghouat region.

Other producers (27%) believe that marketing dates is not profitable. This perception is mainly due to several factors: the quantities produced are limited, and a large part of the production is for self-consumption and donations (an average of 30%), as dates are an integral part of the cultural tradition of the producers. In addition, issues such as the presence of pests, unusual temperature drops during the ripening period, as well as pollination problems also contribute to this perception.

At the same time, the share of date production in the total turnover of farmers varies between 30% and 50% for most phoeniculturists, which underlines the importance of this crop in their economic viability.

Figure 14. Producers' perception of the profitability of date marketing in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Figure 15. The share of date production in total turnover in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

The data collected shows that producers have seen growth in their business activity over the past five years regarding dates. They say that the production of dates is becoming more profitable from year to year, which can be explained by the entry into production of the young date palms planted about twenty years ago when the new palm groves were put into production. Others report that their activity has remained stable since the beginning of their production, probably because their palm grove was already old enough to produce. For producers whose activity is declining, this mainly concerns oases with date palms that are more than 80 years old.

Figure 16. The development of the commercial activity of dates during the last 5 years in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Heritage preservation

The motivation of phoeniculturists is also based on factors other than the economic objective, in particular the preservation of cultural heritage: in fact, dates are a traditional product of the Laghouat territory. On the other hand, the quality of the dates is another element that makes them proud, as the pedoclimatic conditions of Laghouat favour the production of high-quality dates. Finally, the producers point out that their motivation is also linked to the popularity of Laghouat's local varieties, which are very popular with consumers.

Phoeniculturists explain to their customers that their dates are of high quality, from well-known local varieties, such as BENTKBALA and TADALA, which are known for their freshness, and that their cultivation helps to preserve the heritage of Laghouat, a region renowned for its varietal diversity.

Other producers say that these dates are local products that respect the environment, as they do not use chemical inputs during their production.

Figure 17. Explanation to customers for the sale of dates in Laghouat, Algeria

4.4.2.2.6 Consumer motivation

In the living lab in Laghouat, date consumption is similar among both urban and rural people. Laghouat dates are in high demand by both types of consumers: they are generally sold a little cheaper than imported dates and their quality is recognized by local consumers.

Figure 18. Types of date consumers in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Regarding dates, consumers recognize that those produced in Laghouat are of better quality compared to those from other cities, especially Biskra. Customers often ask traders about the origin of the dates, as they prefer Laghouat dates. This preference is explained by the diversity of local varieties and the particular flavours that characterise them.

The price of dates is considered appropriate by consumers, as this product occupies an important place in their culinary culture. Local varieties, in particular, are cheaper and offer good taste quality compared to other well-known varieties, such as Deglet Nour. In addition, producers generally charge fair prices, without distinction between customers.

4.4.2.2.7 Certification

There is no "official" certification of dates. As we have seen, consumers prefer dates produced locally, in the living lab, but there is no certification tracing the origin of the dates. As sales are essentially made in short circuits, consumers can often be sure of the origin of the product and its quality.

4.4.2.2.8 Diagnosis and agroecological potential

Several agroecological practices are observed among phoeniculturists:

Practices related to improving soil quality, including the spreading of manure or compost, are observed by all the producers surveyed. Indeed, as the soils are poor, they need an input of organic matter in the form of manure. Although the date palm can produce even without manure, the yield improves when this application is made. Producers use several types of manure: sheep, horse, goat and cattle, depending on the availability of each one.

Some farmers use crop residues in the form of mulch, in addition to manure and compost to enrich the soil with organic matter, and to manage weeds.

Practices related to the preservation of biodiversity, in particular agroforestry through the tiered system (traditional system), consist of combining the date palm with other trees such as lemon, olive, pomegranate, as well as medicinal plants (sage, lavender, thyme). They also associate the date palm with viticulture. Some producers with old date palms incorporate goat farming to control weeds.

4.4.2.2.9 Interactions and synergies between agroecological practices

The analysis of agroecological practices in the living lab reveals that they are not implemented in isolation but are part of a systemic approach creating synergies between the different components of the agricultural system:

The integration of agriculture and livestock farming, the complementarity between livestock farming (sheep, goats, cattle) and arboriculture (olive trees, date palms) allows for a virtuous cycle - animal manure fertilises the soil, while certain agricultural by-products feed livestock (dry and

immature dates, etc.). etc.). This synergy is particularly visible in small family farms that practice mixed cropping and livestock farming.

Integrated resource management, including the combined adoption of different conservation practices (mulching, organic manure, localized irrigation) makes it possible to optimize the use of scarce resources such as water and organic matter. For example, crop residues used as mulch contribute to both water retention and progressive soil enrichment.

Multi-tiered crop associations, especially in the traditional system of date palms, fruit trees and low crops, create a favourable microclimate and optimise the use of space. Olive trees play a multifunctional role in serving as windbreaks for other crops while producing olives.

Ecosystem services, with the integration of beekeeping into olive orchards, illustrates the search for positive synergies, with bees providing pollination while producing honey. The presence of aromatic and medicinal plants also contributes to functional biodiversity.

This synergy and interaction of EA practices within value chains strengthens the overall resilience of the system to climate and economic constraints while preserving traditional knowledge. It demonstrates that local agroecological practices are part of a logic of optimization of interactions rather than a simple juxtaposition of techniques.

Figure 19. Agroecological practices observed by phoeniculturists in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.3 Value Chain 2 (Olive Oil)

4.4.3.1 Value Chain Introduction

Area

The wilaya of Laghouat dedicates about 4,000 hectares to olive growing, with nearly 500,000 olive trees planted, with an annual production of olive oil in Laghouat that could be in a similar range, between 3,000 and 4,000 tons (data from the DSA, 2021)

The area dedicated to olive production varies from one farm to another (ranging from 6% to 90% of the UAA), depending on the farmer's production choices.

Figure 20. The share of the UAA dedicated to olive trees and olive production by producers in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Also, the cultivation of olive trees in Laghouat is recent, benefiting from the National Olive Oil Plan (PNO) in 2000, during which the state provided farmers with olive seedlings (200 plants/ha) in order to recognize the role of the olive tree in the region. The objectives of this plan were to extend the area of olive groves to 500,000 ha by 2010 (MADR, 2008), with a view to concretely encouraging olive growing, as an economic activity, a source of wealth and a generator of jobs.

Agricultural calendar

The olive production season starts from the end of October/beginning of November until January/February.

Yields

The average quantity produced is 6 tons. Yield varies greatly from one producer to another, mainly due to production management, including tree size, irrigation and tree density per hectare. The majority of producers have quantities of 6 to 10 tons, mainly intended for processing into olive oil (95% of producers).

The losses in olive production, estimated at between 10 and 30%, are the result of a combination of factors: - The shortage of labour for the harvest, which can be explained by the precarious conditions of agricultural work: low wages, lack of social protection, risk of accidents and lack of professional qualifications. This situation is aggravated by competition from other economic sectors such as services, construction and hydrocarbons, which offer better employment conditions.

-Environmental challenges, including the impact of climate change on bloom and pest damage.

Figure 21. The quantities produced of olives by the producers surveyed in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Inputs

The supply of inputs includes the purchase of olive seedlings, animal manure, the drip irrigation system and chemical inputs. For most olive growers, the state was the main supplier of olive seedlings in the national agricultural development program and did so free of charge to develop olive growing in arid areas during the 2000s.

The table below shows the sources of supply of these inputs:

Table 10: Input supply for olive oil in Laghouat, Algeria

<i>Type of Input</i>	<i>Spring</i>	<i>Origin</i>
Olive Plants	ORIF nursery (Laghouat)	Premises
Animal manure	Breeder in Laghouat/ Djelfa	Premises
Pesticides	Point of sale in Blida	Imported
Fertilizer	Point of sale in Laghouat	Imported

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Commercialization

The olive harvest, followed by their transformation into oil, usually takes place between October and February in Laghouat. It is during this period that the quantities of fresh oil available on the market reach their maximum of 350 l.

After the production season, the role of traders in olive oil storage becomes crucial. Large quantities are often sold out quickly after production, while the remaining stocks are carefully managed to be marketed gradually throughout the year, to meet demand.

4.4.3.2 Value Stream Mapping

4.4.3.2.1 Processing into olive oil

Following harvest, olives are usually stored on the farm for a period of 48 hours to a week, in plastic bags or crates, depending on each producer's practices and the infrastructure available.

Then the 1st step in the value chain is the transformation into olive oil. To do this, the producers transport their production to the oil mills themselves (see below), with their own vehicles. The cost of transport does not exceed 3% compared to the selling price of olive oil.

In the region, there are two oil mills that stand out for their olive oil extraction methods.

The first, the Nathir oil mill, located in Laghouat, was created in 2020 by an entrepreneur who comes from northern Algeria and specialises in cold extraction. This method preserves the aromas and nutrients of the oil, thus offering a high-quality product. However, only 27% of producers use this oil mill.

The second, the Dar Diaf oil mill in Djelfa (100 km from Laghouat), uses a hot extraction method, which, although more traditional, can affect the taste profile and nutritional properties of the oil. Most producers opt for hot extraction.

This difference is mainly due to consumer preferences, shaped by their historical habit of consuming Kabylie olive oil, which is traditionally hot-extracted. Although cold extraction better preserves the

aromas and nutritional qualities of the oil, its more bitter taste clashes with the consumption habits established by some consumers and a lack of knowledge of the qualitative benefits of cold extraction.

Figure 22. Mapping of the olive growing sector in Laghouat and El Assafia (Algeria)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Producers can choose to recover all or part of their production once transformed into olive oil, or to sell part of their production to oil mills:

- Producers recover all or part of their oil

Once the olives are pressed and processed in exchange for a tariff of 1200 DA per quintal (Q), the producers collect the olive oil and package it in plastic or glass bottles. These producers often put labels (official or unofficial) on their bottles in order to sell them through short circuits (specialized shops, supermarkets, on the farm, social networks). Producers who sell their products in supermarkets must have an official label issued by the Chamber of Commerce, including a barcode.

- Producers choose to sell all or part of their production to oil mills

In this case, the oil mills then put the oil in different types of packaging, specifying the type of oil. For oils processed between October and November, they label them as "extra-virgin". For the Nathir oil mill, oil quality analyses are carried out to determine its composition.

4.4.3.2.2 Details on the points of sale

Farm and network sales

For 34% of olive growers, olive oil is sold directly on the farm, as well as through family and friend networks. The price varies between 800 DA and 1,400 DA (between 5.70 and 10 euros). This variation is explained by the fact that:

- The producer uses glass or plastic packaging; The price of glass bottles is higher than that of plastic bottles.
- Laboratory analysis of samples that allows producers to label their products with the composition of olive oil.

Sale to intermediaries

22% of producers sell their processed olive oil only to intermediaries, and the price varies between 450 and 800 DA.

This decision, despite the lower cost of selling, is often driven by the fact that these intermediaries take over tasks such as packaging and order management, relieving producers of these additional responsibilities. These producers, having a heavy workload, do not have time to package the olive oil and market it themselves. Some prefer this method of distribution in order to create jobs for young people, especially since olive growing is not their main agricultural activity. This is particularly the case for winegrowers, who plant olive trees as windbreaks.

Before each collection, producers draw up verbal contracts with these intermediaries, thus ensuring a certain security in their transactions. The middlemen, who are usually traders, then take care of reselling the olive oil on the local market or in specialized shops, thus facilitating access to a wider customer base.

Figure 23. Olive oil marketing channel in Laghouat, Algeria (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Several producers combine different sales methods: 16% sell their oil directly to the farm and to intermediaries; 10% of producers sell their olive oil on the farm, to friends and family networks, as

well as through social networks. A small proportion of olive growers sell all the quantity produced on the market and in specialized shops in Laghouat.

Specialty Stores

Olive oil (such as dates) is sold by some producers in stores dedicated to local and gastronomic products, thus targeting a segment of consumers looking for superior quality products and local products. These shops highlight local products from the region, thus contributing to their enhancement and the promotion of artisanal know-how.

Oil mill

As we have seen, part of the production can be sold to oil mills, which then take care of the sale themselves. The Nathir oil mill in Laghouat is thus a point of sale for olive oil, it specializes in the production of two main types of olive oil: extra-virgin olive oil and virgin olive oil. Extra virgin olive oil is obtained between October and November by cold extraction methods, thus guaranteeing superior quality, intense aromas and a rich concentration of nutrients. Virgin oil, although of slightly lower quality, is still a popular choice for its culinary versatility. Nathir olive oil is also marketed in Algiers, notably at Algiers airport, the Dzair local shop.

Figure 24. Olive oil produced and marketed in Laghouat, Algeria

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.3.2.3 Olive Oil Prices

As for olive oil, the price is set in most farms by producers (about 70%), who base themselves on production costs, especially labour, which is considered to be the highest cost (harvesting, maintenance, spreading of animal manure). For others, the price is set jointly by producers and intermediaries (18%), and from the beginning of the production season, intermediaries contact producers to set the quantities requested and the price. Negotiation is between the two parties. The rest of the respondents base their selling price on market prices.

Figure 25. The price of olive oil in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.3.2.4 Motivation of producers

Profitability

Half (50%) of olive growers consider the marketing of olive oil to be profitable. On the other hand, 29% of producers believe that the sale covers the costs of production, but no profitability is identified. Other producers say that the marketing of olive oil does not generate additional income.

For the first category of producers, several factors can explain the profitability of olive oil marketing, in particular the use of family labour, especially during the olive harvest (availability, cost, qualification of the workforce), which reduces the production costs associated with the employment of seasonal labour. These producers often consider the olive farming activity to be their main production, which encourages them to prioritize the maintenance of the trees over other crops. In addition, things like the price, packaging, and labeling of olive oil can also improve profitability, as these aspects can lead to faster sales, especially as consumers become more informed about the product.

On the other hand, producers who believe that the activity is not profitable mainly highlight the cost of labour. Other factors identified by these producers can also reduce profitability, such as olive fly problems, weed overgrowth, as well as year-to-year variability in production.

The share of olive oil production in the total turnover of farms varies between 5% and 80%, with most producers having a share of 20% to 30%.

Figure 26. Producers' perception of the profitability of olive oil marketing in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Figure 27. The share of olive oil production in total turnover in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

At the same time, most olive growers are seeing that their business activity is growing. This is mainly due to the diversification of marketing channels, in particular sales via social networks, which makes it possible to expand the points of sale and attract new customers. This is also linked to the profitability of the business and the increase in production from one year to the next.

Some producers believe that their business activity is stable, linking this to the quantities produced. Others say that marketing is declining due to a lack of outlets for sale and the unstable availability of intermediaries.

Figure 28. The development of commercial activity during the last 5 years in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Product quality and respect for the environment

All olive oil producers strive to convince their customers that their product is of high quality. They highlight the exceptional characteristics of their oil, such as its rich taste and distinctive aromas. They claim that their olive oil offers significant nutritional benefits.

At the same time, they emphasize that their production respects the environment, by eliminating chemical inputs.

Other producers point out that they consume their own olive oil. This self-consumption testifies to their confidence in the quality of their product and creates an authentic link between the producer and the consumer.

Figure 29. Explanation to customers for the sale of olive oil in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

4.4.3.2.5 Consumer motivation

Olive oil consumers are predominantly urban, as in rural areas, locals often produce their own oil. On the other hand, olive oil consumption is still limited in some regions, especially in areas where alternative, often cheaper, oils are preferred. Thus, although olive oil is a widely consumed product in some circles, it is not yet fully anchored in all the eating habits of the city of Laghouat.

Figure 30. Types of Olive Oil Consumers in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

Customers, as we have seen, are increasingly aware of the nutritional quality of products, especially olive oil. This awareness is mainly due to its traditional use in the treatment of certain diseases, as well as its benefits in cooking. Depending on the merchant, there are several categories of consumers:

- Consumers with high purchasing power, who can afford to choose a high-quality olive oil.
- Consumers with average purchasing power, who orient their choice mainly according to price.

Consumers suffering from diseases, who are forced to choose a healthy and good quality olive oil for health reasons. The latter generally opt for small capacity bottles in order to better control their budget.

4.4.3.2.6 *Diagnosis and agroecological potential*

Several agroecological practices are observed among olive growers:

Practices related to improving soil quality

Producers seek to improve soil quality by spreading manure or compost to enrich the soil with organic matter. Indeed, the soils used for the production of olive trees are often rocky and calcareous. Some farmers apply manure every three years, because of the high cost and availability of manure.

Water-saving practices

The drip irrigation system is ubiquitous on all farms, in Laghouat and El Assafia due to the scarcity of water in these areas. This method allows for efficient use of water, which reduces waste. However, despite its economic benefits, many farmers do not master the appropriate water doses for olive trees, as there is little support from the state on the use of this new irrigation system installed since the 2000s, which can affect the health and yield of the crops. Drip irrigation was introduced as a state initiative in 2000, as part of programs to support olive cultivation and improve agricultural techniques

in drought-affected areas. This system has been designed to optimize water resources and promote sustainable agriculture.

Practices related to the preservation of biodiversity and crop protection

Among these practices, we stand out the association of beekeeping with olive trees. The presence of bees can improve pollination and, therefore, the yield of olive trees. The beehives also promote biodiversity in the ecosystem, creating a healthier environment for olive trees and other plants.

Some farmers use the rows of olive trees as windbreaks for vine crops. This practice helps protect the vines from strong winds, reducing the risk of damage and promoting a microclimate that is more favorable to their growth. In addition, the shade provided by olive trees can also help regulate soil temperature and humidity, which is beneficial for the development of the grapes.

Combination of several agroecological practices

88% of producers combine several agroecological practices, including drip irrigation, manure or compost application, use of crop residues as mulch, and crop combination.

4.5 Reminder of Main Findings and Recommendations

As stated at the beginning of the report, the conclusion concerns the two value chains combined (olives and dates) because there are many observations shared between these two sectors, and producers often grow both productions on their farms.

1. Main difficulties for farmers

Farmers (olive and date palm combined) face several difficulties related to the production and sale of their products.

Figure 31. The difficulties encountered by the producers surveyed in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

- **Availability and cost of labor**

Labor is one of the major difficulties encountered by producers, both for olive and phoeniculture. Agricultural labour in Laghouat is scarce, as many residents prefer to work in other sectors, including services and administration. The origin of the workforce in this study area comes mainly from the Saharan regions or northern Algeria. The results show that the qualification of the workforce also represents a significant challenge for producers, especially for specialized tasks such as pruning olive trees, harvesting, processing, as well as pollination of date palms. The cost of labour is very high for producers. The latter pay at least 1,500 DA/day (the equivalent of 10 euros/day) for a seasonal worker in charge of harvesting or pruning the olive trees, and 2,000 DA/day (13 euros/day) for a seasonal worker in charge of pollinating date palms.

- **Production and packaging costs**

Other costs are also considered high, including that of packaging (glass), as well as inputs, including animal manure (3,000 to 10,000 DA per truck per year). In addition, beyond the high cost of inputs and packaging, their availability is a major problem for producers.

- **Soil and climate conditions and global warming**

23% of respondents reveal that pedoclimatic problems, such as poor soils, erosion, drought, siroccos and sand winds, are major challenges. These problems are exacerbated by diseases and pests, mainly related to climate change in Laghouat (according to producers). The study area has indeed experienced climate change over the last ten years. Farmers report that they have been reduced from four to two farming seasons, and rainfall has decreased, while drought has intensified, leading to a lack of water for some producers.

- **Pricing and marketing arrangements**

The marketing of products is also another challenge. 14% of respondents raise this problem, which is mainly linked to marketing conditions, in particular the arrangement with intermediaries, who are often very demanding regarding the quality of production. This is especially true for oil mills, which are looking to certify their products or participate in events on a national or international scale. Another problem for producers is pricing: intermediaries often offer prices that do not correspond to the quality of the product, which is mainly due to the quantities sold.

In addition, the use of verbal and informal contracts for the marketing of products represents a risky practice for producers. This is because intermediaries do not set quantities and prices before harvest, and can sometimes cancel their orders. This forces producers to look for other sales channels, which is especially complicated for fast-consumption dates.

Indeed, for the two products (dates and olive oil), the arrangement between producers and buyers (direct consumers and/or intermediaries) is informal and verbal. Before each harvest period, buyers contact producers to set the quantities requested. The price is set at the time of purchase: sometimes it is the producers who set it, and sometimes it is an agreement between the producer and the buyer.

The arrangement is sometimes a bit complicated between producers and intermediaries. For 16% of the producers surveyed, they do not offer a suitable price in relation to production costs, because they are based on a market price that does not really reflect these costs. Negotiation between producers and buyers is generally satisfactory, although it depends on the type of buyer and the producers. For those with a very heavy workload, they are looking to sell their products, regardless of the price, because they lack time.

The arrangement between producers and direct consumers is often simpler and easier than with intermediaries. In the beginning, consumers sometimes negotiate on prices, especially for olive oil. However, after a first experience and knowing the quality of the product, the arrangement becomes more and more simple and easy.

Finally, the main constraints that retailers face include the high cost of rental costs for specialist stores, which are often disproportionate to the profits generated. In addition, there is poor logistical organisation, aggravated by the monopoly exercised by certain wholesalers, particularly when date stocks are out of stock, which unbalances the market. Finally, the lack of storage depots is a major obstacle, limiting the ability of players to effectively manage their products and meet the growing demand.

2. A short circuit business that has some shortcomings

The value chains of dates and olive oil in Laghouat are distinguished by their short circuit, characterized by limited production volumes and high demand from local consumers. This strong demand is due to the recognition of many consumers for the exceptional quality of these two products, as well as their deep integration into the cultural and culinary heritage of the region. These local products embody the identity of Laghouat and are particularly appreciated for their unique characteristics and intimate connection to the land.

However, these value chains face several challenges in terms of marketing. From the producers' point of view, the price set by traders often does not reflect the quality of the products, which can make negotiations difficult, especially when the quantities available are limited. In addition, some producers believe that the marketing of these products requires more time to inform and train traders. They must then pass on this knowledge to consumers in order to make them aware of the value of agroecological products. As a result, prices sometimes remain lower or similar to those of conventionally farmed products, despite their higher quality.

On the merchants' side, the main constraints include limited quantities, which reduce their ability to meet growing demand. The monopolization exercised by certain wholesalers, who modify prices when stocks are out of stock, especially for dates, aggravates this situation. In addition, the lack of specific training of traders on agroecological products, as well as the absence of clear regulations to structure this market, hinder their ability to effectively value these products.

Nevertheless, the analysis of the role of intermediaries in these two sectors reveals an atypical configuration where their power remains marginal, unlike other agricultural value chains such as fruit and vegetables in Algeria. This situation is mainly explained by the predominance of short circuits, with only 2% of olive oil producers choosing to go through intermediaries, while their presence is almost non-existent in the date sector. This low level of intermediation is the result of several structural factors: the modest size of farms, limited production volumes, and strong local demand that values the geographical proximity of producer and consumer. While intermediaries perform some logistical functions such as packaging and order management for olive oil, their ability to influence prices or market conditions remains limited, with producers largely retaining control of marketing via direct sales (34%) and social networks due to this geographical proximity which has created bonds of trust between consumers-producers.

This particular configuration helps to maintain a distribution of added value that is favourable to producers, while preserving the traceability and authenticity of products, aspects that are particularly valued by local consumers.

Most producers also use social media as their main marketing channel for their products. Through these platforms, they can easily reach a large audience and establish direct contact with their customers. Some producers rely on third-party delivery services to transport their products, while others prefer to make deliveries themselves, allowing them to strengthen the close relationship with their customers.

This method of marketing is widely favoured because of its simplicity and efficiency. Social media allows producers to present their products in an attractive way, answer customer questions directly, and build trust.

3. Certification Dynamics

- Certification dynamics at the national level and at the living lab:

Algeria does not yet have an internationally recognized national organic certification label, unlike Tunisia or Morocco, which have specific regulations in place aligned with European and international standards.

Producers often have to make do with certification by foreign bodies such as ECOCERT, which represents a significant cost and limits the accessibility of small farmers to these labels. In addition, foreign certifications are not always adapted to the specificities of agricultural systems, particularly the traditional oasis, which are based on ancestral agricultural methods that are difficult to standardize according to the requirements of international labels (Hadjou, et al, 2013).

Regarding the olive sector, no official and formal certification is currently set up by producers within the Living Lab. The latter market their products in short circuits. The relationship between producers and consumers is essentially based on mutual trust. Consumers are looking for olive oil that is perceived as healthy, natural and has superior organoleptic qualities. In response, producers highlight the transparency of their practices by explaining their production process and insisting on the minimal use of chemical inputs.

In addition, they encourage tasting before purchase, which builds consumer confidence and builds loyalty. Some producers, concerned about enhancing the quality of their oil, carry out laboratory analyses and communicate the results through labelling, social networks and their participation in national and international events. These steps aim to increase the recognition of their production without resorting to official certification.

This process is common in short supply chains and agroecological systems, where the proximity and transparency of agricultural practices is sufficient to ensure buyer loyalty. However, several studies show that the lack of certification can be a barrier to access to wider markets and exports, especially in a context where quality and traceability standards are increasingly demanding (Benmihoub et al., 2021).

At the same time, the results also show that the dates marketed at the Living Lab do not have an official certification or a GI label. Although several producers grow the Deglet Noor variety there, these dates are sold without the need for certification or a label attesting to their origin or variety, simply because consumers easily recognize Deglet Noor thanks to its characteristic appearance. For growers, some consumers also identify other varieties native to Laghouat, such as Bentkbala and Tadala, thanks to their distinct visual characteristics.

However, the majority of producers do not see certification as a necessity, as the demand for their agroecological products remains strong and consumers already trust them. Indeed, products from agroecological agriculture benefit from a price deemed suitable, and the quantities placed on the market remain limited, thus guaranteeing a rapid sale. This situation allows producers to access markets without the administrative constraints of certification, although this approach potentially limits their expansion to a limited segment of consumers.

- **Certification knowledge and producer awareness**

The majority of producers are not familiar with the certification process, which is, for some, mainly due to the heavy workload they have to manage. On the other hand, 20% of producers are informed on this subject, in particular thanks to the associative movement, the media, and specialized events.

These producers do not have official certificates for the marketing of their olive oil or dates. However, they do use labels to indicate varieties, such as "Deglet Noor" for dates. For olive oil, olive growers typically limit themselves to using a barcode to identify and sell their products.

Table 11: Knowledge of the certification process in Laghouat (Algeria)

Knowledge of the certification process	Answers
No	24
Yes	6

At the same time, more than half of the producers surveyed say they are motivated to engage in certification processes to promote their products. In particular, they want to highlight their quality and stand out thanks to their agroecological practices. Another motivating factor is the growing consumer awareness of the importance of reducing the use of chemical inputs, which certificates can ensure. These producers show a particular interest in organic certification as well as participatory certification schemes.

On the other hand, the rest of the producers do not show interest in certification. They justify this by the limited quantities they produce and by a workload that does not allow them to devote time to training in the certification process. Some also feel that certification is unnecessary, as they already have a loyal customer base that trusts them without the need for official labels.

Figure 32. Motivation to commit to the certification process in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

4. Agroecological practices and perspectives

- Oasis systems and agroecological products

Oasis systems are typical agroecological systems, based on a three-layer organization (date palms, fruit trees and vegetable crops), and have historically allowed optimal management of resources in arid environments. The traditional oasis system still exists in Laghouat, but the majority of these oases are not as productive as they used to be. Many farmers have abandoned them, although some producers continue to harvest dates there, as is the case for a single farmer in the El Assafia oasis. This trend is explained by several factors, including increasing aridity, which reduces water availability and accelerates soil salinization, jeopardizing the viability of these agricultural systems (CARI, 2023). In addition, urbanization and migration to cities have led to a socio-economic transformation, moving away from traditional oases to other, more profitable sectors of activity (Rezzoug, 2013)

On the other hand, according to the results of this survey, based on exploration and observation, the producers of the Living Lab want to reproduce the old oasis model. Many of them are returning to three-layered cultivation, seeking to recreate the traditional oasis, convinced that this ecosystem is more resilient to climate change and natural phenomena. This agroecological model, which combines palm trees, fruit trees and vegetable crops, allows for better management of water resources and protects the soil from erosion. They also consider that this system makes it possible to diversify agricultural activity by integrating, for example, goat farming, a practice that was once central to the economy of the Laghouat oases (Faci et al., 2017).

In Algeria, scientific studies have demonstrated that traditional oasis systems create a microclimate favorable to the conservation of biodiversity while optimizing the use of water resources (Bessaoud et al., 2019). The biodiversity present in these systems plays a key role in the natural regulation of pests and soil fertility, thus reducing the use of chemical inputs. In addition, research conducted in the oases of southern Algeria, particularly in Ghardaïa and Ouargla, has revealed that agroecological practices applied to these ecosystems make it possible to produce agricultural products with high environmental value, free of pesticides and adapted to extreme climatic conditions (Benmihoub et al., 2021). Thanks to their resilience and the promotion of local know-how, Algerian oases are a model of sustainable production.

Figure 33. Photo of a phoeniculturist taken during the surveys, the middle photo shows a farm where the producer wants to set it up as an oasis using the three floors of trees in Laghouat, Algeria.

- Future and current opportunities in relation to agroecological products

The majority of the producers surveyed believe that there are promising opportunities for the marketing of agroecological products. According to them, this trend is explained by growing health concerns, including diseases associated with products from intensive agriculture, which have made consumers aware of the importance of product quality and public health issues.

Other producers point out that a well-positioned supply can generate demand, although this is still relatively new. However, they believe that it is possible to encourage it further, provided that continuous awareness-raising is put in place, in particular through mediation and the dissemination of information to intermediaries and consumers.

In addition, some producers (16%) identify a strong potential for agroecological projects focused on local products from Laghouat, such as dates, which benefit from a high value among consumers. These products, renowned for their quality and authentic origin, are generating a growing demand that could be further exploited.

The agroecological practices observed by the actors marketing dates and olive oil reflect a strong connection with short circuits and local specificities. Consumers, mostly local, prefer products from their region, especially those from Laghouat, renowned for their quality. Supermarkets have also integrated shelves dedicated to local products from Laghouat to attract customers and make them aware of the advantages of these local productions. Although there is no specific certification, the guarantee for consumers is based on the very origin of the product: being grown in the specific climate of Laghouat and by recognized local producers.

For dates, the diversity of local varieties and their unique flavors attract consumers, who are looking for fresh products directly from Laghouat's farms. Regarding olive oil, marketing reflects local consumption practices: small capacity smoked glass bottles (250 ml, 500 ml, 1, 1.5 and 2 liters) are used for retail sale, while recycled plastic containers (mineral water cans) or large volume jerry cans (5 to 25 liters) meet the bulk supply needs of certain households consuming large quantities of olive oil. This pragmatic adaptation can be explained by the absence of large glass containers on the local market at affordable prices, leading to the reuse of existing plastic packaging.

These practices, combining short circuits and reuse, are part of a circular economy logic while meeting the specific needs of local consumers.

- **Consumer awareness of agroecological products**

Most producers believe that (local) consumers would be willing to pay more to buy agroecological products in the medium and long term, provided that they are more aware of the quality of these products, especially through their certification and the dissemination of their benefits within the community. These same producers also want to discover new products, especially when it comes to good quality local products (healthy and natural).

The respondents consider that this process requires efforts on the part of producers, value chain actors, but also the community and public decision-makers.

They believe that these products have a nutritional value that differentiates them from products from intensive agriculture. This therefore implies protection and warranty on the market to ensure that they are distinguished from other products, especially in terms of price. This requires producers to organise and control all the necessary procedures, but also to raise awareness among the community

Figure 34. Consumers' willingness to pay a higher price for agroecological products in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

- **Share of agroecological projects in future projects**

The future projects of the producers are mainly the expansion of their farms by integrating other agricultural activities including goat breeding to have animal manure, the diversification of agricultural activity by planting other types of fruit trees, by processing their by-products especially olives.

Other projects concern the preservation of local varieties or the use of biological control.

Figure 35. Future projects of producers in Laghouat (Algeria) (in French)

Source: NATAE survey, June 2024

- **Future Opportunities**

Regarding future opportunities related to agroecological products, local players are observing the emergence of a promising market driven by several converging factors. The geographical proximity and the relationships of trust established between producers and consumers create a favourable context, reinforced by a growing concern among consumers about the intensive use of pesticides in other parts of the country. This awareness of health issues, combined with a cultural attachment to local products from Laghouat, generates a willingness among consumers to financially value local agroecological products, despite slightly higher prices. The structural characteristics of the territory (small farms, limited volumes, dominant short circuits) help to maintain the visibility and differentiation of these products from those from conventional agriculture. This specific territorial dynamic allows certain agroecological products (mainly dates and olive oils) to find their place on the local market, driven by consumers who consider the additional cost as an investment in their health and in the preservation of their agricultural heritage. Even if their price remains slightly higher, consumers can

adopt/develop suitable purchasing strategies, for example by planning purchases for Ramadan, holidays, ceremonies... etc., to integrate these products into their diet.

To add value to these products and expand their consumption, the state could intervene in several ways: by organizing the logistics of the value chain, by supporting producers through subsidies or training, and by providing financial support to improve storage infrastructure. In addition, the introduction of trade regulations aimed at regulating the activity of wholesalers and reducing monopolistic practices would be beneficial. Finally, targeted support for consumers with modest purchasing power could promote access to these products and encourage their consumption.

5. Recommendations for the development of date and olive oil value chains

Although initiatives have encouraged the recognition of olive oil in the Laghouat region, no regulations have been put in place to promote agroecological products from these sectors. In addition, the quantities produced remain modest due to the lack of skilled labor, difficult working conditions, and the lack of organization within the olive oil sector. The state can structure and organize this sector before considering a significant expansion of olive production.

As far as dates are concerned, several initiatives have been put in place to encourage their production and strengthen the competitiveness of phoeniculture. The State has supported the extension of the areas dedicated to date palms and the rehabilitation of existing palm groves, subsidies and specialized training have been granted to producers to improve their agricultural practices, particularly in terms of pollination, maintenance and harvesting. The enhancement of local varieties, such as Bentekbala, has been promoted through campaigns, fairs and exhibitions.

However, modern infrastructure, such as packaging units and cold rooms, remains insufficient, which limits storage capacity and affects the quality of marketing. In addition, no significant state intervention has been observed to effectively structure and organize the marketing of dates.

The strategy for a niche market for dates and olive oil in Laghouat could be based on a valuation focused on quality and local origin, highlighting the authenticity of the products.

- To ensure that these products are preserved and presented in the best possible way, investment in modern infrastructure, such as packaging units and cold rooms, would be essential. In addition, the promotion of short circuits would strengthen direct sales between producers and consumers, while promoting closer links within the local community.
- In addition, the creation of a local label authenticating the quality of products would help to better target national and international markets, including through attractive packaging that complies with export standards, with the support of certification bodies.
- Encouraging producers to join together in the form of cooperatives is a crucial point in order to strengthen their position on the market. These cooperatives make it possible to pool

resources, reduce production and logistics costs, and improve access to modern equipment. In addition, they give producers greater bargaining power vis-à-vis buyers, allowing them to sell their products at a more advantageous price. In addition, cooperatives facilitate the implementation of certifications, quality management and compliance with standards, which strengthens their competitiveness in national and international markets.

- In addition, training traders on certification processes and raising consumer awareness of the benefits of local products would play a key role in promoting these two products.
- Finally, integrating cultural values into this strategy would strengthen the identity of products by linking modernity and traditions, while meeting consumer expectations.

4.6 Final conclusion

Dates and olive oil stand out for their quality, their close link with the local heritage, and their position as local products. However, the quantities produced remain limited, mainly due to the limited agricultural areas compared to other regions of Algeria, such as Biskra, widely renowned for the production of the Deglet Nour variety.

In Laghouat, the decrease in date production is largely explained by the gradual abandonment of phoeniculture by some producers, the arduousness of harvesting work, and the lack of agricultural labour, particularly qualified. This last point is crucial, especially for large date palms that require experienced workers, who are able to climb the trees to carry out the harvest.

Despite these challenges, dates remain deeply rooted in the region's culinary culture, especially during holidays and special occasions. Citizens show a strong preference for local varieties, such as the Bentkebala and Tadala varieties, which are appreciated for their flavours and authenticity.

For olive oil, this crop is relatively new in the region, largely thanks to state programs since the 2000s, especially through the financing of irrigation systems. However, these efforts are not enough to guarantee optimal production. Most producers lack knowledge about the frequency of irrigation needed to maximize the yield of olive groves. In addition, tree pruning, which is essential for proper growth and productivity, is often poorly controlled, contributing to lower yields.

Another recurring problem concerns the workforce, which is often unskilled, whether for practices related to olive trees or date palms (such as pollination), which has a direct impact on the quality and quantity of production.

Laghouat has competitive potential thanks to its local varieties of dates, which are still little known nationally, but which could compete with the Deglet Nour. These varieties are often produced using relatively environmentally friendly methods, with a rational use of chemical inputs. However, farmers

face major challenges, such as poor soils. Despite the use of manure and compost, additional nitrogen is still essential to improve soil fertility. The high cost and limited availability of manure are also frequently mentioned problems.

These challenges do not prevent producers from seeking to promote their products, particularly through direct sales, which offers producers a unique opportunity to better value their products by directly explaining to consumers their nutritional quality and uniqueness. This approach builds customer loyalty and collects valuable feedback to improve products.

The reluctance of producers to adopt a certification system can be explained by a pragmatic perception of the local market, where demand exceeds supply and where distribution channels remain under control. This situation shows that certification is not an immediate priority as long as profitability is ensured without additional administrative constraints. However, this approach may prove to be limiting in the medium and long term, due to increasing competition and regulatory changes in national and international markets.

Studies have shown that in several Maghreb countries, including Morocco, producers engaged in a certification process, particularly with organic labels or PGIs, have benefited from a better positioning on the markets and a strengthening of consumer confidence (Bessaoud et al., 2019). Thus, a collective reflection on the implementation of certifications adapted to local realities could offer a lever for differentiation and securing outlets without necessarily imposing excessive constraints on producers.

However, more work needs to be done to raise consumer awareness of the value of these local products. Training offered to producers and retailers is still too rare. Retailers, often motivated solely by sales, lack knowledge and do not take the time to explain to customers the characteristics and added value of these products compared to others from conventional agriculture. An awareness-raising and training effort could strengthen the position of Laghouat's agroecological products on the market.

Finally, the organization of the value chain of these two products requires close collaboration between political decision-makers in the agricultural, commercial and industrial sectors, in order to effectively value them and strengthen their recognition among consumers.

4.7 Report Appendix. Photos taken during the survey

Photo of the date palm

Source: survey, June 2024

Photo of the date palm association with other trees (tree floor)

Photo of an olive grower and a winegrower based in the commune of Laghouat. This farmer planted olive trees as windbreaks. He sells his production to retailers. He does not use chemical inputs for the production of olives, but he applies fertilizer to his vineyard plot (table grape) as well as other chemical treatments on an occasional basis. Source (survey, May 2024)

Photo depicts the reuse of weeds from the date palm as goat feed (source: June 2024 survey)

Photo taken with a primary producer of olive oil and dates based in El Assafia. This farmer, who is very aware of biodiversity, is motivated to recreate a wooded floor on his farm, by integrating date palms, citrus fruits and medicinal plants. Concerned about preserving the environment, he does not use any chemical inputs for his trees.

Photos of the olive oil produced by several respondents

Chapter 5

Value chain analysis report for the Tizi-
Ouzou Living Lab (Algeria)
Olive Oil and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

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Chapter 5. Value chain analysis report for the Tizi-Ouzou Living Lab (Algeria) – Olive Oil and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

Summary

This analysis examines the value chains of olive oil production and aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in the Kabylie region (wilaya of Tizi-Ouzou: Yakouren and Azazga areas), focusing on the dynamics of local producers and the contextual factors influencing their activities. Focusing on the olive oil sector, the primary problem we were able to identify concerns the fight against environmental challenges, including water scarcity, diseases, and climate-related risks, such as chronic recurring droughts and forest fires. These different and combined issues can have a significant impact on production capacity and profitability. In addition, these value chains reveal complex interaction between producers and other stakeholders, including local associations, olive oil extraction units, and local representatives of rural and agricultural development administrations. Although there is a lack of producer organisations, many of them are part of the “Tharwa n Yakouren” women association, which operates in facilitating markets access and knowledge sharing. However, the lack of awareness and mastery of certain specific regulations hinders their ability to further develop new markets. Producers' motivations for cultivating olive oil vary considerably, ranging from managing surplus production to responding to the growing consumer demand for healthy agricultural products. In addition to women’s associations, often informal networks among producers also play an important role in improving product quality and sharing innovative practices.

Despite the observed challenges, growth opportunities still exist. For example, producers recognize a growing demand for organic products, which indicates that consumers are already willing to pay more to eat healthy. Furthermore, our analysis highlights the potential for expanding product ranges and developing cooperative initiatives to strengthen the resilience of local food systems, especially those of proximity.

In the context of the aromatic and medicinal plant value chain, production is primarily geared towards market demand. The dynamics of this value chain in the region are driven by several factors and manifest in various forms. Three main categories of producers have been identified: 1- Small-scale producers, who capitalize on the - growing demand for organic and healthy products. They market their products—primarily spices and medicinal plants, either fresh or dried—through direct short supply chains. 2- Producers of plant-based products sourced from wild plants, particularly lentisque, gathered from forested - areas. These products are sold through local stores specializing in regional

goods or through online commerce, often with a loyal customer base. 3- Producers of cultivated aromatic and medicinal plants, from which essential oils and hydrosols are extracted. These plants are grown using agro-ecological practices. The largest producer in the region is committed to an agro-ecological production model, which he actively promotes through training sessions.

The institutional environment (Chamber of Agriculture, Forestry Services, and the Training Institute) which is supposed to facilitate and supervise this value chain. Faces several faces several challenges and is trying to address them through several mechanisms, namely: 1) the dissemination of information on new regulations relating to the use of forest land for the cropping of AMPs, 2) the support for the creation of producer cooperatives and 3) the establishment of mechanisms for mobilizing both public and private actors. These efforts aim to enhance the skills of producers and development actors, fostering the growth of this sector while addressing the natural, institutional, and cognitive barriers that hinder its full potential.

5.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

In recent years, the agricultural sector has become increasingly important in the country's economy, contributing in a proven way to employment, especially in rural areas, and to food security for certain products. The national agricultural landscape is today characterized by a juxtaposition of agricultural models, traditional and modern farming, sometimes on the same territories. The recent agricultural reforms proposed are strongly oriented towards strategic crops like cereals and legumes, as well as horticulture and livestock production. The government has implemented various strategies to improve productivity and sustainability, especially in light of climate challenges.

Focusing on the Kabylie region, which hosts the Living Lab, we find a unique agricultural system that integrates traditional practices with emerging agroecological approaches. The region is known for its diverse climatic conditions, which support a variety of crops, including olives, almonds, and various fruits. The predominant farming systems are small-scale, often family-run operations, with an average farm size rarely exceeding two hectares. These farms typically combine crop cultivation with livestock farming, which is part of a diversified approach to secure market access. Key opportunities the Living Lab territory include the growing demand for healthy products from agriculture that does not use chemicals, particularly olive oil, which has gained popularity both locally and internationally. Producers are looking to capitalize on this opportunity by maintaining their production methods that are strongly aligned with the principles of agroecology, perpetuating agricultural practices that enhance soil health and biodiversity while meeting consumer preferences for product quality.

However, the region faces major challenges. Water scarcity, exacerbated by the drought of recent years, constitutes a critical threat to agricultural activity. Growers also face pests and diseases that can affect yields. Additionally, socio-economic factors, such as limited access to markets and

information, hamper the economic profitability of merchant farmers. The Living Lab in Tizi-Ouzou therefore represents a dynamic but vulnerable agricultural ecosystem.

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Figure 36: Map of the area of the LL of Tizi-ouzou (Algeria)

Source : Meddour-Sahar O, Derridj A . Le risque d'incendie de forêt : évaluation et cartographie. Science et changements planétaires / Sécheresse. 2010;21(3):187-195. doi:10.1684/sec.2010.0249

5.2 Methodology

To investigate and analyse these two value chains analysis we mobilised a systematic approach that is well suited to capture the complexities of both agricultural production and marketing in the Living Lab context. The process included several steps:

The selection of value chains was done through a short questionnaire developed by the task leader, aimed at identifying the most widespread agricultural products and practices in the region. This preliminary survey was followed by discussions with key stakeholders, including producers and local experts.

Producers were selected based on specific criteria, including their scale of production, type of crops grown, and their engagement in agroecological practices. While the approach was qualitative and representativity through statistical attributes was not sought, efforts were made to ensure diversity in

the selection of participants. In order to capture the diversity of situations as much as possible, the sample included farms of different sizes and practicing different production systems. Although precise data on the total number of actors in the region is limited, the selected farms represent key examples of the practices and challenges encountered in the region. Most of these farms operate on small area, typically ranging from 1 to 8 hectares, reflecting the predominant farm structure in the region.

After that, the survey with producers was done with the producers selected from the two value chains and also those with retailers and processors.

Table 12: Numbers of surveys done for each value chain in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

	Olive oil	Aromatic and medicinal plants
Participants to the survey	Number	Number
Primary producers	16	10
Retailers	3	3
Processors	3	3

5.3 Value Chain Selection

The Living Lab has selected two key value chains for in-depth analysis: olive oil and aromatic and medicinal plants.

The olive oil value chain is rooted in a rich agricultural tradition that is an integral part of the region’s cultural identity and economy. In the Kabylie region, olive oil production represents a significant share of agricultural activities, with 723,368 quintals of olives harvested and processed, representing an average yield of 16 litres per quintal (according to the Agricultural Directorate of Tizi-Ouzou, 2022). This production contributes to both local consumption and national markets. Its per capita consumption remains high, reflecting its culinary importance. The growing demand for quality olive oil offers significant growth opportunities in local and export markets. However, challenges such as price fluctuations, environmental factors such as water scarcity pose risks to its sustainability. As for the selection of aromatic and medicinal plants, the choice is motivated by the region’s biodiversity and the cultural heritage surrounding these plants. With growing global interest in natural and organic products, there is an opportunity to capitalize on this demand, particularly for herbal teas, essential oils and natural remedies. The cultivation of these plants offers agroecological benefits, such as enhanced biodiversity and improved soil health. Additionally, it presents new income opportunities for farmers, particularly in rural areas where job prospects are limited.

Both the olive oil and aromatic medicinal plants value chains were chosen for their cultural significance, market potential, and alignment with the region's socio-economic goals.

5.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterisation

5.4.1 Olive Oil Value Chain

5.4.1.1 Introduction of the Olive Oil

The olive cultivation in the kabylie region is above all a symbol of local heritage, contributing significantly to the livelihoods of many families, especially the most deprived. Moreover, the production landscape is mainly composed of small and medium farms, many of which still develop traditional agricultural practices. However, a gradual transition to more modern methods, particularly for oil extraction is underway.

The Mediterranean climate offers a favourable environment for olive growing. This climate is characterized by rather hot dry summers, and mild and humid winters. Farmers generally cultivate three to four varieties, intended for the oil production. Although the production is mainly for self-consumption, small can be marketed on local or even national markets. The current evolution towards agroecological practices resonates with the growing demand of consumers (often having illnesses) for healthier food products. This gives producers an additional boost to innovate and improve their practices.

As already mentioned, the olive oil value chain is not free of challenges. On the economic front, the instability of prices and competition from imported oils pose threats to the profitability of small producers. Socially, the aging of producers, combined with a lack of interest from younger generations in tacking over, threatens the sustainability of this transitional sector. On the environmental front, water scarcity, the impacts of climate change and pest infestations also pose present permanent risks for production.

Historically, olive oil production has been a key part of the region's agricultural practices, passed down through generations. But while traditional methods remain today predominant, there is also an openness to modern techniques that aim aims to improve the efficiency and the quality productions.

The respondents are predominantly male (14 out of 16), with only two female participants aged 46 and 74. The participants' ages range from 29 to 74, with an average age of around 55 years.

Table 13: Socio-economic and agronomic profile of the producers studied in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

Characteristics	Details
Gender	Men: 14; Women: 2
Average age	Average: 55; Min: 29; Max: 74

Level of education	Primary: 7; Secondary: 6; Higher Education: 2; No Formal Education: 1
Number of years of activity	Average: 23; Min: 3; Max: 38
Land tenure	100% privately owned
Total area (Ha)	Average: 2.8; Min: 1; Max: 8
Percentage of area dedicated to olive cultivation	Average: 23%; Min: 5%; Max: 90%
Share of product value/Total agricultural activity	Average: 51%; Min: 10%; Max: 95%
Product Marketing Rate	Average: 24%; Min: 0%; Max: 95%
Profit trends over the last 5 years	10–30% (2), 30–50% (2), no growth (3)

This indicates that the olive value chain is largely composed of older, experienced producers, which may suggest a potential generational gap in younger people's involvement in this sector. In terms of education, most producers have either a primary (6 out of 16) or secondary education (6 out of 16), with only two having higher education. This relatively low level of formal education could influence their access to modern techniques or information on improving agricultural practices. In a competitive and increasingly technological sector like olive oil production, education may be a factor that determines a producer's ability to adopt innovations. The number of years in the sector ranges from 3 to 38 years, with an average of 24 years, highlighting substantial expertise among producers. This long-standing experience is valuable for maintaining traditional production practices but may also hinder the adoption of more efficient, modern methods. All respondents are independent primary producers, meaning they do not rely on cooperatives or large entities to manage their production.

While this situation offers them autonomy, it also limits their access to collective infrastructure or technical support from the state, for example, which cannot be provided individually. Regarding land tenure, most producers cultivate their own land, which provides them the control over decisions on their farms. Two exceptions are notable: one woman who rents her land and another working on a family property. These different land tenure types can have an impact on long-term investments and the sustainability of their farming activities. Indeed, a tenant, for example, always tends to develop defensive strategies to maximise profits. A significant finding is that only two out of the 16 producers are officially registered with the authorities. This low rate of formal registration may reflect administrative challenges or a lack of incentive to register. The lack of formalization may restrict access to subsidies, training, or formal markets, potentially hindering the development of the olive value chain.

5.4.1.2 Value Chain Mapping

Figure 37: Olive oil Value chain Mapping in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

5.4.1.3 Characterisation and Diagnosis

5.4.1.3.1 General overview of producer characteristics

The producers interviewed for the olive oil value chain analysis showcase diverse characteristics that reflect the agricultural context and complexity of the region. Most producers practice coupled production systems, combining olive cultivation with other agricultural activities. In addition to olives, many producers cultivate supplementary crops like cereals (wheat, barley), legumes (beans, lentils), and various vegetables (tomatoes, peppers), which not only enhance the farm's resilience but also ensures food self-sufficiency. This diversification contributes to the sustainability of their production systems. In addition, many producers practice livestock farming, this association of crop and livestock farming further strengthens certain agroecological principles such as recycling. For example, livestock manure is often used to improve soil fertility. The majority of producers operate small to medium farms, with cultivated areas generally ranging from 1 to 8 hectares, but rarely exceeding 5 hectares. More intensive management of plots is carried out to manage this lack of surface area. We are therefore in a logic of better exploiting the land by adopting the association of crops for example. We can also speak here of an “agroecology of constraints”. These smaller farms must therefore multiply agroecological practices such as composting, intercropping and integrated pest management, to produce at low cost on the one hand but also to stabilize the yields of their rain-fed and therefore

random agriculture. This is why the producers' main focus is on growing olive trees, a very rustic tree that resists lack of water and diseases.

Labor on olive farms remains largely family-based, with family members, typically consisting of five to six members, taking care of most tasks, such as planting, harvesting, and sometimes, for small quantities, housewives may also practice olive oil extraction at home using traditional methods. Using family labour not only reduces costs but also fosters a sense of shared responsibility. However, during peak periods, particularly harvesting, seasonal workers may be mobilised by large producers in particular. These seasonal workers, usually hired from local communities, play a vital role in ensuring that the olives are harvested at the optimum time for oil production. However, women continue to play a role in olive production systems in general. They are heavily involved various tasks, including harvesting, processing and sometimes even marketing the final olive oil product. However, despite their important contributions, women's involvement in decision making is often underestimated.

Younger generations often participate in agricultural activities during school holidays, by participating in tasks that do not require a lot of physical efforts such as gazing, irrigation or piking and harvesting olives. These commitments promote the link with the land and safeguards common values. However, this is not seen as a job for the future, on the contrary, parents invest a lot to allow their child to end up as an engineer or senior executive for example. Agricultural activity is above all a means that nourishes the attachment to traditions shared by all

The olive oil producers of this region therefor represent a balance of traditional and modern agricultural practices that is manifested by strong commitment to family farming, characterised by a diversification of crops and livestock. In addition, the essential role of women and young people in the production process underlines the nature centred on the strong link between farm and family.

5.4.1.3.2 Overview of value chain production

In the analysis of the olive oil value chain, understanding the production process at the farm level is essential. Olive cultivation constitutes a significant portion of producers' agricultural activities, accounting for 40% of their cultivated area. This crop is typically integrated into polyculture systems, where cereals and legumes are also grown to diversify income sources and enhance soil sustainability. Most producers prioritize agroecological production methods, employing practices such as crop rotation, composting, and the use of organic inputs, thereby minimizing the reliance on synthetic chemicals. Fertilizers are often sourced locally, including animal manure and compost, which contribute to soil health and the quality of the olives.

Figure 38: Olive tree surrounded by fava bean plants in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

Some producers also have their own modern on-site milling units. This local processing reduces transportation costs and allows for better quality control of the final product. By-products, such as olive residues, are frequently repurposed as organic fertilizers or animal feed, reinforcing the circular approach of their production systems.

Table 14: Products of the value chain in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

Product	Processed products	By-products
Olive oil (biologic, natural, Local)	Tapenades 	Olive pomace oil
	Olives grec way	

<p>Virgin olive oil</p>		
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5.4.1.3.3 *Producer market characteristics and market strategies*

The analysis of market characteristics for olive oil producers reveals a complex dynamic, where most producers do not actively engage in extensive commercialization. Given the small size of their operations, which rarely exceed one hectare, issues related to marketing are minimal. Olive oil from the region is in high demand and is often sold through short family circuits, where producers directly supply their local communities. Producers rely heavily on self-consumption and local distribution, which allow them to maintain ties with consumers. For those embarking on large scales sales, the primary focus is on direct channels, such as local markets and family networks, Otherwise, sales are also made through oil mills: 22 transformers are found in the living lab area.

5.4.1.3.4 *Certification*

Since olive oil production is primarily intended for at self-consumption (only 24% of total production is sold), producers do not face major difficulties in terms of marketing. For those who engage in sales, transactions are often carried out within local or family networks, which guarantees a fluid and and direct exchange with a minimum of obstacles. Therefore, formal certification is not an issue for producers. However, some see certification as a way forward for a better market organization and to preserve the quality of their olive oil. They recognise the potential of certifications to better organise the market and protect the quality of products, guaranteeing their authenticity and protecting them from competition. Currently, the relationship of trust between producer and consumer remains essential, serving as a informal certification. This personal link guarantees the quality of and the transparency concerning the product, without the need for formal labels. However, as the market evolves, it is increasingly recognised that certification could play an important role in ensuring long-term competitiveness and market access (Hadjou et al, 2013).

5.4.1.3.5 *Focus on collective efforts, short circuit markets, and direct contact with consumers*

In this region, the production of olive oil is confined to various forms of collective organization, one of the most notable being the historical Twiza system (see: Hachelaf and Parks, 2018). This tradition offers producers the opportunity to unite their efforts, particularly in harvesting. By working together, efforts are therefore optimized. in the same way. Twiza not only improves efficiency, but also

strengthens social ties and fosters a sense of community among producers, in line with the cultural values of the region. This form of collective action plays a crucial role in ensuring the sustainability of olive oil production in rural areas where labour shortages might otherwise pose a challenge. In addition, the practice of Twiza contributes to the preservation of traditional agricultural knowledge and techniques, transmitted from generation to generation.

5.4.1.3.6 Motivation and Quality/value perception of producers

Only some producers confirm having information on the certification processes. They are often informed through the media or agricultural training provided by state agencies. However, there is a lack of motivation for these producers to engage in these processes, as in any case commercial activities remain very limited. Some producers are aware of the quality standards to be respected regarding these certified products. This highlights that their motivations are not currently market-oriented. This is mainly due to the fact that they do not identify themselves as real commercial producers, but just having inherited this activity and that there is a moral obligation to perpetuate it. In a context where production is mainly intended for self-consumption, the commitment to commercialize the products therefore remains low. In addition, in many cases, agriculture is not the main source of income for producers, which reduces their motivation to invest in certification processes. Thus, for many, the olive tree, as already highlighted, represents above all a cultural heritage than an economic opportunity. This heritage, seen as something to be preserved and passed on to future generations, is often valued for its traditional and family aspects rather than as a commercial product to be certified.

5.4.1.3.7 Barriers and opportunities to production and market access

Our LL producers face various challenges, including lack of access to advanced technologies, climatic constraints, difficulties in accessing land and water. In addition, the lack of effective support and financing structures constitutes a major obstacle to the development of this sector and even others. The family-oriented nature and focus on self-consumption further limit the ability of the LL area producers to achieve large-scale commercial production. Consequently, the expansion of olive plantations is hindered by the restricted availability of agricultural land, complicating efforts to increase production despite rising demand. Similarly, the water issue remains critical, particularly during the first two years of olive tree planting. During this period, young trees require regular irrigation to establish strong and resilient root systems. Climatic fluctuations, especially prolonged drought periods and increased fire risks, constitute another serious threat to olive groves. Forest fires, which are very common in Kabylie, can cause irreversible damage to olive plantations. To mitigate fire-related risks, producers must adopt both curative and preventive practices. A crucial curative measure after a fire is to carry out severe pruning of the trees. This practice allows for the removal of damaged parts and stimulates the regeneration of olive trees, thus minimizing losses. However, these interventions

require significant resources and specific expertise, particularly in pruning techniques, to be carried out effectively.

Simultaneously, preventive practices play a crucial role in protecting olive groves.

One of these practices is to regularly clean and clear the areas surrounding olive groves. This involves removing dry grass, brush and other flammable materials. This action allows for a safety zone, thus managing the risk of flames reaching the olive trees in the event of a fire. Another rather preventive practice is to use hedges of prickly pears around farms. These hedges serve as natural barriers that can slow down or even stop the spread of flames. Indeed, prickly pears are known for their effectiveness in stopping fires. Planting them around olive groves therefore represents an additional crop protection strategy. In addition to this protective role, prickly pears offer other significant advantages. First of all, it is a fruit tree that produces fruits that are very popular with the local population. Not only are these fruits tasty, their production is also very inexpensive. It requires virtually no production costs, allowing producers to benefit from a fruit or source of income at zero or near zero cost. By adopting these curative and preventive practices, producers can better protect their olive groves.

Limited access to modern technologies is also a constraint. Traditional methods of cultivation and harvesting, although valuable for heritage preservation, are not effective when it comes to large-scale farms. The adoption of these technologies, such as mechanized harvesting techniques, could improve efficiency and reduce the cost of production, but it also implies additional investments. In the absence of adequate institutional and financial support, LL producers continue to practice traditional methods, even with difficulties. Enabling specific subsidies, low or zero interest loans, and technical training programs are essential to support smallholder farmers in modernising their agricultural practices.

Concerning agricultural policies, there are initiatives that have been implemented to support the development of the olive oil sector. The Algerian government, for example, has implemented specific policies for olive growing, such as financial support for the establishment of new olive groves, subsidies for irrigation systems, and funding for technical training programs for producers. These initiatives are part of a broader framework of the Agricultural Development Program, which focuses on increasing production capacity and improving product quality. However, challenges remain in terms of access to these programs. Limited awareness, bureaucratic obstacles, and unequal distribution of subsidies often prevent producers from benefiting from them. Indeed, unlike large investors who benefit from stronger financial solvency and better social and economic networks, small producers often face obstacles in mobilizing this public funding. This disparity thus limits their ability to modernize their production methods. The eligibility criteria for these programs therefore tend to favor large farms, making it difficult for small producers to compete on and keep in this race.

Producers in our Tizi-Ouzou LL also have opportunities for the development of the olive sector. The growing demand for oil produced using traditional methods, without chemicals, represents one of these opportunities. Indeed, consumers are increasingly interested in healthy and natural food products. They are now aware and more sensitive to the harmful effects that conventional products can have on their health. This trend encourages producers to perpetuate their environmentally friendly agricultural practices. One farmer in the region stressed the importance of returning to natural agricultural methods by saying: “We must return to the land”. Another noted: “There are plants that kill other plants, so we must mobilize them in treatments, for example”. This reflects the growing awareness among farmers of the importance of preserving the health of soils and crops. These integrated production approaches thus reduce dependence on pesticides while promoting a more sustainable agricultural environment. Moreover, while the extraction of olive oil was once done by hand, requiring hard work, the growing number of modern oil mills now significantly reduces labour time and increases production efficiency.

5.4.1.3.8 Value chain governance and decision-making power

Most farmers in the region are affiliated to a structure or organization, such as the Chamber of Agriculture, cooperatives or various associations. These affiliations provide many benefits to producers, such as access to common resources, technical advice and market opportunities. They play a role in maintaining channels of cooperation and coordination for certain agricultural activities, which allows for more efficient management of resources. The Chamber of Agriculture, a decentralized state institution, is under the supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture. It is a public structure that works closely with the private sector to promote agricultural development. It operates in the facilitation and implementation of national agricultural policies at the regional level. The Chamber can also be considered as a platform where farmers can express their concerns, request expertise and participate in various agricultural programs. The Chamber of Agriculture supports cooperatives and associations, ensuring that resources are shared and that local agricultural activities do not overflow into national agricultural strategies. Furthermore, the organization of olive oil production in Kabylie is still inspired by the values of “*thajmaât*”, a traditional institution deeply rooted in the local culture. (For further reading on the concept of “*thajmaât*” and its role in Kabylie, see the work of Kara and Aknine., 2018). The *thajmaât* system is built around the principles of solidarity, cooperation, and shared responsibility, often in the context of agricultural activities such as harvesting, irrigation, or the maintenance of shared resources. It is anchored in the social fabric of Kabylie and perpetuates community ties, allowing the smallest farms to benefit from collective action. For example, the practice of “*Twiza*”, an ancient method of collaborative work, is still used to, for example, organize harvests and therefore optimize work.

At the farm level, tasks are divided between women and men. Women, with their soft hands, are responsible for picking up the olives that have fallen to the ground, while men climb the trees to pick the olives. This division of labour, based on traditional roles, allows for an efficient use of the human resources available in the family home. In addition, during the harvest season, it is common for the extended family to gather at the father's house, for example, to launch the harvest campaign. These harvest times are also times for reunions, which further strengthen family ties and perpetuate local traditions. Farmers in the region, relying on inherited know-how, are able to overcome the challenges of their small farms and limited resources.

5.4.1.3.9 Interactions with other value chain(s)

The practice of intercropping, -resulting from poor access to land- is a practice shared by many olive producers in our living lab, where olive trees are often grown alongside other crops, such as cereals and legumes. This polyculture approach, sometimes combined with livestock, not only optimizes land use, but also improves biodiversity, leading to healthier ecosystems. Legumes, such as fava beans (*Vicia faba*) and beans (*Phaseolus* spp.) for example, are grown to fix nitrogen and fertilize the soil. This intercropping strategy helps manage pests and reduces the need for chemical inputs, which are usually rare. Farmers often collaborate with local association to market their products, fostering a sense of community and encouraging sustainable practices. While many farmers are indeed aware of the importance of agroecological practices, their motivation stems primarily from the fact that the main function of their farms is to produce food for their families. This priority of self-consumption leads them to adopt practices that ensure the health of the soil and the sustainability of their crops.

Olive oil is also sold through local grocery stores, direct sales at homes, and oil mills, which also function as distribution points. These channels allow for small-scale sales, with most production intended for self-consumption or sold in small quantities within the community. This connection promotes consumer awareness about the benefits of locally produced, organic olive oil, thereby creating a demand for sustainable agricultural practices.

5.4.1.3.10 Agroecological diagnosis and potential

In the LL region, agroforestry based on olive trees as a strategic crop, has significant potential to produce more with the few resources available such as land and therefore has a positive impact on economic profitability. In addition, by integrating olive trees with traditional crops, farmers can improve soil fertility and water retention, which are already scarce production factors in the region. This practice is also seen as a form of diversification of income sources and an additional opportunity for livestock management. For example, crop residues can be used as fodder resources, promoting circular economies where each component of the agricultural system is valued or reused. The presence of olive trees can also provide shade for livestock, improving their well-being and productivity. In addition, olive-based agroforestry promotes biodiversity, creating habitats for various

species that can support pest control and pollination. This connection with other sectors, such as livestock farming, further enriches the potential for sustainable development.

5.4.1.4 *Main recommendations for the reinforcement of agroecological potential in the value chain*

To further advance and strengthen the agroecological potential of the olive oil value chain in the region, there is an urgent need to implement strategies to not only support responsible olive oil production but also to foster a broader transition to agroecological practices. The following recommendations are proposed to strengthen this potential and facilitate the integration of agroecological practices in this value chain:

- Encourage local producers to develop and strengthen the integration of olive trees with other crops and livestock on their farms. It is also imperative to carry out more severe pruning for older trees
- Support the creation of new local associations to, for example, facilitate the collective purchase of inputs and shared access to machinery. The "*Tharwa lakouren*" association can also play a role in this support and supervision.
- Organize workshops and training sessions to design new agroecological innovations and work on their social acceptability, while identifying the specific needs of the LL region,
- Improve Water Management: Implement community-based water management strategies that encourage efficient irrigation practices, such as drip irrigation or rainwater harvesting. Training farmers in these methods can help address water scarcity.
- Advocate for the diversification of crops grown alongside olives, such as legumes or medicinal plants, which can improve soil health, reduce pest pressures, and enhance resilience to climate variability.
- Develop local markets for agroecological products to strengthen the producer-consumer connection. Other successful initiatives such as the TORBA association can provide hope for this.
- Help farmers - those who wish to do so - to adopt certification of their products, by providing them with the necessary resources and knowledge.
- Improve or even renew agricultural extension services by developing training on agroecological practices and supporting farmers in their adoptions.
- Encourage the sharing of local knowledge on peasant practices. For example, engaging older farmers in educational efforts can help preserve and perpetuate traditional knowledge and know-how that works

- Engage with local policymakers to promote supportive policies for agroecological practices, including land tenure security and financial incentives for sustainable farming practices.

5.4.2 Aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) value chain

5.4.2.1 Introduction to the aromatic and medicinal plants value chain

The MAP sector in Algeria is just beginning to be integrated into agricultural development programs. The National Plan for the Sustainable Exploitation of Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) was introduced in Algeria in 2016. In the case of WFPs, this plan aims to develop value chains and improve their added value¹⁶, while putting in place sustainable management mechanisms. The measures taken are designed to prevent over-exploitation of the species collected, given the dynamic nature of this sector. Several regulatory initiatives have been taken to facilitate access to these species, as well as their cultivation and sustainable use, including the promulgation of a new Law No. 23-21 on forests and forestry resources, including article 109 of December 23, 2023 on forests and forest wealth, which relaxes user rights and authorises the planting of aromatic and medicinal plants. International organisations, such as the FAO (FAO, 2022) and the GIZ, are providing support for pilot programmes to set up micro-businesses to extract value from MAPs and women's cooperatives to collect and extract lentisk (Mastic) oil, as part of the GENBI¹⁷ project which has been set up in the east of the country to support women in creating women's cooperatives for the production of MAP (GIZ, 2017).

The participatory approach is favoured in these programmes and in those developed by the state services to intensify training programmes and to create and develop partnerships for the preparation of investment plans, the proposal of standard specifications and agreements within the framework of support programmes for young people and women for the creation of micro-enterprises (Rahmani, 2019).

The roadmap of the Ministry of Agriculture has just seen the creation of an interprofessional council but it remains disorganized, even if cooperatives are increasingly being created, such as the Nopaltec cooperative of prickly pear by-products in Souk Ahras and Miramia cooperative of the MAP of Boumerdes. The Aromatic and Medicinal Plant Cooperatives were created in 2016. They are therefore the result of the farmers' desire, not the state's, as was the case with the old cooperatives, which had public status until the 1980s. They are generally small, with no more than 5 members - the minimum required to form a cooperative.

¹⁶ The production is mostly informal and there is no data about the production delivered by the ministry of agriculture.

¹⁷ The project identified four ecosystems that provide twenty ecosystem services. The project carried out an economic evaluation of fourteen of these ecosystems and, on this basis, developed four product lines: lentisk oil (*Pistacia lentiscus*); prickly pear oil and vinegar (*Opuntia ficus-indica*).

This observation of disorganization had already been established by Ilbert et al. in 2016, even though interprofessional councils for the aromatic and medicinal plants sector have been created in several wilayas¹⁸ and the State has integrated the MAPs into research programs, especially research projects with socio-economic impacts. In addition, the new law on the management of forest estates promulgated in 2023, paves the way for the planting of aromatic and medicinal plants. However, farmers in the sector do not benefit from incentives such as subsidies, as can be the case for sectors considered strategic.

In Tizi-Ouzou, several species of aromatic and medicinal plants are listed. Various research studies show that the number of users is expanding (Kadous et al., 2016; Izeroual et al., 2022). In 2022, Izeroual et al. carried out an ethnobotanical study that identified 53 aromatic and medicinal species and identified the traditional knowledge and uses of these plants and the co-products that are extracted from them and described the methods of transmission of this knowledge which are mainly verbal. Another research project was carried out in Yakouren. This is an ethnobotanical survey carried out by Mancer and Slimani in 2023, the results of which show that 93 medicinal plants are used to treat different types of illness are known and used by the local population, although their knowledge and use is less widespread among young people. The study shows that the population uses aromatic and medicinal plants for medicinal purposes, but also for food, fodder, cosmetics and handicrafts, and that it is women who use them most and who are the holders and sources of knowledge about MAPs.

5.4.2.2 Value Chain Mapping

Three categories of producers have been identified according to the production and marketing factors to which they have access.

The first group consists exclusively of women. These women produce a diverse range of products: parsley, coriander, thyme, verbena, sage, etc., on small plots of land. The products are marketed fresh or dried in a short circuit, either at the farm or delivered to local shops, generating a modest but significant income for the household. Transport costs account for at least 50% of production costs, due to the isolation of the main production area for these aromatic and medicinal plants, which is located at the lowest altitude in Yakouren, which means that the microclimate is not as cold as in the rest of the region. One farmer explains: *“I grow aromatic and spice plants such as coriander, parsley and mint, and medicinal plants such as verbena and thyme to contribute to the household income. I deliver the products myself. It's not easy because I live in a town with very poor transport links. I have to use the services of the few transporters who charge quite a lot to deliver to my customers: fruit and vegetable shops. During Ramadan, my income triples. Customers prefer my products and those of*

other women who do the same, because they know they're organic and that coriander and parsley, which are in great demand during Ramadan, are full of chemicals". Saffron is a product that was introduced to the Living Lab area by the Chamber of Agriculture, following a training and demonstration course for women members of the rural women's association '*tharwa lakouren*'. Since then, a number of women have gone on to plant bulbs and produce saffron and bulbs which, unlike their predecessors, they market outside the Living Lab, attending fairs and exhibitions and, for the most skilled, even selling online, building customer loyalty¹⁹. One of the women said: "*I sell saffron at the exhibitions to which the Tharwa lakouren association is invited, and I recently sold the bulbs I harvested via the online sales platform 'Oued Knis*". Recently, competition from large producers in the east of the country has driven down the price of saffron and the income of the women who grow it in the Living Lab.

The second category in the value chain consists of men and women who produce vegetable oils from lentisk collected in the forest. Access to the lentisk (mastic) fruit is free (no permit required). Harvesting from the wild (forest) is generally done manually by households and takes place from October to January. The extractors are either of the traditional type for small batches marketed to loyal customers, in this case mainly women producers, or automatic extractors with a larger capacity. The oils are packaged in bottles and sold either to loyal customers or to intermediaries who sell them on to specialist shops, either inside or outside the farm.

The third group consists of a small number of men who invest in the production of vegetable oils and essential oils from aromatic and medicinal plants. They invest in more modern, higher capacity equipment. One of them²⁰ produces a wide range of essential oil and hydrolat products and even provides training to groups of young people who want to invest in this area. These products can be found in specialist shops throughout Algeria, are sold online and are even exported to Belgium.

¹⁹ The association's managers were asked by a national association of saffron producers to analyse the saffron produced in the Living Lab area and, according to them, the results show that it is of superior quality. However, they only received verbal feedback on the results.

²⁰ He is a member of the Living Lab representative board

Figure 39: Diagram of the MAP value chain in the Tizi-Ouzou LL (Algeria)

5.4.2.3 Characterization and diagnosis

5.4.2.3.1 General overview of producer characteristics

The production of medicinal and aromatic plants and their derivatives: vegetable oil and/or essential oil is mainly practiced by women in the living lab area. As a result, the sample of 10 producers includes 80% women. The majority of the retailers and processors interviewed were women or were part of household projects where women were part of the decision-making process. This is fairly representative of the general situation. The overwhelming majority of WFP producers are women and fall into the first (70%) and second (20%) categories described above. Men are in the minority and are involved in harvesting and marketing tasks in the second category. The third category, in which there are only men, is very much in the minority and accounts for 10% of the total.

Table 15: Characteristics of the surveyed MAP farmers in the Tizi Ouzou LL (Algeria)

Characteristics	WFP (8 women and 2 men)
Age	Average: 52 years Min: 35 years, Max: 64 years
Level of education	Medium, Primary
Type of land tenure	Concession (male) owner (male) Family land (women)
Total area	Average: 0.845 ha Min: 0.2 ha, Max: 2.5 ha

Area Value Chain	Average: 0.67 Min: 0.12 ha and Max: 2.5 ha
Membership in an organization	Tharwa Yakouren Association (majority of women) 70% of women
Rate of the product CV/Total agricultural activity	Avg: 45% Min:10%, Max: 100%
Commercialization rate of the CV product	Avg: 60% Min: 10%, Max: 100%
Statement of earnings last 5 years	+10 to 30% (6), 50% (2), no growth (2)

Data sources: farmer survey NATAE project

The situations of producers are varied and complex. Thus, for 45%, MAPs are the main production in relation to the agricultural activities of households. On average, 60% of production is marketed, the rest is consumed and/or donated and all producers note a growth in production of 10 to 50% over the last five years.

For the other actors in the value chain, we surveyed: three (3) retailers and three (3) processors (producers of vegetable and essential oils), one of which is a producer of its own aromatic and medicinal plants.

5.4.2.3.2 Value Chain Production Overview

The production of MAPs in the Tizi-Ouzou living lab is very varied and presents several types of producers. First of all, small producers who are mainly women, with very small areas: 0,2-0,8 ha, who can produce aromatic and medicinal plants to be marketed at local retailers or for direct sale, with no use of phytosanitary products or chemical fertilizers. Their activity allows them to supplement their household income. They also manage to market their products thanks to the rural women's association.

Figure 40: A plot of parsley, mint and thyme at the Tizi-ouzou living lab (Algeria)

Saffron producers, which is a production introduced a few years ago by the rural women's association, are also involved in this specific value chain by joining a network of producers' organizations that organize exhibitions and training on this production. These women sell both saffron and bulbs, including through e-commerce. The association *tharwa iakouren*, which is also in the process of becoming a cooperative, is a women's organisation that brings together women producers of local products, in particular vegetable oils such as olive oil and its derivatives, and aromatic and medicinal oils such as lentisk oil. It has 780 members (men and women). Its objectives are to promote rural women and rural development in general, particularly through the development of local products.

Women producers of vegetable oil, particularly from mastic oil collected in the forest area and who use artisanal or even semi-artisanal equipment for extraction and who have a network of loyal customers to whom they supply their production, but they also supply retailers locally or even outside the territory of the living lab.

The territory is also home to a major producer compared to other producers in the area. It is the only one operating an 800 litre extractor. This producer produces vegetable oils, essential oils and by-products such as hydrosol which is a fragrant water that is produced as a by-product during the distillation process of essential oils from plants. When plant material, such as flowers, leaves, or herbs, is steamed to extract essential oils, the steam condenses and forms two products: the essential oil (which is highly concentrated) and the hydrolat (which is a much more diluted, water-based solution). This producer supplies retailers in several wilayas, sells directly, sells through e-commerce via social networks and even manages to export its production.

Table 16: Value Chain Products and By-Products

MAPs Harvested	MAP products	Transformed MAPs	By-products
Lentisk Laurel	Lavender, verbena, geranium rosa, lemon balm Parsley, coriander, mint, rosemary, kiwanu	Vegetable oils (mastic, carob). Carob molasses is a sweet, thick extract made from the pods of the carob tree. Essential oils: mastic, lavender, rosemary, eucalyptus, laurel, eucalyptus, cistus, viscous inule, etc. MAP hydrosol: the different plants from which the oil is extracted: lavender, mastic, rosemary, etc.	Oilcake, pomace: compost Paste used as a dressing for animals Soap (mastic paste + olive oil) Plant waste Distillation waste used for mulching

5.4.2.3.3 Characteristics of the Producer Market and Market Strategies

Several marketing channels are adopted by producers and they depend on the nature of the production: sold as is or processed, the size of the production, the type of producer: small producer or large producer, level of education, the location of the production plots and the type of consumer.

Table 17: Type of market and marketing channels by type of product and producer of MAP in Tizi Ouzou (Algeria)

Type of products	Type of Producers	Marketing channels
Mastic and carob vegetable oils	Smallholder farmers	Direct sales
	Large producer	Direct sales Online sales Intermediates Specialty Shops
Essential oils of different plants	Large producer	Direct marketing Online sales Intermediates Specialty Shops
Aromatic plants: parsley, coriander, verbena, basil, etc.	Small-scale producers in small plots	Retail sales Direct marketing
Saffron and by-products (bulbs)	Small-scale producers	Local product shops Fairs and exhibitions Online sales

Products from the extraction of vegetable oil or essential oil using traditional methods or modern extractors are marketed through direct sales and specialized shops. Two of the producers manage to market their production through intermediaries in specialized shops in different wilayas of the country. While the others sell their production either to local consumers or to consumers who travel specifically to acquire the products.

The presence of several shops specializing in local products in the living lab area, which is a tourist area and located on the passage of a national road, is an opportunity for the marketing of products.

Online sales are also used by producers who have the necessary level of education to use this channel. Vegetable and essential oils, carob molasses and saffron are marketed through this channel.

Figure 41: Local produce shop in the Tizi Ouzou Living Lab area (Algeria)

These products are sought after by insider consumers who use these products as skincare products and usually get their supplies directly from the producer or from shops, they deem credible especially since the majority of production sales remain informal (Ilbert et al., 2016). The government is in the process of setting up an institutional environment to ensure that production complies with standards and that products are of high quality. In addition, the recent creation of a code for cooperatives producing MAP will enable producers to be integrated into the formal system as MAP producers, as they were previously obliged to join together in artisanal cooperatives.

On the other hand, small-scale producers of aromatic and medicinal plants, which are sold as such, market their products through local retailers and transport their production themselves.

Fairs and exhibitions, often organized by associations in collaboration with local authorities, are a significant opportunity for marketing production.

Products of this nature are sought after for their organic character and for their nutritional qualities and freshness. This is the case, for example, of certain condiment plants such as parsley, coriander, basil, etc., which are particularly successful during the month of Ramadan.

The prices of products are essentially determined in the first place by the costs of expenses: inputs (plants), packaging, and transport, bearing in mind that the latter constitutes up to 50% of the price, especially for small producers of aromatic and medicinal plants. For producers of vegetable and essential oils, the price is also set according to market prices and even for one of them, according to international market prices.

However, for all producers, climatic conditions influence the price of products. In the event of drought, the production of seedlings is low and prices increase, whether for the production of seedlings by

producers, for sale as they are and therefore low yields, or for the extraction of oils, or for the gathering of aromatic and medicinal plants.

Producers reserve part of their production (average 10%) for donations or for sale at low prices to specific categories of consumers: the sick, people with low incomes, acquaintances, etc. In this case, prices can be halved.

The agroecological nature of products can benefit from an added value of up to 200% higher prices than conventional products.

- Packaging

Aromatic and medicinal plants sold in a fresh state are transported in plastic boxes, while those sold in a dry state are packed in plastic bags.

Vegetable and essential oils are presented in dark-coloured bottles and some producers affix brands to them, even if the production is carried out in the informal sector, such as the "Yakouren" brand for the largest producer in the region. (Below are photos taken at the retailers' shops).

Figure 42: Examples of MAPs produced and marketed in the Tizi Ouzou Living Lab region (algeria)

- Logistics

Producers all face a problem of lack of agricultural land to produce more, whether it is small producers of aromatic and medicinal plants marketed fresh or dried, or producers who specialize in the extraction of vegetable and essential oils and who produce their own plants or who wish to do so.

However, in its article 109 of Law No. 23-21 of December 23, 2023 on forests and forest wealth, it is stipulated that authorization is granted to natural or legal persons in the public forest domain, on portions of land provided for by the forest management plan, to cultivate aromatic and medicinal

plants. A lack of information on regulations in this area was noted for both men and women in the LL area had no knowledge of this law ²¹.

Small-scale women producers highlighted a problem with transporting produce in areas underserved by public transit. They often use informal transporters to transport their production to retailers generally located between 2 and 3 km from their plots. Because of the scarcity of means of transport and the absence of regulated carriers, informal carriers charge exorbitant rates. As a result, transport represents 50% of their production costs.

Finally, in terms of logistics, high prices for distillation equipment limit women's production potential. They are unable to purchase modern distillation equipment to produce MAP essential oils in sufficient quantity and quality to make their efforts profitable. They produce vegetable oil with artisanal equipment and want to produce essential oil but cannot acquire a distiller that meets the standards due to lack of means.

- Competition

Even though the medicinal and aromatic plants sector is emerging, it has been expanding rapidly in recent years, due to the increase in demand for its products, especially for vegetable and essential oils. However, producers are able to sell their goods because of the particular nature of these products, the quality of which is guaranteed only by the producer and the efficiency perceived by customers. As a result, the absence of certification, whether to guarantee the quality of the products or their differentiation, allows producers to have a niche market with their customers.

- Key Players Involved

The main actors in the MAP value chain in Tizi Ouzou are represented by the institutional actors who are involved in the emergence of this sector, its organization and expansion. The economic actors who are trying to benefit from the economic opportunity that this sector represents and the producers' organizations, in this case in the living lab area, are presented in the below table. They include an organization of women producers that tries to serve as a relay for agricultural training and advisory institutions but also to create market access opportunities for women.

Table 18: Organisations involved in the MAP value chain in the Tizi Ouzou LL territory (Algeria)

Local shops selling local products and vegetable retailers	Marketing of products and ensuring market access for producers
Intermediates	Intermediaries are mainly present in the vegetable and essential oil value chain. This allows producers to secure a

²¹ The representative of the General Directorate of Forest, who is a member of the representative board of the LL of Tizi-Ouzou, gave some explanations to the farmers during the workshops of the project and encouraged those interested in producing MPA and who have land issue to identify a forest land suitable to the law and to

	market for their production and outsource certain parts of the value chain, including transport and marketing. However, they are able to generate significant profits by controlling purchase prices. The women who produce MAP in the LL have chosen to organize themselves into a cooperative in order to strengthen their bargaining power in relation to the intermediaries.
Women's Association "Tharwa Yakouren"	It is an association created and run by women and which specializes in supporting rural women farmers and craftsmen in the realization of their projects. The association's producers offer local local products, including MAP, and the association promotes these products on all occasions and by participating in various activities: fairs, exhibitions, development projects, research projects, etc.
Forest Conservation	It is an important player insofar as MAP is collected in forest areas and regulations encourage the planting of MAP in forest areas. For now, the plants are mostly collected.
Agricultural Training Centre	This center, located in the wilaya of Tizi-Ouzou, offers free training to farmers interested in the production of MAP products and the extraction of vegetable and aromatic oils.
Large local producer	This producer present in the living lab region has a significant dimension and experience that it can represent an opportunity to share his experience with small producers.
freelance trainers	They have been trained either by the Ministry of Agriculture or through development projects with international organisations (FAO, GIZ). They offer paid training, especially to young people or women's organisations that want to invest in MAP.
Agricultural Services Branch and its local branches	The agricultural services make farmers aware of the need to organize themselves into cooperatives and are responsible for receiving and processing files.
Local authorities: The mayor of the municipality and elected representatives, the Daira (district)	The local authorities provide financial support to the women's association that accompanies women producers of MAPs and provide them with the logistical means to organize exhibitions, sales and training.

5.4.2.3.4 Certification

The certification of agricultural products in Algeria can be done through two types of circuits, one public and allows through a public system to benefit from obtaining an "organic product" label or a "GI" geographical indication. These certifications granted by the Ministry of Agriculture do not enjoy international recognition and only three agricultural products have been able to obtain one of these labels. These are the *Deglet Nour date* from Tolga, the dried fig from *Beni Maouche* and the *Bouheza cheese*. All three products are marketed under the "GI" label. The other form of certification, particularly for "organic farming" certification, is obtained through international certification bodies.

MAPs are ingrained in local habits as kitchen products, as traditional remedies or treatments, and for aesthetic uses by women. Local know-how is passed on, especially through women. As a result, even if the products do not have official certification, the "organic" character for fresh and dried products and "good quality and effective" for essential and vegetable oils are recognized by consumers. This

positive perception of products by consumers allows producers to benefit from market access without the need for official certification.

Producers are still interested in a collective certification process which may be possible thanks to the rural women's cooperative in creation which wishes to initiate a certification process for the productions of its members. However, the informal and disorganized nature of all segments of the MAP value chain in the living lab area is an obstacle that will have to be overcome to achieve this.

5.4.2.3.5 *Favouring collective effort, short circuit markets and direct contact with consumers*

The particularity of the living lab area is that women are involved in agricultural activity, especially in Yakouren where they represent 37% of the farmers registered in the chamber of agriculture. In reality, they are many more, and that many of these women are members of an association "*Tharwa N lakouren*" which has integrated among its missions, the promotion of local products and the support of women producers for access to production factors, training and agricultural advice and access to the market. This organisation has become a legitimate interlocutor for actors who wish to intervene in the territory, as part of development or research projects. This gradually makes it possible to improve the skills of women producers and their capabilities. Some of them created a cooperative to produce PAM. Cooperatives are source of valorisation of local resources as for dry figs, lentisk and prickly pears (Boumali et al, 2023). The other particularity of the area is the presence of shops selling local products that allow you to sell local products, including MAPs, which are very popular during the summer season with passing tourists. Social networks and sales platforms are also a way adopted by producers to communicate with their customers and build their loyalty.

5.4.2.3.6 *Motivation and perception of quality/value of producers*

Producers are aware that their products are not harmful to the environment and human health. Despite the lack of any official certification, their representation of their activity is positive. One of the producers says: "*I introduce new products every time I hear about them or see them at an exhibition. For example, that's how I discovered the kiwanu²², a fruit that's very good for health. I started producing it, and then other women from the association followed suit.*" Human health is the first motivation mentioned and is considered a reason for pride. They feel that they are serving society by providing remedies that they are convinced are effective. This is especially the case for producers of vegetable and essential oils and carob molasses.

The environmental issue is also raised and the degree of awareness is high, knowing that chemical fertilizers and pesticides are not used at all by producers.

²² Kiwanu is a fruit from sub-Saharan Africa rich in vitamin C and antioxidants.

Quality, or even superior or even unique, quality is a reason for pride and motivation. This is a selling point that is usually reflected in the natural and organic nature of the products. Agroecological production practices are put forward to convince customers of the healthy nature of their products: organic fertilizers, crop rotation and association, soil quality: rich in organic matter, agroforestry, etc.

The profitability of production is perceived differently depending on the product, the quantity produced and the nature of the market to which producers have access. For some: those who produce essential and vegetable oils, the production is profitable and more than covers the costs of production and covers the needs of households, generally during the marketing period, which is often seasonal.

For women producers, the income from MAPs production allows access to financial autonomy and serves to supplement the main household income.

5.4.2.3.7 Barriers and opportunities to production and market access

The value chain is subject to obstacles of different kinds: structural and organisational, environmental, related to working conditions, lack of production factors.

Access to land is one of the constraints. The territorial analysis carried out in the Living Lab area as part of the NATAE project showed that land tenure issues, such as limited access to land and undivided land ownership, result in subsistence farming with limited access to local markets. Farmland is often fragmented into small plots, making mechanisation and efficient farm management difficult.

Women are even more affected, as they are excluded from land ownership, which is passed on to men from generation to generation. However, there is an opportunity for MAP producers, as this type of crop is now included in the list of crops permitted on forest land, which makes up more than 50% of the territory of the LL. Article 109 of Law No. 23-21 of 23 December 2023 on Forests and Forest Resources stipulates that, in the public forest estate, licences may be granted to natural or legal persons for the use of parts of the land provided for in the forest management plan for the following purposes: the development of bare land by means of plantations of hardy trees, para-forestry and forestry; the cultivation of aromatic and medicinal plants; the establishment of nurseries specialising in forestry and para-forestry production; the establishment of nurseries specialising in aromatic and medicinal plants;

On the organizational and structural aspects, the value chain being emerging and has just been officially considered as a sector of interest by the Ministry of Agriculture, according to the law No. 23-21 of 23 December 2023, which has created an interprofessional council for it and encourages the creation of cooperatives in the field, does not fail to suffer from its informal nature for the majority of producers, the lack of product certification, even if its expansion is certain. In addition, newcomers have rushed in to offer services around the production operation, such as manufacturers of vegetable oil and essential oil extraction equipment who market inefficient equipment despite their cost. More

and more manufacturers are taking advantage of the growing demand for distillates, but many have not yet fully mastered the production process. As a result, the essential oils produced do not always meet standards and do not satisfy customers²³.

The same applies to independent trainers who do not have sufficient skills to intervene in the production of MAPs and the extraction of oils and their derivatives, but who offer paid training.

The effects of climate change are important natural obstacles that this value chain shares with other agricultural value chains: drought and fires are the main significant effects²⁴. For cultivated plants, there is a lack of nurseries, especially nurseries that produce good quality plants and seeds and offer a wide range of aromatic and medicinal plants.

The working conditions are considered difficult by some of the producers who produce MAPs and pick and extract vegetable oils by hand, and highlight the health risks²⁵. Others point to the lack of manpower and the lack of interest of young people in agricultural activity.

However, it is a value chain with good prospects. Institutions are increasingly organizing themselves to improve the training and consulting offer and producers, in this case women producers, want to organize themselves into cooperatives. The three types of agricultural cooperatives in Algeria are: the specialised service agricultural cooperative, the sectoral agricultural cooperative and the multipurpose agricultural cooperative. The MPA cooperatives are the most recent sector cooperatives. They are mostly local and small cooperatives²⁶. They can be an effective form of organisation if they manage to take advantage of the benefits offered by the regulations governing them: the possibility of using subsidised loans, the possibility of benefiting from subsidies.

Despite its disorganization, the market is demanding products and this is due to interested and increasingly informed consumers. Finally, this value chain is specifically an opportunity for greater autonomy for the women who engage in it, not only for those who produce MAPs and their oils, but also for those who specialize in the training of producers and the marketing of their products.

5.4.2.3.8 Value Chain Governance and Decision-Making Power

Public institutions, including the Chamber of Agriculture, agricultural services and forestry services, each intervene according to its missions and push for the development of this value chain in the

²³ The Living Lab's main producer of MAP had to design its own distiller because the ones offered by several manufacturers were unsuitable.

²⁴ Territorial Diagnostic Report prepared under the NATAE project

²⁵ Irritation to the respiratory tract, the skin and even the eyes, Skin reactions, accidental or excessive ingestion of essential oils, particularly those considered toxic, can cause serious symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, headaches and even nervous system disorders, some essential oils are not recommended during pregnancy or for young children, as they can affect foetal development or cause adverse reactions

²⁶ The number of MAP cooperatives is not available but the first four women cooperatives were created in the eastern wilayas of El Taref and Annaba where women were assisted for the creation of these cooperatives in the project of the German NGO the GIZ in 2021.

region : Legal reform to allow access to forest land for the cultivation of MAP, training for young people and women interested in this value chain, creation of inter-professional MAP councils in the wilayas, authorisation of the creation of MAP cooperatives, financing of MAP micro-enterprises through the Micro-credit Management Agency (*Agence Nationale de la Gestion du Micro-crédit*) or within the framework of cooperation projects with international organisations. However, the management of forest areas is the most influential element in the production of MAP.

The regulation of the management of the forest area intervenes for the regulation of the gathering of aromatic and medicinal plants and also the right of use for the production of aromatic and medicinal plants and which has been authorized since the promulgation of the law of December 2023. Yet, the majority of producers are not properly familiar with the regulations. Public agricultural extension services need to improve their skills to meet the demand for advice from MAP producers. These crops are not considered priority crops, such as cereals and potatoes, which are of greater interest to these extension services. As a result, this gap in public services is partly filled by international and local NGOs and by solidarity among producers in sharing information.

The Chamber of Agriculture and the agricultural services are pushing producers to form cooperatives, in order to be able to collectively benefit from their support, in particular training and agricultural advice.

It should be noted that local traditions of solidarity intervene in the use of land and the "*thadjmaat*" village committees manage conflicts between neighbours or inter-families concerning land use, even if overall a certain solidarity allows a certain flexibility in the use of family land. This is especially the case for the members of the community who own the land and who do not reside in the territory of the living lab, but who allow their land to be exploited by the locals. This is the case, for example, for the cultivation of saffron by the women's association "*tharwa lakouren*" on the property of an emigrant in France According to the data collected during the territorial analysis, although women are excluded from land ownership, they still have access to its use, including land of those living abroad or in the cities

The association also has a role in governance since it is now a privileged interlocutor of various actors and manages to capture development projects that integrate the gender dimension. The association also manages to mobilize financial resources for the organization of events that allow women to market their products and organize training. The women are also able to exchange and share advice and inputs: seeds, organic fertilizers, agroecological practices, etc.

5.4.2.3.9 *Interactions with other value chains*

Aromatic and medicinal plants are often combined with other crops, and also with fruit trees (agroforestry). The plant residues derived from them are used for animal nutrition and the distillation

residues of these plants are used for mulching. Households in this situation use the same marketing channels, which are essentially local: they supply local shops or sell their produce on the farm. The MAPs produced in this case are sold fresh or dried and are not processed (no oil is extracted). This is the case, for example, of women who produce aromatic and condiment plants and supply local shops which, even if they are not specialised in agroecological products, have a section dedicated to these products and a loyal clientele.

5.4.2.3.10 *Diagnosis and agroecological potential*

The use of agroecological practices is traditionally integrated into the production of aromatic and medicinal plants. No chemical inputs are used and some producers do not even use organic products and even avoid irrigating their production. This is especially the case for one of the producers who consider that the extraction of essential oil requires an itinerary without any external intervention « *I do as little as possible to manage the MAPs I grow. I don't even water unless it's really hot. I think that gives me better quality essential oils* ».

However, several agroecological practices and combinations of practices are adopted by the majority of farmers. Fertilizers are exclusively organic (manure) and are either produced for farmers who integrate livestock into their production system or acquired free of charge from breeders. Aromatic and medicinal plants are also a very important part of the agroforestry system. They are often associated with fig and olive trees and are also grown in intercrops with other agricultural products.

The particularity of MAPs is also that they are integrated into landscaping around agricultural plots or/and fruit trees and their residues are used as food for the animals. In addition to the economic aspect, aromatic and medicinal plants around agricultural land offer several benefits to crops: biodiversity and environmental management. Here are the main benefits: MAPs attract a wide variety of pollinating insects, such as bees, butterflies and other beneficial insects. This diversity helps to improve pollination of nearby crops, which can increase yields. In addition, certain aromatic plants (such as lavender, rosemary or mint) have natural repellent properties against pests such as aphids or mosquitoes. They can act as crop barriers, reducing the need for chemical pesticides. They can also maintain soil structure, prevent erosion and improve water retention, which is particularly helpful during dry periods. Some of these plants, such as chamomile, can also be used as companion plants to improve soil health. Aromatic and medicinal plants can help limit weed growth by forming a dense vegetative cover, reducing competition for resources such as water and nutrients. Their growth can also suppress some weeds. Certain medicinal plants, such as nettles, are known to increase soil fertility due to their high mineral and nutrient content. Incorporated into crop rotations or used as companion plants, they can improve soil quality in the long term.

Figure 43: Plants of rosemary and cypress around a plot of land in Yakouren (in Tizi-Ouzou Living lab, Algeria).

5.4.2.4 Key recommendations for strengthening agroecological potential in the value chain

To support the dynamics of the Aromatic and Medicinal Plant (MAP) value chain and ensure its long-term success, several strategic actions need to be implemented. These recommendations aim to strengthen the capacity of farmers, especially women, through training and collective organisation. They also advocate integrating local expertise and improving access to key resources such as water and land. These measures will help to optimise agroecological practices and promote the sustainable development of MAP production:

- Improve farmers' skills in agroecological practices by facilitating their access to training organized by agricultural advisory services and training centres, especially for women.
- Encourage the organization of farmers to enable them to bring their concerns to public institutions and to be able to group their offer of agroecological products and their needs in terms of strengthening their skills.
- Mobilize local skills, even private actors (farmers, independent trainers) on agroecological practices adapted to MAP and integrate them into agricultural training and advisory systems.
- Organize demonstration sessions with leading farmers on the different stages of production including the extraction of vegetable and essential oils.

Informing and training farmers on e-commerce to improve their access to the market.

- Improve access to water and rationalize its use by informing farmers about existing mechanisms and mechanisms that allow for collective mobilization of water through collective storage devices.
- Inform producers about the regulations for access to forest state land to increase MAP production and solve the problem of access to land in the area.

5.5 Conclusion and Recapitulation of Main Results

The two value chains analysed in this report: olive oil and aromatic and medicinal plants were chosen because of their anchor in the living lab area of Tizi-Ouzou, but also for their potential development and their inclusion in agroecological production systems.

The olive oil value chain is completely integrated in social, economic and environmental terms with the territory. Olive cultivation and extraction is an ancient activity: there are olive oil mills dating back to the Roman era in the territory. The olive tree is so sacred that until recently, olive trees were a separate part of the distribution of the inheritance separated from the division of the land. This study has analyzed the structure, dynamics, and the influential factors that have shaped the development of olive oil value chain. Among the most striking changes is the shift from traditional methods of olive oil production to more mechanized processes. The increasing number of modern oil mills in the region has greatly reduced the labour intensity associated with olive oil extraction. The result of this has been improved productivity and efficiency, and meanwhile the production is at a better level, which is consistent and important in the context of the current situation when consumer demand is increasingly seeking organic and premium olive oils. A number of other important challenges that limit the full potential of the olive oil value chain in the living lab area were also put forward. Water availability is an ongoing issue, with water for irrigation used by the producers from limited sources. The efficiency of the wells is deteriorating; on top of that, the cost of drawing groundwater is increasing due to the fall in the level of water tables. Again, there is fragmented land ownership by farmers, preventing them from realizing economies of scale. But despite this setback, the study has also brought into focus immense opportunities for the olive oil sector in Tizi-Ouzou.

The increasing global demand for healthy, organic, and locally sourced foodstuffs provides a unique opportunity for the olive oil producers of the living lab area (Yakouren-Azazga) to enhance their competitiveness. Improvement in the production practices, organic certification, and differentiation in the marketplace could help them access niche markets at both local and international levels. The study stresses that there is an urgent need for strengthening collaboration among key stakeholders within the value chain. It also depends on the involvement of farmers, oil mill owners, local authorities, and market actors in leveraging the sector's potentials, due to systemic problems within the sector.

Coordination at better water management, investment in infrastructure, and technological capacity would enable the small producers to compete with larger and more mechanized producers. Furthermore, the promotion of training and technology transfer programs may address the knowledge gaps most producers face that prevent them from modernizing or increasing productivity. This would partly be a collective organizational approach, such as through the establishment of cooperatives that can overcome some of the barriers related to fragmented land ownership and provide access to better resources, technical know-how, and economies of scale for small producers. It would also facilitate collective marketing and distribution strategies, ensuring that the living lab area's olive oil products reach broader markets.

Aromatic and Medicinal Plants (MAP) have always been cultivated, but mainly for self-consumption. It is only in recent years that their commercialization, as well as the oils extracted from them, has become a goal for many households. This shift has been made possible by the combination of several factors: the increasing demand for MAP and their vegetable and essential oils, development programs for certain sectors supported by agricultural services and the chamber of agriculture (such as for saffron), as well as the dynamism of local rural women's associations.

These associations offer their members the opportunity to take part in training courses and sales exhibitions, thereby encouraging them to invest in the sector and market their products.

Other factors encouraging the marketing of products include the presence of shops specialising in the sale of local products, which represent a real sales opportunity, as well as online sales via digital platforms.

Nevertheless, a number of obstacles still stand in the way of this sector reaching its full potential. Among the main challenges are: the lack of sufficiently large plots for MAP cultivation, the isolation of production areas making it difficult to transport fresh products to local markets, and the lack of financial resources to purchase distillers needed to produce high-value essential oils. Additionally, the absence of cooperative organizations prevents producers from benefiting from subsidized loans and grants intended for such structures. The lack of expertise among public agricultural advisors to support women and MAP producers in general, as well as the absence of mechanisms or systems for sharing knowledge between large and small producers (particularly women), highlights gaps in governance and sector organization.

In light of these challenges, the main recommendation is to strengthen the skills of cooperatives currently being established by women, so they can fully benefit from access to credit opportunities. Furthermore, these cooperatives could serve as a central hub for production and commercialization, improving product quality as well as marketing.

It also seems that a dynamic future for this value chain can be realized by mobilising current initiatives: supporting the creation of micro-enterprises, pooling public and private human resources within training organizations and private trainers, and implementing regulations governing the use of forest areas.

5.6 Report Appendixes

Appendix A. Aromatic and medicinal plants found in Yakouren and their therapeutic uses (Mancer and Slimani, 2023)

Family	Scientific name	English name	Kabylian name	Therapeutic properties according to local beliefs
Acanthacées	<i>Acanthes mollis</i>	Soft Acanthus	Taifra	Against coughs and flu
Amaranthacées	<i>Atriplexhortensis</i> L.	Garden arrowroot	Armés elaghemane	Cysts, goitre, infection
Amaryllidacées	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Onion	Leysel	Cough, anaemia, haemorrhoids, colds
	<i>Allium Sativum</i> L.	Garlic	Thichaerth	Lowers cholesterol, high blood pressure
	<i>Allium triquetrum</i>	Three-cornered garlic	Vivras	Remineralizing
	<i>Allium ampeloprasum</i> L.	Leek	Tharnasth	Remineralizing
Anacardiacees	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>	Lentisc	Thidekth	Varicose veins, antimicrobial
Apiacées	<i>Apium graveolens</i> L.	Celery	Krafez	For diets, stress relief, digestive aid
	<i>Cuminum cynminum</i> L.	Caraway	Kemoun	Relieves bloating and constipation
	<i>Ammi visnaga gaertn</i>	Ammi	Avalaw ahirsou	Skin diseases
	<i>Daucus carota</i> subsp. <i>Sativus</i> Hoffm	Carot	Zrodia	Anemia
	<i>Foeniculum Vulgaire</i> L.	Fennel	Avesvas	Lack of appetite
	<i>Petroselinum crispum</i> Mill	parsley	Maadnus	Vertige, facial care

	<i>Thapsia garganica</i> L.	Thapsia	Bunafaa adharyes	The prostate
Apocynacées	<i>Nerium oleander</i>	Pink laurel	Defla	Abdominal pain
Aracées	<i>Arum maculatum</i> L.	Spotted aroid	Avqouq	Rheumatism, flu
Aristolochiacées	<i>Aristolochia longa</i>	Long Aristolochia	thferlalma	Antidiabetic
Astéracée	<i>Inula viscosa</i>	Slimy inula	amagraman	Diarrhoea, gastric ulcers
	<i>Pulicaria odora</i>	Scented Pulicaria	Silmesksa	Wounds, gastric ulcer
	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>	Absinth	Chedjrat mariem	Menstruation, anti-influenza, fever
	<i>Artemisia herba-alba</i>	White wormwood	Chih	coughing, diarrhoea, hypertension
	<i>Carthamus caeruleus</i>	Blue safflower	Thagalekhla	Diabetes
	<i>Cynara cardunculus</i>	Cardoon	Thaga	coughing
	<i>Atractylis gummifera</i>	Chardon á glu	Ada	Diabetes

	<i>Plantago Serraria</i>	Plantain	lferbagmar	Cough, bronchitis
	<i>Anthemis arvensis</i>	Chamomile	chivlharth	Healing, against mouth ulcers
	<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Wild chicory	Thizaghdarth	Calming digestive disorders, digestion
	<i>Cynara scolymus</i>	Artichoke	Elkarnoun	Constipation, rheumatism
	<i>Helminthia echioides</i>	Picride false viperine	hlafa	Decongestant

	Hyoseris radiata	Hyoserium, radiant	Thoughmesthtemgharth	Skin care
	Taraxacum officinale	Dandelion	thamarzaghouh	Urinary system
	Sonchus oleraceus	Sow-thistle	amezoughbghad	Warts
Borraginacées	Borago officinalis L.	Borage	Chikh levqoul	Colds, anti-wrinkle
Brassicacées	Brassica sp L.	Turnip	lefth	Coughs
Cactacées	Opuntia ficus-indica L.	Prickly pear	kermouss	Diarrhoea
Caprifoliacées	Fedia cornucopiae	Horn of Plenty	Tiqejar n teskourth	Anorexia
Caryophyllacées	Paronichia argentia Lamk	Silver Paronychus	Aderkil n'anvi	Flu, cholesterol

Cistacées	Cistus monspeliensis L.	Montpellier rockrose	Thouzalt	Diabetes
Convolvulacées	Convolvulus althaeoides	Bindweed marshmallow	Thajgagalt	Constipation
Cucurbitacées	Cucumis sativus L.	Cucumber	lekhyar	Dryness
	Cucurbita sp L	Pumpkin	Thakhessayth	Dryness
	Luffa aegyptiaca philip Miller	Sponge squash	lahvel	Diabetes
	Cupressus semervirens	Cypress	Elbestan	Haemorrhoids
Cypéracées	Cyperus esculentus L.	Yellow nutsedge	Hab el3aziz	Anemia
Equisetacées	Equisetum ramosissimum desf.	Horsetail	vumezrane	Blood circulation
Ericacées	Arbutus unedo L.	Arbouser	Assisnu	Arthritis, anaemia, cancer
Fabacées	Ceratonia siliqua L.	Carob	Akharoub	Diarrhoea, ENT infections, osteoarthritis
	Cytisus triflorus	Cytise triflore	ilgui	Digestive disorders
	Lens culinaris Medik	Lentil	Eladhess	Anaemia, measles

	Vicia faba	feve	ivawen	Dermatophytes
Fagacées	Quercus ilex L.	Green oak	Aveloud n lahlou	Haemorrhoids
Genianacées	Centaurium umbellatum	Common knapweed	Qlilou	Diabetes
Iridacées	Gladiolus segetum Miller	Harvest Gladiolus	Thafruth ggiger	Cancer
Juglandacées	Juglans regia L.	Walnut	Eljouz	Tooth decay, mouth ulcers
Lamiacées	Lavandula stoechas L	Stoechade lavender	Amezir boudrar	Digestive disorders, respiratory diseases
	Marrubium vulgare L.	White horehound	Marouyeth	Back pain, increased fertility
	Melissa officinalis L	Lemon balm	lfer izizwi	Flu, colds
	Manthe piperata L.	Peppermint	Nana3	Sore throat, coughs, colds
	Mentha pulegium L.	Poultry mint	Felgou	Colds, cholesterol
	Ocimum basilicum L.	Basil	lahvaq	Dizziness, headaches, anxiety
	Origanum vulgare L	Oregano	zathar	Allergy, flu, gastralgia, anaemia

	Rasmarinus officinalis L.	Rosemary	Amezir ouroumi	Burning, colds, coughs, diarrhoea
	Savia officinalis	Sage	Agourim	Gastralgia, diabetes, cholesterol, mouth ulcers
	Thymus sp L.	Thyme	Ze3itra	Flu
Lauracées	Laurus nobilis L.	Laurel	Rend	Flu syndrome
Lythracées	Punica granatum L.	Grendier	Reman	Stomach ulcers, diarrhoea, anaemia
Malvacées	Malva sylvestris	Mallow	Mejjir	Mumps
Moracées	Ficus carica L.	Fig tree	Thankout	Warts, osteoarthritis, cough, tonic
Oléacées	Fraxinus sp L.	Ash	aslen	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE
	Olea europaea L	Olive tree	Azamour	Diabetes, cholesterol, osteoarthritis, wounds, breast cancer, cysts, hair loss
	Olea europaea var sylvestris L.	Oleaster	Ahechad	High blood pressure, diabetes, flu, vomiting
Papaveracées	Papver rhoeas L.	Poppy	Lahirir igran	Cough
Pinacées	Pinus halepensis Mill	Aleppo pine	azoumbil	Flu, dizziness, rheumatism

Pipéracées	<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.	Black pepper	Ifefel avarkan	Flu, cancer
Rhamnacées	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq.	Hawthorn	idhmim	Allergy, asthma, cough
	<i>Ziziphus</i> sp Mill	Jujube	Azougar	Alopecia
	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i> Mill	Quince	Kthounya	Cholesterol, diarrhoea
Rosacées	<i>Malus domestica</i>	Apple tree	Tefah	Goitre, diet
	<i>Prunus armeniaca</i> L.	Apricot	Mechmache	Diarrhoea, gastralgia
	<i>Rosa</i> sp	Rose	El warde	Facial care
	<i>Rubus fruticosus</i>	Bramble	Anjel	Angina, rheum, rates, digestive disorders
Rutacées	<i>Citrus limon</i> L.	Lemon	Qares	Respiratory conditions, obesity, stain removal
	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Orange	tchina	Colds, flu
	<i>Ruta graveolens</i> L.	Garden Street	Awarmi	Digestive disorders, respiratory conditions
Scrofulariacées	<i>Scrophularia tenuipes</i>	<i>Scrophularia tenuipes</i>	Aggerref	Breast cancer
	<i>Capsicum baccatum</i> L.	Pepper	Ifefel aqarhan	Intestinal cancer

Solanacées	Solanum lycopersicum L.	Tomato	Tomatiché	Plantar nail
	Solanum tuberosum L.	Potato	Batata	Headaches
Urticacées	Urtica dioica L.	Nettle	Azegdouf	Rheumatism, arthritis diabetes colds
Verbénacées	Aloysia triphylla palau	Verbena	Tizana	Fatigue, bloating, angina

Appendix B. Some MAP products in the LL of Tizi-Ouzou, Algeria

HYDROLATS ET SAUX ESSENTIELLES		
Produits	Prix (Dinars) DA	
	100 ML	500 ML
- LAVANDE VRAIE	290,00	490,00
- LAVANDE FINE ALTITUDE	290,00	490,00
- GERANIUM ROSAT	290,00	490,00
- EUCALYPTUS GLOBULUS	290,00	490,00
- EUCALYPTUS RADIATA	290,00	490,00
- EUCALYPTUS CITRONNE	290,00	490,00
- ROMARIN A CINQOLE	290,00	490,00
- CYPRES	290,00	490,00
- CITRONNELLE	290,00	490,00
- VERVEINE ODOORANTE	290,00	490,00
- LENTISQUE	290,00	490,00
- MYRTHE	290,00	490,00
- ORIGAN COMPACT	290,00	490,00
- THYM	290,00	490,00
- ORTIE	290,00	490,00
- CAROTTE SAUVAGE	290,00	490,00
BOURGEONS * (Gemmothérapie)		
- FIGUIER	290,00	490,00
- CÉDRÉ DE L'ATLAS	290,00	490,00
- AUBEPINE	290,00	490,00

PRÉPARATIONS A BASE D'HYDROLATS		
Symptômes	Prix unitaire (DA)	
	100 ml	500 ml
SOINS VISAGE		
- LOTION DEMAQUILLANTE	300,00	500,00
- LOTION ANTI TACHE - ANTI ROUSLEURS	400,00	600,00
- LOTION DESINFECTANTE (bouffons, points noirs...)	300,00	500,00
SOINS CHEVEUX		
- ANTI CHUTE - AIDE A LA REPousse (Cheveux gras, secs, tombés)	300,00	500,00

Chapter 6

Value chain analysis report for the Luxor
Living Lab (Egypt)

Tomatoes and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

Othman El Shaikh (external expert)

Chapter 6. Value chain analysis report for the Luxor Living Lab (Egypt) – Tomatoes and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

Summary

This report presents an analysis conducted under the framework on the NATAE project Task T3.2. The study analysed two key value chains in Luxor, Egypt: tomatoes and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs). These value chains were selected based on their economic significance, potential for agroecological transition, and local stakeholder interest. The study aimed to evaluate current trends in production and market strategies, challenges in production and accessibility, and the potential for agroecological inclusions in these sectors. The study employed a qualitative approach, based on a standard semi-structured questionnaire supported by focus group discussions conducted with 20 producers along with key stakeholders such as government officials, market intermediaries, processors, and civil society organizations. Main findings and observations show that producers in Luxor face a multitude of challenges that extend from production constraints, market access and financial barriers, financial constraints, and others. At the production side, land fragmentation is seen to scatter landholdings following traditional inheritance, and thus limit the capacity of diversification and achieving economies of scale. This is met with an increase in land reclamation projects and cultivations that do not align with agroecological and sustainability principles, and which include the use of chemical inputs, imported seeds, inefficient irrigation methods and other farming practices. Prices of inputs also pose a serious challenge with rising costs. At the downstream level, producers are mostly seen to face market access challenges related to dependency on middlemen, lack of certification adoption and their accessibility/feasibility, and infrastructural limitations in transportation and storage. Thus, producers tend to mostly depend on middlemen such as local traders for accessing markets, especially export. Indeed, international export markets are a main objective for producers and middlemen alike due to the higher economic returns that could be attained given price volatility at the local and national levels. Yet, by passing through middlemen, producers limit their economic return and bargaining power especially when operating individually. Collective action is not advanced in rural regions such as those in Luxor, and cooperatives remain incapable to properly respond to their needs or provide effective services. Yet, the tomatoes and MAPs value chains are seen to hold potential for adapting farming practices and empowering small producers and especially women. Reasons for that include the favourable climatic conditions, important solar radiation and low humidity, making it suitable for innovative sun-drying processes, especially with tomatoes, while minimizing energy costs. These processes become more interesting with existing drying stations in

Luxor that have successful experiences in mobilizing local producers following standardized and adapted farming practices to meet demand. Such facilities also interestingly provide important employment for women who play an essential role in the processing operations, mainly preparation, drying and packing. Initiatives forming such facilities have risen not only from private investors, but also from development associations and government-affiliated local development offices, showing interest and awareness in initiating such activities for the benefit of local small producers. Therefore, and in order to develop these value chains in a context like in Luxor, recommendations revolve mainly around providing adequate awareness and capacity building to producers to help raise their understanding on the benefits of adopting agroecological practices and innovative processing as sun-drying. Other main recommendations include enhancing infrastructural needs to facilitate access to markets, such as in logistics, storage and transportation. Special attention is recommended on encouraging collective actions such as in cooperatives and farmer groups, with the needed reforms in their service provision and management, to help consolidate efforts, augment negotiation power and reduce dependence on middlemen. Effort should also be given on enhancing financial and political support especially in access to microcredit and adapted subsidies and adaptations into local policies revolved around sustainable practices. By addressing these challenges and leveraging opportunities, the tomato and MAPs value chains in Luxor can be positioned for greater sustainability, resilience, and benefit for local producers.

6.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

6.1.1 Overview of the agricultural sector in Egypt

The agricultural sector in Egypt consists one of the essential economies in the country, contributing approximately 12% to the national GDP and employing around 25% of the workforce (World Bank, 2018). The importance of the sector shows by the size of the agricultural land, reaching 3.6 million hectares, which is roughly 3.8% of the country's total land area (FAO, 2021). Since historic times dating back to the ancient Egyptian civilization, the agricultural activities in Egypt have been concentrated along the Nile River and the Delta given the high fertility of the soil in those areas and their water resources. Agricultural cultivation in Egypt depends a lot on irrigation since levels of precipitation are low given its arid and semi-arid climate, and particularly around the Nile River. Moreover, the agricultural sector constitutes a significant source for employment, at around 25 to 28% of the national workforce. This proportion increases further in rural areas, such as in Upper Egypt, reaching up to over 55%. This indeed reflects the essential position that the sector holds in relation to the sustaining of livelihoods. Despite its importance, agriculture in Egypt remains limited to small farms scale that deploy traditional practices rather than more modern operations that meet international standard. Today's intensive crop production still dominates in Egypt using this dynamic

of small family farms under traditional methods in a surface area of less than one hectare, thus impacting productivity and competitiveness mainly to limited access to modern technologies and applications.

Egypt's agricultural output includes staple crops like wheat and maize, which are essential for domestic food security. The nation is also known for high-quality cotton, historically vital for export. Other significant crops include rice, sugarcane, and an expanding variety of fruits and vegetables such as citrus, grapes, and pomegranates. Egypt exports a significant amount of fruits and vegetables, with markets in Europe and the Middle East. Egypt's food trade balance is marked by substantial reliance on imports, especially staple foods such as wheat, corn, and oilseeds, due to the limitations of domestic agricultural production and the demands of a rapidly expanding population. Egypt is among the world's top wheat importers, underlining the critical importance of imports for ensuring food security and stabilizing market prices (FAO, 2021). While the country does produce various agricultural products such as fruits, vegetables, and rice for local consumption and export, these exports fall short of compensating for the extensive cost of imports (World Bank, 2022). Consequently, Egypt experiences a negative food trade balance, which poses challenges for achieving food self-sufficiency and economic stability amid global market price volatility and currency fluctuations (Abdelaziz et al., 2020).

In **Upper Egypt**, which extends from the area south of Cairo to Aswan in the south, plays a significant role in the nation's agriculture. This region encompasses a substantial portion of Egypt's total planting area, with vast expanses of fertile land along the Nile Valley suitable for various crops.

Upper Egypt is home to approximately **38% of Egypt's population**, with a high concentration in rural areas engaged in agricultural activities (CAPMAS, 2017). Despite its agricultural potential, Upper Egypt faces significant socioeconomic challenges such as poverty and economic disparities:

- **Poverty Rate:** The poverty rate in Upper Egypt is notably higher than the national average. According to the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), the poverty rate in Upper Egypt's rural areas was estimated at **51.9%** in 2015, compared to the national average of **27.8%** (CAPMAS, 2016). Some governorates, like Luxor and Aswan, have poverty rates exceeding **55%**.
- **Economic Disparities:** The region suffers from limited industrialization, high unemployment rates, and inadequate access to services and infrastructure compared to Lower Egypt.

Yet, the agricultural sector still holds an important significance in the area mainly in terms of cultivated surface area, production characteristics and employment.

- **Total Planting Area:** Upper Egypt contributes significantly to the country's total planting area, with an estimated **1.2 million hectares** under cultivation (Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation, 2019). This accounts for about **33%** of Egypt's total agricultural land.
- **Crop Production:** The region specializes in crops such as sugarcane, cereals, legumes, vegetables (including tomatoes), and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs). The climatic conditions favour year-round cultivation, especially in governorates like Luxor.
- **Employment:** Agriculture is a primary source of livelihood, employing over **55%** of the workforce in Upper Egypt's rural areas (CAPMAS, 2017).

Egypt, with its predominantly arid climate, faces significant challenges in managing its water resources. The country relies heavily on the Nile River, which supplies approximately 97% of its freshwater resources (Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation, Egypt, 2022). The total annual renewable water resources are estimated at 55.5 billion cubic meters (BCM), as per the Nile Waters Agreement of 1959. However, due to population growth and increased economic activities, the demand for water has surged, leading to a substantial gap between supply and demand. Egypt faces a significant water scarcity challenge due to its arid climate and reliance on the Nile River for over 90% of its water resources (Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation [MWRI], 2020). The country's total renewable water resources are estimated at 60 billion cubic meters per year, while the national water demand has reached approximately 80 billion cubic meters annually, resulting in a deficit of around 20 billion cubic meters (World Bank, 2021).

Agriculture is the predominant consumer of water in Egypt, accounting for about 86% of the total water usage (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2019). This heavy agricultural water consumption significantly impacts water availability in Upper Egypt, including the Luxor governorate. In Luxor, the scarcity is exacerbated due to higher temperatures and evaporation rates, leading to increased water demand for irrigation (El-Sayed et al., 2020).

The agricultural sector's extensive water use contributes to anticipated water deficits, especially in Upper Egypt. Projections indicate that by 2025, Egypt's water deficit could widen to 26 billion cubic meters if current consumption patterns continue (MWRI, 2020). This scenario underscores the critical need for efficient water management practices in regions like Luxor, where water scarcity directly threatens agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

Traditional Irrigation Methods still dominate in Egypt with surface Irrigation (flood irrigation) usage on approximately 70% of irrigated lands, particularly in the Nile Delta. General water use efficiency is low, around 50%, due to losses from evaporation, deep percolation, and runoff (ARC, 2022). Such

conditions lead to challenges main related to waterlogging, soil salinity, and inefficient water distribution among farmers.

For, modern irrigation techniques, Egypt is investing in modern irrigation systems to improve water use efficiency and productivity. These include sprinkler, drip irrigation, and subsurface drip irrigation systems. Sprinkler Irrigation is implemented on about 15% of irrigated lands, mainly in newly reclaimed desert areas. They can reduce water usage by 30-40% compared to traditional methods and are suitable for field crops, vegetables, and fodder crops. Drip irrigation is used on approximately 15% of irrigated lands, particularly for high-value crops like tomatoes, fruits, and vegetables. They increase water use efficiency to over 90%, saving up to 50-60% of water. Drip irrigation holds multiple benefits mainly in yield increase (boost crop yields by 20-30%), and fertilizer efficiency (allows for fertigation, reducing fertilizer usage by 20-25%). However, certain associated challenges with drip irrigation include the initial cost (high installation costs, averaging around \$1,500 per hectare) and maintenance which is required to prevent clogging. Finally, subsurface drip irrigation is an emerging technology which delivers water directly to the root zone below the soil surface. Its main advantage consists of further reducing evaporation losses and minimizing weed growth.

Other than the major issue of water scarcity and overuse, Egypt faces multiple challenges at the level of its national agricultural sector. These include mainly

Land Limitations and soil Degradation: with only about 4% of Egypt's total land area being arable and under the threat of urbanization reducing available space for agriculture, along with the overuse of chemical fertilizers and unsustainable practices degrading soil quality.

Infrastructure and supply chain limitations: Poor transportation and storage facilities hinder market access and contribute to postharvest losses, along with supply chain issues affecting both domestic distribution and export capabilities and impacting farmers' income and the availability of produce in the market.

Socio-economic factors: The agricultural sector in Egypt is characterized by a high number of small-scale farmers, which can limit economies of scale and the capacity for larger investments. High poverty rates which are higher in rural areas where agriculture is the primary source of livelihood, contribute to limited access to education, healthcare, and other essential services, impacting agricultural productivity and investment potential.

Figure 44: Diagram summarizing the agricultural challenges in Egypt

6.1.2 Significance of the agricultural sector in Luxor

Luxor, located in Upper Egypt along the eastern bank of the Nile River, is renowned for its historical heritage and agricultural productivity. The region's agriculture is sustained by the Nile's waters, which provide essential irrigation in an otherwise arid climate (FAO, 2015). Luxor's alluvial soils are rich in nutrients due to centuries of Nile flooding, supporting a diverse range of crops.

Agriculture plays a vital role in Luxor's local economy, second only to tourism. It is a primary source of employment and income for the rural population. Approximately **60%** of Luxor's workforce is engaged in agricultural activities (Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation, 2019). The sector contributes significantly to food security and provides raw materials for agro-industries, thereby bolstering economic stability in the region. Luxor's climate, characterized by hot, dry summers and mild winters, allows for year-round agricultural activities, although water management is crucial due to its arid environment. Traditional farming methods still play a significant role, often integrated with modern irrigation techniques to optimize water use.

Luxor's favourable climatic conditions and fertile soils within the valley allow for the cultivation of a variety of irrigated crops including:

- **Cereals:** Wheat and maize are staple crops essential for local consumption.
- **Sugarcane:** Luxor is one of the major sugarcane producing regions in Egypt.
- **Vegetables:** Tomatoes, onions, eggplants, and okra are widely grown, with tomatoes being significant for both domestic markets and export (Abou Hadid, 2010).
- **Fruits:** Dates, bananas, and citrus fruits contribute to the region's fruit production.
- **Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (MAPs):** There is a growing interest in cultivating MAPs such as chamomile, basil, and mint due to their economic value and demand in herbal medicine and essential oil industries (ElKhateeb et al., 2014).

Some of the main challenges being faced by the Luxor area include issues such as:

- **Poverty Rate**

Despite its agricultural potential, Luxor faces significant socioeconomic challenges. The poverty rate in Luxor Governorate is notably higher than the national average. According to the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), the poverty rate in Luxor was approximately **47%** in 2015, compared to the national average of **27.8%** (CAPMAS, 2016). High poverty levels are attributed to factors such as:

- **Limited Industrial Development:** Reliance on agriculture and tourism with minimal diversification.
- **Unemployment:** Seasonal nature of agriculture and fluctuations in tourism affect job stability.
- **Inadequate Access to Services:** Limited access to quality education, healthcare, and infrastructure in rural areas.

Dynamics in Land Tenure and Historical Land Fragmentation

Understanding the historical context of land tenure in Upper Egypt is crucial for a comprehensive socio-economic analysis of agricultural value chains, particularly for crops like tomatoes and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs). The region has witnessed significant transitions from traditional "old lands" along the Nile River to "reclaimed lands" in desert areas, affecting farm sizes, ownership patterns, and agricultural productivity (Fahmy, 2018).

Historically, agricultural land in Upper Egypt was concentrated in the fertile Nile Valley, known as the "old lands." These lands were characterized by smallholder farms passed down through generations, often resulting in fragmented plots due to inheritance practices (Bush, 2007). The average farm size in these areas is approximately 1.5 feddans (0.63 hectares), with many holdings less than one feddan (CAPMAS, 2017).

In the mid-20th century, the Egyptian government-initiated land reform policies to redistribute land from large estates to landless farmers, aiming to reduce inequality and boost agricultural output (Adriansen, 2009). This led to further fragmentation but increased the number of smallholders. To address land scarcity and overpopulation in the old lands, the government launched land reclamation projects targeting desert areas, creating "reclaimed lands" (Sims, 2015). These projects expanded agricultural land and were allocated to graduates, investors, and sometimes small farmers under various tenure arrangements (Denis & Kuppinger, 2020).

In reclaimed lands, farm sizes tend to be larger, averaging between 5 to 10 feddans (2.1 to 4.2 hectares), due to policies promoting commercial agriculture (El-Hefnawy, 2018). Ownership patterns differ significantly from the old lands; reclaimed lands are often acquired through government allocation, purchases, or long-term leases, sometimes leading to tenure insecurity due to bureaucratic

challenges and unclear land rights (Allam, 2020). In contrast, the old lands exhibit high degrees of fragmentation, with ownership divided among family members over generations. This fragmentation poses challenges for efficient farming practices, mechanization, and economies of scale (Awad & Al-Attar, 2017).

Recognizing the adverse effects of land fragmentation on agricultural productivity, the Egyptian government has implemented policies to encourage land consolidation. The Sustainable Agricultural Development Strategy Towards 2030 emphasizes the need for land consolidation to improve efficiency and productivity (MALR, 2009). Initiatives include:

- Promotion of Cooperative Farming: Encouraging farmers to form cooperatives to pool resources, access credit, and adopt modern technologies (Kassim & Hussein, 2018).
- Land Improvement Projects: Implementing programs that facilitate voluntary land consolidation, providing technical assistance and financial incentives to participating farmers (FAO, 2015).
- Legal Reforms: Enacting laws to streamline land inheritance and transfer processes to reduce fragmentation over time (Soliman, 2019).

These policies aim to create more sustainable agricultural practices by enabling larger, more economically viable farm units, particularly in reclaimed lands where the potential for commercial agriculture is higher.

Including historical data on land tenure and fragmentation enriches the socio-economic analysis by highlighting the structural challenges faced by farmers in Upper Egypt. Land fragmentation limits the ability of smallholders to invest in advanced agricultural practices, access markets, and improve livelihoods (El-Hefnawy, 2018). Understanding ownership patterns and government policies provides insight into the barriers and opportunities within the tomato and MAPs value chains.

6.1.3 Farming Systems in Luxor

Luxor's agricultural landscape is a mosaic of diverse farming systems that have evolved over centuries, harnessing the fertile alluvial soils of the Nile River and adapting to the region's unique climatic conditions. The farming systems in Luxor are integral to the livelihoods of its rural population and play a significant role in the local and national economy.

Main productions

Luxor's farmers cultivate a wide array of crops, including:

- **Cereals: Wheat:** Grown during the winter season (November to April), wheat is a staple food crop essential for local consumption and contributes to national food security. **Maize:** Cultivated in the summer season (May to September), maize serves as both a food crop and animal feed.
- **Sugarcane:** Luxor is one of Egypt's primary sugarcane producing regions. Despite being water-intensive, sugarcane remains economically important due to its use in sugar production and employment generation.
- **Vegetables:** Luxor is renowned for its vegetable production, supplying both local markets and other regions. **Tomatoes:** A significant crop due to high local demand and export potential. Multiple cropping cycles are possible due to the warm climate. **Onions and Garlic:** Grown for domestic use and export, these crops benefit from Luxor's dry climate, which is ideal for bulb development. **Eggplants, Okra, and Cucumbers:** Commonly cultivated vegetables that contribute to dietary diversity and income.
- **Fruits: Dates:** Date palms are culturally and economically significant, with varieties like Siwi and Saidi cultivated. **Bananas:** Grown in areas with ample water, bananas are a high value crop. **Citrus Fruits:** Although not a primary crop, citrus cultivation includes oranges, lemons, and mandarins, contributing to both local consumption and export.
- **Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (MAPs):** Hibiscus, chamomile, basil, peppermint, lemongrass, and fennel: These plants are gaining importance due to their high market value in the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries. They are well-suited to Luxor's climate and can be grown with relatively low water requirements.

Irrigation practices, cropping patterns and soil fertility

In Luxor, traditional and more modern form of irrigation exist. Traditional flood irrigation is still prevalent among smallholders, utilizing Nile water through canals. Modern irrigation methods on another hand include drip and sprinkler irrigation systems which are being increasingly adopted, particularly by larger farms and those engaged in high value crops, to enhance water use efficiency and conserve water resources. Monocropping is still common for staple crops like wheat and sugarcane, whereas intercropping and crop rotation practices are applied through the intercropping of legumes with cereals or vegetables, which enhances soil fertility through nitrogen fixation and reduces pest incidences. In terms of soil fertility management, chemical fertilizers are commonly applied to meet the nutrient demands of high yielding crop varieties. Organic amendments are used at a lesser extent and include the use of animal manure and compost to improve soil structure and fertility. The overapplication of chemical fertilizers in Luxor, as in other agricultural regions in Egypt,

has been a significant concern due to its impact on soil health, water quality, and long-term agricultural sustainability. Farmers in Luxor, seeking to maximize crop yields and maintain productivity in a challenging environment marked by high temperatures and limited rainfall, often resort to using large quantities of chemical fertilizers. This practice is driven by a desire for quick results and the need to meet market demands, especially for crops like sugarcane and vegetables that are commonly grown in the region.

Farm Sizes, land tenure and labour force

Smallholder farms constitute the majority in Luxor, with landholdings typically less than 5 feddans. Such farms normally rely heavily on family labour and traditional farming methods and face challenges in accessing credit, technology, and markets. On a lesser extent, medium to large farms also exist ranging from 3 to over 5 Feddans. Such farms are more likely to adopt modern technologies and irrigation methods, and normally engage in commercial farming with better access to inputs and services.

In terms of land ownership, some farmers in Luxor own their land, providing security and incentive for long term investments. Others undergo the leasehold and sharecropping with farm being leased land or through sharecropping arrangements, which can impact their willingness to invest in sustainable practices. Small farmers in Luxor often face challenges related to land access, which impacts their ability to sustain livelihoods and expand agricultural activities. Land ownership in the region can be complex due to historical, social, and economic factors. Many small farmers in Luxor hold small plots of land that have been inherited across generations, leading to fragmented holdings that limit large-scale, efficient farming practices. These small plots can make it difficult for farmers to achieve economies of scale, affecting their overall productivity and profitability. Access to land for new or expanding farmers is often constrained by limited availability and high land prices, driven by competition for fertile areas along the Nile River. Additionally, government land reclamation projects, which aim to convert desert areas into arable land, sometimes pose challenges for small-scale farmers due to the significant investment required for land development, irrigation infrastructure, and ongoing maintenance.

Agriculture is the primary employer in rural Luxor. The labour force of farmers is composed predominantly of smallholder and family-run agricultural operations, which form the backbone of the region's agricultural sector. These farmers rely heavily on manual labour, often involving family members who contribute to planting, tending crops, and harvesting. Due to the traditional nature of farming in Luxor, farming practices are generally labour-intensive, with limited use of advanced machinery compared to larger, more commercial operations found in other parts of Egypt. The agricultural labour force in Luxor includes both permanent and seasonal workers. Permanent workers

are typically involved in ongoing farming activities, while seasonal workers are employed during peak periods, such as planting and harvest seasons, especially for labour-demanding crops like sugarcane and vegetables. Seasonal laborers often come from nearby rural areas, contributing to a fluctuating workforce depending on the time of year and crop cycle.

Women in Luxor’s agricultural sector constitute between 30-40% of the agricultural workforce, particularly in labour intensive tasks such as planting, weeding, harvesting, sorting, and postharvest processing. Despite their significant contributions, women often have limited access to land ownership, credit facilities, and decision-making roles within farming communities.

Mechanization varies widely in Luxor, with larger farms applying more use of tractors, combine harvesters, and mechanized irrigation systems. Smallholders on another hand often rely on manual labour or animal drawn implements due to financial constraints.

Figure 45: A summary of farming systems in Luxor, Egypt

Main Challenges in Luxor’s Farming Systems

Luxor’s farming systems face a multitude of challenges that threaten their sustainability and productivity. Water scarcity is a significant issue, driven by increasing competition for Nile water due to upstream developments and the impacts of climate change. Additionally, overextraction of groundwater in some areas has caused declining water tables, exacerbating the problem. Soil

degradation and salinity further strain agricultural productivity. These issues are often the result of improper irrigation practices, overuse of chemical fertilizers, and a lack of crop rotation, leading to reduced crop yields and long-term soil productivity. Climate change compounds these difficulties, as rising temperatures and changing precipitation patterns heighten the vulnerability of farming systems. Extreme weather events, such as heatwaves and unseasonal rains, increasingly damage crops. Farmers also face obstacles in accessing essential agricultural inputs and services. Smallholders struggle to obtain quality seeds (imported), fertilizers, and pesticides being heavily applied, while limited access to credit and financial services prevents investment in improved technologies. Furthermore, poor rural infrastructure, including inadequate roads and storage facilities, hampers market access and contributes to significant postharvest losses. Collectively, these challenges underscore the need for integrated solutions to bolster the resilience and efficiency of Luxor's agricultural systems.

Figure 46: A diagram representation of the main challenges in Luxor's agricultural sector, Egypt

Given Luxor's farming systems context, opportunities for improvement are important to consider through targeted interventions and sustainable practices. Within that regard, multiple possible topics could be addressed. Other than the adoption of agroecological practices and sustainable agronomic techniques (such as conservation agriculture, organic farming, and agroforestry that can enhance resilience and productivity while promoting sustainability and integrated nutrient management), the strengthening of capacity-building initiatives and agricultural extension services is another crucial step. Providing farmers with training, demonstration and support, while involving them in participatory decision-making and knowledge exchange, fosters innovation and practical solutions tailored to local

conditions. Value addition and agribusiness development also present promising avenues. Establishing local processing facilities for crops like tomatoes and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) can also possibly contribute to the increase of farmers' incomes. Promoting entrepreneurship, especially among youth and women, can further drive economic growth in rural areas. Additionally, forming and strengthening farmer associations can improve access to essential inputs, services, and markets. These organizations empower farmers through collective action, enhancing their bargaining power and enabling economies of scale. Finally, expanding access to credit and financial services is vital. Microfinance institutions and government programs can offer tailored financial products to smallholders, facilitating investment in irrigation infrastructure, modern equipment, and sustainable practices. Together, these measures can unlock the full potential of Luxor's agricultural sector.

6.1.4 Government and Institutional Support

The primary authority overseeing agriculture in Egypt is the **Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation (MALR)**, the **Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation**, the **Ministry of Environment and other directorates**.

Recent agricultural policies in Egypt have been designed to address key challenges in the sector, such as water scarcity, limited arable land, and the need for modernization. The **Sustainable Agricultural Development Strategy (SADS) 2030** remains a cornerstone of the country's agricultural policy, aiming to improve food security, boost productivity, and promote environmental sustainability. This strategy emphasizes sustainable water management, modern irrigation techniques, but focuses on land reclamation projects to expand cultivable areas and increase agricultural outputs for national food security and export objectives.

Water management policies have been a significant focus, given Egypt's heavy reliance on the Nile River. The government has implemented measures to promote the use of water-saving technologies, such as drip and sprinkler irrigation systems. Additionally, there are regulations to limit the cultivation of water-intensive crops and encourage the planting of crops that are more drought-tolerant.

In Luxor, local authorities involved in the agricultural sector include the *Directorate of Agriculture*, which operates under Egypt's Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation. This office is responsible for overseeing agricultural policies, managing resources, providing support to farmers, and implementing government agricultural programs within the governorate. The *Irrigation Department*, part of the Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation, also plays a critical role in managing water

distribution for agriculture, ensuring that the limited water resources of the Nile are used efficiently and equitably.

Additionally, there are various local agricultural cooperatives and farmer associations that support smallholder farmers by providing resources, training, and access to markets. These cooperatives often work in collaboration with government agencies to implement development projects and enhance agricultural productivity. Local research institutions and agricultural extension services also contribute by introducing modern farming techniques and improving crop management practices to boost yields and sustainability in the region.

Efforts to enhance agricultural systems in Luxor are supported by a range of initiatives focusing on sustainability, resilience, and integration with broader socio-economic opportunities. Government policies play a central role in promoting agricultural development. These focus on increasing productivity, enhancing food security, and encouraging sustainable resource use. Programs to subsidize inputs, modernize irrigation systems, and invest in agricultural research aim to support these goals. Research and development collaborations with universities and institutions focus on creating and disseminating crop varieties and farming techniques that are resilient to climate change and pests. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) complement these efforts by targeting vulnerable groups, including women and smallholders, through capacity-building projects and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices. The cultural and historical context additionally adds a unique dimension, as traditional knowledge possessed by local farmers provides valuable insights into sustainable farming. Combining these indigenous practices with modern techniques is believed to create more resilient systems. Luxor's status as a prominent tourist destination further offers opportunities for agritourism, integrating agriculture with tourism to generate additional income and promote cultural exchange. Sustainability and resilience are indeed mentioned as priorities through environmental conservation efforts, such as protecting the Nile River and promoting biodiversity, alongside community engagement initiatives. Involving local communities in decision-making processes is encouraged as to foster social cohesion and enhance resource management, along with education campaigns to encourage sustainable practices.

Yet, Luxor's challenges in the agricultural sector faces still hinder its growth and sustainability. Climate change poses a major threat, with increased heatwaves and water scarcity severely affecting crop yields and overall agricultural productivity. Infrastructure limitations exacerbate these issues, as inadequate storage and processing facilities result in considerable postharvest losses, reducing the economic returns for farmers. Furthermore, market access remains a persistent obstacle. Logistical constraints and the lack of necessary certifications make it difficult for farmers to reach larger markets, limiting their ability to capitalize on high-value opportunities. Finally, land fragmentation remains a

significant challenge in Luxor's agricultural sector, where farmland is often divided into small, scattered plots. This situation arises from traditional inheritance practices, which result in land parcels being subdivided among heirs over generations. The fragmentation of land creates several issues that impact agricultural productivity and efficiency such as reduced economies of scale, inefficient resource use, lower productivity, challenges in market access, management difficulties and increased vulnerability.

Figure 47: A summary of the main possible improvements in Luxor's agricultural sector, Egypt

Figure 48: Map of the Luxor Living Lab territory, Egypt. Source: Ahmed, A. A. (2014).

Figure 49: A representation of the main stakeholders in the agricultural sector in Luxor, Egypt.

6.2 Methodology

The study employed a qualitative research approach, utilizing semi-structured interviews and questionnaires provided by the research task team at the CIHEAM IAMM to gather data from producers and key actors within the tomato and MAPs value chains. The value chains were selected based on their significance to Luxor's agriculture, potential for agroecological transition, and interest expressed by stakeholders during bilateral discussions and validation by the Living Lab Board, as elaborated in the next section.

Producers partaking in the data collection procedure were selected on the basis of representativity of farmer profiles in Luxor. This means that they included producers engaged in tomato and MAPs cultivation, representing different farm sizes, locations, and levels of agroecological practice adoption. In total 10 producers for each value chain were selected for interviewing. In addition, other types of questionnaires were filled with 8 key informants and actors in the area including 4 government officials from the Ministry of Agriculture, governor office and the local extension department and agriculture directorate, 1 processors, and 3 traders and market intermediaries.

The analysis represented in this report focused on the qualitative characteristics mainly concentrating around farm properties, production processes, market strategies, overview of agroecological practices, and the challenges they face. Data were analysed using thematic analysis to identify key patterns and themes as seen relevant.

For complementation of the information collected from individual questionnaires, two Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were also conducted. The first was conducted with a group of farmers (16 attendees) engaging in the tomato and MAPs value chains, and the second was conducted with a mix (17 attendees) of farmers, government officials, local development office, and representatives of civil society which helped obtain qualitative insights into the value chains, market dynamics, governance structures, and the adoption of agroecological principles at local level.

The data collection tools used during this task consisted of the questionnaires that were developed by the task team at the CIHEAM IAMM based on the objectives and research questions, covering sections on:

- Farm and producer characteristics
- Production processes and agroecological practices
- Market access and strategies
- Barriers and opportunities
- Value chain governance

For the Focus Group Discussions, open ended questions were asked to facilitate discussions around topics related to:

- Market strategies and barriers
- Motivation for adopting agroecological practices
- Value chain dynamics and governance
- Collective efforts and stakeholder collaboration

Training of enumerators and facilitators next took place covering information on ethical considerations and informed consent procedures, and interview techniques and questionnaire administration.

Person-to-person questionnaires were next conducted face-to-face with the selected 20 farmers (10 from each value chain) and the selected key actors. Interviews were scheduled at convenient times and locations for the farmers and the responses were recorded on paper questionnaires and later digitized. On average, interviews lasted between 1 to 1.5 hours.

For focus group discussions, each session lasted approximately 4 hours, following the discussion plan outlined. Participants were provided with an introduction on the NATAE project and objectives of the task, followed by a discussion around the planned questions. Researchers were attentive to cultural norms and practices and efforts were made to ensure that all participants felt comfortable and respected during interactions.

Finally, data analysis was conducted following the report outline provided by the research team which includes both quantitative overview descriptive analysis and mainly qualitative and comparative analysis.

The data collection and analysis was conducted following the NATAE project ethical considerations. Informed consent was collected from each interviewee whether in individual or group meetings for the collection of data but also for image use (photo/video/audio). Personal identifiers were removed during data analysis to maintain anonymity. Raw data was stored securely and only accessible to the local research team. The results represented in this report attempt to capture the dynamics of the selected value chains given the local context and collected data. Yet, it should be noted that the small sample size could pose a limit and the generalizability of the findings. In addition, since the study focuses on depth, providing detailed insights was maintained from a selected group of participants. These conditions could be limiting to the study but the sampling was conducted rather purposively in order to target the proper interviewees needed, while including a diversity in the participants range.

6.3 Value Chain Selection

The value chains selected in Luxor, Egypt consist of 1) Tomatoes and 2) Medicinal and Aromatic Plants. These two VCs were selected particularly due to their sun-drying processing which presents a competitive advantage given the favourable hot and dry climate in Luxor. Additionally, sun-drying processes provide an interesting pathway for the participation of women in the economic cycle especially in a community which is characterized by a rather conservative environment with limited activities dedicated for women.

Main justification behind the selection of the VCs

1. Tomato Value Chain

Despite not being one of the major productions in term of volume, the tomato value chain in Luxor presents an interesting potential in the region. Tomatoes are a significant crop in Luxor, with substantial local consumption and export potential. The value chain offers certain opportunities for agroecological practices and involves various actors, from smallholder farmers to processors. Economically, tomato cultivation is a vital part of the agricultural sector due to its high demand and the value it adds through various processed products. The crop presents a versatility to the value chain, from fresh consumption to processed goods. The tomato production could hold a potential for community development by providing employment opportunities especially for women in processing, and has the potential to improve livelihoods especially in rural areas where smallholder farming is prevalent. The selection of the tomato value chain as a focus for agricultural development is justified by its economic importance, its role in supporting socioeconomic structures, and the potential for improvement and adaptation to climate change.

2. Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (MAPs) Value Chain

The selection of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) for cultivation and use is supported by several compelling reasons that span economic, socioeconomic, and environmental considerations. MAPs like hibiscus, basil, peppermint, and others are commonly cultivated in Luxor and have high economic value and demand in both local and international markets. The value chain could also hold potential for agroecological enhancement and diversification of farmers' income sources. The export potential of these crops is particularly strong, as they are valued for their quality and natural cultivation methods. Socially, the cultivation of MAPs provides livelihood opportunities for many rural communities, particularly smallholder farmers. It is a labor-intensive sector that creates employment across the value chain, from cultivation and harvesting to processing and marketing. The sector also empowers marginalized groups, including women, who often play key roles in production and value-added processing. Therefore, the MAP sector in Luxor is considered a promising area for economic

diversification and sustainable development. With strategic interventions and support, it can contribute to the region’s economic growth.

Validation Process

The selection was validated through discussions with the Living Lab Board, considering factors such as:

Economic and Social Importance: Contribution to the local economy and employment.

Agroecological Potential: Opportunities to implement sustainable practices.

Stakeholder Interest: Engagement levels of producers and other actors.

Figure 50: Representation of the flow of discussions on the selection of value chains to be studied in Luxor

6.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterization

6.4.1 Introduction to the studied value chains

6.4.1.1 Tomato value chain

Egypt stands as one of the foremost producers of tomatoes globally, playing a pivotal role in both the national economy and food security. The country's unique climatic diversity allows for year-round cultivation, but seasonal variations significantly influence production volumes, regional contributions, pricing, and the movement of tomatoes. As of 2023, Egypt's annual tomato production was approximately 8 million tons, positioning it among the top tomato-producing nations worldwide (FAO, 2023). This substantial output is facilitated by Egypt's varied climatic zones, which enable continuous

cultivation throughout the year. Tomatoes account for about 34% of the total vegetable production in the country, reflecting their significance in Egyptian agriculture (CAPMAS, 2022).

According to the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), the Nile Delta (summer Season for tomato production contributes approximately 60% of total production. Upper Egypt (winter season for tomato production) accounts for about 35%, whereas the remaining 5% comes from greenhouse production and specialized cultivation areas distributed in other regions in the country (CAPMAS, 2022). The Nile Delta region, including governorates like Beheira, Kafr El Sheikh, Gharbia, and Sharqia, dominates summer tomato production. The fertile alluvial soils and favorable climate conditions contribute to high yields. The summer season, spanning from April to September, witnesses peak production in these areas (Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation, Egypt, 2023). For Upper Egypt, Governorates such as Minya, Sohag, Qena, and Luxor take the lead in winter production. From October to March, the warmer winter climate in these southern regions allows for optimal tomato cultivation when northern regions are less suitable due to cooler temperatures (Egyptian Agricultural Research Center [ARC], 2022).

Figure 51: Distribution of tomato production surface area in Egypt (source and year N.A)

The tomato value chain in Luxor encompasses production, processing, and marketing activities. Tomatoes are widely cultivated due to favourable climatic conditions and soil fertility in the valley. Yet, land reclamation is expanding in the desert and requires high application of fertilizers, a fact existing in the valley as well. Sun-drying is considered an added-value activity since the desert climate with low humidity and extended solar radiation provide excellent drying conditions with low resources needed. Once sun-dried, products are usually destined for export since sun-dried tomatoes are not commonly consumed in the local or national cuisine. Despite being recent and novel, the tomato value chain in Luxor holds an interesting potential for innovation, incorporation of possible agroecological practices and standardization of processes, women participation and ultimately better returns for producers.

The tomato value chain in Luxor, Egypt mainly revolves around the involvement of the following stakeholders:

Producers: Small to medium scale farmers cultivating tomatoes for local markets and contracted once the product is destined to processors (i.e. export market).

Processors: Mainly drying stations and companies like Golden Valley Company processing tomatoes into sundried products. Several drying stations, around 4, are found in Luxor. 1 is privately owned, 2 are owned by local associations, and 1 is recently constructed by the local development office and is currently looking for investors for its functioning.

Markets: Local consumption and national distribution mainly for fresh tomatoes, and international exports, particularly to European markets for sun-dried tomatoes.

Main challenges of the tomato VC in Luxor mainly include climatic stresses and the limited and fragmented farm sizes, market saturation during peak harvests leading to significant reduction in prices, and infrastructural limitations. Other major challenges include the overapplication of chemical inputs and low awareness of producers on the negative impacts of such inputs on the environment and public health.

6.4.1.2 *Medicinal and aromatic plants value chain*

Luxor, historically known as Thebes, is a region rich in cultural heritage and biodiversity along the Nile River. The area has been a cradle for the cultivation and use of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) since ancient times. These plants have played a significant role in the daily lives of the local population, serving culinary, medicinal, and ceremonial purposes (Nunn, 2002). Today, production of MAP in Egypt revolved around herbs, spices, and essential oils (ILO, 2020).

Common Medicinal Plants in Luxor

- **Hibiscus (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*)**
Historical Usage: Known as *karkade*, hibiscus was consumed by ancient Egyptians and used in religious ceremonies (Mabry et al., 1970).
Culinary Use: Brewed into a tart, cranberry-like flavoured tea.
Traditional Medicine: Used to lower blood pressure, reduce cholesterol, and as a diuretic.
- **Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) and Spearmint (*Mentha spicata*)**
Historical Usage: Mints were widely used for their refreshing qualities and digestive benefits. Pharaohs favoured mint for its fragrance and medicinal properties (Nunn, 2002).
Culinary Use: Added to teas, beverages, and dishes.
Traditional Medicine: Used to relieve gastrointestinal discomfort, nausea, and as a cooling agent.
- **Basil (*Ocimum basilicum*)**
Historical Usage: Considered a symbol of love and good fortune, basil was used in embalming practices and as an offering to deities (Darby et al., 1977).
Culinary Use: Integral in local dishes like *koshari* and salads.
Traditional Medicine: Employed to alleviate respiratory ailments, headaches, and as an antimicrobial agent.
- **Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*)**
Historical Usage: Chamomile was revered in ancient Egypt for its healing properties, particularly as an anti-inflammatory and antipyretic agent. It was dedicated to the sun god Ra and used in rituals (Manniche, 1989).
Culinary Use: Chamomile tea is a popular beverage in Luxor, consumed for its calming effects and pleasant aroma.
Traditional Medicine: Used to treat digestive disorders, skin irritations, and to promote relaxation.
- **Lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*)**
Historical Usage: While not native, lemongrass has been adopted into Egyptian herbal practices for its therapeutic properties.
Culinary Use: Used in teas and soups, imparting a citrus flavour.
Traditional Medicine: Utilized for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties, often in treating colds and headaches.
- **Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*)**
Historical Usage: Found in tombs, indicating its value in ancient times (Darby et al., 1977).
Culinary Use: Seeds are used in spice blends and to flavour bread.
Traditional Medicine: Employed to enhance lactation, manage diabetes, and soothe gastrointestinal issues.
- **Marjoram (*Origanum majorana*)**
Historical Usage: Associated with happiness and used in love potions.
Culinary Use: Used to season meats and stews.
Traditional Medicine: Utilized for its antiseptic properties and to relieve digestive and respiratory problems.

- Cumin (*Cuminum cyminum*)

Historical Usage: Used as a spice and preservative in mummification processes.

Culinary Use: Essential in dishes and spice mixes.

Traditional Medicine: Aids in digestion and is used as a remedy for colic and bloating.

- Anise (*Pimpinella anisum*)

Historical Usage: Valued for its sweet aroma and medicinal properties.

Culinary Use: Brewed into teas and used in pastries and bread.

Traditional Medicine: Treats coughs, indigestion, and promotes lactation.

Usage in the Local Kitchen

In Luxor, medicinal and aromatic plants are integral to both the culinary and cultural traditions, playing a significant role in the local cuisine. Herbal teas and beverages, such as those made from chamomile, hibiscus, mint, and anise, are staples in Luxor households, consumed not only for their refreshing taste but also for their medicinal properties, offering various health benefits (Nunn, 2002). Additionally, aromatic herbs like basil, marjoram, cumin, and coriander are fundamental in seasoning traditional dishes, enhancing flavours while contributing to the nutritional value of meals (ElKhateeb, 2014). These plants are also key ingredients in condiments and sauces, such as duqqa (a spice mix) and zabadi (yogurt sauce), which accompany many meals and snacks, further highlighting their versatility and importance in the region's culinary practices (Elsharkawy & Zaher, 2017). The use of these plants reflects a deep cultural connection to both the land and its agricultural practices, where food and health are intertwined.

Luxor, historically a centre of knowledge and medical activity in ancient Egypt, played a pivotal role in the development of herbal medicine. Ancient texts like the Ebers Papyrus and Edwin Smith Papyrus, which date back to the 16th century BCE, reference numerous medicinal plants used for a variety of ailments, highlighting the sophisticated medical practices of the time (Nunn, 2002). The ancient Egyptians also practiced holistic healing, where medicine was intertwined with religious and magical beliefs. Priests, often acting as physicians, used plants not only for physical ailments but also for spiritual healing (ElKhateeb, 2014). The medicinal practices included topical applications, inhalations, and oral remedies, all derived from plant extracts, infusions, and poultices (Gliessman, 2015). Many of these plants still hold cultural significance today, with chamomile linked to the sun god and basil regarded as a protective herb (Zahran & Willis, 2009). The knowledge of these plants has been passed down through generations, with local healers, often women, continuing to prepare remedies for their communities (Mahmoud, 2024). Despite the rise of modern medicine, many locals still turn to these traditional remedies for primary healthcare, demonstrating the lasting relevance of these plants (GIZ, 2022). Economically, the cultivation and processing of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) contribute to Luxor's economy through local sales and exports, while herbal markets and workshops have become important cultural and tourism attractions (World Bank, 2023).

The MAPs value chain in Luxor involves the cultivation, processing, and marketing of plants like hibiscus, peppermint, chamomile, basil, and lemongrass. The value chain is significant due to its high demand, economic potential (as opportunities for export and value addition), and potential transition to more agroecological practices given the suitability of the climate and soil conditions. The value chain for medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) in Luxor is a critical component of Egypt's agricultural sector. In Upper Egypt, 92% of the country's MAPs are produced, making the region a key player in both the national and global markets, with 26.05% of this production accounted for from the governorates of Qena, Luxor and Aswan (El-Sayed, 2020). In 2018, Egypt produced around 133,000 tons of MAPs, of which 80% was exported, generating approximately \$173.83 million in revenue. The main export destinations for these products include the USA, Europe, and East Asia, reflecting Egypt's strong position in international markets (GIZ, 2022).

The Luxor region in Upper Egypt has emerged as a significant hub for the cultivation, processing, and marketing of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs). The convergence of favourable climatic conditions, rich agricultural heritage, and growing global demand has propelled Luxor's MAPs sector onto both domestic and international stages.

The MAPs sector contributes significantly to the local economy:

- **Employment:** Provides jobs for thousands of individuals in cultivation, processing, and distribution.
- **Income Generation:** Value-added processing increases income for farmers and processors. Essential oils, for example, have a much higher market value than raw herbs.
- **Foreign Exchange Earnings:** Exports of MAPs contribute to Egypt's foreign exchange reserves.

Recent studies have highlighted the significant market potential of four specific MAPs crops—chamomile, marjoram, basil, and fennel. These crops have been identified as having strong international demand and offer opportunities for value addition, particularly in the form of essential oil production. Furthermore, investment in the MAPs sector has been projected to significantly boost Egypt's agricultural GDP by 2026 (IFPRI, 2021).

The sector also offers important opportunities for job creation, especially for women in rural areas. With growing global interest in natural and organic products, Egypt's MAPs sector is well-positioned for continued growth, provided that investments in sustainable farming practices and value chain development continue (Mahmoud, 2024).

By focusing on these key areas, the MAPs value chain in Luxor and Upper Egypt can expand its contribution to both domestic economic growth and export markets, helping Egypt solidify its position as a major global supplier of medicinal and aromatic plants.

6.4.2 Value Chains Mapping

6.4.2.1 Tomato value chain

The tomato value chain in Luxor, Egypt normally involves the following main steps:

The dynamics of the value chain of tomato production in Luxor, Egypt mainly depends on the final market of the product. It is mainly divided in two routes destined for either the local market or for export. Processing of tomatoes is mainly revolved around sun-drying as the climatic conditions of the desert climate is considered a competitive advantage for drying processes. Sun-dried tomatoes are mainly exported as they are not common in the national cuisine. Thus, when sun-drying is involved, it is through the sun-drying stations available in Luxor which contract farmers to standardize production according to the international client's specifications in addition to their provision with seeds and some input support. In other cases, fresh tomatoes are destined to the local market whereby traders and collectors similarly provide the farmers with input and fix the selling price prior to cultivation before eventually transferring the product to either the local wholesale market or the large wholesale market in Cairo. Only farmers that are financially capable, are able to handle access to wholesale markets themselves and mainly that of Cairo.

The below diagram summarizes the tomato value chain map:

Figure 52: Tomato value chain mapping in Luxor, Egypt

6.4.2.2 Medicinal and aromatic plants value chain

Similar to the tomato VC, two dynamics dominate according to the end market of the product; whether domestic or national market or export market. For export market, farmers are usually contracted by the drying station in order to standardize cultivation practices and inputs according to the needs and specifications of the export client. On the other hand, when products are destined for the local markets, farms usually deal with traders and collectors to access wholesale markets and whereby the price is usually fixed prior to cultivation.

The two following diagrams summarize i) the main actors involved and ii) main mapping steps in the VC of MAPs in Luxor, Egypt:

Figure 53: Medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) value chain mapping in Luxor, Egypt

6.4.3 Characterization and Diagnosis

6.4.3.1 General Overview of Producer Characteristics

In general, farmer producers in Luxor are usually smallholders with farm sizes ranging between 0.5 and 3 Feddans; with one Feddan equivalent to 4,200 sqm. The traditional agricultural landscape of Upper Egypt in fact is dominated by fragmented landholdings due to inheritance practices and limited availability of arable land along the Nile River (Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics [CAPMAS], 2020). The main characteristics of farming systems in Luxor are therefore described as:

- **Smallholder Dominance:** The prevalence of small farms is significant, with many producers owning less than 1 feddan. These smallholders rely heavily on tomato cultivation as a primary source of income.
- **Land Utilization:** Producers maximize land use through intensive cultivation techniques, often implementing crop rotation to enhance productivity and soil health.
- **Access to Reclaimed Lands:** Some producers have expanded operations onto reclaimed desert lands, where larger plots may be available. However, these areas require substantial investment in irrigation and soil fertility improvement.

Plots are usually dedicated entirely for the production of one cultivation with minimal diversity due to the small farm sizes. This is performed in order to maximize production possibly from the plots to attain market potential scale. In some cases, a small section of plots could be dedicated for feed production for the consumption of the small quantity of livestock owned by the producers on-farm with the objective of reducing purchase cost of feed.

According to the latest agricultural census of 2019, Luxor has around 16,500 feddans dedicated for tomato cultivation, with a winter-based production season extending from January to around May of each year. No clear recent data on the production quantities of MAPs exist, but it is known that nationally, Egypt dedicates around 90,000 feddans for MAPs farming, making it a major producing country even when wild grown herbs are not equated. According to the CAPMAS, in 2015/2016, Luxor has an area of 2.5 thousand feddans (top 10 in the country) dedicated for MAPs from which it was able to produce a quantity of 6.1 thousand tons (top 6 in the country after Fayoum, Menia, Beni Suef, Aswan, and Assuit) (ILO, 2020).

Agricultural employment in Luxor for both tomatoes and MAPs is mainly revolved around a combination of family labour, full-time producer activities, and seasonal workers. Full-time producers normally work on their farm, and when needed, they would get employed to assist with labour of other neighbouring farms around them. Part-time farmers also exist, who are employed in other economic

activities but who also work on their farms on off-work times. Yet, it is quite known that the MAPs sector is quite labour-intensive when compared to other cultivations in Egypt generally. Women constitute 30-40% of seasonal workers and are mainly involved in sorting and packing, and especially in the sun-drying processes of tomatoes where they constitute the majority of the labour force. For MAPs, the proportion of women is a little higher with 40 to 50% of the workforce (FAO, 2019), with their involvement being mainly in harvesting, processing (mainly sorting, preparing for sun-drying) and in knowledge transfer. It is however not common for women to own farms except when they are directly inherited. Despite the evident participation of women in certain specific aspects, major challenges remain in their access to land ownership, credit and access to decision-making positions.

6.4.3.2 *Overview of Value Chain Production*

Production dynamics of tomatoes and MAPs in Luxor are seen to be highly dependent on their end market. These include the local market, transfer to the capital market in Cairo, or the export market. The export market is in fact one of the most attractive directions for farmers as being a source of hard currency leading to higher levels of profits attained as compared to the local or national markets. For tomatoes, once destined for export, they usually go through a sun-drying process. This process forms a first processing, which gets exported in bulk to receive further processing by foreign industries, such as oil preservation in jars afterwards. In fact, tomatoes destined for the export market and sun-dried in drying stations found in Luxor are usually under more control than those destined for the local market. Sun-drying stations contract farmers and provide them with seeds and inputs to standardize production practices and quality in line with the requirements and specifications of the export clients. In such cases, farmers could possibly capture a higher return rate of their production once contracted by around 10 to 20% more than their locally marketed counterparts. During the production season, local farmers are contracted, but during off-seasons, and to extend working season of the drying units to about July-August, tomatoes are transported from other surrounding regions of about 5 hours away. The remainder of the year is used to dry other products such as dates, peppers, herbs, and others.

On average, farms produce 50-60 tons of tomatoes annually. Most practices are conventional and utilize nowadays chemical inputs as fertilizers and pesticides. Yet, some practices falling under agroecological concepts are present and include the application of inputs like organic fertilizers, biological pest control, and drip irrigation systems. The use of byproducts is rare but possible in, for example, the utilization of tomato residues for composting.

For processing, tomatoes are mostly sun-dried given the hot and dry climatic conditions in Luxor, and those processed sun-dried tomatoes are majorly destined for the export market. The sun-drying of tomatoes is considered a primary processing since the end-product consists of the sun-dried tomatoes being directly packaged in boxes without further treatment and shipped under refrigeration.

It is in the export market where these tomatoes are undergone further processing (mainly oil preservation in glass jars) and packaging for the end market. Sun-dried tomatoes are not common in the Egyptian cuisine and their local and even national consumption is minimal, therefore not in high demand. Yet, the export market remains a main objective for producers to supply directly to processing units abroad, receiving premium prices.

Regarding the MAP sector, Upper Egypt mainly and including Luxor enters in the zone that contributes significantly to the national MAP production. In Egypt, MAPs are mainly in the form of either fresh or dried consumption as herbs, spices, and teas, or as for other uses such as essential oils and cosmetics. Main productions nationally include anise, cinnamon, chamomile, caraway, fennel, liquorice, mint, basil, and others, with a prominent presence of hibiscus cultivation especially in Luxor. The medicinal and aromatic plant (MAP) sector in Egypt generally holds important economic and export value, with cultivation areas averaging around 37,800 hectares and contributing to an estimated 8 to 10 billion Egyptian pounds annually to the national income. Luxor's climatic and soil conditions are favourable for cultivating various MAPs reflected by the Egyptian government objectives to expand MAP cultivation to approximately 105,000 hectares while encouraging farmers to adopt practices that enhance economic and export benefits²⁷. The processing of MAPs in Egypt however requires the use of equipment especially in the case of essential oil extraction. For that, and although the production and processing of MAPs into essential oils is considered an old industry in Egypt, one of the main challenges it faces is the weak compliance to safety standards which lowers the quality of products thus compromising the sector's export potential (ILO, 2020). Despite that fact, Egypt remains one of the top exporters of plants and plant parts, ranking 5th worldwide with 5.8% of global exports as per the ILO (ILO, 2020). To date, main export markets for the MAPs sector include Europe and the United States, with some lesser quantities reaching the Gulf, Asia and Australia.

6.4.3.3 *Producer Market Characteristics and Market Strategies*

Market access, commercialization circuits, and price dynamics play a significant role in the structure of local agricultural markets, particularly in regions like Luxor, where small-scale farming dominates. Contract farming is commonly practiced especially for tomato and MAPs cultivation. This facilitates the compliance to standards requested by clients, especially when export-oriented, to which contractors are able to control through the provisions given to producers such as seeds, inputs, and practices. For sundried tomatoes, producers are typically contracted by drying units, which in turn control their inputs and farming practices based on the specifications of traders supplying the orders.

²⁷ Source: online article available in Arabic at

<https://akhbarelyom.com/news/newdetails/3223958/1/%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%86%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AA%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B7%D8%A8%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D8%B7%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%83%D9%86%D8%B2-%D8%A7%D9%82%D8%AA%D8%B5%D8%A7%D8%AF%D9%8A-%D9%88-%D8%A7>

As for MAPs, contract farming is performed mainly for products destined for processing as essential oil extraction by large-scale industries and processors found in cities such as Cairo. This approach facilitates overlooking the practices applied by farmers, and ensuring that they align with the requested norms. On another hand, when products are not accessible to exports, they get directed to the local or national market, for which production practices remain operated independently. Local middlemen and traders remain the main interlocutor between producers and the markets. They negotiate prices and collect products from producers after which they distribute to wholesalers, whether locally or nationally, with special interest to the largest wholesale markets in Cairo. It should be noted however that the majority of fresh tomatoes today are consumed fresh nationally and exports remain at much less quantities when fresh, unlike the sundried/processed tomatoes. It is also common for wholesalers to provide in-kind capital to farmers, who receive an advance with the promise of selling their product at a discounted price—typically around 25% less than market value. This arrangement is favored by producers, as it mitigates the financial risks associated with acquiring bank credit. Additionally, traders and producers enter into legally binding contracts, offering a layer of security for both parties. Farmers also have the option to sell at the local farmers' market, which takes place once a week, usually every Tuesday. However, this market is relatively small and cannot absorb all the produce, leaving many farmers reliant on traders or wholesalers. Only economically capable farmers, those with the financial resources to arrange their own transportation, can directly access the Cairo wholesale market to sell their goods at better prices. Ultimately, the export market remains a main objective for processed / sundried tomatoes since it provides access to higher prices and returns. Profit maximization comes as a normal objective for producers for multiple reasons, and mainly due to the farmer needs in seeking ways to meet their domestic and family needs in food and resources. Drying units are strategically placed in Luxor as a connection between farmers and the export end-market. Drying units, whether managed by the private or public actors or associations, are able to standardize cultivation, production and processing practices in compliance with the client's specifications. They also provide the farmer with the needed inputs and normally fix the price at levels that are moderately higher than the wholesale market, especially in cases of associations to attempt and provide a higher return to the producers.

The logistics of this system face significant challenges due to inadequate infrastructure, making transportation difficult and costly. Furthermore, the price dynamics within these markets are subject to fluctuation, especially as saturation increases. In response, processors often offer stable pricing through contracts, providing some predictability for producers. However, the broader market remains volatile, with prices dictated by supply and demand forces. Packaging practices also vary depending on the market. For local markets, producers typically use basic packaging, while standardized

packaging is used for products destined for processors. This difference in packaging reflects the varying requirements of the markets and buyers.

Given the limited landholding size in Luxor, typically less than one feddan per producer, there is little opportunity for production diversification. Farmers must focus on maximizing the output of their primary crops to ensure profitability. In some cases, a small portion of the land may be used for feed production to support the farmer's own livestock, helping to reduce feed costs. However, the small size of most holdings limits the scope for diversification, and farmers are largely dependent on specialized crops like tomatoes to generate income.

Regarding MAPs, the main market access of MAP products in Luxor revolves around providing supply to herbal tea companies, essential oil extractors, and local markets. Usually, around 40% of the local production in Luxor is channelled to local markets which price is based on local demand whereas the remaining 60% are normally destined for processors/export market which price is subject to contractual terms. Overall, the value chain involved smallholder farmers, cooperatives, and exporters. Yet, local farmers typically rely on intermediaries and traders to connect with both domestic and international markets, as most MAPs in Luxor are destined for export due to high demand in European and Gulf markets. This normative dynamic leads to the common challenges of limited direct market access for farmers, high dependency on intermediaries, and insufficient infrastructure for value addition at the local level. At the same time, the export market, which emphasizes quality, certification, and adherence to international standards, also leads to barriers for small-scale producers without sufficient support. Prices fluctuate depending on market competition with higher prices reached for quality products. Basic packaging is adopted for local sales while more standardized packaging is used for the export market.

Marketing and distribution of MAPs in Luxor is various which depends on whether the product is destined to the domestic or international markets. For the local market, the regular mechanism described for the tomato VC also applies. This means that farmers mostly relate to intermediaries and middlemen to secure the sale of their products. On a lesser extent, farmers could also sell their products to herbal shops, tea companies, or directly to consumers via farmers' markets and community-supported agriculture initiatives. Luxor's tourist concentration also pushes domestic sales though MAP-based souvenirs and wellness products found in souks or archaeological sites. Yet the norm remains in dealing with local traders when the product is to be marketed locally. Such traders are in a position in between the producers and the market which also include their dealing with exporters also. Similar to the dynamics observed in the tomato VC, and expected to characterize many of the farmer's activities, such middlemen provide farmers with inputs and technical assistance they need so that to manage the quality of production especially when destined to export. Additionally,

large-scale exporters or processors of MAP products exist in Egypt and are known to either conduct the entire phase of processing steps, or screening and packaging, or purchasing of final products directly from local traders but without any clear control of the quality or level of specialization given the variety of products together (ILO, 2020). Cases of directly contracting farmers are also prevalent in efforts to standardize production methods while at the same time fixing prices with the producers. Pricing is usually conveyed by local traders to small producers with little negotiation whereas larger exporters or processors are able to have more accurate information on market price trends (ILO, 2020). What is clear through with exporters is that organic pesticide-free MAPs are preferred so that to avoid issues of quality. Therefore, for the export market, exporters are in the position to manage main aspects such as manage logistics, compliance with regulations, and connections with key international destinations, including Europe, the Middle East, and North America.

For processing, MAP products usually undergo drying, grading and classification, cleaning, blending, packaging, and storage. For essential oil extraction, other than large-scale processors, farmers and local traders could on a lesser extent conduct these primary steps locally. Yet, large processing and exporting companies remain located in Metropolitan cities such as Cairo and Alexandria. However, Luxor's sorting, packaging and cooling station located at the airport has facilitated the conditioning, storage and connectivity of perishable foods such as fresh MAPs thus increasing overall competitiveness (FAO, 2015). Despite that, limited market intelligence and logistical constraints remain a challenge, but investments in cold chain and especially drying and packaging infrastructure are creating opportunities for growth and enhanced product quality. Yet, the many challenges related to marketing and market access remain significant for small producers especially at the level of access to market information, high dependency on middlemen, inconsistent quality standards, high logistics costs, and limited awareness on marketing channels.

6.4.3.4 *Certification*

In Egypt, the process of certification for agricultural crops such as tomatoes and MAPs could be considered as important for the distinguishing the quality, safety and competitiveness especially at the global scales. These certifications help producers meet international standards and access premium markets, where consumers and buyers demand traceability, sustainability, and high-quality products. In regions like Luxor, tomato and MAPs farming could benefit from the same available certification routes as those found across the country, although certain processes and types of certifications might slightly differ based on the target market characteristics as well as the specific location. These include:

Organic Certification: Managing Bodies: Egyptian Center of Organic Agriculture (ECO), Control Union Egypt, CERES Egypt.

Organic certification seems to be lagging behind in Luxor especially with smaller producers targeting only the local market. This is because large producers ignore the local market and are sustaining their production to penetrate the export market or are focused on expanding their domestic reach by dominating the premium segment. Despite the fact that it could fetch up higher prices in international markets, organic certification is however likely to be slower among farmers in Luxor compared to other areas in Egypt because of the relatively small size of the farms in the area. Obstacles to that adoption, other than land fragmentation, include inaccessibility to the required organic inputs and the absence of organic farming education.

Global G.A.P. Certification: Managing Bodies: Accredited certifiers like SGS Egypt and TÜV Nord Egypt.

Even if the Global G.A.P. certification could help better meet the requirements of international markets, small-scale farmers in Luxor may face challenges to access such certifications. This is mainly due to the limited access to training and resources. Yet, cooperatives and farmer groups who are able to achieve a more official frame, could be instrumental in helping producers access the necessary support and reduce certification costs. Global G.A.P. is highly valued by large-scale wholesalers and exporters, and it seems that Luxor's producers are beginning to recognize the value of such certification in improving their market access.

ISO Certifications: Managing Bodies consist of international and local bodies like Bureau Veritas and SGS.

Given the demand for high-quality and safe products in export markets, some larger tomato producers in Luxor pursue ISO certifications such as ISO 22000, especially those involved in processing and packaging tomatoes for export. These certifications ensure that production processes adhere to international food safety standards, which is crucial when entering markets with strict regulations, such as the EU and the U.S.

Fair Trade Certification: Managing Bodies FLO-CERT (for Fairtrade International standards).

While Fair Trade certification is not as widely applied in Luxor as organic or Global G.A.P., it is an option for producers aiming to access niche markets that value ethical trade practices. Luxor's tomato farmers may be less likely to pursue this certification due to the relatively small scale of production and the additional organizational requirements. However, some cooperative efforts may facilitate the certification process for groups of farmers, helping them collectively meet the FairTrade standards.

Despite it being essential to access premium markets and to ensure compliance to quality standards, the certification dynamics of in Egypt generally and in Luxor specifically remains relatively limited and complex to adopt by small producers. Main challenges when pursuing agricultural certifications is related to the **high costs** associated with certifications which producers are not able to handle, especially for small producers who have limited resources in market access and depend mainly on traders and intermediaries to sell their harvest. Additionally, certification process could include **complex procedures** as documentation and record-keeping, which could not be handled by individual producers alone. On another hand, there is a general need for awareness building of producers around the importance and benefits of certification, their applicability, requirements, and capacity building when it comes to market access and infrastructure. This **lack of awareness** among producers is particularly evident in rural areas such as those in Luxor. Limited understanding of the benefits and processes associated with certification, compounded by language barriers and restricted access to information, prevents many farmers from taking advantage of certification opportunities. Ultimately, the value chains can be described as mostly being reactive to the demands of the market and certification may more or less be adopted only when requested from the international market demand. In fact, it is the large-scale producers or exporters who, through their trade with foreign importers, are the actors who have better accessibility to market information, quality management system, certification schemes and international promotion and distribution.

6.4.3.5 *Focus on Collective Efforts, Short Circuit Markets, and Direct Contact with Consumers*

In Egypt, agricultural cooperatives have historically played a significant role in the agricultural sector since the 20th century. They provided various aspects of activities around the agricultural sector such as for credit, agrarian reform, and reclaimed lands. Official figures indicate the presence of over 5,500 cooperatives with little less than 5 million farmers affiliated (ECES, 2021), with agricultural cooperatives linked to the Ministry of Agriculture. Out of these, Upper Egypt has the second highest percentage of cooperatives after lower Egypt, with Luxor having however less than 2% of such cooperatives in the sector. Yet, the challenge of agricultural cooperatives in Egypt remains in the way that cooperatives function, and especially in them being semi-governmental entities. What is known is that cooperatives in Egypt generally have problems in weak service provision and human capabilities in management, follow-up, extension and investment along with weak technical and managerial capacities which hurdle the development of such structures. In fact, cooperatives in Egypt have the reputation of functioning as financial tools with strong shift to the private sector for the supply of chemical inputs and purchasing of strategic crops (ECES, 2021). Such dynamics have therefore limited the flexibility of cooperatives in responding to farmers' needs especially small farmers, and in

attaining marketing needs. The centralized nature of these cooperatives often results in bureaucratic inefficiencies, making it difficult for them to quickly adapt to new market demands or introduce actions that could provide the needed assistance and services to their members.

Despite these limitations, cooperatives are crucial for aggregating smallholder farmers' production, providing them with access to shared resources like inputs, equipment, and market information. However, many producers in Egypt and especially in Luxor still operate individually due to a lack of awareness or distrust in the cooperative model. On another hand, there is considerable potential for expanding the role of cooperative-like structures which are referred to as 'Rabita' or Union of producers. These unions exist in Luxor, even if in shy numbers, but are seen to group similar producers (similar cultivations, practices, irrigation techniques) together with efforts to reduce costs. These structures have the potential to structure farmer-led organizations and enhance their responsiveness to local needs. This would potentially allow farmers to better negotiate with traders and intermediaries, and to access higher-value markets. It is also important to mention that with the many challenges of the sector, many development agencies and civil society organizations have provided initiatives in support to producers through alternative models of organization. Under the supervision of the Ministry of Social Solidarity, several NGOs are working to foster collective action among farmers, promoting sustainable farming practices and facilitating access to markets. These efforts are often more agile than traditional cooperatives and better suited to supporting farmers in adopting agroecological methods or improving their resilience to market and climate-related risks.

In rural communities in Egypt such as those in Luxor, one of the most common forms of direct producer-consumer interaction occurs through weekly street /farmers' markets. These markets provide a platform for smallholder farmers to sell directly to local consumers, and thus linking producers directly to consumers. This is the case with the Tuesday weekly market. For farmers, the weekly market offers a consistent outlet to sell their produce, while consumers gain access to fresh, locally sourced food at reasonable prices. However, these weekly markets are typically limited in their scope and capacity. While they are effective for small-scale producers selling vegetables, fruits, and other daily essentials, they are not sufficient for handling larger, more specialized crops like tomatoes or MAPs. The production scale for tomatoes and perishability of products like MAPs make it difficult for weekly markets to accommodate the entire local supply. For that reason, farmers still prefer to sell their products in bulk to intermediaries who have the infrastructure needed to distribute them to larger urban markets or export them or to process their harvest. This is to avoid the farmers themselves having to handle fragmented quantities and the large efforts for diverse marketing channels. This creates another layer of continuous reliance on intermediaries which in turn means that smallholder farmers often receive lower prices for their products, reducing their profit margins.

6.4.3.6 *Motivation and Quality/Value Perception of Producers*

Tomato and MAPs producers in Luxor are seen to express motivation to adapt their production practices to align with agroecological principles, especially when combined between environmental and health concerns of conventional productions but especially when driven by economic return (export potential) and cost reduction. This shows an emerging but not normative understanding of environmental and health concerns, and a drive for changing practices or habits as a response to market demands. Issues of quality perception are not evident per se or by those adding value with the change of practices, but producers seem to be interested by reducing costs and the possibility of reaching premium markets. This aspect should be considered when approaching farmers with aspects of change. This could whether be included at the added value in terms of pricing or at the cost-saving potential with the proposed actions or practices. In fact, farmers are aware that by following certain circuits, especially those managed by local players such as drying units, the capability of acquiring an improved economic return is possible and especially with a producer's entire marketing of their end products being guaranteed. This forms an indirect encouragement for adopting changes in practices and marketing channels. This is how, possibly with the support of local demonstrations, that potential of agroecological methods serves as a strong incentive. These financial benefits, coupled with the opportunity to possibly target premium markets that demand sustainably grown produce, make agroecology a compelling choice for many farmers seeking competitive advantages. Producers are also starting to recognize the possible tangible improvements that agroecological practices could bring to the quality of their yields and soil health. This perception of improved yield quality adds to the value of adopting agroecological methods, reinforcing the idea that such practices are beneficial not only for the environment but also for the long-term success of farming operations. Therefore, the addressing of barriers through targeted support, such as subsidies for certification costs or simplified procedures, could encourage more producers to formalize their commitment to agroecology. By alleviating financial and procedural constraints, policymakers and stakeholders could enable a broader adoption of sustainable practices, helping producers capitalize on the environmental, economic, and market advantages agroecology offers.

6.4.3.7 *Barriers and Opportunities to Production and Market Access*

The tomato and MAPs value chains in Luxor face a mix of challenges at different stages of the value chain; a fact that transcends to the overall agricultural landscape in Egypt. Major challenges exist today in the farmers' production trends that risk creating serious barriers against adopting new practices, especially if no guarantee systems are put in place to mitigate these risks taken. These main barriers include high levels of poverty and low investment power of producers. This comes along with a weak access to training and technology added to the fact of low financing opportunities which

limited the decision-making power of producers. With weak or inadequate access for transportation/distribution, storage and infrastructure to access markets, a strong reliance of producers on middlemen emerges as a mean to ensure the selling of their produce, in bulk, even if this highly risks attaining much lower returns. This problem is worsened by limited access of farmers to market information, demand trends and consumer preferences thus deepening their reliance on intermediaries and creating more imbalance. In their habits of maintaining productivity and quality, producers revert to the purchase of imported hybrid seeds such as for tomatoes, and applying of chemical fertilizers and pesticides along with inefficient water use (such as flood irrigation). The matter is worsened by trajectories that allow reclamation of desert land with unsustainable practices that strongly utilizes inputs and resources. Yet, these dynamics occur as land tenure adds an additional layer of complexity with farmers' land access and inability to diversify productions and achieve economies of scale as they are highly limited by small fragmented plots. Economic constraints such as low access to credit is further limiting and exacerbates the financial constraints and hinders farmers' ability to invest and adopt new techniques. Farmers also face policy or operational barriers, such as those related to the complex procedures related to certification requirements, as well as a variety of environmental and climate-related challenges like water scarcity and soil degradation. Limited awareness of modern marketing channels, such as e-commerce or social media, also exacerbates market access and direct consumer relations. In an attempt to counter these barriers, and for an additional channel than intermediaries, partnerships with processors is seen to be a potential to achieve better levels of profits for farmers. These routes are also capable of encouraging possible adoptions of new practices and techniques which could fall under the umbrella of agroecological practices. Yet, this has been seen to occur when such requirements get integrated within the standards or conditions of foreign dealers, and mainly when destined for the export market. Seasonality of productions, and particularly in the case of tomatoes, additionally introduces other complexities. The dynamic nature of winter (Upper Egypt) and summer (Lower Egypt) harvests of tomatoes requires efficient regional distribution to balance supply and demand. Economically, seasonal fluctuations normally cause price volatility that affect both farmers (incomes when prices are low in peak production times) and consumers (affordability when prices are high in low production times). Socially, the seasonal nature of tomato farming creates fluctuations in labour demand, highlighting the need for equitable labour policies and local employment opportunities.

Addressing such challenges requires interventions relating to the capacity and awareness building of producers, infrastructure development, and policy support. Investments in supply chain logistics, such as packaging, cold chain or drying facilities, could hold important potential in improving product quality during transit and enhancing export potential. Similarly, promoting sustainability and market diversification and direct marketing channels can open access to niche markets. This however should

be coupled with awareness and capacity building of producers on such methods as well as their empowerment in adopting such ways. Opportunities found in places of higher demand for natural and organic products could be tapped through added value processing facilities. Although drying units function more within the tomato value chain, other types of local processing could be considered for MAPs such as drying (onsite rather than in units) and distillation equipment. Additionally, encouraging stronger collective initiatives, such as those based on the ‘Rabita’ approach, could possibly act as pilot efforts in demonstrating the benefits.

On another hand, the role of women should be looked at as an interesting opportunity for their economic participation that both value chains hold. This is especially true at the level of processing and drying units in Luxor, which to date mostly rely on women labour in preparation and sun-drying. This becomes the more interesting as the local conditions in Luxor, and the available geo-climatic conditions, provide the main needed resources and favourable conditions to achieve quality sun-drying processing with no significant investment costs. By addressing these economic, environmental, and social dimensions, the tomato and MAPs value chains can become more sustainable and resilient, fostering better outcomes for farmers, workers, and consumers alike.

6.4.3.8 *Value Chain Governance and Decision Making Power*

Institutional Governance

In Egypt, regulations coming from the Ministry of Agriculture significantly impact the entire sector productions including normally those of the tomato and MAPs value chains. Policies related to land use, water rights, and export regulations are particularly influential. Although the Ministry has introduced agricultural modernization strategies, these are generally focused on conventional agriculture, with minimal direct support for agroecological practices within these value chains. The continued, albeit reduced, subsidies for fertilizers and fuel encourage input-heavy farming systems, which limits the adoption of more sustainable agroecological approaches (GIZ, 2022). Furthermore, Egypt’s “Sustainable Agricultural Development Strategy Towards 2030” acknowledges the need for sustainability, yet specific support for agroecology remains limited (CAPMAS, 2018). This becomes especially important with the significant focus public policy considerations give for the increase in export objectives.

Producer Governance

The governance among producers within the two value chains is predominantly informal, with smallholder farmers making individual decisions regarding their production processes. Unlike more organized agricultural sectors, producers in these value chains lack formal cooperatives or associations that could provide collective bargaining power or shared resources. This individualistic

decision-making reduces their ability to leverage economies of scale, negotiate better prices for their products, or adopt innovations collectively. For many producers, decisions are driven by immediate needs and are influenced by limited market access and knowledge transfer.

External Influencing Actors and Local Policy

Several NGOs and extension services are working to support small producers within the value chain. Programs by organizations such as GIZ and FAO have introduced practices like integrated pest management (IPM), organic farming methods, and sustainable water use strategies. However, despite these efforts, the scale and impact of such interventions are still constrained by the lack of systemic policy support and the informal nature of producer governance (GIZ, 2022). The local public policy environment in Egypt has not yet become a strong lever for promoting agroecological value chains. While Egypt's agricultural policies include sustainability goals, the concrete support mechanisms for agroecology are minimal. Current policy frameworks continue to favour conventional, input-intensive farming models, with subsidies and incentives more aligned with large-scale industrial agriculture than with the smallholder-based, knowledge-intensive practices required for agroecology. However, certain regional and international programs have helped introduce sustainable farming techniques, particularly in export-oriented sectors like tomatoes, where global demand for organic and fair-trade products is growing (GIZ, 2022).

6.4.3.9 Interactions with Other Value Chains

The tomato value chain in Luxor intersects with other agricultural value chains through shared resources, complementary processing, and integrated market access. One key point of intersection lies the added-value processing through sun-drying. Drying stations in Luxor that commonly dry tomatoes are also employed for drying other crops like peppers, dates, and more. This shared infrastructure reduces costs and boosts efficiency and operations year-long, but also creates competition for space and resources during peak production seasons. Tomatoes and other crops also depend on the same water and labour resources, with seasonal demands often overlapping. Crop rotation further links tomatoes to other value chains such as MAPs, onions, and cereals, as farmers alternate crops usually without any real consciousness regarding planned rotations to maintain soil fertility and managing pests but rather as a response to market needs. Shared market channels, like weekly markets and export logistics, integrate the tomato and MAPs value chain with other fresh produce. Policies promoting sustainability, such as integrated pest management and water-efficient irrigation, often target tomatoes alongside other crops, emphasizing their shared reliance on agroecological practices. The use of tomato by-products and residues in composting also intersects in the production of other crops.

For MAPs, given that the diversity of products is multiple and represent a variety of plants and herbs, then that automatically opens the floor for interaction between the separate productions within this group. Main areas of interaction also include land use, shared resources, by-product utilization and market linkages. For crop rotation, farmers often incorporate MAPs into their rotation schedules for multiple reasons which sometimes are not consciously chosen, but could include reasons for maintaining of soil fertility, manage pests, and optimize water usage. Additionally, farmers cultivating MAPs frequently rely on the same labor pool as other agricultural activities. Waste from MAPs production, such as stems and leaves, can be repurposed for animal feed or compost, whereas certain by-products from the extraction of essential oils can sometimes be used as fertilizers, or in other industries, linking the MAPs chain to broader value-added sectors even if this approach does not represent the larger norm. As regarding marketing linkages, farmers often share distribution channels for MAPs and other crops especially when dealing with the same traders, targeting local, national, and international markets. Luxor's tourism sector also provides a market for MAP-based products like herbal teas, oils, and crafts.

6.4.3.10 *Agroecological Diagnosis and Potential*

Luxor's climate is one of its important strengths as it is well-suited for the cultivation of both tomatoes and MAPs. This is because this area receives regular strong solar radiation. Its hot temperatures and dry desert climate provide an exceptional resource for sun-drying. Therefore, by integrating value-added processes like sun-drying tomatoes, farmers can create high-value products for export rather local markets since the product is not common in the cuisine. Luxor's intense solar radiation makes it an ideal location for this process, requiring minimal energy inputs compared to industrial drying methods. An important social element is held in the potential of participating women in the economic cycle and especially in harvesting and processing (sun-drying). Thus, such elements provide applicable practices in line with Egypt's development goals and policies especially in the environmental sustainability and social aspects when coupling women and youth engagement with the use of the available resources and water management. The tomato and MAPs value chains also hold an important market potential in their fresh form. Tomatoes are a staple in local and national cuisine and are not exported much. The demand for organic and sustainable produce, although not entirely clear, shows evidence of being in rising. The potential of such a value chain could therefore be thought in its empowering smallholder farmers by providing them with sustainable income opportunities when coupled with sun-drying stations. Organic and sustainable farming practices that fall under the principles of agroecology are driven, even is partly, by the demand of especially the export market. This fact stands true not only for Luxor but for the whole farming systems in Egypt.

Therefore, and even if the current context needs development to reach that goal, the encouraging of production shifts to more environmentally-friendly practices are normally to be encouraged by the same dynamic, driven by demand and passed through to the farmers through influencers such as processors and drying units. Collectives, such as producer unions, could also hold an important aspect of reducing production costs for similar producer groups and possibly aiding them in improving their negotiation powers to decrease the influence on middlemen when it comes to pricing decisions. Training programs could provide helpful ways in raising these aspects into applicable actions, along with the improvement of production practices for the preservation of traditional farming techniques and transformation into more agroecological practices.

However, multiple challenges in Luxor need to be considered. Water scarcity in Egypt poses a major challenge, particularly for tomatoes, which are water-intensive crops. The high costs of installing water-saving infrastructure remains non-accessible to all producers and especially those small-scale which represent a majority of the farming population. Another major problem remains in the dependence of producers on inputs provided to them by the traders and middlemen who ensure the end-market (mostly wholesale). These include not only seeds (which are mostly imported hybrids for tomatoes, and local for MAPs) but chemical inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides. Limited technical knowledge about sustainable and agroecological farming practices benefits, requirements and high investment costs further hinders adoption, as many farmers lack the training or resources to meet these standards effectively. Additionally, the fragmented nature of land ownership in the region restricts scalability and makes adopting any change less attractive due to weak risk mitigation measures available. This becomes especially important when producer revert to expanding cultivated areas in reclaimed desert land which require heavy application of chemical inputs improving soil fertility and reliance on heavy irrigation practices. In fact, land reclamation projects in Luxor support Egypt's policy goals of increasing agricultural productivity through modern irrigation and water management to address resource scarcity and food security objectives while promoting crop cultivation and export-oriented agriculture. These circumstances therefore exacerbate the dependence of producers on middlemen to ensure their access to the needed inputs the marketability of their produce. This dynamic is mainly characterized by the fixing of prices prior to harvest and even prior to cultivation itself which many times limits the economic returns. It is important to recognize the position of middlemen given that producers themselves have low access to end-market points whether because of low resources for transportation, distance from the market, or insufficiency of accessible farmers' markets to Luxor to the production capacity. Moreover, differentiation is still weak in Luxor specifically and Egypt generally. This means that the end product itself, whether produced conventionally or under agroecological practices, has no clear methods for its visible valuation by the producers themselves, meaning labelling or certification. Certification is still quite inaccessible to small

producers and their adoption is low given the high costs and administrative complexity of traditional third-party certification systems, which often exceed their financial capacity. Therefore, without external support to producers and stakeholders alike, whether in the form of subsidies or capacity and awareness building and networking efforts in building sustainable market channels, the transition to agroecological value chains remains a challenging task for a context like that of Luxor.

6.4.3.11 *Main Recommendations for the Reinforcement of Agroecological Potential*

The tomato and MAPs value chain in Luxor presents an attractive opportunity to consider reinforcing agroecological transition, with its possible contribution to economic growth, environmental sustainability, and social equity. It is however important to acknowledge the challenges that exist in the context of that territory. These include especially at the level of primary production such as seeds or plantlets—largely imported for tomatoes—alongside land fragmentation and water scarcity sourced from the Nile. Fertilizers, labour, energy (primarily for irrigation pumping), and pesticides are also integral components of this value chain's primary production. In addition, other main challenges at the level of the value chain include issues of market access barriers with high dependence on middlemen (both for input access and pricing), financial constraints exacerbated by rising inflation and production costs, and infrastructural limitations that hinder full realization of agroecological potential.

Within such as context, the main recommendations that could be raised are:

Develop Value-Added Processing through sun-Drying, especially in the case of tomatoes coupled with essential oil extraction for MAPs. Given Luxor's climatic conditions—high solar radiation and low humidity—make it ideal for natural drying processes that minimize environmental impact while lowering production costs. Sun-dried tomatoes have the possibility of capturing higher prices however being on international markets given the steady growth of global demand rather than the local and national markets where demand remains low. When compared to fresh produce that is mostly marketed locally and nationally depending on seasonal fluctuations, present an opportunity to improve farmers' incomes by tenfold per unit weight (fresh tomatoes sell for approximately USD 0.20 per kilogram in local markets while sun-dried tomatoes reach up to USD 4–6 per kilogram in international markets (FAO, 2019). It is recommended to link producers with strategically located drying units run by non-profits or supported through government investment. Such units can ensure compliance with international standards, acquire necessary certifications given their financial capability compared to producers, and stabilize primary production while encouraging potential participation of women. Additionally, the sun-drying process could possibly create job opportunities, particularly for women, fostering rural economic development as certain pilot initiatives have shown. By aligning producers,

processors, and government stakeholders, and with the support of development associations, the sun-drying initiative could be considered as an interesting route for the region's tomato sector.

Policy considerations at local scale by adapting national strategies to meet local needs and in supporting capacity building of local producers on best practices in sun-drying, quality control, and hygiene to ensure consistent product quality. Initiatives in facilitating access to agroecologically-suitable inputs and resources (including but not limited to seeds, organic fertilizers and pesticides, suitable irrigation techniques, etc.) should also be considered. Investment in processing facilities by developing modern processing units equipped with quality assurance laboratories could help in meeting export standards and in considering the support for local producers and not only prioritizing the attraction of investors. This could be further encouraged by considering subsidies or low-interest loans for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) investing in such infrastructure. Collective models as cooperatives or 'Rabita' models should also be encouraged to pool resources, share knowledge, and enhance bargaining power with buyers.

NGO support for the promotion of agroecological practices and capacity building. To address challenges in primary production, NGOs and other development organizations are placed in a pivotal position to provide training programs on sustainable farming techniques and demonstrating the positive impact of transitioning of practices which could be unknown to the producer. Topics could focus on primary production techniques and inputs from seed acquisition, pest management, irrigation and water management, fertilization, composting and others which improve environmental sustainability and soil health. These practices, when backed by scientific research and demonstration projects, can provide farmers with the tools to improve productivity while fostering environmental resilience.

Enhancing market access, infrastructure and consumer awareness in support to the value chain downstream dynamics. Considerations could entail efforts of differentiation of agroecological products such as certification and labelling in order to boost competitiveness. These could be coupled with investments in transportation networks, storage facilities, and cold chain infrastructure which reduce post-harvest losses and ensuring accessibility to markets especially when collective transport is encouraged. This could be envisioned through private-public collaboration and direct linkages to reduce producer dependency on middlemen. This could in turn open the route for stimulating changes in agricultural practices applied based on the norms provided for the market, which could be communicated directly through such collaborations. On another hand, it is useful to prioritize the awareness building of end consumers on products that are not commonly consumed, such as the case with sundried tomatoes, in efforts to help their integration and consumption. Such efforts could

encourage local and national consumption while alleviating pressures on export-only objectives for producers.

6.5 Conclusion

The tomato and medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) value chains in Luxor are vital components of Egypt's agricultural sector, holding significant potential for sustainable growth and economic development. However, these value chains face several challenges related to the overall agricultural sector and which impede their full potential, especially among smallholder farmers. Key issues can be summarized as: i) production constraints related to limited access to agricultural inputs, escalating costs and heavy use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides with weak access to agroecological inputs, fragmented land holdings, and imported seeds mainly for tomatoes; ii) limited market access linked to the dependence of producers on middlemen to access markets, weak adoption and awareness around certifications, and infrastructural challenges in transportation and storage impeding producers' capacities to access markets and possibly contributing to post-harvest losses; iii) socioeconomic constraints and institutional barriers that affect women's participation. These include issues such as traditional land inheritance, limited access to credit and financial resources given the individuality of operations with cooperatives remaining relatively inefficient collective structures that require support in their service provision, management, and operations. In addition, weak access to capacity building and training remains a challenge except when producers are exposed to development agencies and civil society interventions.

The main results of this study have showed that primary producers are linked vertically with actors of the value chain rather than horizontally. This is evident through their clear reliance and dependency on middlemen such as local traders rather than consolidating efforts together in the form of collective groups as cooperatives. The normative approach followed by most farmers consist of having middlemen purchase the entirety or majority of harvests at fixed prices, which are most of the times much less than market prices. In return, these middlemen and traders would guarantee market access for the producers to either local, national or import markets through their connections. In addition, some middlemen provide the necessary capital and inputs needed by the farmers to initiate their production cycle annually, thus deepening the cycle of dependence. In fact, the export market seems to be the main objective for producers and traders alike. The reason behind that is to reach international markets that are capable of attaining higher profits compared to local or national markets and issues related economic uncertainties. Examples of those would be mainly due to the volatility of the local currency's value and price volatility in peak versus low seasons. Yet, through the connections to export markets, strategic players such as processing units and specifically drying stations in Luxor

have been able to successfully adapt the agricultural practices applied by local producers and mainly in the tomato value chain through direct contract farming. These experiences show that by the need to abide to standardized requirements of the export market, such drying stations have been successful in standardizing farming practices and in turn the use of chemical inputs, thus better aligning with agroecological practices. In that way, they were able to be placed in a position between the primary producers and the end market, and therefore in some cases, directly provisioning the needed inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and others, while implementing a specific set of practices. In addition to stimulating a shift into more environmentally friendly practices, drying stations are able to provide a space for the employment of women and their participation in the production/processing cycle mainly as employed workforce. In certain cases, certified drying stations managed by associations with local development objectives, were able to provide higher salaries and profits back to the women employees and contracted farmers.

Given these observations, the main recommendations provided revolve around i) providing support in capacity/awareness building and extension directly to producers in order to show, preferably through demonstrations, the benefits of adopting agroecological practices that are suitable to the conditions found locally especially given the small plots found. This would help in overcoming misconceptions related to thinking that conventional practices are the more productive and thus more profitable methods. For that, civil society and research linkages with the support of local authorities are important, but also considering other strategic players such as the drying stations run by associations. Such players could play a key role in encouraging the transition in practices and adding value added processing, with some success stories already existing, and in providing a space for the participation of women at processing/drying operations. Yet, their main market remains export with international markets remaining a main target to most producers for its higher economic returns. Adaptations could also be incorporated in initiatives, such as drying stations, implemented by government affiliations (as the local development office of the Upper Egypt Department in the Southern Upper Egypt). With the support of such offices, ii) collective action could be encouraged through reform of the cooperative sector at a long-term, but with stimulating the 'Rabita' approach which already exists in certain cases. Such formations could alleviate pressures related to accessing markets, and therefore facilitating them while decreasing dependence on third parties and middlemen. Such efforts should normally be coupled with support in infrastructure related to transportation and storage and optimally with development of certification facilitations (at the producer side) and encouragement of local consumption (at the consumer side including local tourism). Finally, iii) recommendations entail financial and policy support to agroecological inputs and credit/financing adapted to small producers whether at the individual or collective scales. For now, many producers still operate individually and their access to finance is still low due to complexities and fear in

approaching banking systems for example. On another hand, producers are sometimes enticed to cultivate in reclaimed desert land, a trajectory which is does not fit with agroecological and sustainability objectives. But programs with the help of civil society and local authorities could take proper considerations and actions in facilitating or advocating access to land, funds and resources.

By addressing the identified challenges through strategic interventions and collaborative efforts with the help of multiple actors (public, private, civil society), the tomato and MAPs value chains in Luxor can achieve greater resilience and inclusiveness, and align better with agroecological principles. Empowering smallholder farmers, promoting agroecological practices, and enhancing women's involvement will not only strengthen these value chains but also contribute to the socio-economic development of the region. With focused attention on improving access to suitable inputs, adopting sustainable practices, facilitating market access, and leveraging new legal frameworks, Luxor's agricultural sectors are well-positioned to meet the growing demands of both domestic and international markets. This holistic approach ensures long-term sustainability for the local communities involved, aligning with national development and sustainability goals

Chapter 7

Value chain analysis report for the PK-17

Living Lab (Mauritania)

Onion Bulbs and Turnips

Cheikh Sidya Fall (GRDR)

Chapter 7. Value chain analysis report for the PK-17 Living Lab (Mauritania) – Onion Bulbs and Turnips

Summary

The PK17 LL is located in the Commune of Riyadh south of Nouakchott and 17 km from the centre of Nouakchott, the capital of Mauritania. Peri-urban agriculture is possible thanks to the pond created following the accumulation of water preventing water discharges due to the cleaning of the filters of the water treatment plant from the Senegal River and which is used for drinking for the Nouakchoitt population. Water for irrigation can also come from the water table, which is between 3 and 7 m deep. Water is the main problem facing producers. The pond is not sustainable and an overexploitation of the water table increases the risk of salinization. Despite this challenge, more and more producers are coming to settle in the area to exploit the land either by making land available by the State or the Region or by an illegal occupation but which remains authorized only for agricultural activities. 90% of the plots are occupied by market gardening, including onion and turnip crops, which represent a large part of the farmed area. The way these value chains are organized does not allow the vast majority of PK17 producers to earn income that is fair to the value of their efforts. Only women farmers with access to the Zein'Art Market and producer-traders sell directly to consumers, which successively give them the highest profit margins. Interactions between onion and turnip value chains with other value chains (intercropping, livestock products) optimize the use of agricultural resources, diversify farmers' incomes, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. These synergies can have positive effects on the profitability and resilience of agricultural systems.

Strengthening the agroecological potential of the onion and turnip value chains in Mauritania requires an integrated and multi-sectoral approach that includes the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices, better management of natural resources, training of producers, installation of agroecological input supply companies, and support for public policies and strategic partnerships for access to marketing channels that allow for sustainable agricultural production. Fair remuneration of local producers.

7.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

Despite the obstacles of the arid Sahel-Saharan desert climate, characterized by galloping desertification, punctuated by repeated droughts and exacerbated by the country's vulnerability to climate change, Mauritania has natural assets that encourage public and private investment in the

agricultural sector. This is an agricultural potential of more than 513,000 hectares (SDSR, 2013) (MDR 2012, SDSR) which offers significant opportunities for intensification, diversification and improvement of competitiveness and challenges the various actors as to their ability to design and establish sustainable management systems for the consolidation of the gains made in this context.

The agricultural sector employs a large number of inhabitants and its contribution to GDP is estimated at 4% in 2020 and provides income to nearly 54.98% of the population (PA2 SCAPP) (MAEPSP 2021, PA2 SCAPP). It is managed on the basis of the National Agricultural Development Plan (PNDA 2016 – 2025). Agricultural production is not able to adequately cover the food needs of the population. Low yields of major crops, including cereals, as well as inefficient food storage, processing, and distribution systems limit the availability of agricultural products and the regularity of supplies. Producers, especially women and youth, as well as other actors involved in the production, processing and marketing process, face challenges along the value chain of key agricultural value chains. This situation justifies the adoption of a value chain approach in the implementation of new interventions in the agricultural sector, not only to increase production and enhance the potential of the various production systems, but also to improve the conservation, processing and sale of agricultural products.

The main challenge for agriculture is therefore to take advantage of the great potential of agricultural land and water potential for crop diversification and intensification through public and private investment.

Nouakchott enjoys a Sahelian climate, with a short and irregular rainy season. Rainfall occurs only from July to February, however it is heaviest during the months of August to September. Moreover, the average annual temperature is 25.6°C and the average annual rainfall is 47 mm (<https://fr.climate-data.org/afrique/mauritanie/nouakchott-222/>).

The PK17 WLL is located in the south of the Wilaya (region) of Nouakchott, in the commune of Riyadh and more precisely in the peri-urban area of PK-17, a road linking the two regions of Nouakchott and Trarza. It is one of the most vulnerable areas of Nouakchott and the second most populous municipality in Mauritania with an estimated population of 228,856 inhabitants (RGPH2023) (ANSADE 2023, RGPH). Its inhabitants, especially young people who work in the tertiary professions, generally leave in the morning to work in the other communes of Nouakchott and return in the evening because there are no work opportunities in Riyadh. Since 2016, we have seen that the State, the Nouakchott Region and development partners have been supporting the development of arable land to allow farmers to develop market gardening activities in the area where a large part of the agricultural plots are irrigated from water from the cleaning of the filters of the water filtration plant that pump water from the Senegal River to supply the Nouakchott population with drinking water.

The PK17 LL has an area of 350 ha but only 40 ha are currently farmed by three types of farmers: the cooperative of military pensioners recon who have 78 members each occupying a 600 m² plot of land developed by the State; the beneficiaries of the plots developed by the Nouakchott Region who are 130 in number each occupying a 700 m² plot; and finally the independent farmers whose number varies from 200 to 250 and who occupy the land illegally with plots varying from 425 m² to 1ha.

90% of the plots of land in the PK17 LL are dedicated to market gardening and 80% of market gardeners have integrated arboriculture. The main challenges are access to water and land; the attack of diseases and crop pests, exposure to prevailing winds and the difficulty of marketing products, especially those from agroecology. Despite these challenges, PK17 WLL is a recent production area that started operations in 2016. This peri-urban agriculture has not only created employment opportunities in the agricultural sector but has also helped to supply Nouakchott's peri-urban markets with fresh vegetables while contributing to the city's food security.

Figure 54: Map of LL-PK17, Riyadh, Mauritania

7.2 Methodology

Exchanges on Task 3.2. were initiated in July 2023 with the sending of a questionnaire for the pre-selection of two value chains by the CIHEAM-IAM team to the Coordinator of the Living Lab. of PK-17. Following meetings, the pre-selected Onion and Tomato value chains were discussed with farmers and the LL-PK17 Steering Committee. According to their importance in the production of

PK17 and unanimously approved by the steering committee to be studied are the bulbous onion and the turnip, the two crops whose value chains were finally validated.

To understand value chains, questionnaires were developed and administered to the various actors in the value chains, ranging from production to marketing.

The selected producers have all been in agricultural activity for a few years and belong to one of the three types of farmers in the LL area of PK17. A total of 30 farmers were approached during the interviews carried out and are divided into 17 independent market gardeners, 8 retired military men converted into market gardeners and 5 beneficiaries of the market gardening project in the Nouakchott Region. This selection of producers was made on the basis of the land use by the 3 types of farmers in the LL area and the production of onions and turnips, but also on criteria such as the source of water, the irrigation system, the inputs used, the agricultural techniques used, etc.

The other stakeholders involved in the onion value chain are also important for a better organization of the chain. During the surveys, 8 retailers, 4 intermediaries and 4 wholesalers were interviewed. To this end, it was first necessary to identify the markets where the vegetables from the production of LL-PK17 are sold.

The following table shows the distribution of the questionnaires administered to the actors in the chain:

Table 19: Number of questionnaires carried out by actors in PK-17, Mauritania

Actor	Number of questionnaires
Producers	30
Retailers	8
Intermediate	4
Wholesalers	4
Total	46

7.3 Value Stream Selection

In the questionnaire developed for the pre-selection of the two value chains, guiding questions were asked to rank them in order of agroecological importance. The results of the questionnaire were then discussed in bilateral meetings held in August and September 2023. These exchanges made it possible to analyse, identify and decide which value chains can be targeted for study (mapping, characterisation, diagnosis and agro-ecological assessment). The result was the pre-selection of two value chains for the peri-urban agri-food system of PK-17, namely leaf onions and tomatoes. During the workshop to launch the NATAE project in September 2023 at the Riyadh City Hall in Nouakchott,

these two value chains were presented to the actors to start discussions. They have opted for bulb onions, potatoes and turnips.

- Potato: Average Consumption; Problems of access to imported seeds; High and high water production cost; Significant imports; Not widely grown in PK17;
- Bulb onion: Very high consumption at the local level; Adapted to the type of soil; Organization of the chain; Support for advocacy involving a review of imports;
- Turnip: high production at PK17; Considerable consumption; On-site seed production; Fresh vegetables therefore less competition with imported products; Year-round production; More or less structured value chain.

A meeting of the steering committee was held in early November 2023 to study, decide and validate the value chain proposals. The coordinator of the PK-17 OSS, accompanied by some members of the steering committee, was able to meet with the representatives of farmers in the PK-17 area to argue and choose the two final value chains, which are the bulbous onion and the turnip. These choices were unanimously validated by the steering committee and the farmers.

7.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterization

7.4.1 Value Chain 1: Bulb Onion

7.4.1.1 Value Chain Overview

The onion value chain in Nouakchott, the capital of Mauritania, plays a critical role in urban and peri-urban agriculture, as well as in food security and local economic dynamics. Onions are a strategic crop in Mauritanian agriculture, both in terms of production and trade. Nouakchott, due to its geographical position and growing demand for food products, is a central market for onions in Mauritania, but also a commercial hub for distribution throughout the country and to international markets.

Onions are a crop introduced to Mauritania several decades ago. Its production in Nouakchott increased sharply with the improvement of irrigation techniques in the 1990s, which made it possible to expand the cultivated areas and ensure more stable production. Since then, onions have become a strategic product for the country's food security.

Onions are a crop that relies heavily on irrigation to ensure regular production in the peri-urban areas around Nouakchott (PK17, Toujounine and Dar Naim), thousands of small-scale producers grow

onions on small irrigated areas (from 40 to 625 m²), often using traditional and manual methods. Some small-scale producers have introduced the drip irrigation system

Onions are one of Mauritania's main vegetable crops and are an important source of income for many farmers. Onion production in Nouakchott is not only crucial for the capital's food supply, but it also plays a key role in the rural economy, especially for farming families and marketing actors.

Onions are also a cash crop for producers, as they have good profitability potential, especially when irrigation management is well controlled and yields are optimized.

The onion value chain is marked by the presence of wholesale and retail traders who are responsible for distribution in local and national markets.

The main onion markets are those of the 9 communes of Nouakchott including the central market of Socim where the largest wholesalers are found and where the vast majority of local production and all vegetable imports also arrive (Morocco, Senegal, Holland etc...). It is also the starting point for vegetables to national markets, the main ones of which include cities such as Atar, Zouerate, Rosso, and Kaédi. In the River Valley, some producers in the south of the country, due to the drop in prices on local markets, prefer to cross the river to sell their onions in neighbouring Senegal.

On economic challenges, many smallholder onion farmers have limited access to finance and credit, which hinders their ability to invest in better irrigation infrastructure, quality seeds, and modern agricultural equipment.

Price inflation is uncontrollable, which means that onion prices are very sensitive to changes in supply and demand. During the period of a heavy harvest, prices fall, reducing producers' profit margins. Conversely, in times of shortage, prices rise, making onions unaffordable for certain categories of the population.

In terms of social challenges, onion farmers, especially seasonal agricultural workers, face difficult working conditions, often without social protection or security. Manual tasks, such as cleaning and harvesting onions, are arduous and low-paid. Also, smallholder farmers are particularly vulnerable to economic and climate shocks, and many producers live in poverty or are highly dependent on agricultural yields for their livelihoods.

Land degradation and water depletion are environmental challenges to be taken into account: Intensive irrigation, especially in peri-urban production areas, puts pressure on groundwater resources, a growing problem in the Sahel region. In addition, excessive use of chemical inputs can lead to long-term soil degradation.

Finally, the Mauritanian government is implementing agricultural policies aimed at improving the productivity and competitiveness of agriculture. Agricultural policies and support programs for smallholder producers are essential for the development of the onion value chain. Projects supported by NGOs and international funding agencies also support the onion value chain through training, subsidies (for the acquisition of agroecological materials, equipment and inputs, working capital, etc.) and support for a sustainable agroecological transition.

7.4.1.2 Value Stream Mapping

Figure 55: Mapping of the CV of the bulbous onion displaying the stages, the VC actors, the external influencing actors

7.4.1.3 *Characterization and Diagnosis*

7.4.1.3.1 *General overview of the characteristics of the producer*

The area of LL-PK17 is occupied by 15% of retired soldiers, 25% by beneficiaries of the project from the Nouakchott Region and 60% by independent market gardeners.

Data collection was carried out from thirty (30) producers divided according to the three types present in the PK17 LL area, namely:

- **08 farmers retired military were beneficiaries of plots developed and made available by the State**

They have benefited from plots of 600 m², wells equipped with solar energy and a water storage basin. They irrigate their plot manually using watering cans. They use organic manure to amend their soil but still use chemicals to control diseases and pests. They are organized as an agricultural cooperative. Agricultural practices differ from one farmer to another. They pool their efforts in the fields, receive support from the state, make group purchases of inputs, and some market their vegetables together according to the quantities harvested from retailers and wholesalers in the major markets of Nouakchott or even in the field.

- **05 market gardeners benefiting from plots developed and made available by the Nouakchott Region**

They have benefited from 700m² plots and equipped with a drip irrigation system whose water source is the pond created by the PK17 water filtration plant. Like the retired soldiers, they modify their soil with organic manure and also use chemical pesticides. The transport of the harvested production to the city is facilitated by the Region, but each beneficiary is responsible for the sale of his or her individual or grouped production according to affinities. The harvested products are sold in the field, at the market (retailers, wholesalers), in the neighbourhoods (retailers, grocers, shopkeepers, restaurants, etc.).

- **17 "illegal" independent farmers**

They occupy the land in an illegal manner commonly known as "Gazra" in Mauritania. Even if the State has not made the land available to them, they are authorized to exploit the land only for agricultural activities. Each producer finances the development of his plot himself according to his means and knowledge. Some producers have been or are still beneficiaries of support from agricultural projects implemented by NGOs that promote agroecology and therefore these producers have received training and support towards an agroecological transition. Conventional producers who use chemical inputs are also being found. Exchanges on good practices between producers make it

possible to promote sustainable practices to face the challenges encountered. All plots have water storage basins in their plot which are fed by pumps equipped with solar panels installed either in the wells or at the level of the pond of the filtration station. The mode of commercialization differs according to the choice, ambitions and relationships of the producer.

As far as the age of producers is concerned, an analysis of the following graph shows that 70% of farmers are between 27 and 57 years old and 30% are over 57 years old. The youngest of the farmers surveyed is 27 years old, while the oldest is 82 years old. Generally speaking, the farmers working the plots in the PK17 LL zone are ageing, but there has recently been a move by young people and women.

Figure 56: Age of the producers surveyed in PK-17, Mauritania

Analysis of the graph on the gender distribution shows that women farmers take over less than 25% of the farmers on the plots. This can be explained by the vision that women have of agricultural jobs and the arduousness of working the land, but also by access to the production area because they have to walk 2 km every day to reach the plots. It should also be noted that almost all the farmers are present in their plots only during the mornings to ensure irrigation and some maintenance work. 30% of farmers, including some elderly farmers and women, use agricultural ouvrier paid monthly to ensure the monitoring, maintenance and guarding of the plots. Only 20% of the farmers surveyed live in the LL area.

Figure 57: Gender distribution of surveyed producers in PK17, Mauritania

We also note that nearly half, or 43%, of the farmers surveyed have not received any formal education, compared to 37% who have attended elementary school and 20% who have reached secondary school. The agricultural experience of these producers ranges from 3 to 25 years.

Figure 58: Surveyed producers' level of education in PK-17, Mauritania (in French)

As far as the workforce is concerned, among the retired military there are producers, some of whom are helped by one or more members of their family, full-time or seasonal employees. All this workforce contributes to the realization of activities such as soil preparation, sowing/transplanting, crop maintenance, irrigation, harvesting and marketing. On the other hand, among the beneficiaries of the

Region's project, the workforce is limited to the beneficiary/farmer and sometimes a member of his or her family.

7.4.1.3.2 Overview of the production value chain

In the PK17 zone, the bulb onion is generally transplanted into the field after a 45-day stay in the nursery. The bulb onion cycle varies from 3 to 4 months depending on the variety. The most commonly used onion varieties are Galmi Violet and Texas Grano Classic in addition to the local variety called White Onion. Planting periods are generally at the beginning of October for a harvest at the end of January or in the off-season at the beginning of February for a harvest at the end of May. Among the farmers surveyed, the bulbous onion occupies between 15 and 30% of the cultivated areas. This is explained by its importance in meal menus in Mauritania. Onions are consumed daily by Mauritanian households. 21% of the plots benefit from support in the form of subsidies and technical advice from the Regional Delegation of Agriculture and 7% of the plots benefit from the support and assistance of national and international NGOs. As far as inputs are concerned, 93% of inputs (seeds, fertilizers, pesticides) are purchased by farmers in specialized stores located in the capital's two markets, the Socim market and the chicken market (source: Nouakchott Region 2024).

As for agroecological products (seeds, biofertilizers, manure, compost, biopesticides) they are either provided by NGOs that promote agroecology or paid directly by farmers. The inputs used for agroecological production differ according to the types of producers. Some independent market gardeners have been trained as part of projects or programmes implemented by national and international NGOs and are therefore more oriented towards agroecology. As a result, they use inputs such as: farmers' seeds, goat or poultry manure or compost, some prepare solutions themselves to fight diseases and pests and others buy biopesticides or biofertilizers from suppliers such as Banlieues du monde which has put on the market products such as Super GRO as foliar fertilizers and Super 10 which is a biopesticide allowing a preventive control of diseases and pests. These products are highly valued by farmers who use them because they believe that their use improves their yield. Compost is prepared on-site to amend soils and manure, bagged and dipped into water storage ponds, purchased from suppliers and used to improve soil fertility and crop growth. Each farmer is responsible for the sale of these products (via intermediaries or by direct sales: in the fields, markets, shops). To combat the winds, independent farmers introduce fruit trees and hedgerows such as Maralfalfa as windbreaks. Some farmers sell the harvested fruit while others prefer to keep it for self-consumption. Maralfalfa is also used as a fodder plant.

For retired soldiers, there is a use of goat manure and the significant introduction of fruit trees in their market gardening plot. The use of chemical pesticides is common in more than 75% of this type of

grower. Seeds and other inputs are paid for in groups because these farmers are grouped together in a cooperative of retired soldiers which allows them to sell their products in groups.

The beneficiaries of the plots developed by the Nouakchott Region, like retired soldiers, use goat manure but still use chemical pesticides. It is noted that this category of farmers uses maralfalfa, introduced into the LL by independent farmers, to fight against the winds. All inputs (seeds, fertilizers, manure, pesticides) are provided by the Nouakchott Region, which also facilitates the transport of their market gardeners to the sale of the vegetables produced.

Surveys of the 30 producers revealed that 10 to 15% of the onions harvested are intended for self-consumption and donations.

7.4.1.3.3 Characteristics of the Producer Market and Market Strategies

Surveys of producers and other stakeholders (intermediaries, wholesalers, retailers) have made it possible to diagnose and analyse the producers' market.

All wholesalers are men with private structures ranging in age from 41 to 54 years old with an experience of 8 to 12 years. All the intermediaries are men with private structures, their age varies from 29 to 44 years old with different experiences from 2 to 15 years old. 25% of retailers are women, the age of retailers varies from 35 to 40 years old.

Onions are sold fresh by producers: 36% of the products are sold on site, 41% are sold directly to retailers or shopkeepers and 23% are brought to markets and sold to wholesalers (cases of overproduction to avoid the risk of production rot) and retailers. The products sold on site are bought by producers-traders and intermediaries. Direct sales to the field are the least economically beneficial method because the products are sold at low prices to intermediaries and producer-traders to avoid losses and reduce the producer's profit margin.

Agroecological onions are sold at the same price as those from conventional agriculture despite their quality and longer shelf life. The price of a kg of onion varies from 15 to 40 MRU (0.36 to 0.96 €) depending on the period. When the product is at 40 MRU on the market, it means that the intermediary and the producer-trader have bought it for around 20 MRU, or (0.48 €) in the field. As a result, the intermediary can resell between 30 MRU (0.72 €) to wholesalers and 35 MRU (0.84 €) to retailers and the producer-trader sells directly on the market at 40 MRU (0.96 €). Some producers transport their onions to sell for between 30 and 35 MRU to shopkeepers, grocers and restaurateurs, which makes them an attractive profit margin. Of all the farmers in PK17's OSS, only two independent women farmers have access to a market called Zein'Art where agroecological products are sold. It is a weekly market that is exclusively frequented by expatriates, who are more aware than local consumers of healthy eating issues. The price of a kg of onion varies from 30 to 50 MRU (or from

0.72 to 1.20 €). The selling price of onions is considerably higher at the Zein'Art market level and could constitute a much more interesting added value than at the institutional markets, but the problem is that this market is not very large and its access to producers-traders is limited. The owner of the Zein'Art market withholds 10% of the merchants' income from each weekly sale.

Onions harvested at PK17 are packed in plastic bags or nets that cost 5 MRU or (0.12 €) unit and can be transported to the points of sale. The transport of onions sold in the field is taken care of by the buyer. The products brought to markets, shops and other products are provided by independent producers and retired soldiers via their personal cars or the rental of taxi-transporters, while the Nouakchott Region uses their bus to transport the harvests of the beneficiaries of its project. Shipping costs range from 10 to 20% of the sale price. Without these means of transport, 64% of the crops cannot be sold because access to the production area is difficult. The customer shops are all located in the municipality of Riyadh while the markets are scattered throughout the city of Nouakchott. The markets most frequented by producers for the sale of onions are: PK8 and PK10 Markets in Riyadh, Poles Market in Arafat, Socim Market in the center of the city and Bus Stop Market in El Mina.

The onion value chain mobilizes several actors, starting with input suppliers, then producers who are at the heart of the chain and who use agricultural workers to ensure continuous production. Under informal contracts, agricultural workers are paid either 150 MRU (3.6 €) per day or 3000 MRU (72 €) per month. This value chain is continued by farmer-traders, intermediaries, wholesalers and retailers and ends at consumers. Note the involvement of technical services in agriculture but also the support of national and international NGOs in the promotion of ecological agriculture for a better management of natural resources and in the consideration of healthy diets.

7.4.1.3.4 Certification

Agricultural products of a general marl and onion in particular are not subject to any formal certification in the LL area of PK17. Agroecology has not been taken into account in public policies. As a result, agroecological products are sold at the same price as those from conventional agriculture, but buyers (wholesalers, retailers, shopkeepers and intermediaries) continue to praise the quality of agroecological products and their shelf life.

On the other hand, at the level of the weekly Zein'Art market, an informal certification is in force because consumers often want to find out about the traceability of vegetables and therefore one or two visits to the fields are planned by the owner of the market. These field visits at least make it possible to verify that pesticides and chemical fertilizers are not used in the production of vegetables sold in his market. In the framework of the NATAE project, the integration of the participatory guarantee system (GSP) will be important for the labelling of agroecological products, which will allow

better visibility/communication of agroecological products and contribute to a better valorization of these peri-urban products in order to facilitate their sale.

7.4.1.3.5 Prioritise collective efforts, short circuit markets and direct contact with consumers

In the PK17 area, we noted the presence of the Military Treaty Cooperative. This cooperative allows them to buy inputs as a group, to help each other carry out agricultural activities, to be able to gather and sell their harvest together. This cooperative also allows them to seek funding and to have some support from the Ministry of Agriculture. For the beneficiaries of the project from the Region and independent producers, there is a lack of cooperatives, producers generally act individually. Good relations between producers can enable them to help each other in carrying out certain tasks, for example sowing, phytosanitary work, harvesting, etc.

As for short circuit markets for independent producers, the two farmers with access to the Zein'Art market can sell directly to consumers, generally foreigners, residing in Mauritania and who are aware of healthy eating. They make the highest profit margins since in this market agroecological products are valued at a higher price than conventional products. Some independent producers who are at the same time traders pay for the harvest from neighbouring producers. They have outlets in the various markets of Nouakchott, which allows them to reach local consumers directly. On the other hand, among producers in the Nouakchott region, retired soldiers and some independents, the marketing channels are longer and therefore affect their profit margins. They use wholesalers, intermediaries, retailers, shopkeepers, grocers, restaurateurs, etc. There are cases where the consumer is in direct contact with the producer. The order is placed by telephone (call or WhatsApp) and the producer delivers the product to the consumer without intermediation. But the quantities ordered are generally not very large.

7.4.1.3.6 Motivation and perception of quality/value of producers

Motivation of PK17 producers in Riyadh

The main motivation for onion growers in this area is economic potential. Onions are a profitable crop that provides a stable source of income, especially in a region where agricultural land is limited and employment opportunities in urban areas remain low. The continued demand for onions in Nouakchott, which is the main market, is prompting producers to take up this crop.

Onion is often considered a fast-growing product with relatively high yields. Growers are motivated by the possibility of a quick return on investment, which is crucial for many farmers, who often face immediate financial pressure.

PK17's location in Riyadh, close to Nouakchott, is another motivating factor. Producers can benefit from direct access to wholesale markets and local traders. This reduces transportation costs and improves profit margins by avoiding long-term middlemen, although selling prices can still fluctuate depending on supply and demand.

For many small producers, onion cultivation is part of the local agricultural traditions. Although production methods are slowly modernizing, onions remain an important crop in agricultural habits, which is a motivating factor in terms of family and cultural continuity.

Producers' perception of onion quality

Onion growers in the PK17 area are generally aware that onion quality has a direct impact on market demand and on the selling price. Therefore, some growers make great efforts to ensure optimal quality in terms of onion size, shape, and color. The quality of the seeds used is seen as a crucial element for the success of the crop. Some farmers choose higher-quality local farmers' seeds or varieties that are resistant to diseases and local climatic conditions.

Quality-conscious growers work on irrigation management and measured use of fertilizers and pesticides so as not to affect onion quality, while maximizing yield. Competition among onion producers in Nouakchott, especially during periods of high production, can affect the perception of quality. If a surplus of onions invades the market, even good quality products can be sold at low prices, which discourages some producers.

PK17 producers also face challenges in storage. The lack of adequate temperature-controlled storage infrastructure increases the risk of spoilage and reduces the shelf life of onions after harvest, which can affect the quality perceived by end consumers. As a result, products can be discounted at low prices to traders to avoid the risk of large losses.

If local production coincides with large onion imports, prices can fall, affecting profitability. Producers often express frustration with these fluctuations, which are beyond their control but which the state can regulate to better support local production.

Access to the local market or wider distribution networks is often limited by intermediation behaviours that reduce the value that PK17 producers perceive for their products. Field sales through wholesalers or producer-traders may mean that the producer does not receive a fair share of the final value of the product. Producers who sell to shopkeepers and grocers earn a higher margin than those who sell in the field. The producers who sell their onions in the Zein'Art market and the producer-traders who pay for the onion from other producers realize the greatest beneficiaries because they are in direct contact with consumers.

7.4.1.3.7 *Barriers and opportunities to production and market access*

Onion production in Nouakchott, Mauritania's capital, and market access present both obstacles and opportunities. These dynamics are influenced by several economic, environmental, and social factors that affect the onion value chain. The main obstacles and opportunities faced by onion producers and market players in Nouakchott:

Obstacles to onion production in Nouakchott

- **Harsh weather conditions**

Nouakchott and its surroundings often suffer from extreme climatic conditions, including prolonged drought and high temperatures. These conditions make irrigation essential, but can also limit onion production, which requires a relatively large amount of water. Climatic variations due to global changes, including erratic rainfall, make the management of onion harvests more uncertain. This poses a challenge for the stability of returns.

- **Lack of irrigation and storage infrastructure**

Irrigation is crucial for onion cultivation, but irrigation systems in Nouakchott are often insufficient and poorly maintained, limiting production efficiency. Most producers use manual irrigation, which results in voluminous water losses.

After harvesting, the storage of onions is a major problem. Without proper warehouses or storage facilities, much of the production can be lost due to rot or product degradation. This affects the availability of onions on the market and the income of producers.

- **High cost of agricultural inputs**

The costs of quality seeds, fertilizers and phytosanitary products are relatively high in Mauritania. This limits smallholder farmers' access to these inputs and reduces their ability to improve yields. Onion farmers in Nouakchott, especially smallholders, have limited access to the financing needed to invest in quality inputs, modern equipment, and storage infrastructure. The lack of agricultural credit and adequate financing mechanisms aggravates this situation.

- **Soil degradation and erosion**

Intensive cultivation without crop rotation can lead to soil degradation, which reduces fertility and affects onion yields in the long term. Soil erosion, especially in irrigated areas, is a recurring problem that limits the ability of growers to maintain productive soils for onion cultivation.

- **Market access issues**

Onion producers in Nouakchott often face price fluctuations in the markets, due to high competition, seasonal variations, and changes in demand. This makes profitability uncertain and decreases incentives to invest in production. Transporting onions to domestic markets can be problematic, due to poor road quality and lack of suitable transport solutions for perishable products.

Opportunities for onion production in Nouakchott

- Growing Demand for Local Onions

Onions are a staple in Mauritanian cuisine, and local demand remains stable. With the population growth and urbanization of Nouakchott, the demand for fresh, quality onions is set to increase. RGP2023 shows that the population of Nouakchott is estimated at 1,446,761 inhabitants, about a third of the Mauritanian population.

- Opportunities for improved farming techniques

The adoption of more efficient agricultural techniques, such as ecological agriculture, the use of improved seeds and localized irrigation, could improve yields and reduce dependence on extensive irrigation. By adopting agroecological practices, such as integrated soil management and crop rotation, producers can improve soil health, reduce input costs, and increase the sustainability of production.

- Improving access to finance

Access to finance remains a priority. Initiatives to improve access to credit for small-scale producers, through microcredit programmes or subsidies for the purchase of inputs, can help strengthen the capacity of producers to invest in their business. Collaboration between the public and private sectors to develop modern storage infrastructure and irrigation systems can create new opportunities for onion growers.

- Development of logistics infrastructure

The construction of cold storage warehouses and storage centres for onions, as well as the improvement of road and logistics infrastructure, could reduce post-harvest losses and facilitate access to local and regional markets.

- Institutional support and agricultural partnerships

The Mauritanian government could play a key role in putting in place policies and programs to support local onion production, reducing onion imports and taxes on agricultural inputs, and promoting food self-sufficiency initiatives.

Training initiatives to improve farmers' skills in onion cultivation techniques, farm management, and market access can enhance production efficiency and market competitiveness.

7.4.1.3.8 Value Chain Governance and Decision-Making Authority

The onion value chain in Mauritania, like other agricultural sectors, is governed by a complex set of actors with distinct roles. This governance can be divided into three main categories: institutional governance, producer governance, and external influencers.

- Institutional governance (official and regulatory bodies)

Institutional governance of the onion value chain in Mauritania is mainly ensured by public institutions and regulatory structures that set the rules of the game, coordinate agricultural policies, and facilitate access to markets. These institutions play a crucial role in regulating the sector, managing resources, and implementing public policies.

Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty: This is the central institution for the formulation of agricultural policies in Mauritania, including those related to the production and marketing of agricultural products such as onions. This ministry oversees food security, the management of water resources for agriculture, the regulation of agricultural inputs, and the creation of export opportunities.

Ministry of Trade: In charge of market regulation, this ministry supervises the import, export, and trade of agricultural products, including onions, by putting in place mechanisms to stabilize prices (regulate imports, support local production, set selling prices on the markets according to the periods) and guarantee good quality on local markets.

The Regional Delegations of Agriculture : Responsible for the management and promotion of agricultural development projects, it plays a role in supporting productivity, particularly in irrigation, seed improvement, and farmer training.

Customs authorities: These structures participate in the regulation of trade, in particular for onion imports from countries such as Senegal, Morocco and Holland, by ensuring compliance with trade standards and facilitating market access for local producers.

- Producer governance (associations, cooperatives and groups)

Producer governance is provided by grassroots organizations that bring together farmers, often in the form of cooperatives or producer groups. These actors have decision-making power in the management of their production, the negotiation of prices and the coordination of agricultural activities.

Agricultural cooperatives: These structures play a key role in the collection, storage, processing (if applicable) and sale of onions. They facilitate access to agricultural inputs, technical training, and collective financing for producers. Co-operatives can also help producers band together to negotiate better prices with buyers.

Onion growers' associations: These associations are often made up of small-scale onion producers who organize themselves to pool resources, defend their interests, and benefit from services such as farm management training, access to irrigation, and product promotion. They can also play an important role in raising awareness of better agricultural practices. These formal associations are not yet present in the PK17 OSS, but informally some producers are pooling their efforts to reduce costs.

Farmers' federations: Sometimes several cooperatives may organize themselves under a federation that represents their interests at a regional or national level. These structures often play a role in defending producers' rights with public authorities and private actors.

Producers: Some producers have benefited from the support of projects implemented by NGOs in training and support on agroecological practices and play a relay role in the dissemination of good agricultural practices in their environment.

- **External influencers (NGOs, civil society, development agencies, etc.)**

External actors play a role in support, raising awareness and financing in the onion value chain. Although they do not have direct decision-making power, they influence the practices of producers and institutions by providing expertise, financing and technical support.

NGOs and civil society organisations: These organisations, such as the Research and Implementation Group for Rural Development (GRDR), the Group for Research and Technological Exchange (GRET), the Mauritanian Association for Self-Development and the Mauritanian Association for Self-Development (AMAD), Ecole de développement (ECODEV) etc., often intervene in the field of raising awareness of sustainable agricultural practices, access to financing for small producers, and training farmers on sustainable techniques for production and management of natural resources.

International development agencies: Agencies such as the EU, USAID, the World Bank, or IFAD finance development projects to improve agricultural productivity, build resilience to climate change, and develop sustainable agricultural value chains. These agencies influence public policies and can support specific projects for the improvement of the onion sector.

Agroecology awareness-raising actors: More and more, local actors are participating in the promotion of agroecology in Mauritania, encouraging environmentally friendly cultivation practices,

reducing the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, and promoting sustainable cropping systems, especially for onions.

Private companies: Supply chain companies (input suppliers, traders) also have an impact on the value chain by influencing agricultural practices, selling prices and production conditions. Inputs are the most widespread on the markets but lately we have seen small companies, with the support of projects, set up for the supply of natural inputs (organic and foliar fertilizers, natural treatments against diseases and pests, compost etc...)

Interactions between these three categories of actors are essential to develop an efficient and sustainable onion value chain. Strengthening producers' capacities on sustainable practices, improving infrastructure, and promoting favourable agricultural policies are key levers for the success of this value chain.

7.4.1.3.9 Interactions with other value chains

In the southern regions of Mauritania and along the Senegal River, onions are often grown alongside crops such as rice, maize or millet. Agricultural practices are therefore interconnected, especially for irrigation techniques and soil management.

At the LL level of PK17, onions share growing spaces with other vegetables such as tomatoes, peppers, zucchini, etc. This allows for diversification of harvests and crop rotation strategies.

Organic waste from livestock production, including goat and poultry manure, is widely used in the PK17 area as fertilizer in onion cultivation, creating a link between the livestock and onion value chains. Manure is a key resource for improving soil fertility in onion fields and therefore improves quality and quantity of yields.

In addition, onions are an essential part of the diet of the Mauritanian population. The interdependence between food products from crops and livestock influences production practices but unfortunately not onion prices on the Nouakchott is market.

7.4.1.4 Key recommendations for strengthening agroecological potential in the value chain

Strengthening the agroecological potential in the onion value chain in Mauritania, which is one of the most important chains, is essential to ensure sustainable production, resilience to climate change, and improved yields while respecting the environment. Recommendations are made at all levels to integrate and strengthen agroecological potential in this value chain:

Promotion of sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural practices

- Promotion and adoption of sustainable agricultural techniques such as crop rotation, crop associations for example, alternating onion cultivation with legumes or crops that enrich the soil with nitrogen. Incorporate fruit trees/windbreaks and use cover crops (such as legumes or grasses) to prevent soil erosion and increase soil fertility by fixing atmospheric nitrogen;
- Encourage the use of compost, manure and other organic inputs to replace chemical fertilizers, which can deplete soils in the long term. This would help improve soil structure, water retention capacity, and enrich soil microbial biodiversity. It would also be interesting to promote compost production at the local level so that farmers can reduce their dependence on expensive inputs (chemical or organic fertilizers) and improve the sustainability of their agricultural practices.

Sustainable management of water and natural resources

- Promote the adoption of drip irrigation systems, which allow for more efficient water management by providing moisture directly to plant roots and reducing evaporative losses;
- Developing solar-powered irrigation systems, a sustainable option for drylands. These systems can be profitable in the long term and reduce dependence on fossil fuels;
- Setting up water management systems at the scale of peri-urban areas to ensure a better distribution and use of water resources (wells, ponds, etc.). This includes improving access to water for irrigation, and integrated water resources management.

Training and awareness-raising of producers on good agroecological practices

- Organize regular trainings for producers on agroecological practices, such as integrated soil management, the use of organic inputs, and the adoption of technologies adapted to sustainable agriculture. Trainings could also include practical demonstrations on pilot plots to encourage the adoption of new techniques;
- Raise awareness among producers of the risks related to climate change (droughts, floods, etc.) and teach them resilience techniques such as the use of drought-tolerant varieties and crop diversification;
- Encourage collaboration between producers and agricultural extension services so that knowledge on agroecological techniques can be easily transmitted and implemented in the field.

Agricultural cooperatives and producers' associations can play a key role in the dissemination of these practices, acting as relays for the training and adoption of good practices.

Strengthening policies and partnerships for agroecology

- Promote public policies that support agroecology and encourage sustainable agricultural practices through subsidies, green agricultural credits, and tax incentives for producers who adopt environmentally friendly practices;
- Integrate agroecological principles into national agricultural policies and food security strategies, aiming at the transition to more resilient and sustainable production systems.
- Collaborate with NGOs that promote agroecology to develop specific projects in the area of the onion value chain. These partnerships can provide financing, training, and tools adapted to producers;
- Encourage the implementation of climate finance and subsidy mechanisms for environmentally friendly agricultural projects, supported by development agencies such as the World Bank and the European Union.

Development of marketing channels and storage infrastructures

- Build environmentally friendly storage companies (such as silos made of local materials and naturally ventilated) to avoid post-harvest losses. It would also reduce reliance on chemical or energy-intensive storage solutions;
- Developing cold storage facilities that allow onions to be stored after harvest for longer periods of time, using energy-efficient technologies, would improve profitability and limit losses.
- Promote short distribution circuits, where producers sell their products directly to local consumers or to regional markets. The establishment of points of sale for agroecological products and school canteens can also constitute short circuits for the sale of onions.
- Develop commercial partnerships, in the medium term, to facilitate the export of onions to neighbouring markets, integrating agroecological practices and meeting international quality standards.

7.4.2 Value Stream 2: Turnip

7.4.2.1 Value Chain Overview

Turnip cultivation in Mauritania, although less widespread than other vegetables such as onions, plays a key role in agricultural diversification and food security, particularly around the capital, Nouakchott. PK17, located in the commune of Riyadh, is an important agricultural area for this production. This

overview covers aspects related to production, marketing, challenges and the enabling environment for the turnip value chain at the national and local levels, with a focus on PK17.

Turnips, being a seasonal crop, are mainly grown when water is available for irrigation: turnips are produced all year round at PK17 with the use of water from then or the pond of the water filtration plant. Cultivation is carried out on small areas but it is present in almost all the producers' plots.

Turnip production at PK17 is characterized by the use of relatively modern farming techniques, including the use of organic or chemical fertilizers and plant protection products to maximize yields. However, the majority of producers remain family farmers who cultivate limited areas, often with limited resources but increasingly aware of agroecology.

The turnip growing cycle is relatively short with varieties that last 1.5 months to 2 months, allowing growers to achieve several annual harvests.

Although turnips are not the dominant crop in Mauritania, they play an important role in local market gardening, particularly in peri-urban areas of Nouakchott such as PK17, Toujounine or Dar Naim. It is a significant source of income for local farmers and contributes to the diversification of agricultural production.

Turnips are mainly intended for local consumption, being an important component of Mauritanian cuisine, especially in traditional dishes such as soups and stews.

Due to the generally small size of local farms, total turnip production can reach several tonnes per year, with harvests spread over several cycles.

The markets of sale (Riyadh, Socim, Arafat, El Mina...) turnips are the same as those where onions are sold (Turnips usually go through wholesalers who redistribute them to local retailers and traders. Direct sales between producers and consumers are also common, as was the case with onions.

As with many vegetable crops, the price of turnips can fluctuate significantly depending on the season and the available supply. These fluctuations can affect profitability for producers. Competition for market access is only between local producers because imports are very limited.

Producers may face challenges in accessing more lucrative markets or in connecting with larger buyers.

Agriculture in Mauritania, including turnip cultivation, is strongly influenced by climatic conditions. Water scarcity and periods of drought can have a negative impact on production.

Irrigation, while essential, requires efficient water management, and overexploitation of water resources, especially in areas like PK17, can lead to sustainability issues.

The Mauritanian government supports the agricultural sector through various financing initiatives, subsidies for the purchase of agricultural inputs, and projects to improve irrigation systems. But this support has so far been insufficient to achieve the desired results.

7.4.2.2 Value Stream Mapping

In LL-PK17, the mapping of the actors in the turnip value chain is identical to that of onions. It is the same producers who produce turnips and onions.

Figure 59: Mapping of the actors in the turnip value chain in PK-17, Mauritania

7.4.2.3 *Characterization and Diagnosis*

7.4.2.3.1 *General overview of the characteristics of the producer*

Turnip producers are the same as onion producers in PK17 (refer to paragraph 4.1.3.1.) It is the same producers who produce vegetables on areas distributed according to their choice and the share of crops in their economy.

7.4.2.3.2 *Overview of the production value chain*

In the PK17 zone, turnips are sown directly without going through the nursery. Seeds are purchased from input suppliers. The turnip cycle varies from 1.5 to 2 months depending on the variety. The most widely used variety of turnip is the Chinese Appolo turnip, which is imported. Planting periods are generally at the beginning of October for a harvest at the end of January or in the off-season at the beginning of February for a harvest at the end of May. Among the farmers surveyed, turnips occupy between 20 and 40% of the cultivated areas. This is due to its short cycle, an important source of income, its appreciation in many Mauritanian dishes and especially the fact that turnips compete less with imports. We present the same analysis as for onions, only a few data, such as prices, have been adjusted.

7.4.2.3.3 *Characteristics of the Producer Market and Market Strategies*

As with onions, turnips are sold fresh by producers: 36% of the products are sold on site, 41% are sold directly to retailers, grocers, restaurateurs, shopkeepers and 23% are brought to markets and sold to wholesalers (cases of overproduction to avoid the risk of rotting their production) and retailers. The products sold on the spot are bought by producers-traders and intermediaries. Direct sales in the field are the least economically beneficial method. Even if it cancels out the costs of transporting products, it reduces the profit margin because the products are sold off at the lowest price and the producer does not really earn his credit. But sometimes this could be explained during periods of overproduction to avoid the risk of production loss.

Agroecological turnips are sold at the same price as those from conventional agriculture despite their quality and longer shelf life. The price of a kg of turnips on the market varies from 5 to 30 MRU or 0.12 to 0.72 € depending on the period. When the product is at 30 MRU on the market, it means that the intermediary and the producer-trader have bought it for around 15 MRU, or 0.36 € in the field. As a result, the intermediary can resell at 20 MRU or 0.48 € to wholesalers and at 25 MRU or 0.60 € to retailers and the producer-trader sells directly on the market at 30 MRU. Some producers transport their turnips to sell for between 20 and 25 MRU to shopkeepers, grocers and restaurateurs, which makes them a good profit margin. Of all the farmers in PK17's OSS, only two women farmers have access to a market called Zein'Art where agroecological products are sold. It is a weekly market that

is exclusively frequented by expatriates, who are more aware than local consumers of healthy eating issues. The price of a kg of turnips varies from 20 to 40 MRU, or from 0.48 to 0.96 €. The selling price of turnips is considerably higher at the Zein'Art market level and can constitute a much more interesting added value than at the institutional markets, but the problem that arises is that this market is not very large and its access to producers-traders is limited. The two farmers pay 10% of their weekly income to the owner of the Zein'Art market, which represents the rental costs of the place.

Turnips harvested at PK17 are packed in plastic bags or nets can be transported to the points of sale. The transport of turnips sold in the field is taken care of by the buyer. The products brought to markets, shops and other products are provided by independent producers and retired soldiers via their personal cars or the rental of taxi-transporters, while the Nouakchott Region uses their bus to transport the harvests of the beneficiaries of its project. Shipping costs range from 10 to 20% of the sale price. Without these means of transport, 64% of the crops cannot be sold because access to the production area is difficult. The customer shops are all located in the municipality of Riyadh while the markets are scattered throughout the city of Nouakchott. The markets most frequented by producers for the sale of turnips are: PK8 and PK10 Markets in Riyadh, Poles Market in Arafat, Socim Market in the center of the city and Bus Stop Market in El Mina.

The turnip value chain mobilizes several actors, starting with input suppliers, then producers who are at the heart of the chain and who use agricultural workers to ensure continuous production. This value chain is continued by farmer-traders, intermediaries, wholesalers and retailers and ends at consumers. Note the involvement of technical services in agriculture but also the support of national and international NGOs in the promotion of ecological agriculture for a better management of natural resources and in the consideration of healthy diets.

7.4.2.3.4 Certification

Certification of local turnips is non-existent in the country. The owner of the Zein'Art market just checks in the field to ensure that the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers is reduced or even non-existent.

7.4.2.3.5 Prioritise collective efforts, short circuit markets and direct contact with consumers

For turnips, it is the same mode of organization as for onions in the PK17 zone. Only one cooperative present is that of retired soldiers. This cooperative allows them to buy inputs as a group, to help each other carry out agricultural activities, to be able to gather and sell their harvest together. This cooperative also allows them to seek funding and to have some support from the Ministry of Agriculture. For the beneficiaries of the project from the Region and independent producers, there is a lack of cooperatives, the producers generally act individually. Good relations between producers

can allow them to help each other in carrying out certain tasks, for example sowing, phytosanitary control, harvesting, etc.

As for short circuit markets for independent producers, the two farmers with access to the Zein'Art market can sell directly to consumers, who are generally expatriates. They make the highest profit margins since in this market agroecological products are valued at a higher price than conventional products. Some independent producers who are at the same time traders pay for the harvest from neighbouring producers. They have outlets in the Socim or PK10 markets, which allows them to reach local consumers directly. Among producers in the Nouakchott region, retired soldiers and some independents, marketing channels are longer and therefore affect their profit margins. They use wholesalers, intermediaries, retailers, shopkeepers, grocers, restaurateurs, etc. There are cases where the consumer is in direct contact with the producer. He places his order by phone (call, WhatsApp) and the producer delivers the vegetables to him. But the quantities ordered are generally not very large.

7.4.2.3.6 Motivation and perception of quality/value of producers

The main motivation of turnip producers is the same as that of onions, since they are the same producers and the economic potential is paramount. Turnips are a profitable crop that is grown all year round and provides a stable source of income for producers. The continued demand for turnips in Nouakchott, which is the main market, is encouraging producers to start growing turnips.

PK17's location in Riyadh, close to Nouakchott, is another motivating factor. Producers can benefit from direct access to wholesale markets and local traders. This reduces transportation costs and production losses and improves profit margins by avoiding long-term middlemen, although selling prices can still fluctuate depending on supply and demand.

Turnip producers in the PK17 area are generally aware that turnip quality has a direct impact on market demand and on the selling price. The quality of the seeds used is seen as a crucial element for the success of the crop. Some growers choose higher quality seed or varieties that are resistant to diseases and local climatic conditions. However, farmers' seeds must be used and multiplied to ensure independence in seed purchases.

PK17 producers also face challenges in storage. The lack of adequate temperature-controlled storage infrastructure increases the risk of spoilage and reduces the shelf life of turnips after harvest, which can affect the quality perceived by end consumers. As a result, products can be discounted at low prices to traders to avoid the risk of large losses.

Access to the local market or wider distribution networks is often limited by intermediation behaviours that reduce the value that PK17 producers perceive for their products. Field sales through wholesalers

or producer-traders may mean that the producer does not receive a fair share of the final value of the product. Producers who sell to shopkeepers and grocers earn a higher margin than those who sell in the field. The producers who sell their turnips in the Zein'Art market and the producer-traders who pay for the turnips from other producers make the biggest beneficiaries because they are in direct contact with consumers.

7.4.2.3.7 Barriers and opportunities to production and market access

The obstacles and opportunities for turnips are the same as for onions and all market gardening crops. Obstacles include harsh climatic conditions, lack of irrigation and storage infrastructure, high cost of agricultural inputs, soil degradation and erosion. With regard to the opportunities for turnip production in Nouakchott, there is growing demand from the population, opportunities to improve agricultural techniques, improved access to finance, development of logistics infrastructure, institutional support and agricultural partnerships. Unlike onions, turnips are not imported and therefore there is no competition with imported products. Local production makes it possible to meet national needs and the surplus can be transported to neighbouring countries (Senegal, Mali).

7.4.2.3.8 Value Chain Governance and Decision-Making Authority

The governance of the turnip value chain is the same as that of onions and vegetable crops in general. It concerns three main categories: institutional governance, producer governance, and external influencers.

Institutional governance (official and regulatory bodies) which involves the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, the Ministry of Trade, the Regional Delegations of Agriculture. Public institutions have significant decision-making power, particularly with regard to the definition of agricultural policies, the allocation of agricultural subsidies and credits, and the regulation of the market. However, their ability to respond to the practical challenges of producers can sometimes be limited by budgetary constraints, coordination and policy implementation issues.

Producer governance (associations, cooperatives and groups) involves agricultural cooperatives, producers' associations, farmers' federations and producers. Cooperatives and producers' associations have significant decision-making power over the collective management of turnip production and marketing. They can influence prices, market access and the implementation of agricultural development projects. However, their power remains limited in negotiations with large institutional and private actors, unless they are well organized and have external support.

External influencers (NGOs, civil society, development agencies, etc.), on the other hand, involve NGOs and civil society organizations, international development agencies, agroecology awareness actors and private companies. External actors have influential power, particularly through project

funding, training, and the creation of strategic partnerships. However, their power remains indirect, as it is often subordinated to the will of local and national authorities. Their influence also depends on their ability to work in concert with other actors (producers and institutions).

The interactions between these three categories of actors are essential to develop an efficient and sustainable turnip value chain. Strengthening the capacities of producers on sustainable practices, improving infrastructure, and promoting favourable agricultural policies are key levers for the success of this turnip value chain.

7.4.2.3.9 Interactions with other value chains

For soil fertility improvement, intercropping legumes such as beans and peas, fix nitrogen in the soil, which can reduce the need for chemical fertilizers for turnips. Lettuce and radish are planted between the rows of turnips in the PK17 zone and can help reduce weeds or pests, which reduces the use of pesticides in turnip cultivation. Producers can sell both turnips and intercropping products, diversifying their sources of income. For fertilization, goat and poultry manure is used as organic fertilizer.

As for turnips, their tops can be used as a feed supplement for goats and cows, adding value to agricultural products. Turnip waste (e.g., defective or unharvested roots) can be composted and used as organic fertilizer for subsequent crops. This can reduce reliance on chemical fertilizers and improve the sustainability of turnip production.

7.4.2.4 Key recommendations for strengthening agroecological potential in the value chain

Strengthening the agroecological potential in the turnip value chain in Mauritania requires a holistic approach that combines sustainable agricultural practices, integrated management of natural resources, as well as technological innovations adapted to the local context. Following the example of the onion value chain, the main recommendations to strengthen the agroecological potential of turnips:

Promotion of sustainable agricultural practices

- Introduce regular rotation with complementary crops such as legumes (peas, beans) to improve soil fertility, reduce the risk of turnip-specific diseases, and avoid soil depletion.
- Developing intercropping systems to optimize space utilization, reduce weeds, and increase biodiversity, while improving profitability. Crops such as lettuce or legumes (which fix nitrogen) can be adapted.
- Encourage the use of composts and organic fertilizers (e.g., livestock manure) to improve soil structure, limit the use of chemical fertilizers, and promote soil regeneration.

Integrated Water Resources Management

- Adopt efficient irrigation techniques such as drip irrigation or sprinkler irrigation, which can better manage water resources in a country where water is scarce. This reduces water waste and increases crop productivity;
- Encourage the collection and storage of rainwater to irrigate turnip fields during a period of the year, using reservoirs, ponds or recovery systems.
- Integrated water resources management in the PK17 area needs to be developed to regulate the pumping of groundwater by producers to reduce the risks of salinization of the water table.

Enhancing biodiversity and soil health

- Encourage the use of cover crops to prevent soil erosion, improve soil structure and maintain biodiversity. These plants also help to fix nitrogen and provide organic matter;
- Encourage the integration of crops such as legumes or other plants that, after harvest, can be incorporated into the soil as green manures to enrich organic matter and improve fertility.

Pest and Disease Management

- Encourage the use of biopesticides to control diseases and pests;
- Promote the use of turnip varieties adapted to edaphoclimatic conditions and resistant to disease, which would reduce dependence on chemicals and allow for more sustainable disease management, which would have a positive effect on yield.

Raising awareness and training of farmers

- Provide continuous training to farmers on agroecological practices such as sustainable soil management, crop rotation, organic fertilization, and natural pest and disease control techniques;
- Raise awareness among turnip producers of the importance of integrated management of water resources, biodiversity and soils. Training on water management techniques and reducing water waste can be useful, given Mauritania's arid conditions.

Enhancing access to technology and innovation

- Introduce Mauritania-friendly agricultural technologies, such as drought-tolerant seeds and modern cultivation tools (e.g., mechanical seeders and low-energy irrigation systems);
- Develop and disseminate climate-based agricultural information tools to help farmers plan turnip cultivation based on weather forecasts, including drought or floods.

Strengthening sustainable marketing channels

- Establish infrastructure for the storage, packaging and marketing of turnips to reduce post-harvest losses and competition between local producers in cases of overproduction;

- Also encourage the export of turnips by adapting production to the requirements of neighbouring foreign markets;
- Encourage the formation of agricultural associations, federations and cooperatives to strengthen the bargaining power of turnip farmers, facilitate access to inputs and promote sustainable agricultural practices at the community level;
- Facilitate the establishment of short turnip marketing circuits allowing the improvement of the incomes of local and national producers;
- Establish central outlets for agroecological products and links between producers and school canteens in Riyadh to promote local production and consumption.

Government Policies and Support

- Encourage the implementation of incentive policies, such as subsidies for the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (e.g., composting, drip irrigation, biopesticides, etc.), as well as accessible credit programs for small producers;
- Strengthen partnerships between farmers, local authorities, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and research institutions to promote a coordinated approach to agroecology and ensure the sustainability of initiatives related to promising value chains.

7.5 Conclusion and Summary Main Results

The PK17 area south of Nouakchott, which is the capital of the Islamic Republic of Mauritania (RIM), is a recent occupation zone and a new production hub in Nouakchott to support the city's food security. Support from the State and development partners remains insufficient for the increase in agricultural areas because less than 15% of these are exploited. 90% of producers grow vegetables, including turnips and onions, which can occupy up to 40% of farmers' plots in the PK17 area (Source: Nouakchott Region).

The onion and turnip value chains in Nouakchott are an essential component of Mauritanian agriculture and food. With economic, social and environmental challenges, its strengthening requires better management of resources, improvement of agricultural productivity and support for public policies. The sector has significant growth potential, particularly with the adoption of agroecological practices and the improvement of irrigation and storage infrastructure.

Although onion and turnip production in Mauritania faces significant obstacles, such as climate challenges, limited access to finance, and infrastructure issues, it also offers many opportunities. Improved infrastructure, adoption of modern and sustainable agricultural practices, institutional support, as well as access to the production area and new markets, can help strengthen the onion

and turnip value chain and support producers in their efforts to meet the growing demand in Mauritania and the sub-region in line with international standards.

Interactions between onion and turnip value chains with other value chains (intercropping, livestock products) optimize the use of agricultural resources, diversify farmers' incomes, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. These synergies can have positive effects on the profitability and resilience of agricultural systems.

To strengthen the agroecological potential of the onion and turnip value chains in Mauritania requires an integrated and multisectoral approach (public decision-makers, technical services, NGOs, value chain actors) that includes the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices, better management of natural resources, training and support for producers, and support for public policies and strategic partnerships to improve the quality of agricultural products. access to fair pay short circuits. By investing in these areas, RIM can not only increase the productivity and profitability of these two sectors, but also improve the resilience of producers to climate change and promote a more environmentally friendly agriculture that meets the onion and turnip needs of the population and can export surplus local turnip production to the sub-region.

The SRHR and the PNDA, which are reference documents for agricultural public policies, will expire in 2025 and their updating should normally make it possible to promote agroecology, improve the technology package, create an environment conducive to access to production factors and investment at both the level of small and large producers, to adapt the financing system to the specificities of the most promising agricultural value chains, including onions and turnips, without omitting the crucial area that is sought, and finally to structure the actors of these value chains. These different actions represent elements that can increase the quantity and quality of agroecological production. These can increase their value on both the national and regional markets and ensure a certain competitiveness, especially with regard to products that are widely imported and consumed by the Mauritanian population, such as onions.

Chapter 8

Value chain analysis report for the
Boulemane Living Lab (Morocco)
Olive Oil and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

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Chapter 8. Value chain analysis report for the Boulemane Living Lab (Morocco) – Olive Oil and Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

Summary

This study examines the context of local learning (LL) in Skoura M'daz through the analysis of olive and aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) value chains. The main issue is the need to improve the sustainability and performance of these chains in the face of challenges such as water management, access to finance and the high cost of agroecological products, which limit their accessibility for many consumers.

The analysis reveals that local cooperatives play a crucial role in the promotion of local products. They help structure value chains, increase the visibility of products on local and international markets, and ensure fair remuneration for producers. However, despite a growing demand for agroecological products driven by environmental and food safety concerns, the high cost of these products remains a major obstacle for many consumers.

Producer dynamics are influenced by a variety of internal factors, such as the level of training and equipment, as well as external influences, including agricultural policies and climatic conditions. In addition, the limited participation of women in decision-making processes, especially in the olive sector, highlights the need to increase their involvement for inclusive and equitable development.

The main findings highlight the importance of diversifying product offerings, improving logistics infrastructure and building the capacity of cooperatives. In addition, financial and technical support is needed to help producers adopt agroecological practices. With a focus on valuing the role of women and improving infrastructure, this study aims to promote sustainable and inclusive development of value chains in Skoura M'daz, thereby contributing to the local economy and food security.

8.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

Local products, including olive oil and aromatic and medicinal plants, are at the heart of the local economy of Skoura M'daz. These products, beyond their economic value, symbolize the cultural identity of the region. Skoura olive oil, renowned for its exceptional quality, is produced using traditional cultivation and pressing techniques, adapted to local climatic conditions. Aromatic and

medicinal plants, on the other hand, have been used for generations for their medicinal and culinary virtues, representing a rich natural and cultural heritage.

The preservation of these products and their know-how is crucial for biodiversity and the maintenance of sustainable agricultural practices. Ancestral cultivation methods and respect for natural cycles guarantee the quality and authenticity of local products. These agricultural practices also contribute to landscape conservation, avoiding soil degradation and biodiversity loss.

Professional organizations, such as cooperatives and associations, play a key role in structuring and professionalizing local agricultural value chains. By bringing producers together, they facilitate the sharing of knowledge, the improvement of production techniques, and the establishment of quality standards. They also help producers access financing and innovative technologies, while representing their interests in negotiations with intermediaries, wholesalers and processing industries.

Although there is not yet a local label or brand for Skoura M'daz's products, professional organisations could play a central role in their development in the future. By creating quality labels and certifications, they would strengthen the credibility and competitiveness of the region's products. Increased visibility on local, regional and international markets would ensure a fair remuneration for producers, while preserving the authenticity of the products.

This report aims to examine and analyse the value chains of aromatic and medicinal plants, as well as that of the olive tree, two sectors selected by the Skoura M'daz Living Lab committee because of their importance for the local economy. The study focuses on the processes of cultivation, processing and marketing of these products, and proposes strategies to improve their performance and sustainability.

The objectives of the study include:

- Carrying out a diagnosis of the main value chains of the Living Lab, studying production routes, valorisation processes and marketing circuits.
- The analysis of local professional agricultural organizations and their predisposition to promote agroecological practices in the region.
- The evaluation of the performance of value chains with agroecological potential, with a detailed analysis of the stages of production, processing and marketing.
- Identification of agricultural practices that promote environmental and economic sustainability.
- The proposal of accompanying measures, based on a SWOT analysis, to promote agroecology and support Morocco's Green Generation strategy.

This Green Generation Strategy 2020-2030 is an ambitious roadmap for Morocco's agricultural and rural development, aimed at strengthening the sustainability and resilience of the sector. It is based on two main pillars. The first concerns the emergence of a new generation of farmers, with the aim of integrating 350,000 young people into agricultural sectors and supporting the creation of new agricultural and rural businesses. This strategy also promotes land ownership of collective land, facilitating access to land for young people. The second pillar focuses on human development, with particular attention to the social inclusion of rural populations, the improvement of the quality of life and the promotion of the agricultural middle class. The strategy also focuses on sustainable agriculture by integrating innovative practices, including agroecology, to ensure food security while preserving natural resources.

8.2 Methodology

8.2.1 Study Area Monograph

8.2.1.1 Geographical location of the region

The Fez-Meknes region, with a total area of 47,075 km², has 2 prefectures (Fez and Meknes) and 7 provinces, one of these provinces is Boulemane, with a total area of 10.5 km². The province of Boulemane has 21 communes, among them Skoura M'Daz, our study area.

Figure 60: Map of the Fez-Meknes region with a zoom on the Boulemane area, Morocco (Source: Ministry of Agriculture)

The study area of Skoura-Boulemane SMDZ (31°03'45" N, 6°33'09" W) is located at an altitude of 1200 meters, indicating its mountainous character and rugged terrain. The neighbouring douars of Skoura M'Daz are Adrej, Tazouta and Dar El Hamra. Skoura M'Daz is a delta, framed by the Tichoukt range to the southeast with an altitude of 2000 meters, the Jbel Taboujebert chain to the southwest culminating at 1900 meters, and the lower Ich Irhanimone mountain range, reaching 1000 meters to the north (HEUSCH, 1959).

Figure 61: Topographic map of Skoura M'Daz, Boulemane, Morocco (Source: Google earth, 2024).

The total agricultural area of Skoura M'Daz is 41,153 hectares, of which 9.36% (3,853 ha) is utilised agricultural land (UAA), with 2,000 ha irrigated. Forests cover 35,786 ha, and rangelands cover 1,514 ha. According to the Regional Directorate of Agriculture (DRA), the 13 douars of Skoura M'Daz are surrounded by a wide variety of fruit trees, including more than ten types and varieties such as olive, almond, fig, apple, pear, peach, apricot, plum, cherry, quince and vine trees.

The two main income-generating activities in the region are olive cultivation and the breeding of small ruminants (sheep and goats). These activities depend on the collective exploitation of natural resources: forest and non-forest rangelands, where herds are driven extensively, as well as water used for irrigating olive trees. This system is supported by a technically advanced irrigation network.

The agricultural area of Skoura M'Daz is characterized by relatively small farms, reflecting traditional agricultural practices in mountainous environments. The majority of farms are family-owned, with areas ranging from 1 to 4 hectares in the majority of cases. The main crops are cereals, such as wheat and barley, which dominate, followed by legumes and some fodder crops adapted to local

climatic conditions. Arboriculture is also present here, especially olive, almond and other trees, which benefit from the soil conditions and climate of the region. Irrigation practices are mostly gravity-based, using local water resources, although efforts to introduce more modern techniques, such as drip irrigation, are underway in some areas to improve water efficiency. This agricultural diversity is supported by a local farmers' organization, enabling them to cope with the constraints linked to the relief and the specific climatic conditions of the region.

8.2.1.2 Climatic and soil conditions of the region

8.2.1.2.1 Climatic conditions

The climate of Skoura M'Daz (SMDZ) is semi-arid, with an average annual rainfall of 350 mm. Temperatures vary from 0°C for the minimum to 35°C for the maximum, according to studies by the DRA, Boulemane Province in 2023. The monthly distribution of precipitation is irregular, with a notable concentration in late spring, particularly in May and June. This climate does not prevent the use of water sources for agricultural activities. Some of the main sources of water include Ain Tadout, Ain Rached, Ain Ait Ouahyan, as well as the surrounding natural areas (Tmari, 2021).

Table 20: Climate Data from Sefrou, Morocco (1999-2019), Source: (Climate Data, 2022).

	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Average temperature (°C)	6.5	7.4	10.1	12.5	16.1	20.7	24.3	24.5	20	18	10.3	7.7
Average minimum temperature (°C)	1.8	2.4	4.5	6.7	10	13.7	15.9	17.3	14.1	10.9	5.9	3.2
Maximum temperature (°C)	12.7	13.6	18.4	18.7	22.5	27.5	31.5	31.7	26.6	22.3	18	13.8
Precipitation (mm)	55	60	72	83	78	33	14	23	56	70	64	54
Moisture (%)	89%	89%	66%	66%	62%	53%	48%	45%	57%	62%	68%	69%
Rainy days	5	6	8	9	9	5	3	5	7	6	6	6
Sunshine Hours (h)	7.4	7.9	8.7	9.2	10.3	11.9	12.5	11.8	10.2	8.8	7.5	7.4

Figure 62: Precipitation in the commune of Skoura, Boulemane Morocco, for the 2022/2023 agricultural season (Source: DRA of Boulemane, Morocco 2023). (in French)

8.2.1.2.2 Soil characteristics

The Skoura M'Daz region (SMDZ) is characterized by a high presence of clay-limestone soils, according to data from the DRA, 2022. These soils are rich in organic matter, particularly in the surface layers (2 to 4%). The limestone content is high, varying between 30 and 60%, with a notable importance of active limestone. The soils also have similar fine sand and clay contents, each around 20%. The layers of earth have a high capacity to retain sediments, especially water (about 40%), and a rapid rate of infiltration, which explains the permeability of the soil and its arable nature (B. HEUSCH, 1959).

8.2.1.3 Socio-economic data

The majority of the inhabitants of Skoura M'Daz are subsistence farmers, living mainly from their fields and modest livestock. They are either owners or tenants of their land. For them, agriculture is the main source of income. They mainly grow olive trees, carob trees and cereals. At the same time, some of them run small local businesses, engage in handicrafts or community jobs, and some drive public transport vehicles.

About 5% of men and 2% of women leave the commune to look for work in other regions or abroad, particularly in Europe, in order to financially support their families who have remained in Skoura M'Daz, by sending them a significant part of their income. In terms of the division of labour, women bear a disproportionate share of domestic and agricultural responsibilities compared to men. However, the introduction of new technologies has reduced the workload for both sexes (Anjedi, 2020).

8.2.2 Methodological approach

8.2.2.1 *Upstream study*

The upstream study consisted of a territorial diagnosis aimed at identifying the resources and economic, social and environmental potential of the region. This diagnosis made it possible to draw up a complete picture of the territory, its agricultural sectors and the existing value chains. We used several methods of investigation, such as literature review (reports, previous studies, economic and statistical data), interviews with key local actors (communities, cooperatives, public bodies) and field visits.

Based on the results obtained, the selection of value chains focused on the value chains with the greatest development potential for the region, taking into account the following criteria:

- **Economic criteria:** The strong market demand for MAPs products (especially for export) and olive oil, as well as their potential to create local jobs, were key factors in the selection. These sectors also contribute to increasing producers' incomes and boosting local cooperatives.
- **Social criteria:** The MAP, in particular, play an important role in local development, particularly in terms of women's participation. In the Skoura region, several women's cooperatives specialize in the production of MAP, and this activity promotes their economic inclusion. The olive sector, on the other hand, offers a structured framework with well-established OPAs and cooperatives, which facilitates the organization of producers and their access to markets.
- **Environmental criteria:** The two selected value chains are well suited to the agroecological conditions of the region. MAP and olive trees are climate-resilient crops and require few inputs, which reduces their environmental impact. The valorization of MAP, for example, is based on practices that preserve local ecosystems and promote the sustainability of natural resources (agroecological practices, sustainable soil management, etc.).

8.2.2.2 *Sampling*

The sampling was designed to represent a diversity of actors within the MAP and olive value chains, although not statistically representative. Due to time and resource constraints, we chose directed sampling, supplemented by a "snowball" method. This made it possible to identify the most relevant actors through the recommendations of the initial producers.

- **Selected actors:** The sample included 28 olive and MAP producers, divided into two main groups: members of agricultural cooperatives and unaffiliated individual producers. The sample was expanded thanks to successive recommendations from key players (producers,

intermediaries, retailers). 15 value chain actors representing both value chains were also selected including 5 retailers, 5 intermediaries, and 5 market actors/consumers.

- **Snowball method:** This approach consists of starting from an initial sample (reference producers) and gradually expanding the panel by collecting the recommendations of the first respondents on other key actors in the network. This has made it possible to obtain first-hand information, while accessing local networks that are difficult to reach through traditional methods.

8.2.2.2.1 *Development of investigation tools*

In order to obtain accurate qualitative and quantitative information, we have developed different investigation tools adapted to the local context:

- **Focus groups:** These focus groups were held with producers and cooperative members to identify key value chains and explore the challenges they face. These discussions provided a better understanding of local dynamics and the identification of opportunities and constraints specific to each value chain.
- **Semi-structured interviews:** To deepen the analysis, semi-structured interviews were conducted with local market actors (sellers, intermediaries). These interviews made it possible to collect information on commercial practices, the structuring of the sectors and the relationships between the different links in the value chain.
- **Questionnaires:** The questionnaires provided by the CIHEAM-IAMM have been adapted to local realities. These tools were used for producers, retailers, and intermediaries to collect accurate data on production practices, marketing, production volumes, and distribution channels. In addition, a questionnaire has been specially developed for consumers, focusing on purchasing criteria (price, quality, origin), their preference for local and agroecological products, as well as their perception of conventional products.

8.2.2.2.2 *Conducting field surveys*

The field surveys were carried out in a methodical manner in order to collect qualitative and quantitative data on the value chains of MAP and olive trees. The process took place in several stages:

- **Stakeholder interviews:** Producers, intermediaries, wholesalers and retailers were interviewed through interviews and questionnaires to understand their practices, challenges and opportunities within value chains. Discussions focused on production techniques, marketing methods, and the impact of climate change on their activities.

- **Collection of consumer perceptions:** Local consumers were included in the survey to understand their preferences and purchasing behaviours towards local products (RTP, olive oil), and their perception of agroecological products compared to conventional products.

8.2.2.3 *Data analysis*

The collected data was processed via Google Forms, allowing for pseudonymization of sensitive information. This numerical method has facilitated data management by automating the process of coding and classifying responses. The responses were converted into an Excel spreadsheet to allow for structured analysis. Each question in the questionnaire corresponds to a column in the table, while each respondent is represented by a row. Responses were coded according to predefined value scales (e.g., "yes/no", "very satisfied/satisfied/dissatisfied").

8.2.2.4 *Data analysis*

The analysis of the data was based on a descriptive approach, making it possible to identify the main trends and characteristics of the sectors studied:

Descriptive analysis: This method made it possible to summarize the data in the form of percentages, averages, and graphical representations (histograms, pie charts). Visualization tools played a key role in interpreting the results by providing a clear and visual reading of the data collected. This descriptive analysis made it possible to compare the results obtained for the different profiles of producers, retailers, and consumers, highlighting the notable differences between the actors of the two value chains.

The methodological approach adopted, combining field studies, questionnaires, focus groups and semi-structured interviews, made it possible to collect rich and varied data, offering an in-depth analysis of the dynamics of local value chains.

8.3 Value Chain Selection

The two value chains, namely those of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) and olive trees, were validated in July 2024 during a participatory workshop organized in Sekoura, bringing together a diversity of stakeholders. Among these, local producers have played a central role, especially those from cooperatives or operating individually in the MAP or olive sectors. In addition to the producers, the presidents of some local cooperatives, institutional representatives such as ENAM teacher-researchers, members of the Chamber of Agriculture and the National Office of Agricultural Advisory (ONCA) as members of the advisory council, were present to provide their expertise and

recommendations on the structuring and development of the sectors at the Skoura level. A local elected official also actively participated in the discussions, contributing to the validation of value chains with a regional development perspective. These institutional actors highlighted the importance of MAP and the olive tree in creating jobs, strengthening local economies and sustainable agricultural practices. This workshop made it possible to strengthen the collaboration between the different actors and to establish the same vision to reflect together on how to contribute each with their expertise to the development of these sectors in the Skoura region.

8.3.1 Importance of the Olive Sector in Morocco and Sekoura M'daz

The olive sector in Morocco plays a central role in agriculture and the national economy, particularly in rural areas where it is a driver of economic and social development. With about 1.2 million hectares dedicated to olive cultivation, representing 65% of the country's tree area, it provides jobs for about 380,000 people, contributing to poverty reduction and improving living conditions in these regions. Olive groves, often managed by small family farms, are a stable and regular source of income for many families. Morocco produces between 1.5 and 2 million tons of olives per year, 25% of which is destined for olive oil production, with an annual average of 160,000 to 200,000 tons. Moroccan olive oil, a flagship export product, generates between 5 and 7 billion dirhams per year and contributes significantly to the country's trade balance. Thus, about **80%** of Moroccan olive oil production is destined for export. Morocco, being one of the leading producers of olive oil in the world, ships much of its production to international markets, mainly in Europe, North America and Asia, strengthens Morocco's presence in international markets and brings in essential foreign currency.

The sector is also closely linked to the promotion of Moroccan local products, with olive oils of recognized quality, such as those from the Moroccan Picholine variety, benefiting from labels such as Protected Geographical Indications (PGI). From an environmental point of view, olive cultivation contributes to the fight against soil erosion and the preservation of biodiversity, while being well adapted to the semi-arid climatic conditions of the country. Sustainable development is at the heart of agricultural practices in this sector, supported by public policies such as the Green Morocco Plan and the Generation Green strategy, which aim to modernize infrastructure, improve yields, and promote sustainable agriculture.

Beyond its economic and environmental importance, the olive tree has a deep social and cultural dimension in Morocco, symbolizing peace, longevity, and prosperity. It is an integral part of Morocco's cultural and gastronomic heritage, strengthening social ties in rural communities and preserving ancestral know-how through festivals, culinary traditions, and centuries-old agricultural practices.

The olive tree in Sekoura M'Daz, located in the mountainous province of Boulemane, represents an essential component of local agriculture, deeply rooted in the life and economy of this region. The most commonly grown variety is the **Moroccan Picholine**, a local variety renowned for its hardiness in the face of extreme climatic conditions and for the superior quality of the oil it produces. This oil is particularly prized for its intense, fruity taste and distinctive organoleptic qualities, often sought after by local connoisseurs and consumers.

In Sekoura M'Daz, agricultural practices remain largely traditional. Olive groves are mainly small family farms between 0.5 and 2 hectares, managed with manual techniques passed down from generation to generation. Dry cultivation, without irrigation, is predominant, which, although limiting yields, makes it possible to produce olive oil of exceptional quality. Yields can vary greatly from year to year, depending on rainfall and weather conditions, but the quality of the oil remains high. This olive oil is mainly intended for local consumption, contributing to the food self-sufficiency of the region's inhabitants.

Beyond its economic contribution, the olive tree in Sekoura M'Daz plays a vital socio-cultural role. Olive cultivation is not only a source of income for many families, but it is also a key part of the local identity, connecting rural communities to their land and cultural heritage. Olive groves are often managed collectively, strengthening social ties within the community.

8.3.2 Importance of the MAP Sector in Morocco and Skoura M'daz

Morocco is one of the world leaders in the production and export of MAP. It ranks 12th in the world, with an annual production of more than 140,000 tons and an export volume of 52,000 tons of plants and 5,000 tons of oils. The flagship species of this sector include thyme, rosemary, lavender, oregano, as well as endemic plants such as mugwort and Damask rose, all renowned for their therapeutic and aromatic qualities. The economic contribution of the WFPs is significant, representing between 4 and 5% of agricultural GDP, with annual revenues of more than 2 billion dirhams. Most of this revenue comes from exports to demanding markets such as Europe, North America, and Asia, where the demand for natural and organic products is constantly increasing. Indeed, Morocco is recognized for the superior quality of its products, often certified organic, which strengthens their international competitiveness.

On the social level, the MAP sector plays a key role in job creation, particularly for rural populations. About 500,000 people, mostly women, find employment in the collection, cultivation, and processing of these plants. This sector thus contributes to the improvement of living conditions in rural areas, by providing a stable source of income and by participating in the empowerment of women. Valorisation initiatives, such as the creation of local cooperatives and the establishment of more efficient marketing

channels, make it possible to maximize profits for producers while ensuring sustainable growth of the sector.

The Skoura M'Daz region, nestled in the province of Boulemane, is a fertile land for the richness of its biodiversity, particularly with regard to aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP). Benefiting from a Mediterranean climate with continental influences, this mountainous area offers an ecosystem conducive to the appearance of various species of MAPs, such as thyme, rosemary, lavender, mints, mugwort and sage.

The practices related to the harvesting of MAP in this region are rooted in ancestral traditions, passed down from generation to generation. Although these plants are mainly harvested in the wild, cultivation is beginning to take shape, supported by local initiatives by the provincial directorate of agriculture for certain species such as saffron, lavender and the rose of Dadesh, aimed at maximizing the valorization of these natural resources. Skoura M'Daz's MAPs are particularly prized for their purity and exceptional aromatic properties, some of which are processed into essential oils, floral waters, or sold dried as herbal teas.

Economically, the MAP sector in Sekoura M'Daz is of paramount importance, generating employment opportunities and constituting an essential source of income for rural households. Women, in particular, are central to this sector, actively participating in the collection, drying, and processing of plants, giving them increasing economic autonomy. The creation of local cooperatives for the development of MAP makes it possible to increase producers' incomes and promote sustainable development within the region.

8.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterisation

8.4.1 Value Chain 1: Olive Value Chain in Skoura M'daz

8.4.1.1 *Introduction of the Value Chain*

The olive value chain in Sekoura M'daz is a complex process that encompasses all activities related to the production, processing, marketing and distribution of olive by-products, such as olive oil, table olives, and other related products such as **Margins (liquid residues** from the crushing of olives are often considered waste), olive **pomace** (solid residues after the extraction of the oil. Producers (e.g. use them as fuel for heating) and **black soap made from olive oil**. It begins with the cultivation of olive trees, an agricultural activity deeply rooted in local traditions, which benefits from a favorable climate and local know-how passed down from generation to generation.

Production: The first step in this value chain concerns the cultivation of olive trees. This phase includes the selection of varieties adapted to the local agro-climatic conditions, the most cultivated variety in the area is the Moroccan picholine that generally producers buy at the weekly Souks and sometimes distributed by the state as in the case of the period of the Green Morocco Plan. The management of olive groves includes:

- Pruning, which is an essential operation that consists of removing dead, diseased, or excess branches, to promote better aeration and light penetration inside the tree. This practice stimulates the growth of productive new shoots, balances the fruit load, and prevents disease. Pruning is usually done after harvest or in late winter, before the new growing season begins.
- Fertilization is an essential step to maintain soil fertility and provide the nutrients necessary for the growth of olive trees. The main nutrients are often applied in the form of organic fertilizers (manure produced at the farm level). Fertilization is adapted according to the specific needs of the olive trees, which vary according to the age of the trees, the planting density, and the local pedoclimatic conditions.
- Irrigation, is particularly important in this semi-arid region of Morocco, where water is a precious resource. Nevertheless, most of the olive groves in Sekoura are rainfed with the exception of a few where drip irrigation systems are used during critical periods, such as flowering, fruit set, and olive growth.
- Harvesting methods can vary from traditional to modern, depending on the size of the farm and the resources available. Olive harvesting methods vary depending on the size of the farms and the resources available. In small farms with an area of between 0.5 and 3 hectares, traditional techniques, such as manual picking or gaulage, are often used, requiring a lot of labour but respectful of the trees. On the other hand, in large farms that exceed 5 hectares, more modern methods, such as tree shakers. Large farms increasingly prefer mechanical harvesting, using tree shakers or vibrators to detach the olives by vibration. This method is quick and effective, but requires a significant investment and careful management to avoid damage to the trees. After harvesting, the olives are sorted to remove damaged fruit, ensuring the quality of the final product. Olives destined for oil are taken to the crushing units to be pressed, while table olives are washed, graded, and processed for consumption. The yield and quality of the harvest depend on many factors, including the climatic conditions of the year, the management practices of the olive groves, and the harvesting method employed, directly influencing the quality of the oil or olives produced.

Thus, the modernization of harvesting techniques depends mainly on the economic means and the size of the farm.

Processing: Once harvested, the olives are processed mainly into olive oil or table olives locally. The transformation process is carried out by mechanical methods, without the use of chemical treatments, to produce oil. Processing requires specific technical expertise and adapted equipment to preserve the organoleptic and nutritional characteristics of the oil (see report annex).

Marketing: The marketing phase includes the marketing of products on local and national markets or very rarely exported internationally.

Distribution: Finally, distribution covers the transport of products from processing sites to points of sale, whether local, national or international.

The links in the olive value chain in Skoura are:

Figure 63: the different links in the olive tree value chain in Boulemane, Morocco (in French)

Each stage of the olive value chain is interdependent and requires effective coordination between the different actors. In addition, institutional support, technological innovations, and the ability to respond to new consumer trends, such as the growing demand for organic/agroecological and high-quality products, are essential to strengthen the competitiveness and sustainability of this sector. Indeed, to remain competitive, the sector must adapt to **new consumer trends**, in particular the growing demand for **organic and agroecological** products. These products meet criteria of quality, authenticity and respect for the environment, which are increasingly popular with consumers. By offering better and more sustainable products, the value chain can better integrate into high value-added markets, thus strengthening its **competitiveness** while ensuring the **sustainability** of the entire value chain.

The olive value chain in Sekoura M'daz is of great economic and cultural importance. Olive oil production is a mainstay of the local economy, contributing not only to farmers' incomes, but also to the preservation of cultural practices. Regional, national, and very rarely international markets represent opportunities to promote local products.

Nevertheless, several challenges remain. Economically, producers face price fluctuations and limited access to finance. Socially, precarious working conditions and the migration of young people to cities

affect the available workforce. Environmentally, climate change and land degradation threaten the sustainability of production, while the use of chemical inputs persists on some farms.

The enabling framework for this value chain is supported by a conducive institutional and political context, where agricultural institutions such as the Chamber of Agriculture and the ONCA play a key role. Initiatives such as the Green Morocco Plan aim to improve the productivity and sustainability of farms. In addition, the shift towards organic and agroecological products, responding to a growing demand for quality and sustainability, represents an opportunity to strengthen the competitiveness and sustainability of this sector.

In summary, despite the challenges, the olive value chain in Sekoura M'daz has significant potential to develop sustainably, provided that efforts are coordinated between producers, institutions and market players, in order to adapt to new consumer trends.

8.4.1.2 Value Chain Mapping

Figure 64 : Olive Value Chain Mapping in Boulemane, Morocco

8.4.1.3 *Characterisation and Diagnosis*

8.4.1.3.1 *General overview of producer characteristics*

The olive producers in Sekoura M'daz are an interesting sample, where 74% of the individuals surveyed (i.e. 20 people) are dedicated to olive cultivation. Among them, two combine this activity with the cultivation of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP). The population practising olive trees is well distributed among the different age groups, with a slight predominance of producers aged 45 to 60, representing 40% of the sample. The other age groups are balanced, with 30% for 30-45 year olds and 30% for those over 60. It should be noted that this activity is exclusively male, which raises questions about the participation of women in this sector.

In terms of education, the majority of producers have a limited level of education: 45% have reached secondary level, 25% have a primary education, 20% have no formal education, and only 10% have access to higher education. This reflects challenges in terms of training and access to advanced agronomic knowledge.

The olive sector in Skoura focuses mainly on the production of olive oil and the cultivation of olive trees. The region's producers have a diversity of experiences, some with ancestral know-how, passed down from generation to generation, integrating traditional techniques, while others, more recently initiated, have acquired their skills through specialized training and the adoption of new agricultural practices. This diversity translates into a variety of capacities to meet challenges and innovate.

The status of producers also varies: some work independently, producing mainly for their own consumption while selling small quantities locally, while others are members of cooperatives. Membership in a cooperative allows producers to pool resources, benefit from collective support, and improve their access to markets. These cooperatives play a crucial role, providing economic and logistical benefits, although their effectiveness may vary depending on contexts and organizational capacities.

Despite the recognized quality of the olive oil and olives produced in Skoura, the olive sector remains poorly profitable. Farmers, despite offering high-quality production, are often forced to diversify their activities for much of the year to meet their daily needs, sometimes working as farm labourers on large farms or in off-farm jobs. The marketing of olive products represents a major challenge, due to the difficulties of access to markets and obtaining essential certifications, such as that of the ONSSA (National Office for Food Safety). This certification ensures that food products, such as olive oil, meet strict health safety standards, involving regular audits and laboratory analyses.

In addition, the low participation of women in the workforce, both within families and among employees, is an additional obstacle. The role of women is mainly limited to manual and seasonal

tasks, such as sorting and harvesting olives, which are often poorly paid and without decision-making responsibilities. This highlights the challenges of inclusivity and gender equality in the olive sector.

➤ **Governance and organization**

Skoura producers work either independently or as members of cooperatives. These cooperatives play a crucial role in enabling the pooling of resources and facilitating better access to markets. However, their effectiveness can vary depending on the quality of their internal organization and the management of available resources. Women's participation in the family workforce is limited, and their contribution is mainly focused on manual and seasonal tasks. They are rarely involved in important decisions, highlighting a lack of representation and female participation in decision-making processes. Remuneration of the workforce is generally based on the tasks performed, reflecting an often informal and temporary work structure, with limited job security.

In summary, olive producers in Sekoura M'daz are characterized by a diversity of experiences and statuses, but face economic, social and environmental challenges that require special attention to improve their situation and promote a more sustainable and equitable olive sector.

Participant's perception of marketing activity in the value chain studied

To stimulate the sale of their products, producers highlight various qualities and values: taste, nutritional benefits, freshness, local origin, respect for the environment, and the preservation of culinary heritage. However, the profitability of the business is sometimes unpredictable, which makes it difficult to predict profits. Market access difficulties are accentuated by income variability and labour shortages, thus limiting sales opportunities.

Increased competition in the market leads to lower prices and profitability, forcing producers to differentiate themselves by the quality of their products. The lack of certifications can also harm their perception in the market. In addition, constraints such as transportation issues and competition remain major challenges. The sector has experienced periods of growth as well as declines, with a modest increase in profits. These fluctuations underscore the need for tailored strategies to stabilize profitability and improve market position.

8.4.1.3.2 Overview of value chain production

In Skoura, olive oil production is a flagship activity, occupying a prominent place in the local agricultural landscape. In fact, about 60% of the farms in the region are dedicated to olive cultivation, while the remaining 40% are divided between vegetable crops, cereals and other fruit trees. This cultivated diversity is essential for producers, as it allows them not only to maximize their income, but

also to reduce their vulnerability to climatic hazards and market fluctuations. Due to the challenges of relying on a single crop, this diversification strategy is proving to be a smart and resilient approach.

Olive oil producers in Skoura implement an array of processing practices at the farm level. The majority of them are dedicated to the transformation of olives into olive oil, a product that is highly valued on the market. At the same time, some farmers are choosing to explore the production of table olives, thus meeting a growing demand for this type of product. Processing methods, although mostly artisanal, are often enriched by recent investments in modern equipment, making it possible to improve the quality, yield and efficiency of production. This is especially true for growers with access to modern crushing units.

As part of their activity, farmers in Skoura do not use chemical inputs on their farms because they do not have the means to buy them and therefore opt for the use of organic fertilizers such as manure to maintain soil fertility and reduce the risk of degradation. In addition, phytosanitary treatments are often limited to natural products, which minimizes the environmental impact of production. This approach helps to strengthen the resilience of farms to environmental threats, such as soil erosion and biodiversity loss.

The processing of olives also generates by-products, including margins and pomace. These by-products, often perceived as waste, are beginning to be recovered by some producers, who use them as natural fertilisers or for energy production. Margins, in particular, can be used to enrich soils or be transformed into bioenergy, thus allowing farms to reduce their energy costs.

In terms of distribution, about 40% of the olive oil production in Skoura is for self-consumption, ensuring families have a supply of quality oil for their daily use. The remaining 60% is marketed in local and regional markets, where the quality of Skourian olive oil is recognized. Producers integrated into cooperatives benefit from a better position in the market, allowing them to sell their production at more competitive prices and to access a wider customer base. In addition, membership in a cooperative facilitates the pooling of resources, collective support and improved access to markets.

However, this value chain, which combines tradition and modernity, faces significant challenges. Producers, while striving to adopt sustainable practices, face persistent economic pressures, such as rising production costs, certification requirements, and the need to diversify their operations to meet their daily needs. For example, many farmers are forced to supplement their income with other seasonal activities, which can affect their ability to invest in their farms.

Modes of supply of the participant in the value chain studied

The products are mainly sourced directly from local producers, including small family farms and cooperatives. This method of supply has the advantage of reducing the costs associated with intermediaries and avoiding the tariff increases they apply.

When products are purchased directly, the main criteria are price and quality. Price negotiations are based on market rates, and transactions are usually made by one-time purchase. Harvesting and transport management is also provided, allowing for more direct control over operations.

The purchase price from the producer for olives in Skoura usually varies between 6 Dh/kg and 12 Dh/kg, depending on market conditions and competition between intermediaries. There is no significant price differential based on the quality of the olives or other criteria, apart from the market price. This uniformity in purchasing criteria, with an emphasis on the lowest price, limits the value of better quality olives. Informal agreements and the absence of written contracts between producers and intermediaries reinforce this dynamic, where the price is mainly determined by market fluctuations and production costs, without taking into account factors such as the cultivation method (organic or conventional) or the size of the farms.

Despite these challenges, the capacity for innovation, crop diversification, the integration of processing at the territorial level and the use of environmentally friendly inputs are determining factors to ensure the sustainability and competitiveness of the olive sector in Skoura. Efforts to enhance production and meet the growing demand for quality products strengthen the vital role of this activity in the local socio-economic fabric, while contributing to the preservation of traditional know-how and the promotion of sustainable and resilient agriculture.

8.4.1.3.3 Producer market characteristics and market strategies

Skoura's olive oil producers mainly direct their sales to regional markets, including local souks and major Moroccan cities such as Fez and Meknes. These markets offer relatively low margins due to intense competition among producers and limited demand for differentiated or higher-quality products. However, some producers are trying to penetrate wider national markets, such as those in Casablanca, Rabat or Marrakech, where the demand for quality olive oils, as well as organic products, is growing. However, these attempts are often hampered by structural and logistical obstacles.

On the one hand, the transport and distribution infrastructure in the Skoura region remains underdeveloped. Poor roads complicate and increase the cost of transportation to more distant markets. Small-scale producers, in particular, depend on middlemen to sell their products in these urban markets, reducing their margins and their control over the conditions of sale. In addition, these intermediaries, although they facilitate the marketing chain, capture a significant part of the added value, thus creating a strong dependence on local producers.

On the other hand, the lack of specific certifications is another major obstacle. Skoura producers have not yet gained access to quality labels such as the Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) or organic certifications. However, these labels are increasingly required, especially in the European and North American markets, where consumers are concerned about the origin and quality of products. However, acquiring these certifications requires not only rigorous agricultural practices, but also technical and financial support that many local producers do not have. The costs of auditing and monitoring these certifications represent a significant obstacle, especially for smallholders.

Price volatility in these markets also represents a major challenge. Olive oil prices fluctuate depending on the quality of the harvest, climatic conditions and demand. This economic uncertainty makes long-term planning difficult for producers, especially those who do not have long-term contracts or strong marketing strategies, which is the case for almost all of the producers surveyed. In addition, local competition, exacerbated by drought, intensifies price pressures, especially when supply exceeds demand.

Among the main challenges faced by Skoura producers, drought appears to be the most worrying risk. This phenomenon, which directly affects olive production, underlines the urgent need for increased support in water resources management. Training to build resilience to harsh weather conditions is essential to prevent declining yields from forcing producers to sell at lower prices, reducing their incomes. Limited access to certifications, such as that of the ONSSA, further complicates the situation by restricting access to more remunerative markets, which reinforces producers' dependence on intermediaries.

However, despite these challenges, opportunities exist. The marketing of agroecological products represents a significant potential. Although local purchasing power may limit sales, better structuring of cooperatives, as well as efforts to obtain at least ONSSA certifications, could help producers access more advantageous outlets. Some producers are also considering innovation projects, such as the opening of local crushing units, which would make it possible to better value their production and improve their competitiveness in the long term.

In short, although Skoura producers face many challenges – drought, failing infrastructure, lack of certifications and price volatility – opportunities for development exist through innovation, the structuring of cooperatives and the strengthening of the marketing of agroecological products. These advances could not only improve the economic viability of local producers, but also strengthen their resilience to environmental and economic challenges.

Marketing channels:

Presentation of the different channels used for the sale of olive oil:

Olive oil producers in the Skoura region mainly use three sales channels to market their production. The first is direct sales, where farmers sell their products directly to consumers, often during weekly souks or through local sales to neighbours and friends. This short circuit promotes a relationship of trust between producers and consumers. Middleman costs are avoided, allowing producers to maximize their profit margins. It also promotes the distribution of local and fresh products. Nevertheless, sales volumes are often limited due to small farm sizes and low excess production. In addition, producers may find it difficult to expand their market. The second channel is to sell through olive cooperatives. Some local cooperatives, such as the Alkhayr Cooperative and the Al Baraka Association, play a key role in organizing and marketing olive oil production. They facilitate producers' access to wider markets, including wholesale. By joining a cooperative, producers benefit from a better sales structure, more stable prices, and common services, including processing and packaging of products. The success of the cooperative often depends on governance and collective management. There may also be internal tensions related to profit sharing.

Finally, intermediaries represent another important channel. Intermediaries play a central role in the long circuit. They buy the production directly from the producers, either before or after the harvest, and take care of the logistics, harvesting, and processing. These intermediaries then sell the production to processing plants in major cities, mainly in Fez, for factories such as SIOF, Belhassane, and Lbeghdadi, which are responsible for bottling and distribution. Intermediaries can also sell to wholesalers and thus allow producers to sell their production quickly without worrying about logistical aspects. It also simplifies crop management for smallholder farmers. Nevertheless, profit margins for producers are often reduced due to prices imposed by intermediaries, which are between 12 Dh/kg and 18 Dh/kg for olive oil.

Retailers are also a critical link in this value chain, typically selling small quantities locally in Skoura and surrounding areas, such as Boulmane. However, they do not provide precise figures regarding the volume marketed. As a rule, they do not record losses or waste, which is a testament to effective management of their inventory.

When it comes to the quality and value of their products, retailers emphasize the unique taste and local origin of their oils, which helps drive sales. They offer two types of oils: a recent oil and an older oil, while presenting their product as authentically local.

However, the business is becoming less and less profitable due to the persistent drought. Retailers are struggling to sell their products, due to increased competition and low consumer purchasing power. An oil retailer notices that some competitors charge higher prices, between 100 and 120 Dh, thus attracting customers thanks to the superior quality of their oil, especially for its highly appreciated

color. This retailer avoids buying oil from these competitors at the crushing unit level because they suspect that they are mixing their oil of the year with that of previous years, which goes against its commitment to providing a pure and trusted product to its customers. In addition, none of the retailers surveyed have certification for their products, which could affect their credibility in the market.

Finally, export markets for Moroccan olive oil include a circuit where factories sell their production in bulk to foreign wholesalers, mainly Spanish. These wholesalers then take care of the packaging and marketing of the oil under their own brands, after processing. This system has advantages, including access to larger international markets, which can increase sales volumes. However, local producers, especially those in Skoura, are not directly linked to this circuit. Indeed, they often have no control over the packaging or final marketing of their product. This can reduce their visibility and recognition in foreign markets, limiting their ability to take full advantage of export opportunities.

Analysis of the supply chains and the links involved:

The olive oil supply chain in Skoura is made up of several essential links, ranging from production to marketing. Producers play a central role in harvesting the olives and processing some of them into oil. They are the first link in the chain. After harvesting, they usually turn some of their olives into oil for self-consumption. The rest of their production is sold directly or through intermediaries, allowing them to generate additional revenue. Intermediaries play a key role in the olive oil value chain in Skoura by purchasing the farmers' production in the form of oil or, sometimes, by acquiring the raw material (olives) on the vine or after harvest. In some cases, they take care of the harvesting, processing and logistics necessary to transport the olives or oil to the factories in Fez. While they absorb some of the risks associated with selling, they often impose higher margins, which can penalize smaller producers. Their activity also includes logistics, which accounts for between 10% and 20% of total costs, as well as losses due to transport and storage constraints, which can reach 25% of total production. However, these intermediaries are not yet committing to eco-friendly practices, such as reducing water consumption or using recycled packaging. Their operation relies heavily on the hiring of seasonal workers, with a strong participation of women in harvesting and sorting. Thus, while they contribute to market stability, their influence on margins and costs can make profitability more difficult for small producers to achieve.

Processing plants take care of crushing when olives are purchased, bottling, and packaging before selling the final product to consumers. They play a crucial role in preparing olive oil for sale, whether on the local market or for export. Wholesalers and retailers buy in large quantities from middlemen or factories and play a critical role in distributing olive oil to end consumers. Wholesalers, in particular, are preferred customers of intermediaries because of their ability to buy in volume. Finally, end consumers, whether they buy through local souks or retailers in the city, are sensitive to the quality

and price of olive oil. Direct sales allow them to have access to high-quality local products, while longer circuits result in more standardized products.

Each link in the chain faces challenges such as losses due to inadequate storage and high logistics costs, which impact the profitability of the value chain. The variability of prices according to the quality of the products. The creation of an olive cooperative and the improvement of storage infrastructure could significantly reduce these losses and improve profitability for producers. Improving infrastructure, particularly for the storage and management of unsold goods, could significantly reduce these losses and increase the overall efficiency of the system.

Logistics and loss management:

Transport and storage are two critical aspects of logistics in the marketing of olive oil in Skoura. The cost of transport can be up to 20% of the selling price, due to the distance to reach processing centres or urban markets. This cost, often borne by producers, becomes an obstacle to profitability, especially for smallholders who do not have access to efficient transport infrastructure. In addition, the lack of adequate storage facilities leads to considerable losses, estimated at between 15% and 25% of total production. These losses are linked to the deterioration of products before they are sold or processed, negatively impacting the profitability of farms. Improved infrastructure and cooperatives could help pool these costs and reduce losses.

Markets and Selling Prices:

Olive oil producers in Skoura operate in a complex market environment, accessing various channels such as local markets, wholesalers, and processing plants. This diversity of markets allows them to explore different sales strategies, but it also exposes producers to significant price fluctuations, influenced by several factors.

The selling price of olive oil varies greatly depending on the quality of the product and the distribution channel. In local markets, producers sell their oil for between 40 and 45 dirhams per litre, reflecting a direct-to-consumer strategy. This approach not only maximizes profits, but also builds trust with customers, enhancing the artisanal quality of the product. However, this direct sale is counterbalanced by the reality of the purchase prices charged by intermediaries, which vary between 6 and 12 dirhams per kilogram for olives and 70 to 90 dirhams for olive oil. And these same intermediaries, by reselling the olives fresh before crushing to processing plants at prices ranging from 12 to 18 dirhams per kilogram, make significant margins, accentuating the need for producers to navigate skillfully between these different circuits.

Fluctuations in olive oil prices in the region are mainly influenced by the quality of the product, production costs, and market demand. Quality is a key determinant: higher quality olives can command higher prices, both in local markets and when selling to processing plants. At the same time, production costs, often impacted by external factors such as climate and available resources, can reduce producers' profit margins.

Prices are usually set by the market and take into account transport costs. Here are some additional criteria influencing prices:

Size and Appearance: The size and appearance of the olives also affect the price. Larger, more attractive olives tend to be more expensive.

Transportation Costs: The cost of transporting olives varies depending on the distance, mode of transportation, and logistical conditions.

Supply and Demand: Fluctuations in supply and demand in the local and national markets can significantly influence prices.

Season: Prices can vary depending on seasonality, with harvest periods often associated with lower prices due to the abundance of olives. Early olive groves or those harvested at the beginning of the season are at an advantage compared to those at the end of the olive season.

Transaction History: A long-standing relationship with a supplier and repeated transactions can lead to preferential pricing.

Negotiations: The ability to negotiate and close advantageous agreements can also impact purchase prices.

Agreements for procurement are usually verbal and are not formalized by formal contracts.

Packaging and Packaging:

The packaging and packaging of products play a crucial role in access to certain markets for olive oil producers in Skoura. Among the options available are food-grade plastic canisters from 5 to 50 liters, or metal canisters from 1 to 5 liters, often with an airtight cap and a handle for easy handling. Ceramic or terracotta pots add an artisanal and local touch, while labelling plays a vital role in providing information about the origin. The use of eco-responsible packaging, such as recycled materials and reusable containers, shows a desire for sustainability, although in most cases it is more motivated by a lack of resources on the part of producers, thus pushing them towards this type of solution.

Very rarely, some producers use various types of packaging to preserve the quality of their oil and improve consumer perception of it, such as glass bottles, transparent or tinted, which protect the oil from light.

Logistics and Transport:

The analysis of the transport infrastructure reveals notable logistical challenges for olive oil producers in Skoura. Distances to markets, combined with transport costs and storage conditions, can impact profitability. Producers need to invest in efficient logistics solutions to reduce losses during distribution.

8.4.1.3.4 Competition in the Market:

All respondents say that competition in the olive oil market is intense, both at the local, regional and national levels. Skoura producers face various challenges, including competitors offering superior quality products labeled IgP or certified organic in other not very distant regions such as Sefrou, Mly Idriss Zerhoun or Taounate at competitive prices.

8.4.1.3.5 Actors involved:

It is fundamental to identify the key players involved in the olive oil value chain, including producers, processors, distributors, exporters and consumers. Each link plays a critical role in the product's success in the market. Cooperatives and associations, in particular, act as indispensable levers for small producers. They offer them valuable logistical and marketing support, facilitating their access to more competitive markets. For example, they make it possible to pool resources to reduce transport costs and optimize the visibility of products by creating collective brands, while strengthening the credibility of producers through quality certifications.

In the Skoura region, olive oil producers face many challenges, especially in terms of fluctuating prices, product quality and logistical constraints related to the distance from markets. Their success will largely depend on their ability to adapt to these obstacles while seizing the opportunities offered by local and international circuits. In addition, improved packaging practices, including eco-friendly and attractive options, are necessary to stand out in an increasingly competitive market. By adopting these practices, producers will not only be able to protect the integrity of their oil, but also meet consumers' growing expectations for sustainability. This blend of tradition, quality and innovation could give them a sustainable competitive advantage.

8.4.1.4 Certification

At the national level, we can mention the Moroccan legislation that governs local products with Law 25-06 on Distinctive Signs of Origin and Quality (SDOQ), as well as the "Morocco" label for olive oil.

These labels offer products official recognition that can result in better value on the market, in particular through a higher selling price and better access to distribution channels. In addition, organic certification, governed by Law 39-12 in Morocco, is also a guarantee of quality, although it is mainly adopted by producers oriented towards the export market.

However, in the Sekoura region, there is neither formal nor informal certification for olive oil. The only form of recognition is based on the reputation of the region, passed on by word of mouth by former customers. The reputation of this oil, perceived as being of good quality, is therefore the only "certification" enjoyed by local producers. This local recognition plays a significant role in the value of the product, even if it does not allow access to larger markets or to obtain the advantages associated with official labels.

The producers of Sekoura are all unanimous on the fact that obtaining a quality label, such as the SDOQ or an organic certification, would have a significant impact on the selling prices of their olive oil as well as on the organization and structuring of this sector. They recognize that these certifications could allow them to better position themselves in the market, access new consumer segments, and increase the added value of their products. However, they also stress the need for support from the State for these approaches to be viable. Indeed, they believe that support in the form of incentive grants would be essential to help them take the necessary steps to obtain these certifications, whether in terms of costs or training. This type of support would ensure better competitiveness of the sector while ensuring the sustainability of environmentally friendly practices.

8.4.1.5 *Focus on collective efforts, short circuit markets, and direct contact with consumers*

This section addresses two essential aspects for the structuring of olive oil producers in Skoura. The first point concerns the forms of collective collaboration to which producers can join, such as cooperatives, unions or Economic Interest Groupings (EIGs). These structures offer many advantages, particularly in terms of sharing resources, pooling production costs and improving market access. In fact, about 80% of producers say they are aware of the advantages of joining these structures and express a real interest in joining a cooperative or other form of collective organization. They recognise that this could improve their bargaining power, promote a better organisation of the sector, and allow them to meet market requirements, such as certifications, with greater ease.

However, about 20% of producers remain more cautious and do not fully trust these structures. Their reluctance can be explained by past experiences where some cooperatives have not kept their promises or by a fear of losing control over their production. They therefore prefer to maintain relative independence, although they recognize the challenges they face in an increasingly competitive market.

The second point deals with the presence of short marketing circuits and channels directly linking producers to consumers. This increasingly popular distribution method allows producers to sell their products without going through intermediaries, which increases their margins while offering consumers quality local products. Producers who organize themselves collectively within these short circuits find opportunities in direct sales at markets or in weekly basket systems. These dynamics show that collective organization and access to short circuits can play a decisive role in improving producers' profitability, provided that trust and institutional support are strengthened.

In Sekoura, the only current short circuit is mainly based on the weekly souk, as well as on sales made to people with whom the producers have family ties. However, this model has limitations, and the opportunities offered by neighbouring cities still need to be further explored. The latter represent a significant potential for the sale of olive oil without the use of intermediaries, which could increase profits for producers by reducing the margins captured by them. The extension of these short circuits would not only make it possible to promote the local product, but also to strengthen the direct links between producers and consumers.

8.4.1.6 *Motivation and Quality/value perception of producers*

Certification is a key issue for Skoura's olive oil producers, although its adoption remains limited in the region. The majority of producers, around 80%, are aware of the advantages that labels such as organic certification or SDOQ (Distinctive Sign of Origin and Quality) can offer. They recognize that acquiring certification could not only improve their access to local and international markets, but also strengthen their credibility with consumers. These producers believe that certification could lead to higher selling prices for their olive oil and promote the adoption of better agricultural practices.

However, about 20% of producers remain more skeptical of this approach. They express reservations about the immediate economic feasibility of certifications, preferring to maintain autonomy in the face of structures that they sometimes consider restrictive. They point to the high costs of complying with certification standards, which can be a barrier for small-scale producers.

On the other hand, long-term economic profitability is a central point of discussion. Producers recognise that, although the initial investments may be considerable, these could be offset by higher sales margins in export markets, in particular through better valuation of the quality of the product.

Agroecology is also emerging as an incentive for producers and the various actors in the value chain. By promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly farming practices, agroecology could not only meet a growing consumer demand for healthier products, but also serve as a lever for innovation within farms. It could also encourage a dynamic of cooperation between producers, promoting the exchange of knowledge and the improvement of agricultural techniques.

Finally, it is crucial to highlight the need for institutional support. Producers express the wish to be supported by the State through incentive subsidies, which could facilitate their transition to more sustainable practices and allow them to access certifications more easily. The establishment of such a support infrastructure could turn the current challenges into growth opportunities for the entire olive sector in Skoura.

8.4.1.7 *Barriers and opportunities to production and market access*

The Skoura M'Daz olive sector faces several significant challenges related to access to inputs, as well as structural and organizational constraints. First, producers face difficulties in obtaining quality inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, and phytosanitary products. High-yielding olive varieties are often difficult to acquire, and their cost can be prohibitive for many farmers. In addition, organic plant protection products, which could improve crop health, are very expensive and often exceed the budget of producers, limiting their ability to adopt sustainable cultivation practices.

These difficulties can be exacerbated by unpredictable climatic variations, which affect not only the health of olive trees, but also the availability and cost of agricultural inputs. In addition, farmers face major economic constraints, including limited access to wider markets, which prevents them from selling their products at competitive prices. The lack of modern infrastructure for the processing and marketing of olive oil is also an obstacle to their development. For example, the lack of suitable presses and storage facilities limits production capacity and the quality of the final product.

In addition, producers are often dependent on intermediaries for the sale of their olives, which can lead to transparency and fairness issues in transactions. This dependence reduces their bargaining power and makes them vulnerable to price fluctuations imposed by intermediaries. Despite these challenges, the sector has considerable potential for development. By integrating agroecological practices and enhancing the value of olive oil through quality labels, producers could not only increase their yields, but also improve their competitiveness on the national market. To this end, efforts must be made to strengthen organizational structures, in particular through the creation and support of cooperatives that can facilitate access to inputs, markets and the training necessary for the modernization of production techniques.

8.4.1.8 *Value chain governance and decision-making power*

Governance within the olive sector in Skoura M'Daz is based on a complex institutional framework that combines public structures, producer organizations, and external actors.

Institutional governance: The institutional landscape is mainly represented by the Agricultural Advisory Centre (ACC) in Skoura, which is the only public structure present on the ground. This institution plays a crucial role in providing technical advice to farmers and facilitating access to

resources. However, the Provincial Directorate of Agriculture (DPA), which manages agricultural policies, is located in Missour, which can create discrepancies in the implementation of local policies. This lack of proximity can limit the responsiveness of services to the specific needs of producers in the region.

Producer governance: Several Professional Agricultural Organizations (OPAs/cooperatives) are present in Skoura, but only a few of them are really functional. These takeovers are essential to organize producers, provide them with training and strengthen their bargaining power in the market. However, the low functionality of some takeovers can hinder the ability of producers to come together to address common challenges, such as market access and the implementation of sustainable practices.

There are no NGOs or development agents active in Skoura, which can limit the resources and support available for local initiatives.

8.4.1.9 *Interactions with other value chain(s)*

The main crops in the region are cereals with 48%, followed by olive 23%, legumes 17%, market gardening 8%, rosaceae 4% and carob 2%. This diversity of crops reflects the variety of agroecological conditions and production strategies adopted by farmers.

The olive oil value chain in Skoura is therefore closely integrated with other crops, especially through the use of crop residues, such as olive branches, to feed livestock, thus valorizing agricultural waste. Intercropping cereals such as barley and wheat, as well as legumes such as alfalfa, improves soil fertility and protects against erosion. In addition, fruit trees such as almond, carob and fig diversify agricultural production, strengthening the economic and ecological resilience of producers.

These interactions create a sustainable agroecological system, where each value chain supports each other, optimizing the use of resources and contributing to local food security.

Together, these farming practices allow producers to integrate both fresh and processed produce, while ensuring sustainable land management and diversification of income sources. The synergies generated strengthen the long-term sustainability of agriculture in Skoura, combining ecological efficiency and economic viability.

8.4.1.10 *Agroecological diagnosis and potential*

The olive oil value chain in Skoura has interesting agroecological potential, particularly through its interactions with other agricultural value chains. Farmers in the region, although unfamiliar with the concept of agroecology, implement traditional practices that align with its principles. For example,

olive tree residues (leaves and branches) are used for animal feed, reducing waste while supporting local livestock farming.

In addition, intercropping with cereals such as barley and wheat, as well as legumes such as alfalfa, plays a key role in protecting and enriching soils. These practices, which combine olive growing and cereal production, help improve land fertility, diversify producers' incomes, and strengthen the resilience of agricultural systems in the face of growing climate challenges. The integration of other fruit trees such as almond, carob and fig reinforces this diversity, providing additional economic opportunities while optimizing local natural resources.

However, despite these practices, several barriers limit the full adoption of agroecological approaches in Skoura. Lack of training and access to finance, as well as difficulties related to water management, are major obstacles. Farmers indicate a growing motivation to adopt more sustainable practices, including to produce healthier food and respect ancestral traditions, but they face structural challenges such as reduced rainfall and grazing areas and the lack of state subsidies to support the agroecological transition in these highly socioeconomically vulnerable areas.

8.4.1.11 Main recommendations for the reinforcement of agroecological potential in the value chain

To strengthen the agroecological potential of the olive oil value chain in Skoura, several avenues can be developed. First, the training of farmers in agroecological practices needs to be strengthened, with a focus on methods such as sustainable soil management, agroforestry and the use of natural compost. The development of drip irrigation and water retention techniques is essential to counter the effects of drought and improve the resilience of farms. The integration of intercropping, such as aromatic and medicinal plants, legumes or cereals, is also crucial, as it not only enriches the soil with nitrogen, but also provides feed for local livestock, creating synergies between olive cultivation and livestock farming and diversifying producers' incomes. In addition, the diversification of crops with fruit trees such as almond, carob or fig contributes to the enrichment of local biodiversity while offering additional economic opportunities to producers. Finally, the creation and strengthening of local markets for agroecological products, as well as the improvement of infrastructure for processing, storage and marketing, are essential measures to encourage the adoption of these practices and ensure long-term economic viability. The adoption of these recommendations could thus help build a more resilient, sustainable and diversified production system in the Skoura region.

8.4.2 Value Chain 2: Value Chain of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants in Skoura M'daz

8.4.2.1 Introduction of the Value Chain

The Middle Atlas region in the province of Boulemane, is a fertile land for the richness of its biodiversity, particularly with regard to medicinal and aromatic plants (MAP). Benefiting from a Mediterranean climate with continental influences, this mountainous area offers an ecosystem conducive to the appearance of various species of MAP, such as thyme, rosemary, lavender, mints, mugwort and sage.

The value chain of these MAP, specifically in Skoura M'daz which is part of this large territory, is distinguished by a diversified production dynamic, including cultivated MAP and wild plants harvested from rangelands and forests, mainly by women, who play a crucial role in this sector. This region, with its mountainous terrain and varied climate, favours the cultivation and gathering of many species of MAPs. Cultivated plants, such as thyme, lavender, and mint, are managed by small-scale family farms. However, a significant proportion of MAP (more than 95%) comes from the collection of wild plants from the rangelands and surrounding forests, such as rosemary, mastic tree, myrtle, savory, and spontaneous sage.

In Skoura, local initiatives for the development of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) are part of a dynamic of sustainable development and the preservation of natural resources. Although MAPs are traditionally harvested in the wild, efforts have been made to structure their cultivation and improve production conditions.

Among the main local initiatives, we can note the involvement of the **Provincial Directorate of Agriculture (DPA)**, which is actively working to promote the domestication and cultivation of certain species, including **saffron, lavender**, and the **rose of Dadesh**. These initiatives aim to reduce pressure on natural resources, while creating economic alternatives for local farmers. Technical and financial support is often provided through public programs such as the **Green Morocco Plan**. Farmer **training** also plays a key role in this transition. Workshops and trainings are regularly organized to introduce cultivation techniques adapted to the semi-arid climate of the region.

At the same time, **local cooperatives** have been created, facilitating access to processing and valorization infrastructures, such as distillation units for essential oils or the production of plant-based cosmetics. These cooperatives also allow smallholder producers to pool their resources and strengthen their market position, while integrating rural women into the value chain, thus promoting social inclusion and economic empowerment.

Economically, the MAP sector in Sekoura M'Daz is of paramount importance, generating employment opportunities and constituting an essential source of income for rural households. Women, in particular, play a central role in the gathering of wild plants, perpetuating traditional knowledge passed down from generation to generation. They carry out these harvests in areas that are sometimes difficult to access, using environmentally friendly techniques, which makes it possible to preserve the resource for future harvests. MAP production in Skoura M'daz, including wild harvesting, is small in size but expanding. Cultivated MAPs are gradually being developed thanks to development projects by the Ministry of Agriculture, while wild plants still represent a significant part of the supply, although often undervalued in terms of price and recognition on the market. The majority of production is destined for regional and national markets, with growing potential.

The aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) of Skoura M'daz are mainly marketed locally, with a strong presence in the weekly souks, where the inhabitants of the surrounding douars come to stock up. A significant part of the sales are made directly on the premises of the women's cooperative, where the women producers offer their dried plants or processed into essential oils or basic cosmetic products, to local customers.

At the regional and national level, the MAP of Skoura also find outlets at specialized events, such as the fairs of local products and the International Agricultural Show of Meknes, where they are valued for their natural and artisanal character. These events allow cooperatives to make their products known to a wider audience and to establish commercial contacts that to this day remain very timid and occasional to individuals.

Some cooperatives, particularly those specialising in rosemary, sell their products to industrialists in Marrakech and Casablanca, who use these plants to manufacture essential oils for the various sectors (agri-food, cosmetics, perfumery, etc.). However, despite the quality of the products, the value chain remains mainly oriented towards the domestic market. To date, there is no direct export of Skoura's MAP internationally, due to the lack of structures adapted to this type of transaction and the difficulties of accessing international markets.

Wild-harvested MAP, mainly harvested by women from the surrounding rangelands and forests, are often traded informally. This lack of integration into structured marketing channels prevents these products from taking full advantage of economic opportunities, thus limiting their value. Better organization and formalization initiatives could strengthen the access of these products to formal markets, thereby increasing their economic potential.

On the economic level, producers and especially pickers face a lack of infrastructure for the processing and marketing of products. Income from wild harvesting remains low, despite the

considerable effort of women, and opportunities to create cooperatives to formalize this activity remain under-exploited. Socially, the role of women, although essential in the gathering and management of wild plants, is often marginalized, and their contribution is not sufficiently recognized, both at the local and institutional levels.

From an environmental point of view, the overexploitation of natural resources represents a serious danger to the sustainability of wild aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in the Skoura M'daz region. Due to the growing demand, especially for regional and national markets, intensive harvesting practices are jeopardizing certain plant species, thus threatening the local ecological balance. This is amplified by the effects of climate change, which are altering fragile ecosystems and reducing the natural growing areas of MAP, making these plants even more vulnerable to extinction.

The increasing pressure on ecosystems requires urgent sustainable management measures. The protection of endangered species requires the adoption of gathering practices that respect plant regeneration cycles and the establishment of quotas to avoid overexploitation. Initiatives to involve local communities, especially women pickers, in sustainable management programmes are essential to ensure the preservation of natural resources while ensuring sustainable incomes.

At the same time, the cultivation and domestication of wild MAP appear to be viable socio-economic alternatives, encouraged by public institutions. This process aims to reduce pressure on wild resources by allowing the controlled production of these plants in agricultural environments. In addition to contributing to the preservation of endangered species, this approach offers farmers and local cooperatives new economic opportunities, by promoting high value-added crops. These initiatives, supported by public programmes and development projects, not only protect the environment, but also empower rural communities.

At the institutional level, initiatives such as the Green Morocco Plan and the Green Generation Strategy have greatly contributed to the promotion and enhancement of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Morocco in general. These programmes aim to modernise the agricultural sector and encourage the integration of MAP into organised value chains. However, although these strategies are generally beneficial for the development of the sector, they have not yet put in place specific measures to support women involved in wild gathering, who play a key role in the harvesting and preservation of natural resources.

The development of women's cooperatives is a promising avenue for strengthening the economic empowerment of women pickers. These structures not only make it possible to improve the valuation of MAP through more organized processing and marketing processes, but also to offer training on sustainable management of natural resources, entrepreneurship and cooperative management.

These training programmes, accompanied by more sustained institutional support, could help to better integrate women into the MAP value chain and strengthen their contribution to the local economy.

The National Agency for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (ANPMA) also plays a central role in providing technical support to MAP producers and gatherers, in particular by promoting research on the valorization of endemic species and encouraging innovation in production methods. However, to ensure the sustainability of these efforts, it is crucial to introduce specific certification labels for wild LDCs, ensuring their traceability and compliance with sustainability standards. Official recognition of the role of women in this sector through targeted support mechanisms and quality certifications would strengthen their visibility and active participation in the regional economy.

The value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura M'daz has considerable potential for development. However, to fully exploit this potential, it is crucial to adopt measures to strengthen the valorization of wild MAP and to formalize the integration of women gatherers into marketing channels. It is also important to further promote the cultivation of high-value-added MAPs in order to reduce the pressure on natural resources. The environmental sustainability of the sector must be guaranteed through responsible management practices.

In addition, women's access to land remains a fundamental issue. Facilitating their access to agricultural land would not only improve their participation in production, but also strengthen their economic autonomy. By combining initiatives to promote women's entrepreneurship, access to resources and sustainable management of LDCs, the sector could become a driver of local economic development while protecting fragile ecosystems and preserving the region's natural resources.

8.4.3 Value Chain Mapping

Figure 65 : mapping the value chain of MAP in Boulemane, Morocco

8.4.4 Characterisation and Diagnosis

8.4.4.1 General overview of producer characteristics

Among the sample studied, 33% of the individuals (i.e. 9 people) devote themselves to aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP), two of whom cultivate these plants in association with the olive tree. This activity is mainly carried out by people aged 45 to 60, with no significant representation of the other age groups. The gender distribution is relatively balanced, with 56% men and 44% women, which contrasts with the practice of olive trees, which is exclusively male. In terms of the level of education of producers, 56 per cent have attained secondary education, 22 per cent have primary education, 11 per cent have no formal education, and 11 per cent have pursued higher education.

The majority of the women surveyed are between 35 and 50 years old, having completed their elementary and sometimes secondary education. They are members of registered cooperatives, which allows them to access resources and a support network offered by the State through local institutions (equipment, training, study trips, participation in fairs, etc.). With an average of five years' experience in a cooperative organization, these women have acquired, in addition to traditional ancestral knowledge, knowledge in the good practices of modern processing of MAP into essential

oils and other cosmetic products, they have acquired specific skills and knowledge in this field thanks to training and support from the institutions of the Ministry of Agriculture and the Regional Association.

The participants employ an integrated approach, combining traditional and modern techniques for the collection of wild aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in the rangelands and forests of the Skoura region. This synergy of know-how allows them not only to optimize the harvest, but also to ensure sustainable management of natural resources.

As for the cultivation of MAPs, they farm a one-hectare plot of land, mainly devoted to mint. Other species are grown according to the needs of the market and the demands of consumers. This flexibility allows them to diversify their production and increase the profitability of their activities.

The participants also master the transformation process, extracting essential oils using a small extractor, thus guaranteeing optimal quality of their products. This extraction method allows them to retain the aromatic and medicinal properties of the plants, thus offering high-end products that meet customer expectations.

It should be noted that approximately 95% of the products marketed come from harvesting. This high proportion underlines the importance of local biodiversity and the richness of the surrounding ecosystems, which provide a variety of wild MAP. By drawing on these natural resources, the participants contribute not only to their own livelihoods, but also to the preservation of local traditions and the enhancement of ancestral know-how.

The majority of participants highlight the unparalleled excellence and meticulous appearance of their products, which are central elements of their business strategy. The uncompromising purity of these products, without any additions or mixing, is a major asset that clearly distinguishes them from the competition. This unique feature guarantees superior quality, highly prized by a loyal and demanding clientele. Consumers particularly appreciate the freshness as well as the strict health and hygiene standards respected, thus strengthening their confidence and satisfaction.

However, despite these distinctive strengths, MAP cooperatives face significant challenges in fully accessing the market. Obtaining the ONSSA (National Office for Food Safety) certificate, which is essential to participate in the International Agricultural Show in Morocco (SIAM), represents a major administrative obstacle for one of the cooperatives. This requirement is a barrier that has restricted business development opportunities and slowed sales growth over the past five years. Indeed, the absence of this official certification could limit access to certain market segments that are more demanding in terms of compliance and standards. To overcome these obstacles, the cooperative will not only have to continue its efforts to obtain the necessary certifications, but also strengthen its strategy of promoting the local origin of its products.

The majority of respondents strive to strictly adhere to quality and health regulations for the sale of their products. In Skoura, they are involved in a cooperative, not only to improve the condition of women and the local community, but also to enhance and promote local products. This membership in the cooperative is essential for the marketing of the herbs grown, playing a key role in supporting the local economy and promoting local resources. In addition, most members benefit from informal relationships, mainly of a family nature, which facilitate the marketing of their products. These family networks allow for a smooth exchange of information and resources, contributing to efficient harvesting, transportation, and sales activities. These community dynamics not only strengthen solidarity within the cooperative, but also optimize the production and distribution processes, thus making the cooperative more resilient and better anchored in the local economic fabric.

8.4.4.2 *Overview of value chain production*

The value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura M'daz is an integrated process that encompasses several key steps, from the collection of plants (whether wild or cultivated) to their marketing, including processing and valorization. Each link in this chain is essential to ensure the quality of the products while maximizing the economic benefits for local actors, especially women, who play a central role throughout the process.

The members of the cooperative take a sustainable approach to the production of MAPs. This process begins with the collection of wild plants during the spring and summer seasons, respecting specific proportions: 70% of a species is harvested, while 30% is left to promote flowering and guarantee regeneration in its natural habitat. In addition, the plants are not pulled out with their roots, which contributes to their renewal. Among the species harvested are rosemary, oregano, thyme, wild sage and savory, carefully sorted, washed and dried in suitable dryers to preserve their properties. Some of the collected plants are then transformed into essential oils or herbal teas, offering products rich in aromas and therapeutic benefits. About 95% of the production comes from wild picking, illustrating the importance of natural resources in the functioning of the cooperative.

In addition to the wild harvests, the participants also grow plants such as lavender and verbena, as well as other MAPs for the production of dried plants and the extraction of essential oils. Fenugreek, whose seeds are pressed to extract vegetable oil, completes this diversity. These cultivated MAPs are also carefully sorted, washed and dried to ensure their quality. This diversification optimizes production while meeting the growing demand for local and natural products.

To support agroecological production, the participants mainly use inputs from their own plots, thus minimising their environmental impact. For example, the cultivation of lavender and verbena is carried out without chemical pesticides, promoting biodiversity and soil health. Cooperatives play a crucial

role in the marketing of products: about 30% of the production is self-consumed, allowing the participants to benefit directly from their work, while 70% is sold in local markets, strengthening short circuits and links with consumers.

The distribution of products is supported by collaborative work within cooperatives, where women are actively involved in packaging, labeling and preparing products for the market. This packaging process highlights the quality and authenticity of the products, thus attracting a clientele concerned about local and sustainable consumption. The support of NGOs and development organizations is essential to improve agricultural practices, processing techniques and to offer training on entrepreneurial management, allowing participants to increase the value of their products.

Logistics are carefully managed to ensure maximum efficiency. When participating in national fairs and events, the cooperative favours the use of taxis to transport products and members. This convenient and flexible method helps reduce post-harvest losses while preserving product quality. Through rigorous management and proper storage, the cooperative maximizes its revenues, strengthens its reputation with consumers and ensures the profitability of its operations.

The first step in the value chain is the collection of MAP, which is carried out manually in the wild, with traditional know-how to preserve local biodiversity. Women are the main actors in this phase, using their extensive knowledge of plants and natural cycles to harvest species in a sustainable way. The cultivation of certain species is beginning to develop in the gardens of all the members of the cooperative, but it remains limited in area, with significant growth potential for the entire area.

MAPs products include dried plants, herbal teas, essential oils and floral waters. The cooperative also carries out simple transformations, such as the soap factory, to create value-added by-products, thus strengthening the local economy and diversifying women's sources of income.

Once harvested, MAPs go through a processing phase that can include drying, grinding, or distilling to extract essential oils and floral waters. In Skoura M'daz, small processing units, managed by cooperatives or specialized local micro-entrepreneurs, carry out these tasks. This enhancement is crucial to increase the added value of the products, and the women of Skoura M'daz, often involved in the drying and preparation of the plants, use traditional techniques to guarantee the quality of the final product.

Harvesting and cultivation practices respect agroecological principles, promoting the sustainability of resources. Cooperatives favour selective and sustainable harvesting methods to preserve biodiversity and ensure the regeneration of harvested species, while avoiding the use of chemical inputs. Picking and processing activities sometimes generate by-products, such as unused leaves and stems, which

can be recovered as compost or used in traditional formulations (flavoured black soap, etc.), thus contributing to the sustainability of the farm.

A small proportion of the MAPs harvested is consumed by families for medicinal and culinary purposes. However, a significant proportion is also marketed on local markets and through short circuits, thus strengthening the link between producers and consumers.

8.4.4.3 *Producer market characteristics and market strategies*

This analysis of the markets followed by producers of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in the Skoura M'daz region covers the different marketing channels, price dynamics, packaging, logistics, competition and the main players involved.

Skoura's Aromatic and Medicinal Plant (MAP) growers access markets through several channels, each with specific characteristics and dynamics that influence their marketing strategy. Among these channels, intermediaries play a crucial role, especially those based in Fez and other cities such as Sefrou, Boulemane, Ifrane and Meknes, which facilitate direct negotiation with cooperatives during harvest periods. This allows them to secure a steady supply while ensuring efficient distribution of raw products without processing. For their part, wholesalers, also located in Fez, buy herbs directly from cooperatives, thus offering producers some stability thanks to a guaranteed market and predictable orders. Retailers, on the other hand, operate mainly in local souks, where they diversify their offer to attract a varied clientele; However, this flexibility can sometimes be accompanied by less sustainable marketing practices, posing challenges for the environment and product quality.

In addition, local and weekly markets allow direct sales to local consumers, thus fostering a close relationship between producers and customers. Co-operatives also take advantage of regional and national events and fairs to sell their products directly to consumers. At the same time, local produce shops that are considered wholesalers, located in large cities, play an important role in selling essential oils and dried plants from cooperatives directly to consumers. This helps to increase the visibility and accessibility of local products while meeting a growing demand for specific, quality products. This diversity of marketing channels provides MAPs producers with valuable flexibility to adapt their strategies to market needs, consumer preferences, and environmental issues. Price dynamics in the marketing of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) vary considerably depending on the channels used, which directly impacts producers' incomes. In the case of intermediaries, prices are often negotiated, which can lead to a lot of pressure on producers. The latter sometimes find themselves forced to sell their products at ridiculously low prices. For example, bulk dried MAPs, such as rosemary, are often sold for less than 10 dirhams per kilogram. However, intermediaries, who take

care of logistics and packaging, can resell these same products with margins ranging from one to three, thus exploiting the gap between the producer price and the final price on the market.

For wholesalers, on the other hand, the prices offered to cooperatives are generally more stable, which provides some financial predictability for producers. This model relies on long-term supply relationships that reduce price fluctuations, although producers' margins remain relatively low compared to retailers or direct sales.

Retailers, on the other hand, set prices by taking into account various factors such as profit margins, local market prices, and the perceived quality of the products. For example, if dried rosemary in bulk does not exceed 10 dirhams per kilogram, once packaged in bags and labelled, its price can reach up to 60 dirhams. This substantial increase applies to most plant species, as adding value through packaging and marketing allows retailers to take advantage of a customer base willing to pay for a ready-to-use product.

When MAPs are processed, as in the case of distilled rosemary, the price of essential oils rises even further. It takes about 100 kilograms of dried rosemary to produce one liter of essential oil, which can be sold at more than 1000 dirhams per liter. This distillation process illustrates how the transformation of raw materials makes it possible to multiply profit margins, to the detriment of producers who often benefit from only a fraction of the final value of the product. Thus, producers must adapt their strategies according to the dynamics of each marketing channel in order to optimize their income in a market marked by significant differences between wholesale and retail prices.

Packaging plays a crucial role in the marketing of medicinal and aromatic plant (MAPs) products, especially in terms of environmental impact and consumer perception of quality. Traditionally, retailers have used plastic packaging, which, while inexpensive and convenient, is causing growing concerns about the ecological footprint and negative impacts on the environment. More and more ethically and sustainability-conscious consumers are demanding more environmentally friendly alternatives, encouraging producers and cooperatives to re-evaluate their packaging practices.

Cooperatives, in particular, have begun to adopt more eco-friendly packaging to add value to their products. For example, for dried MAPs products such as rosemary or mint, they are increasingly using biodegradable materials such as bags made of burlap, recycled paper or natural raffia. These alternatives not only reduce the environmental impact, but they are also perceived by consumers as a guarantee of quality and compliance with sustainable standards. These types of packaging meet the growing demand for more ethical products, especially in the organic and agroecological markets.

When it comes to floral waters, vegetable oils and essential oils, glass packaging has become a standard in cooperatives committed to preserving the environment. Glass is not only infinitely

recyclable, but it also offers better preservation of sensitive products such as essential oils, preserving their therapeutic properties. Glass bottles used for oils and floral waters often come with airtight caps to prevent any alteration of the product. This transition to sustainable packaging allows producers to better position themselves in high value-added markets, where consumers are looking not only for the quality of the products, but also for the overall impact of their consumption on the environment.

Thus, by adopting eco-friendly packaging, producers and cooperatives are not only responding to a growing demand from environmentally conscious consumers, but they are also strengthening the image of their products in the market. This strategy not only improves their competitiveness, but also allows them to actively participate in the preservation of natural resources and the reduction of plastic waste, a major challenge for the sustainability of the MAP sectors.

Logistics plays a central role in the marketing chain of MAPs products, directly influencing the quality and availability of goods. When it comes to transportation, retailers, especially those operating on a small scale or in local markets, typically use their own vehicles to distribute products. This approach allows them to manage logistics themselves, providing flexibility in deliveries and order management. However, while this method reduces the costs of outsourcing transmission, it can sometimes limit distribution capacities, especially in terms of volume or distance. As far as storage is concerned, it is often carried out in domestic spaces, such as garages or dedicated rooms in the homes of producers and retailers. This practice helps minimize overhead costs, avoiding the costs associated with renting warehouses or commercial premises. However, this solution also presents challenges, especially in terms of the storage conditions of the products. Dried plants, essential oils, and floral waters require specific environments to maintain their quality, including controlled temperatures, moisture protection, and minimal exposure to light. Domestic storage may therefore not always meet these requirements, which can affect the durability and efficiency of products, especially in rural areas where adequate conservation infrastructure is often lacking. To overcome these limitations, cooperatives and producers could consider shared storage solutions or the implementation of micro-warehouses equipped with preservation technologies, to ensure better quality throughout the supply chain.

In the Skoura region, competition between producers and retailers of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) is particularly marked, especially in local circuits and weekly markets. Retailers in Skoura not only have to compete with other local sellers, but also with middlemen from cities such as Fez and Marrakech, who buy products in bulk at often ridiculously low prices and resell them at considerable margins after packaging them. Faced with this competitive pressure, some producers and cooperatives in Skoura are turning to innovative strategies to differentiate themselves. For example, local cooperatives are selling the small quantities packaged or have started to adopt more environmentally friendly practices by using sustainable packaging such as burlap bags,

biodegradable paper or glass bottles tinted by a few milliliters for essential oils and floral waters. And sometimes make traditional cosmetic formulations or make flavored soap.

Competition is not limited to price, but also extends to the perceived quality of products. In Skoura, where the production of rosemary, lavender and other medicinal herbs is well developed, retailers have to convince customers that their products, often without pesticides or other inputs (preservatives, etc.) or agroecology without being recognised for this with a label, are distinguished by their freshness, traceability and therapeutic benefits. This approach is aimed not only at local consumers, but also at a wider clientele, attracted by regional and national fairs. Indeed, these events allow Skoura producers to establish direct links with consumers, thus avoiding intermediaries and maximizing their profits while strengthening their brand image. The rise in popularity of local products and short circuits represents an opportunity for local players in Skoura, who must nevertheless continue to innovate to remain competitive in this fast-growing market.

So to sum up, the value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura includes several key links that ensure the production and marketing of products. Producers, often grouped in cooperatives, grow and process RTPs locally, packaging them in sustainable packaging. Then, middlemen buy these products at low prices and resell them at high margins, connecting producers to urban markets. Wholesalers guarantee a stable market for cooperatives by buying in large quantities, while retailers, present in souks and specialized stores, diversify their offers to attract customers. Finally, direct sales at regional fairs and events allow producers to maximize their income while meeting the growing demand for local and ecological products.

End customers are mainly local consumers, who favour value for money in their purchases of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs). However, producers, often women, have developed a good understanding of the preferences of urban consumers. This allows them to adapt their offer according to the expectations of these markets, with a focus on quality, product sustainability, as well as local origin. This in-depth knowledge of consumers gives them a competitive advantage, particularly in the choice of products offered, packaging methods, and communication around the benefits of MAPs.

Here is a table summarizing the different links in the value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura:

Table 21: The different links in the value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura, Boulemane, Morocco

Link	Description	Characteristics
Producers	Grow and harvest the MAPs, often grouped in cooperatives.	Local processing and packaging, use of sustainable packaging (canvas bags, paper, etc.).

Link	Description	Characteristics
Intermediate	Buy RTPs at low prices from producers to resell them at higher prices.	Direct negotiation with cooperatives, high margins on resale.
Wholesalers	Acquire large quantities of MAPs for distribution to urban or international markets.	Guarantee a stable market, wholesale purchasing, regular relationship with cooperatives.
Retailers	Sell MAP products in souks, specialty stores, and local markets.	Set prices according to profit margins and local demand, diversify the offer to attract customers.
Local shops	Sell essential oils and dried plants directly to consumers in major cities.	Promote the sale of local and agroecological products, in response to the growing demand of urban consumers.
Events and fairs	Direct sales to consumers at regional and national fairs.	Opportunity for producers to maximize their income and promote their products without intermediaries.
Consumers	Buy MAPs products for their home, medicinal or cosmetic uses.	Concerned about quality, local origin and sustainability of products, demand environmentally friendly packaging.

This table presents the different players in the value chain and shows how everyone, including consumers, contributes to the dynamics of the MAPs market in Skoura.

8.4.4.4 *Certification*

Certification is a crucial issue for producers of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura, although its adoption is limited. All respondents recognise the benefits of labels, such as organic certification and the Distinctive Sign of Origin and Quality (SDOQ), which could improve their access to markets and strengthen their credibility, leading to higher selling prices. However, all expressed the need for help from the state because of the high costs of certification.

Producers recognize that, despite significant initial investments, long-term profitability could be achieved through higher margins in export markets. Agroecology represents a promising alternative, meeting the growing demand for healthy products while stimulating cooperation and innovation, especially since there is no official agroecological label, which avoids additional costs. In addition, all the producers interviewed stressed the need for institutional support, including through grants, to accompany them in their transition to sustainable practices and facilitate access to certifications, thus transforming challenges into opportunities for the MAP sector in Skoura.

8.4.4.5 *Focus on collective efforts, short circuit markets, and direct contact with consumers*

The value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura is based on collaboration between producers, mainly organized in cooperatives, that facilitate the sharing of resources and knowledge. These collective structures allow producers to strengthen their position on the market and to access short circuits that promote direct sales to consumers. Local markets, especially during events and fairs, create local dynamics, thus responding to customers' preferences for fresh and quality products.

These interactions between producers and consumers contribute to a better valuation of the MAP, while strengthening the sustainability of local agricultural practices.

8.4.4.6 *Motivation and Quality/value perception of producers*

The value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura is deeply influenced by the motivations of producers for certification and their desire to improve the quality of their products. Many producers recognize the benefits of obtaining certifications, such as organic certification, as it could allow them to access more lucrative markets and build credibility with consumers. However, the economic feasibility of this approach remains a concern, as the costs associated with certification can be a barrier for small-scale producers. Despite this, many believe that the initial investments could pay off in the long run, especially when you consider the increase in profit margins in export markets. In addition, agroecology is emerging as a motivating lever for producers and other actors in the value chain, promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural practices. This approach not only responds to a growing demand for healthy products, but also encourages a dynamic of cooperation between producers, facilitating the exchange of know-how and innovation. In this context, institutional support, through grants and accompanying programmes, is essential to help producers overcome the challenges of transitioning to sustainable practices and maximise the economic opportunities offered by the valorisation of MAP.

8.4.4.7 *Barriers and opportunities to production and market access*

Producers of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) in Skoura face considerable challenges in terms of access to inputs and structural and organizational constraints that impact their financial autonomy. Currently, they are unable to achieve a sufficient level of profitability, often limiting themselves to covering their production costs. This situation underlines the economic fragility of their activities, even if producers express some confidence in the willingness of consumers to pay a higher price for agroecological products. They recognize that this growing demand for healthy, quality products is a significant opportunity for their projects.

Despite this opportunity, producers face high production costs, due to the dependence on intermediaries for the marketing of their MAPs. This complexity of the value chain limits their profit margins and complicates access to urban markets where sensitivity to agroecology is more pronounced. Indeed, the logistics of transporting products to these markets remain an obstacle, not only because of the high cost and irregularity of transport, but also because of the increase in fuel costs.

In addition, the market perception of agroecological products poses an additional challenge. Producers feel that they cannot compete effectively with intensive agricultural products, which have

a lower cost of production. This situation makes it difficult to access their products to local consumers, who are often limited by low purchasing power.

However, producers remain optimistic about their future prospects. Some are considering increasing production and diversifying their offerings, while others are expressing uncertainty about strategies to overcome financial challenges. Collective organization within cooperatives plays a key role in pooling resources, but improvements in training, financing and logistics are needed to strengthen the profitability of their activities.

The growth prospects are promising, not least thanks to the growing demand for natural and organic products. To capitalize on this trend, it is imperative to develop continuing education programs tailored to the needs of producers. In addition, financial support mechanisms, such as microcredits, could offer a solution to the current economic difficulties.

Finally, targeted and effective marketing strategies are a must to attract new customers and retain existing ones. It is also crucial to strengthen logistics and storage infrastructure to minimize post-harvest losses and ensure product quality. These improvements are not only essential to maximizing co-operatives' revenues, but they could also solidify their position in an increasingly competitive market.

8.4.4.8 *Value chain governance and decision-making power*

The governance of the aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) sector in Skoura M'Daz is based on an institutional framework that integrates public structures, producer organizations and external actors. The institutional landscape is mainly dominated by the Agricultural Advisory Centre (ACC) in Skoura, the only local public institution, which plays a fundamental role in providing technical advice to farmers and facilitating access to the necessary resources. However, the Provincial Directorate of Agriculture (DPA), which is responsible for developing agricultural policies, is based in Missour, which can lead to delays in the implementation of policies at the local level and limit the responsiveness of services to the specific needs of producers. In addition, several Professional Agricultural Organizations (OPAs) and cooperatives exist in Skoura, but only a few operate effectively. These takeovers are crucial for organizing producers, providing them with adequate training and strengthening their bargaining power in the market, although the low effectiveness of some of them may hinder producers' ability to unite in the face of common challenges, such as market access and the adoption of sustainable practices.

8.4.4.9 *Interactions with other value chain(s)*

In the Skoura M'Daz region, aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) occupy an important place alongside other crops. MAPs, although not the main crops, benefit from a diversified agricultural ecosystem that includes cereals (48%), olive trees (23%), legumes (17%), market gardening (8%),

rosaceae (4%) and carob trees (2%). This diversity reflects the different agroecological conditions and production strategies adopted by farmers.

The value chain of the MAP is thus integrated into this agroecological system, and can be intercropped with olive or other fruit trees such as the almond or fig tree, thus improving the economic and ecological resilience of producers.

These interactions foster a sustainable system where each value chain supports the others, optimizing resource use and contributing to local food security. These practices also allow producers to integrate fresh and processed produce while ensuring sustainable land management and income diversification. The synergies generated thus strengthen the long-term sustainability of agriculture in Skoura, combining ecological efficiency and economic viability.

8.4.4.10 *Agroecological diagnosis and potential*

The value chain of aromatic and medicinal plants (MAP) grown and harvested in Skoura has remarkable agroecological potential, especially due to its interactions with other agricultural value chains. Farmers in the region, although not always familiar with the concept of agroecology, often apply traditional practices that harmonize with its principles. These practices include intercropping with fruit trees, which plays a critical role in the phytosanitary protection of MAP. This approach promotes the diversity of agroecosystems and encourages a biodiversity of auxiliary organisms, thus creating a natural balance that regulates agroecosystems against pests and diseases. By reducing reliance on chemical inputs, these methods not only lower costs for farmers, but also enrich soils, thus promoting more sustainable agriculture.

However, despite these benefits, there are several barriers to the full adoption of agroecological approaches in Skoura. Lack of training in agroecological techniques and limited access to finance are significant barriers. Farmers are expressing a growing interest in adopting more sustainable practices, driven by the desire to produce healthier food while respecting ancestral traditions. However, they face structural challenges such as reduced rainfall, reduced grazing areas, and the lack of state subsidies to support the agroecological transition in areas that are particularly socio-economically vulnerable.

To overcome these barriers, it is crucial to strengthen access to training and finance, as well as to put in place support policies adapted to local realities. By improving access to water and promoting community-based initiatives, it would be possible to encourage wider adoption of agroecological practices. Ultimately, a transition to more sustainable production systems could not only improve farmers' resilience to climate hazards, but also strengthen the region's food security and economic viability.

8.4.4.11 *Main recommendations for the reinforcement of agroecological potential in the value chain*

To strengthen the agroecological potential of the aromatic and medicinal plant (MAP) value chain in Skoura, several avenues must be explored. First, it is crucial to intensify farmers' training on agroecological practices, with a focus on methods such as sustainable soil management, agroforestry and the use of natural compost. The development of drip irrigation and water retention techniques is also essential to mitigate the effects of drought and improve the resilience of farms.

The integration of intercropping, including MAPs, legumes and cereals, plays a key role in enriching soils with nitrogen and providing feed for local livestock. This creates synergies between MAPs cultivation and livestock, while diversifying producers' sources of income. In addition, the diversification of crops with fruit trees such as almond, carob and fig enriches local biodiversity while providing additional economic opportunities for farmers.

Finally, there is a need to create and strengthen local markets for agroecological products, as well as to improve infrastructure for processing, storage and marketing. These measures are essential to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices and ensure long-term economic viability. By implementing these recommendations, the Skoura region could develop a more resilient, sustainable and diversified production system, contributing to food security and the economic well-being of local producers.

8.5 Conclusion and Recapitulation of Main Results

This work has highlighted critical aspects of the olive and MAP value chains in Skoura M'daz, identifying ways to improve their performance and sustainability. Local cooperatives play a central role in the promotion of local products, by better structuring value chains, increasing the visibility of products on local markets, and ensuring fair remuneration for producers. However, the high cost of products remains a major challenge, limiting their accessibility for a majority of consumers. Consumer preferences for agroecological products are mainly driven by the perception of better quality, respect for the environment and increased food safety. Despite this, price remains a barrier for some, highlighting the importance of developing marketing strategies that balance quality and cost.

Another important point raised by this study is the limited participation of women in the olive value chain while they are more involved in the MAP value chain. Indeed, for the olive value chain, women are mainly confined to manual and seasonal tasks. This situation contrasts with their greater involvement in the MAP sector with the presence of a cooperative where all the members are women who have decision-making power. Recognizing and valuing the role of women is essential for the inclusive and equitable development of these two sectors.

Summary of the main results:

The olive and MAP value chains in Skoura show significant potential for sustainable development, although they face challenges such as low access to finance and structural barriers to the adoption of agroecological practices. The involvement of cooperatives, while positive, must be reinforced by targeted training for producers and efforts to increase the diversity of product offerings. The development of markets, both local and international, through quality certifications is essential to improve the competitiveness of products. In addition, financial and technical support must be put in place to facilitate the transition to more sustainable practices.

To strengthen the performance and sustainability of olive and MAP value chains in Skoura M'daz, several recommendations are proposed. It is crucial to diversify the offerings by offering a range of products at different price points, while increasing awareness efforts on the benefits of agroecological products. Improving production techniques and building the capacity of cooperatives are also essential to increase the quality and competitiveness of products.

The development of markets, whether local, national or even international, through quality labels and certifications, is essential to increase the credibility and competitiveness of products. In addition, financial and technical support is needed to help producers adopt agroecological practices and improve their incomes. The alignment of local initiatives with the national Generation Green strategy, with a focus on agroecology, will contribute to the sustainable development of the region.

Finally, valuing the role of women, through greater participation in decision-making processes and specific training, is essential to promote gender equality and inclusiveness. Improving logistics infrastructure to reduce post-harvest losses and ensure product quality through to market is also a priority.

8.6 Report Appendices

Appendix A. Photos related to the olive oil value chain

Appendix B. Photos related to the MAP value chain

Chapter 9

Value chain analysis report for the
Meknes Living Lab (Morocco)

Onions and Mint

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Chapter 9. Value chain analysis report for the Meknes Living Lab (Morocco) – Onions and Mint

9.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

9.1.1 Introduction

Urban and peri-urban agriculture is an activity recognized for its multifunctionality and its strong contribution to food security and poverty reduction. Often associated with market gardening. The production of aromatic and medicinal plants is experiencing significant development on the outskirts of cities, but is still little studied.

The objective of this study on the agricultural value chains of onions and mints is to characterize this agriculture, to assess its environmental and socio-economic functions, as well as to analyze the links and actors that structure it. The method adopted combines a mapping of the value chain of each crop and an identification of the actors and production routes. The study is based on both an in-depth diagnosis of the douar and the analysis of the trajectories of a dozen onion and mint producers in the Ait Othmane douar.

It should be remembered that family farming is the most dominant in the douar and the land tenure status is of a collective type, under the supervision of both the ethnic community and the Ministry of the Interior. The douar Aït Othmane has historically been a paid employment pool for large agricultural estates during the protectorate period. This situation continued after independence in the new properties. While the douar's status as a collective property protected the land from the appetites of the surrounding capitalist entrepreneurs, it nevertheless generated social competition for access to land.

The quasi-egalitarian distribution of shares of less than five hectares of land among the rightful owners, according to the rules of the ethnic community, has led to profound changes towards de facto and individualized forms of land appropriation, thus weakening community modes of land management of collective land. Investments have multiplied and diversified, including the digging of individual wells, the acquisition of water pumping equipment, the construction of individual houses scattered on the farms, and the introduction of new vegetable crops such as onions, potatoes and garlic at the end of the 80s.

The products from the agriculture of the douar Aït Othmane therefore come from semi-conventional agriculture. Our team, NATAE, wants to support farmers towards an agroecological transition adapted

to the peri-urban context, climate change and the requirements of certain customer segments on the market.

9.1.2 Context of the territory

9.1.2.1 Location of the Ait Othmane douar

The douar Aït Othmane is a small territorial unit north-east of the commune of Majjate, with about fifty households, 45 of which are farmers. An Amazigh douar of the Majjate tribe near the agropole and the National School of Agriculture in the peri-urban area of the prefecture of Meknes. It is located about ten kilometers from the city of Meknes and benefits from road infrastructures such as the national road n°6 or the highway n°2. The douar's position offers it real opportunities to adhere to an agricultural transition, adapting to climate change while developing sustainable agriculture. The team's desire is to continue work on this LL even after the completion of the NATAE project.

9.1.2.2 Study context

Morocco has a rich and varied relief and topography. The Fez-Meknes region is composed of four morphological units: the Pre-Rif, the Saïss Plain, the Middle Atlas and the Fez-Taza Corridor (Meknes Urban Agency, 2017). The commune of Majjate is located in the Saïss Plain. Even though it is located at a low altitude and its relief remains relatively flat, the Aït Othmane douar is experiencing a slight elevation that must be taken into account in agricultural techniques.

Figure 66: Topographic map of Morocco

It is in this context of global warming, and more specifically in the case of rising temperatures and long droughts in the Maghreb, that the emergence of Living Labs was born. Their goal is to promote, in a participatory approach, the emergence of agroecological transition in Moroccan rural territories.

The project is part of the NATAE (North African Transition to AgroEcology) program. Aware of the challenges ahead in North African countries, where forecasts predict an increase in demographic pressure while this area is one of the most sensitive to climate change, six living labs have been set up with the aim of boosting a network of relevant actors around the following objectives:

- Understand and identify agroecological practices and identify the perceptions of stakeholders;
- Assess and quantify the impacts of agroecology on agricultural systems and bring out the levers and constraints;
- Expanding value chains and strengthening market access strategies;
- To network various actors in order to allow the exchange of knowledge;
- To empower and raise awareness around agroecology.

Thus, Living Labs are places that promote multi-stakeholder exchange and participation with the aim of bringing out responsible and resilient agricultural scenarios and practices while reducing the negative impact of agriculture on the environment. A place for experimenting with agroecological practices, the Meknes Living Lab, supported by the National School of Agriculture of Meknes, aims to lead to a common reflection on the challenges of climate change adaptation and mitigation while guaranteeing a certain food security in the territory through an agricultural transition. The Meknes Living Lab is located in a peri-urban context.

This document therefore traces the beginning of reflection on the agricultural value chains of the Aït Othmane douar, located near the National School of Agriculture, chosen as the peri-urban LL of the city of Meknes in the NATAE project.

Localisation du Living Lab de Meknès et du douar Aït Othmane

Figure 67: Location map of the LL and the douar Aït Othmane, Meknesm Morocco (in French)

9.1.2.3 Monographic overview of the douar Ait Othmane

9.1.2.3.1 Land tenure status in douar Ait Othmane

The land tenure status of the douar Ait Othmane is characterized by the presence of collective land, governed by the provisions of the Dahir of 27 April 1919 (Dahir of 27 April 1919 26 Redjeb 4327) organizing the administrative supervision of indigenous communities and regulating the management and alienation of collective property at the time of the Protectorate, as amended and supplemented at the time of independence. These collective lands are associated with ethnic communities, defined as tribes, fractions of tribes, douars or any other ethnic grouping. These communities have legal personality under private law and are under the supervision of the Ministry of the Interior.

The right of exploitation and usufruct is generally reserved for male beneficiaries. This practice is intended to ensure the use of the land and to prevent its incorporation by other communities as a result of the marriage of tribal women to men from other communities. Although women are excluded from direct land sharing, they can benefit exclusively through their connection to the group. For example, a widow can receive the share associated with her son as long as the latter is a minor. As daughters, sisters or wives of male heads of households, they can benefit from a share of the harvest thanks to their family ties. However, this family solidarity depends largely on the will of the men in the community. In the event of marriage to a stranger to the lineage, the lost women were automatically entitled to a share of the harvest. A crucial legal effort was made in Law 62-17 adopted in 1919, aimed

at establishing equal access for women to the enjoyment of collective land on an equal basis with men (the case of the soulalyates).

Indeed, this law is a major step forward for women's rights on collective land. Article 6 of this law now grants women the right to appropriate and manage these collectively owned lands. The legislation states that these lands are inalienable, imprescriptible and unseizable, which means that they cannot be transferred, sold, acquired by prescription or seized. It should be noted that the Moroccan government has been engaged in a process of "melkization" for several years, aimed at transforming the status of collective land into individual property (HEM Research Center, 2019).

According to the plan of the douar, it can be seen that the land is divided longitudinally and equitably, thus allocating 5 hectares to each beneficiary of the Ait Othmane lineage (see attached graph).

Nevertheless, the boundaries of the agricultural plots are not clearly visible. Indeed, some farmers have expressed their willingness to call on a topographer who could show the true boundaries of each plot. In addition, farmers identify the boundaries of the plots thanks to the presence of spontaneous vegetation or trees. In total, 25 farmers separated the plots with natural vegetation and 10 with trees.

Figure 68: Plan of the plot boundaries of a farmer in douar Aït Othmane, Meknes, Morocco. March 2024 ©Urban Agency/Meknes

Figure 69: Photographs of trees and natural vegetation as plot boundaries. Ait Othmane, Meknes, Morocco. March 2024

9.1.2.3.2 Production method of the douar Ait Othmane

The traditional agropastoral mode of agricultural production has been profoundly affected by these changes. In the past, it combined cereal farming and the cultivation of legumes in bour with sheep farming on part of the village's collective land. A few vegetable gardens, located near the houses, met the food needs of the families. Agricultural wage labour has always been an essential financial resource for families, allowing them to continue to live locally and to resist the transformations of the local space and society. The successive droughts of the 80s and 90s reinforced this de facto appropriation of the soil.

New rationales of exploitation have emerged, based on the use of the water table for irrigation. This water, initially reserved for domestic consumption, has fostered profound changes in the social structure of the douar. Family farms have thus made significant investments in the digging of wells, the development of the land, and the introduction of crops that are already dominant in the large neighbouring farms.

These transformations have led to changes in the production system, which now combines inherited agricultural practices with a "mimicry" of the conventional farming methods predominant in the

immediate environment. The decrease in economic resources has forced some rights holders to rent their land to "foreigners" in the douar. These newcomers have introduced new crops and invested in cash crops and well-targeted marketing channels. They are "landless" farmers who rent plots in various forms (annual or for long periods). They are not from the douar, often young and invest in short-cycle productions in the peri-urban areas of the city of Meknes.

Currently, agricultural households combine several subsistence activities that allow families to subsist (autumn cereal crops, sheep farming, spring market gardening, raising one or two cows to meet family needs, etc.).

The large estates, where capitalist-type agriculture predominated, occupied the former colonial lands of the Saïss plain as well as new fertile lands. This so-called "conventional" agriculture targets profitable crops (fruit rosacea, onions, vines, etc.) and distant markets. It is a continuation of the agriculture inherited from the protectorate (colonial agriculture), monopolizes natural resources, particularly water, and is based on an intensive production method (pesticides, mechanization, irresponsible use of water resources, etc.). This production system is entirely oriented towards export (to African or European countries) or the national market.

The new farmers of the Aït Othmane douar, almost all of whom have worked on the large farms in the surrounding area, have adopted intensive agricultural techniques and practices while mixing them with practices inherited from their older generations (use of manure, crop rotation, fallowing, etc.). This situation gives an almost hybrid dimension to the douar's agricultural practices.

9.1.2.3.3 *Production system*

According to the definition issued by FAO²⁸, the production system refers to "a grouping of individual farming systems with approximately the same level of resources, the same modes of production, the same sources of subsistence and the same constraints for which similar development strategies and interventions can be developed". The criteria for classifying the production system can be broken down as follows:

"(i) the available agroecological base; (ii) the predominant agricultural activities and sources of livelihood, including their relationship to the market; and (iii) the intensity of production activities" (FAO, 2015).

The douar Aït Othmane is a territory with a strong agricultural component composed exclusively of independent farmers. No cooperative or associative network has been established in the territory. Regarding the products found in the agricultural value chain for the douar of study, we can find first

²⁸ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

and foremost market garden products. Thereafter, cereal production is the most common. And finally, aromatic plants and legumes.

Family farms base their production system on diversification rather than monoculture. Farmers organize their production system according to differentiated methods: production for the market (onions, potatoes, etc.) on small areas (about 1 to 2 hectares) with the use of chemicals, vegetable gardens for family food, and part of the land (1 to 2 hectares) dedicated to cereal farming. Part of it can remain fallow or be reserved for legumes, according to the principle of crop rotation. A fifth of farmers, with plots of land of less than or equal to two hectares or a family garden, grow "beldi" products, locally considered organic, mainly for self-consumption.

All agricultural products are sold in raw format, and no farmers are involved in processing. The marketing process is mainly done through an intermediary, who then sells the products to wholesalers, often on the wholesale markets of large cities. This strategy is favoured in the douar because it is faster and more convenient for farmers, who have immediate financial needs to complete the agricultural season.

While the majority of farmers manage to obtain sufficient income in the douar through agricultural activity, others are forced to rent their land or to enter the wage system as agricultural labourers for part of the year. In addition, apart from a single farmer who seems to stand out for his diversified agricultural activity, the others in the douar are struggling to be visible on the market. The instability of product prices, input costs and the difficulty of finding customers are all problems that slow down agricultural development in the Aït Othmane douar. On the other hand, farmers are showing a real desire to develop their farms and find ways to deal with these difficulties. In addition, climate change causes social vulnerability, due to erratic and insufficient rainfall. Harvests have tended to decrease in recent years and these irregularities lead to uncertain incomes. Finally, the lack of diversification in marketing channels does not allow for a variety of types of income.

All the respondents in our diagnosis encounter difficulties in finding outlets, accessing the market for the sale of their products, and having a financial balance between expenditure and income at the end of the campaign (14%). According to the respondents, these difficulties are mainly linked to the monopolization of intermediaries (72%), the absence of producer organizations and the poor targeting of promising niches on the urban market (14%). In addition, the lack of training and support does not promote the emergence of an agroecological transition in the douar or the establishment of short circuits which could constitute an opportunity for this peri-urban agriculture.

However, they are aware that they need to change their farming practices as customers become more and more demanding of healthy, unprocessed agricultural products grown according to traditional

practices, generally referred to by farmers as "beldi". This observation is all the more legitimate as they are aware of their inability to compete with the products of conventional agriculture in the neighbourhood. The choice to produce for customers and consumers in urban areas is a choice of proximity and could encourage the emergence of an organization of farmers capable of taking charge of themselves. This need for organization is very visible among the farmers of the douar.

In order to differentiate themselves on the market, the majority of farmers opted not to use industrial inputs (64%). Subsequently, some farmers claim to improve the quality of their products in order to be competitive on the market (25%) and to organize themselves into cooperatives (11%). Generally speaking, the reasons that motivate farmers to adapt to the realities of consumers are: the growing demand on the local urban market, the anchoring of peasant agriculture far from the sites where wastewater from the city of Meknes flows and the recognition of the douar as a space of trust traditionally known for generations.

As far as the certification process is concerned, all farmers have a rudimentary knowledge of the certification process. They use labels to designate labels such as organic, beldi or other labels. But overall, they do not know the foundations and principles of the approach and its usefulness for the promotion of their products. On the other hand, they would all like to set up a certification process, seeing it as a challenge and an opportunity to be seized to promote their products. On the other hand, the problem lies in the lack of state labeling and certification for agroecological products. Indeed, a label for organic products exists, but apart from the certification proposed by the RIAM (Network of Agroecological Initiatives in Morocco) and not recognized at the state level, no label for agroecology exists to date in Morocco.

9.2 Methodology

9.2.1 Description

The method used for the realization of this report on the agricultural value chain in the Ait Othmane douar consisted on the one hand of collecting information from the territorial diagnosis of family farming in the Ait Othmane douar, particularly with regard to production methods. On the other hand, a second, more targeted phase of surveys was carried out in order to collect information specific to agricultural value chains: **onion and mint**. The second phase of surveys was carried out in June with a sample of ten farmers.

Indeed, this study was conducted through a methodological approach based on:

- A document review: existing documentation on the onion sector was collected, consulted and summarised. To better understand the social dynamics that shape the informal organization of the sector, the team consulted that the analysis of the onion value chain is very almost absent;
- A diagnosis of 35 farmers out of the 45 in the douar, i.e. 77.7% of the total. This diagnosis is based on a household and farm survey and is based on a questionnaire carried out as part of the NATAE project (see diagnostic report carried out).
- In-depth questionnaires on the value chain carried out as part of the NATAE project, with a dozen farmers growing onions and mints to characterize the onion and mint value chain and identify the actors involved.
- The team also organized focus groups for exchange and discussion. These small group interviews took place in a participatory and trusting atmosphere aimed at documenting the main actions and constraints of the actors, partners, and opportunities for the development of the onion and mint value chains. The exchanges also served to complete the documentary analysis and validate some information in the documents and the survey.

During the diagnosis of the territory of the douar Aït Othmane, 35 interviews were carried out in order to bring out the potential difficulties of adaptation and the obstacles to the transition to an agroecological transition. Subsequently, a sample of ten (10) farmers, i.e. 1/5th of the farmers in the douar, was selected in order to trace the agricultural value chain of the Aït Othmane douar for the onion and mint production chains. The farmers were selected according to the criteria of onion and mint cultivation, age, lineage belonging to the douar (entitled holder) and their relationship with the market.

9.2.2 Onion and mint value chain selection

The criteria that allowed us to select the value chains of onions and mint, rather than other crops, are based not only on the results of the territorial diagnostic surveys, but also on the feedback from focus groups and workshops conducted with farmers. These various consultations highlighted the importance of these two crops in the local economy, both for producers' incomes and for production volumes. In addition, onions and mints are in high demand on regional and national markets, making them strategic sectors for the economic growth of the territory. Workshop participants also highlighted the potential of these crops for the adoption of agroecological practices, including sustainable management of natural resources and reduction of chemical inputs. The social importance of these

sectors, in particular through job creation and the integration of women into the production chain, was also a key factor in our choice.

9.2.3 Characteristics of respondents

Of the farmers surveyed in the context of the agricultural value chain, the majority are between 30 and 45 years old (6/10) followed by people aged 45 to 60 (3/10). Only one farmer is over 60 years old. Moreover, all the people interviewed are men. The level of education, and for the vast majority is primary (7/10), follows with two people who have gone up to secondary level and only one farmer has studied in higher education. In addition, only one farmer among the 10 farmers interviewed cultivates on rented land, while for the others it is their own land.

Regarding the activities carried out in the study douar, five of the ten farmers interviewed are involved in market gardening, particularly onions. Three farmers grow aromatic plants and mainly mint. The last two interviewees, in addition to mint and onions, grow legumes and practice livestock farming. Arboriculture is only very timid (a few trees per household for family consumption, often on the edge of plots or around houses).

As far as livestock farming is concerned, six out of ten farmers have carried it out for more than fifteen years before stopping it in the last five years. Successive droughts and the increase in fodder prices have disrupted the link between livestock and agriculture (agropastoral) that has been strongly inherited from older generations. The desire to return to at least cattle farming is very clear because it is perceived as the basis of a "beldi" agriculture and in harmony with traditional practices.

9.3 Value Chain Mapping and Characterisation

The value chain represents "all stakeholders involved in the coordinated production and value-adding activities that are necessary to produce food". It contains "all the activities necessary for the supply of a product or service, up to the final consumer" (FAO, 2024).

9.3.1 The Onion Value Chain

The study area is marked by the strong presence of agricultural land, farmers are in the majority and onion cultivation occupies almost second place after cereals in the cultivation system. Nevertheless, the territory is prone to difficulties, particularly related to marketing. Agricultural activity is sometimes neglected by farmers who are unable to obtain sufficient income. Some land is rented to farmers from the province or elsewhere in order to allow plot owners to work in non-agricultural sectors (services,

shops, construction, etc.). Thus, some land is cultivated for the sole purpose of self-consumption. In addition, the use of fertilizers and pesticides is recurrent.

The diagnosis identified the main links in the onion value chain and the actors involved in them. We can schematize them in this succession, knowing that each link could be broken down into several values, particularly in large farms of the capitalist type. At the level of the douar Ait Othmane, the diversity of stakeholders is much less, because the farmer first mobilizes family work, which considerably reduces the share of stakeholders in the onion sector.

The links in the onion value chain are:

Figure 70: Diagram of the different links in the onion value chain in Meknes, Morocco

9.3.1.1 *Onion value chain mapping*

Onion value chain mapping highlights a wide range of actors. The main economic actors are input suppliers, producers, intermediaries, wholesalers, transporters and retailers. We also note the almost total absence of institutional actors in the onion value chain.

Carte de la chaine de valeur oignon LL A. Othmane

Figure 71: Map of the onion value chain LL A.Othmane (in French)

Farmers in the Ait Othmane douar thus find themselves alone in the face of private players who exert considerable influence on the onion market and its distribution channels.

Indeed, the suppliers of seeds and inputs are individual traders or companies that supply the inputs at the beginning of the season for a financial advance equivalent to 30 or 50% of the price. The rest is a debt that the farmer must repay as soon as the onion is sold. This constraint weakens farmers' ability to negotiate better prices with intermediaries and wholesalers.

Nevertheless, farmers are very receptive to the discourse on organic farming and agroecology. They see an opportunity to meet the needs of the two large neighboring cities, Meknes (8 km away) and Fez (50 km away). Almost all of them are ready to change their itineraries and production methods to fit into an agroecological approach, which would allow for a significant transition, both in terms of their family economy and in their management of natural resources and their proximity to certain customer segments. The desire to create a cooperative testifies to their desire to take charge of their economic future.

The NATAE project at the scale of the Ait Othmane LL will combine three types of complementary action to initiate an agroecological transition: support and advice for farmers in order to strengthen their entrepreneurial capacities, research and development through the development of measurable, assessable and transferable demonstration sites and support, particularly within the framework of

State programs through the Generation Green strategy, which aims, among other things, at the development of agroecology and organic farming. Subsidies are provided for in the strategy.

The following figure makes the key players in the sector more visible

Figure 72: Diagram of the key actors of the onion value chain in the Aït Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco

9.3.1.2 Onion production

Onions are almost the second most important crop after cereals in the territory of the douar Ai Othmane in terms of area. On the other hand, it is the first production user of water resources and is the flagship income-generating activity for farmers and their families. It is a very water-intensive crop, which jeopardizes its sustainability because of the constant and successive droughts leading to a visible reduction in the areas of onions cultivated over the last five years.

Typologie des cultures par parcelle dans le douar Aït Othmane, Maroc, printemps 2024.

Figure 73: Crop typology map in Ait Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco (in French)

The yield per hectare of onions in the Ait Othmane douar varies according to the production routes of the farmers surveyed:

Table 22: Distribution of onion yields per hectare according to the production methods of the farmers surveyed in the douar Ait Othmane

Typology	Production method	Average production in the douar (Ton)	Average Maximum Production (Ton) in the Vicinity
- Onion in traditional mode	- Unsustainable irrigation - Uncontrolled Seed - Treatment often random	30	40
- Semi-modern onion	- Generalized Drip - Seedlings from trusted growers - Regular follow-up and treatment	60	90
Mechanized onion (introduction of the seeder) ²⁹	- Imported seed (Netherlands very often) - Exclusive Drip - Regular agronomic and phytosanitary monitoring	80	120

²⁹ - A farmer, not from the douar, tenant of the right to exploit about ten hectares of onion land. He practices almost monoculture. It is the only one that introduces the seeder and imported seeds. It achieves yields (70 tons) that are more or less in line with the rates of the large onion producers in the neighborhood.

The table shows that the yields of onion cultivation in the village are far from competitive compared to the large estates of the Saïs plain. This is especially true since the total area devoted to onions on family farms hardly exceeds three hectares, with an average of only about 2 hectares.

The figure also shows that the production method of family farms in the douar is based on crop diversification. Monoculture no longer has any legitimacy in the cultivation system of existing family farms.

Despite the decrease in the area devoted to onion cultivation at the local level, this crop remains essential in the agricultural system, due to its ability to adapt to climatic hazards and spaced irrigation. Of course, irrigation costs have increased due to rising temperatures and the price of energy (especially gas). Nevertheless, farmers while making onion the dominant vegetable crop, they also grow potato, lettuce, garlic, etc. due to its adaptation to the climate of the region and the well-drained clay soil. These crops meet the needs of the neighboring urban metropolises: Fez and Meknes.

The types of vegetable crops are shown in the below figure:

Inventaire des cultures maraichères dans le douar Aït Othmane, Maroc, printemps 2024.

Figure 74: Vegetable Crop Inventory Map in Ait Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco (in French)

The onion production route varies from one farmer to another depending on the means mobilized and the onion cultivation area targeted. The drip irrigation system has become widespread over the past decade, having demonstrated its effectiveness in onion management and its efficiency in water management. Gravity irrigation used to be predominant, but it is painful, labour-intensive, and wasteful water, especially in an area where the water table is receding by about 1.5 to 2 metres each year.

Seed is of two types depending on the two annual winter and summer crops. Farmers get their supplies in different ways, more or less combining these three sources:

- 25% of farmers opt to buy seeds in the surrounding souks. The circuit of these seeds is often unreliable and anonymous.
- 40% produce their own seeds and seedlings.
- 35% buy seedlings from local and neighboring nurseries.

Beyond the immediate advantages announced by farmers (proximity, loyalty/trust, etc.), each method has disadvantages. Farmers cannot always control the quality and authenticity of the seeds grown, their provenance, and their genetic potential. However, they all point out that certified seeds are very expensive and often unaffordable for smallholder farmers. A producer organization to supply collectively could be a solution to the challenges related to seed supply.

For sowing, farmers opt for two methods. The first is the manual method which requires two sowings. The first one starts in November and is sown at a high density. Subsequently, the farmers transplant the plants in March after the tracer has passed. The second method is the mechanical method. It requires only one sowing.

Onions appear in two crop rotation systems. These are wheat followed by potatoes or onions or beet followed by onions and then cereals. These rotations help diversify crops, reduce pressure from crop-specific diseases and pests, and improve soil structure and fertility in the long term.

9.3.1.3 *Onion processing and collection*

Farmers follow common agricultural practices, such as the use of fertilizers, including Diapi applied at a rate of 100 kg/ha before sowing, and treatment against grasses using a mixture of Toyoto and Vosilate. Manual weeding is also practiced, although it requires a large number of farm workers. In addition, farmers strengthen the structure of the plants by applying calcium and increase the volume of the onions with the application of potash. Livestock manure is also used to improve soil fertility and promote crop growth.

Onion collection is a very strategic operation in the production route. It requires a daily agricultural workforce and represents almost 1/3 of production costs. The workforce must be qualified, because the quality of the collection depends on both conservation and storage and other marketing operations. The onion harvest is carried out in August.

Often, family labour is not enough, forcing farmers to call on farm workers in neighbouring douars. It is mainly women agricultural workers who are solicited for onion collection and collection operations.

Onion cultivation requires hired labour:

- On the one hand, a farmer confides that he hires six women to weed onions from month 2 to month 8. Subsequently, he employs fifteen mixed workers in month 4 for manual sowing and finally, he hires a dozen women for the harvest during the fortnight of month 8.
- A second hires at least 10 two people for the sowing of the onion which allows the seed to be produced for the following year. Finally, he needs six women for weeding at month 6 and ten men at month 8 for harvesting.
- A third farmer says he needs to hire two to three farmers for the manual sowing of the onion in month 4 and fifteen to thirty people for the onion harvest.
- A fourth farmer explains that he hires fifteen to twenty men to sow and weed onions in April (month 4).
- The fifth says he needs two to three employees for the manual sowing of the onion and at least 4 and fifteen to thirty employees for the onion harvest.

9.3.1.4 *Conservation and storage*

The traditional preservation and storage of onions in the Fez-Meknes region is a very effective practice to regulate the supply and demand of onions in the markets and thus maintain a profit margin for at least half of the year. They rely on ancestral practices that combine local know-how and adaptation to the climatic conditions of the region.

It is important to emphasize that the preservation of onions depends on different factors. In fact, in order to have **storage onions** that can last longer while avoiding rot, it is first of all important to have quality seeds, but it is also fundamental to follow well-defined technical itineraries. Storage in places away from rain and humidity is also an important factor.

The stages of conservation practices begin with harvesting. This is harvested at full maturity, usually in late summer for summer onions, and in late winter for winter onions. Once harvested, it is left to dry in the field for a few days under the sun. This initial drying reduces the humidity of the bulbs, a

crucial factor for good conservation. Then there is the sorting and cleaning phase to ensure their storage.

The most popular storage technique in the area is that of stone walls (see next photo).

**Figure 75: Onion dryer in the Ait Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco
@NATAE team**

Thanks to these techniques, onions can be stored for several months, without losing their quality. However, growers ensure regular stock rotation to prevent onions from starting to sprout or spoil.

We also observed a loose storage technique in one of the well-ventilated rooms, away from direct light and humidity. Traditionally, these rooms are granaries or warehouses made of local materials such as clay, straw, or stone, which provide good thermal insulation.

Nevertheless, there are only a maximum of ten who have resorted to these techniques of conservation and traditional storage of stone and straw walls, locally called "dryers". These dryers require financial capacities beyond the producers' means. A 25-metre wall, usually the dominant length, requires about 3000 dh including the purchase of 4 to 5 trucks of stones, straw, employment of employees and the rental of a tractor. For the storage of a one-hectare production (50 to 60 tons), 5 rows or dryers would be needed, which is equivalent to 15,000 dirhams.

In addition to the investment price, these dryers require special and regular attention depending on the climate and temperatures (labour, maintenance, regular rotation, etc.). The process involves a

worker who waters the onions, followed by six women who are responsible for placing the onions in racks. Then, ten men transport the lockers with the help of a trolley and place them in the dryer. The latter is made up of alternating layers of straw and onions, covered with plastic and surrounded by a 40-centimetre high stone barrier to ensure effective insulation. However, this technique requires sufficient resources for the implementation of storage infrastructures. In addition, farmers do not have the financial capacity to wait a long time without selling their production. They are called upon by their creditor to repay the campaign credits (fertilizer, treatment, ploughing, labor, etc.) as soon as the harvest is harvested.

9.3.1.5 *Transport*

The service of transporting onions to urban souks and wholesale markets is fundamental in the value chain. Transporters play a vital role in the distribution, transport and supply of inputs to farmers, wholesalers and retailers of onions.

Several types of transport are used depending on the quantity and destination. From pick-ups, vans to trucks, onions from the Ait Othmane douar are transported between Fez and Meknes, or within the weekly souks of the prefecture of Meknes. It is important to note that the onion from the douar Ait Othmane has not yet reached the transnational markets towards African countries.

The cost of transport represents a significant part of the cost price of onions. Transporters are also involved in the transport of fertilizers, seedlings or seeds, labour and gas necessary for the operation of motor pumps for irrigation. Some farmers estimate that transportation accounts for about 15-20% of the total cost of onion production, making it a service of considerable importance.

In the Ait Othmane douar in 2023, almost all farmers opted for on-site sales, which does not require end-of-harvest transport. It is the intermediaries and wholesalers who take care of the transport but also who maximize their grain by lowering the selling prices.

9.3.1.6 *Commercialisation*

Farmers in the douar are struggling to find a stable and permanent market under the aegis of a cooperative organization capable of regulating prices and distribution channels. They indicated that wholesalers maintain direct contact with intermediaries and conclude contracts with them, which prevents farmers from selling their products directly to wholesalers without going through these intermediaries. In addition, some farmers pointed out the difficulty of accessing an already highly

competitive market, where selling prices must be lower than market prices to stand out, leading to reduced incomes for producers.

In addition, the weakness of producers' financial capacities weakens their competitiveness in the face of large onion producers. They start production by taking on debt, at varying levels depending on the farm, and must repay these debts at the end of the season. This situation pushes them to conclude contracts with intermediaries even before the maturity of the product. This practice, called "sale by *Hsira*" (or carpet sale), means that the transaction is done directly on the field, before the harvest.

Some farmers have pointed out that the agri-food market is not stable and obeys the law of supply and demand. Thus, the income from the sale is very uncertain. While for other farmers, it is the sale on the plot that is prioritized. This marketing technique makes it possible to limit the need for storage and transport and thus reduce additional costs.

Marketing in the douar Aït Othmane reflects strong inequalities among farmers. Indeed, income from farms is not homogeneous. Some farmers manage to move between the networks of marketing actors and do quite well, others do not end up selling at competitive prices, which affects household income and investments in the next agricultural season. Thus, according to the responses from the surveys of farmers in the douar, the benefits are very heterogeneous depending on the farm.

Some farmers are forced to carry out a secondary activity to compensate for the lack of income from agricultural activity for ten out of 35 farmers surveyed. In addition, the lack of state subsidies or the complexity of the procedures to obtain them do not favour agriculture in the douar. In fact, 19 respondents do not benefit from subsidies. In addition, most farmers sell their products at prices similar to those of other farmers. They state that the price is set by the market, the quality of the product or by the intermediary who specifies the price. The most recurrent model of payment method for the intermediary is made directly on site in cash.

In the second phase of the survey of ten farmers in the douar, six of them saw their profits increase by 30 to 50 percent over the past five years. They have been able to take advantage of market opportunities by investing in traditional dryers, which allows them to sell gradually, sometimes even by the unit of onion dryer. Prices can go from less than one dirham per kilogram to 3 or 4 dirhams two to four months later. This makes it a profitable investment, especially since the stones are kept from one year to the next and they bring in the plastic, straw and labour.

The large producers of the Saïs plain, on the other hand, are turning to export to African markets (Mauritania, Senegal, Mali, etc.), thus leaving a place for small producers on the national and local markets. Three producers saw their profits stabilize year-on-year, and only one reported no increase in profits.

According to farmers, there is no law governing the sale of products on the market. Only one type of marketing channel is present in the douar, according to the respondents carried out on ten farmers: going through a wholesaler or selling directly to an intermediary. Even if farmers are currently reluctant to diversify their marketing methods because of competition from large producers and imbalances between supply and demand, they consider it important to vary marketing channels. However, the lack of a strong cooperative organization exposes them more to pressure from intermediaries and wholesalers.

On the other hand, we met at least five farmers who sell their own produce in the souks of neighboring municipalities. This direct sale is considered very profitable because it allows the farmer to control the most important links in the value chain: production and direct sales to the consumer as a retailer.

9.3.2 The Mint Value Chain

Morocco is among the world's leading producers of mint. This crop can be considered a niche sector in the market gardening sector where it represents nearly 1% (in production volume). National mint production is quite variable from year to year: while the country was able to record some 98,704 tons in 2018, the total production did not manage to cross the 30,000 tons mark during the 2021 season. This crop is located in the green belts of the cities that give the cultivars their vernacular name: Tiznit mint, Meknes mint, Lbrouj mint, etc.

The total area of cultivation has almost doubled in the last two decades, from 2000 ha in 1998 to more than 4500 hectares in 2022, knowing that the crop in question is grown on small plots almost at the level of all farms (for self-consumption). The Ministry of Agriculture plans to reach 20% of exports for a current rate that is less than 10% of total production³⁰.

9.3.2.1 Mapping the mint value chain

The value chain of mint cultivation in the Aït Othmane douar includes several interconnected links and various actors. Unlike the onion sector, mint seems to be less subject to pressure from local competition. Large farmers are focusing more on export crops and are not yet considering mint as a potential niche for their investments.

Mint cultivation adapts well to small-scale urban and peri-urban land and can generate quick profits through a harvest cycle every 50 days, with intermediaries sourcing directly on site. This saves on production costs. However, farmers also lose profit margins by dealing with intermediaries.

³⁰ - <https://www.lopinion.ma/Culture-et-consommation-de-la-menthe>

Consumers are increasingly demanding freshwater-irrigated cultivation, without pesticides or chemical fertilizers, and they do not buy mint if they do not know where it comes from. The cultivation of an agroecological mint represents an opportunity to target market segments that do not trust mint from traditional urban sources. Promotional work, supported by a well-structured producer organization, could prove distinctive and promising. In any case, this is the commitment of the NATAE project to move towards substantial changes in the management of cultivation, the organization of producers and the management of marketing circuits. Moreover, several good agroecological practices were noted during the diagnosis.

The mapping of the mint value chain provides us with information on the links and actors mobilized by mint.

Figure 76: Mint Value Chain Map in the LL of Ait Othmane, Meknes, Morocco (in French)

9.3.2.2 *Input suppliers*

During our diagnosis, we noticed that mint producers obtain cuttings either from targeted local producers who specialize in the sale of seedlings or directly from the souks. The trend is more towards sourcing from specialist producers so as not to have surprises in terms of the aromatic quality of the mint, diseases or consumer preferences. The supply of the souk is more reserved for domestic vegetable gardens and therefore for family consumption.

One of the producers in the douar, Ait Othmane, told us that he bought his plants for the first time from another producer in a commune in the province of Meknes. Then he became a producer of fresh mint and plants himself. He provides a significant amount of income in the areas of Errachidia (300 km from Meknes) and Erfoud (370 km from Meknes).

The other fundamental aspect of the inputs consists in the search for manure. This is essential for the cultivation of mint. Producers buy manure from neighbouring douars. A 3 cubic meter truck costs on average about 350 dirhams (between 300 and 400 dirhams), a significant amount in the costs of mint production. Manure, once considered "without market value" in the 1980s, is now highly sought after by farmers. This enthusiasm reflects the awareness, even among those engaged in intensive agriculture, of the importance of manure in improving soils and productivity.

In Douar Ait Othmane, a notable reduction in the availability of manure has been observed over the past five years, due to the decline in livestock production due to successive droughts. This situation has made farmers dependent on external supplies. Breeders who, thirty years ago, were happy to get rid of their piles of manure, now consider it as a source of income complementary to livestock farming.

Regarding fertilizers, although producers do not reveal this reality, some provide chemical fertilizers such as nitrogen.

9.3.2.3 *Mint production*

A booming crop, mint and herbs, occupy a central place in the eating habits of Moroccans. These crops have been growing continuously in the Ait Othmane douar for the past five years and mainly meet the demand of the inhabitants of the urban metropolis of Meknes and the urban centers of the prefecture. They are never grown in monoculture, but always in association with herbs (parsley, coriander, wormwood, sage, etc.).

According to the testimonies of farmers, it seems that the development of mint cultivation³¹ heralds new conversions of the agricultural system within the village, accompanying the decline of onion cultivation. This culture was introduced by tenants of land outside the ethnic community. It is an innovation that local farmers underestimated at the beginning, but the current dynamic no longer leaves anyone indifferent. Indeed, the inhabitants of the douar are also beginning to practice this culture and to master its techniques. Vegetable gardens are developing near homes, mainly managed by women. The following figure shows the distribution of these crops at the scale of the Ait Othmane douar.

³¹ - Mint is aromatic in the sense that it is mainly used for its aroma that can be enjoyed in an infusion or found in essential oils. Mint is also a medicinal plant, since its positive effects on human health are also common knowledge.

Figure 77: Inventory map of aromatic plant crops in Ait Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco (in French)

In the douar, the few farmers who grow mint and herbs target local domestic markets. In the value chain analysis, we mainly target mint cultivation because it is the most dominant. It began on half a hectare in a corner of the territory five years ago, and is spreading out inside the territory from one year to the next. Currently, about four hectares are planted with mint cultivation, combined with the cultivation of fine herbs.

The links in the value chain are made visible in a general way by the diagnosis:

Figure 78: Diagram of the different links in the mint value chain in Ait Othmane douar, Meknes, Morocco

The cultivation of mint is a crop that still escapes intermediaries and wholesalers. The producer seems to have control of all the links and often requires only a very small number of participants. We are going to analyse each link in the chain to show its importance and its weight in the sector.

Mint is an aromatic plant that is both very easy to grow but at the same time very sensitive to climatic conditions. Planting preferably takes place in March-April in the interior plains of Morocco and throughout the year in coastal areas.

It is a plant that has a lifespan of four years. Specifically, the spearmint variety is available throughout the year, but its supply decreases significantly in winter. One hectare of cuttings will be used to plant 5 to 7 ha of area. The cuttings will come from 1-2 year old crops and have a 4-year lifespan. The resumption takes place after 50 to 60 days.

The farmers of the Ait Othmane douar have a great knowledge of the technical itinerary of mint production. They use drip irrigation to minimize labor costs and manage the regularity of irrigation themselves and thus reduce production costs.

The vegetative growth of mint is greatly reduced in cold periods, when the photoperiod is less than 10 hours and the temperature is below 10°C.

Producers said they favour a rational management of water resources, because the drip method is more effective. They do not use pesticides, because some western areas of Meknes were recognized, about fifteen years ago, by consumers and health institutions as users of chemicals and wastewater in the irrigation of mint cultivation. Despite the improvement in the production route, these areas still suffer from this stigma, which prevents them from emerging as a "labelled" mint terroir. Instead, they use chemical fertilizers at the time of cutting to speed up the vegetative process. We are therefore witnessing a relocation of mint cultivation from the west to the east of Meknes.

9.3.2.4 *Collection*

The harvest is done with the help of sickles. Cuts are made either at ground level in the case where the stem height is 20 to 30 cm, or at a distance of 10 to 30 cm above the ground level in the case where the stem height is 50 to 80 cm. The lower parts of the stems left behind after harvesting are cut off at ground level with sickles, collected and used after drying in baking bread³².

The time needed to harvest mint by hand is short (4 to 8 days/ha).

Planting is usually carried out preferably in March-April, requiring almost daily irrigation. Manual harvesting is done approximately every 40 days, and weeding requires a permanent workforce. Often, farmers consider the first cut to be of low quality. It takes 40 to 50 days between two successive cuts in the hot season and more than 60 days in the cold season.

³² Abbès Tanji, Technical management of mint, monthly bulletin of information and liaison of the pnnta. (2008).

Collection requires manpower. Farmers have two to three farm workers on an almost permanent basis to irrigate, weed, cut down, etc.

During logging, depending on demand, the number of agricultural workers may increase, the preference is particularly for female labor.

9.3.2.5 *Transport*

Except for a farmer who delivers his production directly to mint retailers in the souika squares of the city of Meknes (urban markets) with his own vehicle, all the others sell on the spot. Intermediaries or sometimes retailers come directly to place their order. Producers, by opting for this option of direct sales on the farm, considerably reduce transport costs. It is the buyers who ensure the transport of their goods. Even when the mint seedlings are sold outside the province, it is the buyers themselves who come to stock up and transport them.

It is noted that transport does not weigh very heavily in the cost of mint production and transporters do not play a crucial role in the strategies of producers in the Ait Othmane douar.

9.3.2.6 *Commercialisation*

The marketing of mint in Douar Ait Othmane does not seem to face any particular problems. Typically, growers sell directly on the plot to middlemen a few weeks before the appropriate harvest stage. At the plot level, producers and intermediaries negotiate the price according to: the area put up for sale, the state of the crop, and the market price. If they can agree on the price, a cash advance is given to the producer, and the rest is paid at harvest time.

Yields in tonnes/ha are quite high in the first two years of production compared to those in the third or fourth year. Production generally varies between 100,000 and 300,000 bunches/ha/harvest (10 to 30 tonnes of fresh mint/ha/harvest, i.e. 40 to 120 tonnes/ha/year) depending on the regularity of irrigation, treatments and the age of the plants. Each bundle weighs about 100 g and contains 15 to 30 mint stems tied together using a piece of doum blade or saw palmetto.

Marketing channels involve four main actors: producers, intermediaries, wholesalers and consumers. Other players are involved in transport and transport. The selling price of mint in the field varies from 10,000 dirhams to 50,000 dirhams/ha/harvest depending on the yields and quality of the mint in the plot.

The below table shows how average prices are distributed among the categories of actors in the marketing chain.

Table 23: Variation in the sale prices of mint according to marketing channels in Meknes, Morocco

Circuits	Producer Selling Price (MAD) (average)
Intermediary selling price	0,30
Wholesale price	0,60
Retail Pricing	1,00
Consumer Selling Price	1,50

Source: Survey

While waiting for the intermediary to decide on the harvest date (and how long it will last, because sometimes they harvest in instalments according to demand), the farmer is required to monitor the plots, irrigate them and carry out treatments if necessary. It is the intermediaries who take care of the harvest, transport and sale of the goods at the wholesale market of Meknes.

The selling price from the producer to the intermediary is on average 0.30 cents per bale. These same boots are sold to wholesalers at an average price of 0.50 per bale on average. The sale to retailers is 1 dirham on average per bale depending on the market, quality and origin. The sale to consumers by retailers is on average 2 dirhams.

At the level of mint producers in Ait Othmane, two farmers sell both fresh mint and seedlings for other producers. The sale of the plants or cuttings brings in a profit margin of about 30% of the farmers' income. All the other farmers in the douar who grow mint go through an intermediary, often linked to a wholesaler.

9.3.3 Onion and Mint SWOT Analysis

Table 24: SWOT analysis of onion and mint production in the Aït Othmane douar

Forces	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rational irrigation system for mint and onion (drip) • Use of farm manure • Local seed or self-production • Good network of local suppliers • Crop rotation for onion • Mastery of the mint marketing circuit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No co-operatives and networking • Competition in the market for onion • Difficulty finding customers • Monopolization by intermediaries • Market instability • Random income • Chemical Inputs and Herbicides • Absence of processing of both mint and onion • Low financial resources for onion investments

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desire to set up a cooperative • Raising awareness of agroecology and the development of short circuits, • Traditional know-how to be valued • Possibility of access to subsidies • Development of short circuits and direct sales • Recycling of mint (drying, syrup, essences, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change • Drought and rising temperatures • Competition • Plant Epidemics and Diseases • Fluctuations in commodity prices • Pressure from intermediaries

9.4 Conclusion

The analysis of the onion and mint value chain shows that the onion value chain is more complex in terms of stakeholders and competition. By integrating sustainability values, we can arrive at a characterization of onion production conditions that are very contrasting:

- **Economic dimensions:** Beyond economic viability, the onion of the douar Ait Othmane is subject to strong competition from large producers who control the routes, marketing circuits and mobilize substantial capital for a better maximization of profits. This competitive environment places small producers in vulnerable positions where they are forced to sell on plots in the majority of them while avoiding the costs of production (labour, transport, processing, etc.). This context causes producers to lose notorious profit margins.

On the other hand, when it comes to mint, producers are showing a certain satisfaction in terms of earnings, made possible thanks to the lack of competition and the reduction of the players involved.

- **Social dimensions:** Family farming is very affected by consecutive droughts and the high cost of onion inputs and processing products. Farmers find themselves very vulnerable and develop survival strategies that place them in processes of impoverishment. Young people emigrate in search of paid work opportunities, work as farm labourers in the neighbourhood and parents tend to take up the challenge by diversifying crops and sources of income. The decline in livestock farming seems to be a major loss in household income. Women participate in several tasks on farms (weeding, maintenance of the few animals, family vegetable garden, etc.).

As far as producers are concerned, the absence of a solidarity-based organisation, such as a cooperative, severely handicaps the ability to negotiate prices with intermediaries and the pooling of means of transport, purchase of inputs, ploughing, etc.

- **Environmental dimension:** Onions consume a lot of water and chemical inputs. Although it is completely in drip mode, a waste of water is still visible, in particular because mulching is not widespread and the management of water needs on the plot is not completely controlled. Water leaks in pipes are frequent due to the aging state of the equipment. The infiltration of plant protection products into the soil can contribute to groundwater pollution (nitrate problem).

The following table summarizes the most salient elements:

Table 25: Synthesis of the most salient elements for the value chains of the douar Ait Othmane, Meknes, Morocco

Type of Production	Production route	Good local practices to be preserved	Intensive practices	Activities or actions to be undertaken to initiate an agroecological transition
Onion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drip irrigation; • Mechanical tracing; • Manual sowing • Transplanting of the plants; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drip Drop; • Drier; • Use of livestock manure; • Manual sowing; • Manual weeding; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive use of inputs; • Intensive mechanization • Herbal treatment; • Application of calcium and potash; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of irrigation systems; • Reduction of chemical inputs; • Promotion of organic farming;
Mint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Almost daily irrigation; • Treatment; • Planting in March-April; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controlled irrigation; • Use of organic fertilizers; • Manual weeding; • Manual harvesting; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive use of water and chemical fertilizers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved irrigation practices; • Introduction of agroecology techniques; • Raising awareness of the use of natural fertilizers;

Regarding the introduction of agroecology, farmers in the Ait Othmane douar are predisposed to adhere to an approach that allows them to distinguish themselves locally and generate stable incomes. Indeed, the choice of the two crops Onion and Mint for experimental trials from the next season seems very relevant with regard to the objectives of the NATAE project. By applying the elements of FAO's agroecology to agriculture in the Ait Othmane douar, the following recommendations can be made that can be translated into an actionable action plan for the agroecological transition in the Ait Othmane douar:

Table 26: Action Plan for an Agroecological Transition of the Ait Othmane douar in Meknes, Morocco based on the 10 elements of the FAO Agroecology

Elements of agroecology	Application in the Ait Othmane douar
Diversity	Practice multi-cropping to increase resilience and productivity: onion, cereal, potato, fodder, chickpeas, and aromatic plants.
Synergies	Use intercropping as in the case of olive trees to optimize the use of resources and increase overall yields.
Efficiency	Improve soil fertility and productivity by applying livestock manure, reducing reliance on chemical fertilizers.
Resilience	Implement crop rotation practices and use irrigation systems such as rain-fed agriculture and drip irrigation to better manage water resources and maintain soil health.
Recycling	Use livestock manure as fertilizer, thus integrating organic waste into the agricultural production cycle and reducing input costs. The ideal is to produce the compost locally.
Co-creation & sharing	Promote traditional know-how and install infrastructure such as an onion dryer to improve the conservation and quality of products, while sharing knowledge among community members.
Human and social value	Promote the establishment of a cooperative to strengthen community ties, improve access to markets and ensure better collective management of resources and benefits.
Culture and traditions	To raise awareness in the community about the importance of ecology , to preserve and transmit traditional know-how and to develop organic home gardens for healthy food and food self-sufficiency.
Circular and solidarity economy	Reduce dependence on intermediaries and combat market instability by promoting direct sales on plots, and by developing more equitable and sustainable local trade systems.
Responsible governance	Address weak state institutions by raising awareness of the need for stronger institutional support, while taking advantage of the grain subsidies offered by the GG strategy to improve agricultural practices.

Chapter 10

Individual value chain analysis report for
the Siliana Living Lab (Tunisia)
Cereals and Olive Oil

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Chapter 10. Value chain analysis report for the Siliana Living Lab (Tunisia) – Cereals and Olive Oil

Summary

This study emphasizes the significant potential of the surveyed farmers to go ahead with adopting agroecological practices. Moreover, it also underscores the need for targeted efforts to address specific challenges in farming practices and decision-making. Outlined obstacles include the unavailability of seeds and fertilizers, water shortage, limited income, diseases, and marketing issues. To prioritize value chains for agroecological transition in the region, the study identifies the cereals and olive oil value chains among the most promising for development, considering economic, social, and environmental factors. Implementing recycling and input minimization principles in the supply chain and bridging the gap between theoretical agroecological concepts and farming practice implementation are recommended to cultivate sustainable agroecological farming systems.

In order to meet the challenges and encourage farmers to move forward with the transition to agroecology, the government, through the Cereals Office (monopoly of the activity) and the National Oil Office, must put in place measures to encourage and support small farmers, essentially through the promotion and recognition of agro-ecological products on the market, the granting of special premiums for agro-ecological products, the provision of the necessary agricultural machinery and all required inputs.

10.1 Introduction and Context of the Territory

Agriculture is a key sector of the Tunisian economy. It employs around 25% of the active population and contributes about 10% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Agriculture in Tunisia is characterized by a wide diversity of crops, from cereals (wheat, barley) to fruit and vegetables (olives, dates, citrus), dairy products and meats. The majority of farms are small, with an average size of 5 hectares. This can make modernization and mechanization of farming difficult. The scarcity of storage and transport infrastructures can also make it difficult to market produce (Adapt, 2024).

The governorate of Siliana is located in the northwest of the country with a total area of around 4,642 km². The governorate's population is 229153 inhabitants (49 inhabitants/km²) and 11163 inhabitants are in El Krib, the territory of our living lab (INS, 2023). About 68% of the population of Siliana governorate lives in rural areas, according to the population census (INS, 2014).

Figure 79: Location of Siliana Governorate and the living lab

The Siliana governorate is surrounded by seven governorates (Beja, Jendouba, Le Kef, Sidi Bouzid, Kasserine, Kairouan and Zaghuan). Like the other north-western governorates, Siliana has a negative population growth rate of -0.48% and a very high poverty rate of 24.7%. According to the Diagnosis Report on the Governorates of Kairouan, Siliana, Kef and Jendouba (DGAT, 2018), this governorate is endowed with several natural assets that need to be exploited to create more wealth and jobs.

Arable land is estimated at 467000 hectares including 313000 ha of cultivated area (CRDA Siliana, 2024), of which 18,400 hectares are irrigated. The region's agricultural potential has enabled the development of sectors such as agri-food, organic farming and other activities such as cultural tourism, thermalism, etc. The governorate of Siliana is characterized by six main agricultural products, including cereals (152266 ha), olives (80696 ha), fodder (54257 ha) fruit trees (9728 ha), legumes (6910 ha) and vegetable crops (1446 ha) totaling 304303 ha in 2018 (CRDA Siliana, 2018). The

diversity of these crops makes Siliana a region with high agricultural potential, especially with cereals and olives that cover almost 50% and 27% of the cultivated area, respectively. Livestock farming has always been one of the dominant activities in the Siliana governorate, coming second behind cereal growing. Livestock farming in the Siliana is dominated by sheep, accounting for 536200 heads, followed by goat farming with 76100 heads, and finally, cattle farming with 31700 heads according to structural surveys conducted by the National Agriculture Observatory. With more than half of the population living in rural areas, agriculture is the governorate's main economic activity. Siliana contributes to national agricultural production by an annual average of 4.7% and cereal cultivation in Siliana in 2022 contributed to 14.2% of national production (DGPA, 2024). The durum wheat is the main cereal species in Siliana and covered 80000 ha in 2022 producing 1319.1 thousand quintals (DGPA, 2024).

Until July, 4th 2024, according to the head of the Department of Major Crops at the Regional Agricultural Development Commission (CRDA), the harvested quantities of cereals amounted to 500 thousand quintals, distributed between 330 thousand quintals of durum wheat, 162 thousand quintals of barley, and 7.5 thousand quintals of soft wheat. The reserves of ordinary barley seeds reached around 80549 quintals, of which 33100 quintals were transferred to the Cereal Office warehouses (L'Economiste Maghrébin, 2024).

Farming system structure and functions:

The findings of the surveys carried out within the framework of the territorial diagnosis show that among the 30 farmers surveyed, it seems that the typical profile of these farmers is predominantly:

- Farm managers
- Married with 3 children
- Aged between 41 and 50
- No agricultural training
- Primary education
- Farming has been their main activity for an average of 30 years
- Landowner

Around 30% of farms have a total size ranging from 10 to 15 ha, and 20% have a size of less than 5 ha while 17% of farms are between 5 and 10 ha, and around 33% are 15 ha or larger.

Figure 80: Total farm size in Siliana and El Krib

53% of farmers do not have a water source on their farms. Among the 47% who do have a water source, 10% have a private well, which they use for irrigation. For some farmers, water is still not used for irrigation, but either for livestock breeding, they are unable to exploit it for lack of means, or they are not authorized to use it. This explains why the majority of these farmers adopt a rain-fed system.

More than 60% of farmers have no agricultural equipment on their farms and often rent the necessary equipment such as seeders and plowing machines (plows, offset plows, Canadian cultivators, etc.) when required.

Cereals in association with olive trees (20%), followed by cereals in association with forage crops (17%) and cereal monocultures (17%) are the dominant cropping systems on all farms. During 2023-2024 season, the most popular crops currently grown are barley (23%), olives 16.5%), followed by oats (15%) and durum wheat (15%).

Challenges and opportunities

Climate change is one of the main challenges facing Tunisian agriculture. Droughts and high temperatures are having an impact on agricultural production, particularly in the country's most arid regions. Water resources are also limited, making irrigation more difficult. Another challenge is competition from imports. Tunisia imports a large quantity of food products, which can reduce the prices that local farmers can obtain for their produce. Traditional farming practices and the use of chemical fertilizers can also affect soil and water quality.

Despite these challenges, Tunisian agriculture has great potential. The country possesses ancestral agricultural know-how, which can be enhanced by high-quality organic farming. Exports of Tunisian agricultural products, such as dates, are growing considerably. The Tunisian government has also launched several initiatives to support agriculture, such as subsidies for the purchase of agricultural equipment and the creation of organic farming zones (Adapt, 2024).

Siliana could be more concerned about climate change issues. In fact, in Siliana, the semiarid climate covers approximately 97% of the total area, with average rainfall rates ranging from 550 mm/year (El Krib Zone) in the North to 260 mm/year in the South (CRDA Siliana, 2012). During the 7 last years, the Siliana governorate, like the entire territory of Tunisia, has experienced periods of drought and irregular rainfall episodes, and thus these levels of rainfall are no longer available. 2023 was the most difficult season with the highest temperatures and lowest rainfall rates. This had a major effect on many crop productions especially those that are under rainfed conditions such as the cereals.

The soil resources in Siliana exhibit a wide variety, allowing for the development of intensive agriculture both in drylands and under irrigation. However, while the nature of the soils and the topography suggest a high suitability for large-scale cultivation, the soils often have shallow crusts that promote runoff and erosion. These soils are prone to accelerated degradation due to both natural factors (water erosion, wind erosion) and anthropogenic activities (excessive deforestation, and inappropriate farming practices). The erosion includes 64% of the area in Siliana and soils could experience decreasing organic matter rates (URAM, 2018).

Farmers in the Living lab El-Krib Siliana as in many Tunisian growing regions faced some socioeconomic challenges:

- The scarcity and high cost of chemical inputs: pose a major challenge for farmers in the region. Fertilizers, pesticides, and other chemicals required to maintain effective cereal production can be expensive and difficult to access for many farmers, especially those with small-scale farms.
- The availability and cost of animal feed are also significant issues: Livestock feeding, which is an essential component of agriculture in the region, result in substantial expenses for farmers. The accessibility to quality and affordable animal feed can directly impact production costs and profitability for farmers.

These socio-economic challenges can have an impact on the economic viability of agricultural operations in the Siliana cereal plain. Farmers have to contend with high costs, which can affect their income and their ability to sustain environmentally sustainable farming practices. Regarding the farmers surveyed as part of the territorial analysis of Siliana, most of whom work in the cereals sector,

future projections for farming activities are in line with national guidelines and take account of current socio-economic and political developments. Indeed, almost all the farmers want to keep farming, either because they have no other training or because it's their only source of income. The main concerns of the farmers interviewed were:

- To have access to a drilling and/or a well (or possibly to develop their well).
- Increase the number of livestock, diversify livestock types (dairy cattle or sheep and fattening cattle) and add a livestock activity where none exists.
- Diversify farming activities and expand the farm (mainly through leasing)
- Install irrigated crops such as tomatoes, legumes (chickpeas, peas, broad beans, etc.), potatoes and tree crops (olives, almonds, peaches and apples).

The living lab territory can benefit from the opportunities that the Siliana governorate also offers such as:

- Tourism: Siliana is a rich historical and cultural heritage city with several monuments and tourist sites, such as the Roman city of Bulla Regia and the town of El Kribi, natural landscapes, and tourist attractions make it a potential destination for visitors. The tourism sector, including accommodation, food services, transportation, and entertainment, contributes to both employment and value-added creation. Jobs in the tourism industry can include tour guides, hoteliers, and restaurant staff.
- Exportations: Major exported agricultural products: Olive oil, essential oils, distilled waters and medicinal aromatic plants
- Regional development strategies: the Master plan for the planning and development of the governorate of Siliana by 2035: Among the proposed actions and programs for promoting an adapted and sustainable agricultural development strategy: respect the agricultural vocations of lands by relying on the potentialities of agro-ecological zones (agricultural map) (2020-2025); develop appropriate agrarian and agro-forestry strategies to combat erosion and maintain soil fertility (2025-2030).

10.2 Methodology

The methodological approach used to diagnose value chains with agro-ecological potential involves surveys of the key actors involved in their respective functioning and governance.

First of all, it should be noted that the selection of the two value chains to be studied/diagnosed was based on the results of the territorial diagnosis carried out between December 2023 and February 2024. These value chains selection has been discussed in a bilateral meeting with the task leader and validated by the Living Lab representative board.

Once the two value chains had been chosen, the stakeholders involved in their functioning were identified. For the cereal value chain these are respectively:

- the cereals office (state institution managing the Tunisian cereals production and trade sector)
- farmers (cereal growers)
- input and agro-supply suppliers
- intermediaries/collectors which are either public or private under the control of the cereals 'office.
- cereal seeds production companies
- wholesalers (flour mills which supply patisseries and bakeries)

The interviews with the above-mentioned stakeholders took place in May 2024. We started our interviews with a representative of the cereal's office, who explained how the Tunisian cereals business works, from upstream (supply of inputs) to downstream (storage of cereals at collecting canters and marketing at flour mills).

Regarding cereal growers, we surveyed 16 farmers operating in the El-Krib Siliana living lab (el Krib delegation), a random sample was selected and focused on family farming.

Furthermore, we surveyed 3 cereal collection and storage center managers, 2 seed production companies and 1 flour mill.

Concerning the olive oil value chain, the main stakeholders involved in its functioning, are respectively:

- Olive oil growers
- Plants and inputs suppliers
- Olive processors

The interviews with the above-mentioned stakeholders took place in September 2024. We started our interviews with a representative of the National Office of Oil, who explained how the Tunisian olive oil business works, from upstream (supply of inputs) to downstream (processing units and marketing).

Regarding olive oil growers, we surveyed 15 farmers operating in the El-Krib Siliana living lab (el Krib delegation), a random sample was selected and focused on family farming.

Furthermore, we surveyed one plants and inputs suppliers and a unit of olive processing.

10.3 Value Chain Selection

The two selected value chains are respectively:

1. cereals
2. olive oil

As mentioned above, this choice was made following the results of the territorial diagnosis, which has shown that these two value chains have a strong agro-ecological potential and given that they are the most important crops in the territory, the bilateral meeting with the activity manager and validation by the internal project team and the living lab representative board.

As for olive oil, it is the second most important crop in the farming systems of the majority of farms surveyed, within the framework of the territorial diagnosis, in addition to its appearance in the future plans of the majority of farmers (including cereal growers) who wish to develop their agricultural activities.

10.4 Value Chain Mapping and Characterisation

10.4.1 Value Chain 1 (Cereals)

10.4.1.1 Introduction of the Value Chain

In Tunisia, cereals have a key economic and social role to perform. For instance, not only do they account for around 30% of the country's Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) and 9% of agricultural use, they also account for 50% of agricultural employment and staple food for the Tunisian population (Adapt, 2024).

Considering its importance, the cereals value chain is regulated by the government through the Cereals Office and the General Compensation Fund:

- Established in 1962, the Cereals Office has a monopoly on the purchase and local marketing of durum and common wheat, as well as on the import of most of these cereals for local consumption. It stores these cereals, through its authorized collectors, and supervises their marketing on Tunisian territory. It also sets selling prices for durum and common wheat at all

stages of the value chain, from production to marketing, and acts as a financial intermediary between the General Compensation Fund and the collecting and storage centers and the processors, mills and bakeries, for whom the State subsidizes sales transactions.

- The General Compensation Fund was launched in the 1970s to improve the population's nutrition through a system of government subsidies designed to reduce the cost of several basic foods, including cereal products (World Bank Report, 1996).

The 2022/2023 cereal campaign and the challenges facing the sector

For the 2022/2023 campaign, the planned cereal areas were 1.269 million hectares, of which 46% durum wheat and 48% barley. The dominance of these two cereals is explained by the fact that they are the best adapted to the country's soil and climate conditions.

According to data from the National Observatory for Agriculture (2024), 66% of the cereals growing area is located in the north of the country, and 44% in the center and south. In Tunisia, cereal growing remains essentially rain-fed, with only 2% of cereal acreage irrigated. Cereals are grown mainly in the north-west of the country, where rainfall is higher. This high dependence on rainfall makes cereal production highly variable, as it is profoundly influenced by the effects of climate change particularly drought and rising average temperatures, which are becoming increasingly frequent.

For the 2021-2022 season, durum wheat yields averaged 14.6 quintals per hectare. Although there are many constraints to production, water stress remains the main factor limiting durum wheat production, with periods of water shortage often coinciding with critical phases in the wheat growth cycle. This phenomenon was particularly noticeable in 2023, a year characterized by unprecedented drought when durum wheat harvests were the lowest in recent years. Production was 60% down on the previous campaign (Adapat, 2024).

As a result of this severe drought, 1/3 of the area seeded (around 300,000 ha) was not harvested, particularly in cereal-growing areas such as Kef, Siliana and Béja which have been declared drought-stricken (Decree no. 2023-616 of October 12, 2023, setting the drought-stricken arable crop zones for the 2022/2023 agricultural campaign). According to the Office des Céréales (2024), in Siliana only 1 230 quintals of durum wheat and 64 quintals of soft wheat were collected while no quintals have been collected for barley and triticale.

As mentioned in the previous section, climate change is not the only issue impacting durum wheat production in Tunisia. In fact, since 2020, the cost of chemical fertilizers has risen sharply, and this increase was reinforced in 2022 by the outbreak of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict. In Tunisia, even if the cost of fertilizers remains lower than international prices thanks to government intervention, the general increase in prices and the lack of availability of these inputs on the national market (since

they are largely imported from Russia) have contributed to increasing production costs. As a result, growers have been forced to limit their use of fertilizers, which may have had an impact on yields.

Given that cereals are the mainstay of the Tunisian diet (around 200 kg of cereals per person per year), the current situation is exposing Tunisia to increased dependence on wheat imports. This dependence on imports not only risks weighing heavily on the country's agricultural and agri-food trade balance but may also have an impact on its food security. Supporting cereal growers, and durum wheat growers in particular, is therefore an urgent priority (Adapt, 2024).

10.4.1.2 Value Chain Mapping

Figure 81: Value chain mapping for cereals in Siliana, Tunisia

The cereal value chain in Tunisia encompasses all the stages involved in the production, processing, and distribution of cereals. It involves a complex network of actors, each playing a critical role in ensuring that the cereals are produced, processed, and delivered to consumers efficiently. This value chain is influenced by both market dynamics and government policies, and it also faces challenges such as climate variability, access to finance, and infrastructure gaps.

The value chain is governed by the cereals office, which intervenes at all levels by setting the purchase and selling prices of seeds and cereals produced, and by subsidising cereal growers and collection centres (storage premium).

The value chain starts with input suppliers, who provide the necessary agricultural inputs, including seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and machinery. The collectors of cereals are also ensuring the function of input suppliers. The collection centres offer credit sales of various inputs (seeds, treatment products, fertilisers, etc.) to cereal growers. In return, the cereal growers undertake to deliver all their production to the said centres and pay their credits after delivery of the production (after harvesting).

Cereals are typically grown using both traditional methods (especially in rainfed areas) and more modern techniques, which may include irrigation and advanced machinery for large-scale production. Seeds are often sourced from local producers or imported, and the government or agricultural cooperatives sometimes provide technical support to farmers.

Downstream of the value chain, the collection centres deliver the cereals to the milling and semolina plants, which in turn supply the pasta and bakery industries, according to the quotas set by the Cereals Office in collaboration with the Ministry of Trade.

10.4.1.3 *Characterisation and Diagnosis*

The findings of interviews and surveys with stakeholders of the cereals value chain in the Living Lab of El Krib-Siliana are presented below.

10.4.1.3.1 *General overview of producer characteristics*

We surveyed 16 cereal producers with the following profiles:

- the majority of farmers surveyed were aged between 40 and 60, with a secondary education.
- they are mainly self-employed (not belonging to farmers' organizations or groups) and manage their farms by hiring seasonal labor, mainly during the seed and harvesting periods. Female labour is not widespread on cereal farms; whenever it is involved, it is the farmer's wife. More than 37% of farmers are owners and tenants and more than 81 % of lands were registered.
- more than half of the sample surveyed have farms of between 15- and 50 hectares in size.

- cereals remain the main activity for all farmers, but they may be associated with various other crops (livestock, legumes, fruit trees, etc.). In El Krib, our investigation showed that the agricultural activities practiced on the farm are dominated by a combined system of cereals, livestock and other crops with more than 56%. The other crops include olives, fodder crops legumes, fruit trees and vegetable crops.

Figure 82: The total area of the farm in El Krib, Tunisia

Figure 83 Land tenure in El Krib, Tunisia

Figure 84: Registration status of the land in El Krib, Tunisia

Figure 85: Agricultural activities practiced in El Krib, Tunisia

10.4.1.3.2 Overview of value chain production

An analysis of the cereals value chain status on the different exploitations surveyed shows that:

- For the majority of farmers, cereals occupy 20-50% of the total area

Figure 86: Cereals as part of the total area in El Krib Tunisia

- Cereal crops account for more than half of total farm production.
- As shown by the figure, for more than 62% of farmers, cereals are fully marketed (between 80 to 100%). The proportion that is not marketed is used for household consumption, donations between family members and neighbours, or may be used in part to supply seed for the forthcoming season.

Figure 87: Part of the cereals marketed in El Krib, Tunisia

- Finally, the main agro-ecological practices identified are crop rotation, the use of manure, and the use of native crops.

10.4.1.3.3 Producer market characteristics and market strategies

As illustrated in the figure below, for the major part of the farmers surveyed (around 44%), cereals account for more than 50% of total sales.

Figure 88: Part of cereals in total sales of the farm in El Krib, Tunisia

For most cereal growers, the level of profits made is very unstable (fluctuating wildly), with a decrease of 10 to 30%. This is essentially due to changing weather conditions, drought, lack of rainfall and the availability and price of various inputs.

All the farmers surveyed confirm that they have no difficulty accessing the market and that there is no competition between them (they generally use the same seed varieties and sell on the regional market of Siliana, under the same conditions).

For all cereal growers, the main marketing channels adopted are the collecting centers managed by the cereal's office. Cereals are shipped in bulk to collection centers. This option is motivated by the following considerations:

- This is a guaranteed market operated by the cereal's office (managing collection centres, setting sales prices and quality-based payment).
- Credit purchase of inputs and payment after harvest (informal/verbal commitment with collection centres).
- Harvest pick-up from farmers: transport provided by collection centres, not by farmers' own means.

Downstream of the value chain, the cereals collecting and stockholding center supplies flour mills and semi-flour mills, with the agreement of the cereal's office (the operator authorized to manage the value chain).

10.4.1.3.4 Value chain governance and decision-making power

The cereals value chain is extremely multifaceted, with five main components: seed production, production of cereals for consumption, collection, storage, and processing and distribution. Each of these various elements plays a decisive function in the value chain (ONAGRI, 2020).

In Tunisia, the cereals value chain is managed by the cereal's office, which has a monopolistic status.

The main duties of the cereal's office are as and when required:

- Supplying the country with local and imported cereals.
- Organizing and monitoring the cereals market.
- Supervising and ensuring the quality of grain collection.
- Building up and safeguarding strategic stocks of cereals and controlled barley.
- Ensuring a public service role.

The storage platform, with a total capacity of 5.1 million quintals, is mainly made up of storage and port grain elevators located in consumption areas. This structure is organized as follows:

- **Seaport storage silos:** with a total capacity of 0.8 million quintals, shared equally between the Rades and Gabes elevators, with 0.3 million quintals each, while the Bizerte elevator has a capacity of 0.1 million quintals.
- **Fallback storage silos:** with a total capacity of 4.3 million quintals, distributed across different regions of the country.

The key stakeholders in the cereals value chain, under the control of the cereals board, are respectively:

1. Farmers: Cereal growers are motivated only by guaranteed sales of their produce (Obligation to sell to collection centers managed by the cereal's office). Farmers are not connected by any formal organization, apart from the Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fishing (UTAP), which gives them access to subsidies. Nevertheless, there may be some informal relationships may exist, namely:

- Exchanging or donating seeds, mainly in times of shortage
- Mutual assistance at sowing or threshing time

2. Collectors: As part of the gradual liberalization of trading activities of a competitive nature, and to encourage private initiative, several professional structures have been involved in grain collection since 2005. In El Krib Siliana Living Lab territory, there are 3 collectors (Comptoir Multiservices Agricoles CMA, Société "Collecte Céréalière du Nord" COCENORD and Compagnie Tunisienne des Activités Agricoles CTA).

3. Processing units: Milling covers 2 main activities: flour milling and semolina milling. Private-sector semolina mills are responsible for producing flour and semolina from soft and durum wheat, mainly for bread and pastry flour, pasta and couscous. The number of active semolina mills currently stands at 23, located in different regions of the country, mainly in consumer areas.

The pricing system is regulated at all stages (production, collection, retrocession, consumption, transport, etc.). The evolution of both producer and consumer prices is decided according to the economic situation and takes into account social aspects and the purchasing power of citizens.

The intervention of the public authorities via the cereal's office guarantees food security (availability, access, and quality) the protection of the environment (availability, access, and quality), and a regular, uninterrupted supply of cereals for consumption (ONAGRI, 2020).

10.4.2 Value Chain 2 (Olive Oil)

10.4.2.1 Introduction of the value chain

Tunisia has a long-standing tradition of olive cultivation, dating back to ancient times, and it is one of the world's leading producers and exporters of olive oil. The country's favorable Mediterranean climate, with its mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers, is ideal for olive growing. Olive trees thrive in the arid and semi-arid regions of the country, making it a key agricultural product for Tunisia.

Olive oil production:

Olive oil production is a crucial part of the national agricultural economy, contributing significantly to rural livelihoods and employment. Olive growing, is one of Tunisia's main agricultural activities. In 2017, with around 82 million olive trees, the country's olive groves cover 41% of the cultivated area, accounting for almost 70% of all tree-growing land. In 2017, this corresponds to around 1.668 million hectares of olive groves out of a total of 2.3857 million hectares devoted to arboriculture. In 2023, according to DGPA the total area of Tunisian olive growing is estimated at 2 million ha covered by approximately 107 million olive trees (ONAGRI, 2023).

Around 309000 people are involved in oil olive production in Tunisia, representing 60% of all workers in the agricultural sector. It is worth noting that the olive harvest remains strongly marked by the participation of women, who account for almost 90% of the harvesting workforce.

95% of olives are grown under rainfed conditions. Central Tunisia and its governorates account for 65% of this area, while the South accounts for 18% (PARM, 2024).

According to data from the Ministry of Agriculture and Hydraulic Resources (2023), oil olive production is on an upward trend, but remains characterized by strong annual variation inherent in the crop's predominantly dry cultivation and consequent dependence on rainfall.

Over the last five years (2019-2023), average olive production in Tunisia has been around 1,100 thousand tonnes, with a production record in 2020 of 2,000 thousand tonnes thanks to favorable climatic conditions. In comparison, the annual average for the period 2014-2018 was 983,000 tonnes.

Figure 89: Growth of olive oil production in Tunisia (1000 tons).
Source: Farm, based on MAHR data (2023)

Olive oil processing:

In Tunisia, olive processing is carried out by a total of 1,625 oil presses, according to Ministry of Agriculture data for the 2023/2024 crop season.

Oil processors handle olives from their own production or those delivered to them by collectors (olive growers or intermediate suppliers). The duration of the processing campaign varies from 30 to 40 days during periods of low production to 90 to 120 days during periods of higher production.

Tunisia has a total of 1,714 listed oil mills, of which 933 are traditional super-press oil mills and 781 are continuous system oil mills. Theoretically, the total number of oil mills ensures a transformation of around 51,116 tonnes per day. It should be noted that 80.8% of the total crushing capacity is provided by continuous chain oil mills. The geographical distribution of oil mills is dominated by the south (Sfax, Medenine, Gabes, Tataouine, Kebili, Tozeur) and the Sahel (Sousse, Monastir, Mahdia) which represent respectively 36.2 and 32.2% of the number of oil mills in Tunisia. The center (Kasserine, Kairouan, Sidi Bouzid, Gafsa) in turn has 18% of the oil mills followed by the north (Tunis, Manouba, Ariana, Ben Arous, Bizerte, Beja, Jendouba, Le Kef, Siliana, Zaghouan, Nabeul) with 13.6% (Fendri et al., 2020). Olive oil production matches the production of oil olives, and the average extraction rate in Tunisia is around 20%. Olive processing capacity for oil production has increased significantly. According to the Industry and Innovation Promotion Agency (APII), it has risen from around 23,000 tonnes per day in 1998 to 34,000 tonnes per day in 2018. This increase in capacity, combined with the modernization of equipment, has reduced the waiting time for olive processing and contributed to a significant improvement in the average quality of olive oils, a crucial aspect for export (APII, 2018).

Figure 90: Growth of olive oil production in Tunisia (1000 tons)
Source: Farm based on MAHR and COI Data (2023)

Local consumption and exports:

While the major part of Tunisia's olive oil production is exported, local consumption remains quite low at around 30,000 tonnes per year. On the local market, self-consumption and direct purchases from oil factories or through informal channels predominate. Per capita consumption in Tunisia has fallen to between 3.5 to 4 kg per year, mainly due to the higher price of olive oil compared to other vegetable oils such as sunflower and corn, as well as the subsidization of soybean oil (PARM, 2024).

Tunisia's export policy for agricultural and agri-food products depends largely on the role fulfilled by olive oil, which is by far the country's leading agricultural and agri-food export. In 2022, olive oil sales generated revenues of around 824 million USD, representing 38% of food export revenues and 3.6% of the country's total exports. Olive oil exports to the European Union alone account for almost 24% of the country's agricultural and agri-food exports and remain the most important source of income for the country (PARM, 2024). In 2022, olive oil exports reached 208 thousand tons, of which 87% were in bulk and 13% were packaged. The share of organic olive oil is around 25% (ONAGRI, 2023 according to data from Tunisian Customs, DGAB, 2023). During the period between 2011 and 2022, exports fluctuated significantly, ranging between 93 thousand tons and 373 thousand tons, with an average of 228 thousand tons recorded over the last 5 years (ONAGRI, 2023 according to data from INS and Tunisian Customs, 2023).

10.4.2.2 Mapping of the value chain

Figure 91: Mapping of the olive oil value chain in Siliana, Tunisia

The olive oil value chain in Tunisia is one of the most important agricultural value chains in the country, as Tunisia is one of the world's largest producers and exporters of olive oil. The sector involves multiple actors, ranging from smallholder farmers to large processing companies, and it is heavily influenced by both domestic and international markets, agricultural policies, and environmental factors. The value chain includes the cultivation of olives, the processing of olive oil, distribution, and export.

The government plays a key role in regulating and supporting the olive oil sector through policies that promote production, improve quality standards, and facilitate exports. The government also provides subsidies and technical support to farmers, as well as investing in infrastructure. This role is ensured by the National Office of Oil (NOO).

Upstream, suppliers of inputs and olive plants provide olive growers. These farmers have the option of either:

- selling the production of olives on the farm, thereby avoiding all the financial costs associated with harvesting and crushing the olives.
- selling the olives after gathering to oil presses.

- gathering their production and bear all the costs of processing and marketing the olive oil.

Downstream of the value chain, processors can sell the oil to the local consumers (on the regional or the national markets) or export production in compliance with the guidelines laid down by the national oil office

10.4.2.3 *Characterisation and Diagnosis*

Olive oil is one of Tunisia's main agricultural products and a strategic export for the country. From upstream to downstream of the olive oil value chain, the stakeholders involved in the functioning of the value chain are essentially:

a- Olive growers (producers) are mostly private actors (small or large olive farms spread throughout the country (mainly in olive growing regions such as the north-west, centre and south of Tunisia). Only one public operator is involved in olive production in Tunisia, the state lands office (a public organisation which manages land belonging to the State).

b- Processors, also private operators. The processing units produce oil of different qualities (virgin, extra virgin, lampante, etc.) which is either sold on the local market in bulk, bottled or exported.

c- Consumption: this involves marketing the oil locally or abroad (export).

d- The National Office of Oil: a public institution whose role is to manage the functioning of the value chain by subsidising upstream olive growers (supply of certain inputs), assisting processors (hygiene rules and good quality control practices), storing olive oil and marketing it (purchase of olive oil).

The findings of interviews and surveys with stakeholders of the olive oil value chain in the Living Lab of El Krib-Siliana are presented below.

10.4.2.3.1 *General overview of producer characteristics*

We have surveyed 15 olive oil producers with the following profiles:

- the majority of farmers surveyed were aged between 40 and 60, with a primary education.
- they are mainly self-employed (not belonging to farmers' organizations or groups) and manage their farms by hiring seasonal labour, mainly during the harvesting periods. Female labour is very widespread on olive oil farms (between 20 and 60 women per exploitation); 40% of farmers are owners and more than 90 % of lands were registered as shown in the below figures.
- more than half of the sample surveyed have farms of between 15 and 50 hectares in size.
- Olive oil production is an important activity for all farmers, but they may be associated with various other crops (livestock, legumes, fruit trees, etc.). In El Krib, our investigation showed that the

agricultural activities practiced on the farm of olive oil producers are dominated by a combined system of olives, cereals, livestock and other crops (33.3%) that may include fodder crops legumes, fruit trees and vegetable crops. On all the farms, the current dominant cropping systems are cereals in association with olive trees, followed by cereals in association with fodder crops and cereal monocultures. Livestock is raised on most farms. It is a characteristic and a heritage of the region.

Figure 92: Land tenure in El Krib Tunisia

Figure 93: Land Status in El Krib, Tunisia

Figure 94: Farm size distribution in El Krib, Tunisia

Figure 95: Farm agricultural activity of olive oil producers in El Krib, Tunisia

10.4.2.3.2 Overview of value chain production

An analysis of olive oil value chain status on the different exploitations surveyed shows that:

- For 40% of farmers olive oil occupies more than 50% of the total area while 33% of them olive oil activity constitutes less than 20% of the total area.

Figure 96: Olive oil as part of total size in El Krib, Tunisia

- Olive oil account for more than half of total farm production.
- As shown by the below figure, for 40% of farmers, olive oil is fully marketed (between 80 to 100%). The proportion that is not marketed is used for self-consumption, donations between family members and neighbours.

Figure 97: Percentage of olive oil trading in El Krib, Tunisia

- Finally, the main agro-ecological practices identified are crop rotation, the use of manure, and the grazing.

Figure 98: Agroecological practices adopted by the surveyed olive oil producers in El Krib, Tunisia

10.4.2.3.3 Producer market characteristics and market strategies

For most olive oil growers, the level of profits made is very unstable (fluctuating wildly), with an increase of 10 to 30%. This is mainly due to the increase in olive oil selling prices over the past five years.

All the surveyed farmers confirm that they have no difficulty accessing the market and that there is no competition between them (they generally use the same plant varieties and sell their products at almost the same price).

For all olive oil growers, three marketing channels are offered:

- **sale of standing crops:** farmers adopt this option to avoid the financial costs of gathering, transporting and processing olives. It allows them a level of financial flexibility and the possibility of saving on expenses.
- **sale of olives gathered at oil presses:** farmers are responsible for collecting the olives, incurring all the associated costs, and then selling the produce to oil manufacturers. This option is motivated by the convenience it offers farmers, who avoid the costs of storing and marketing the final product to consumers.
- **Sale of oil to final consumers:** farmers gather their production of olive oil and support the cost related to transportation and processing and they recover the oil after olive processing to sell it to final consumers (in Siliana or in urban areas like greater Tunis, Nabeul and Sousse). This marketing option is mainly chosen by large-scale growers with a certain degree of financial autonomy and final customers who are accustomed to buying from them.

10.4.2.3.4 Value chain governance and decision-making power

The olive oil value chain in Tunisia is characterized by a mix of smallholder farming, cooperatives, and private sector actors, with governance and decision-making power dispersed across different stages of production and distribution. While there is increasing government support and international recognition, challenges remain in terms of market access, quality control, and the power dynamics between small producers and larger actors in the value chain. In Tunisia, the olive oil value chain is managed by the national office of oil, which has a monopolistic status.

The National Office of Oil (NOO) operates on three levels.

- First of all, it is involved in the production of olive trees through phytosanitary treatment. Then there is the distribution of fertilizers, which are subsidized up to 20%, in addition to the subsidy of harvesting equipment.
- The second level of intervention concerns quality. At the Office National Office of Oil (NOO), skills in quality improvement were developed, thanks in particular to the training provided by an international training center, which is geared towards quality improvement. This is an important point, given that most of the national production is destined for export.
- Finally, the third level is market regulation and export development. On the export front, NOO is currently promoting the quality of Tunisian oil.

10.4.3 General information's about the selected value chains

10.4.3.1 Certification

Most cereals growers interviewed have a good knowledge of certifications (organic, Protected Geographical Indication, etc.) either through information days and/or training courses. However, only one farmer in the interview sample claimed to be adopting a certification.

Farmers' unwillingness to adopt certifications is explained by the fact that they see no benefit in it, since the products are not acknowledged on the market. On the other side, selling prices to collection centers are the same as for conventional products, and final consumers are not sufficiently informed about the availability of certified products and their added value.

Olive Oil producers share the same position about certification as for the cereal ones. They consider the selling prices very interesting actually, so there's no hurry to adopt certification.

10.4.3.2 Focus on collective efforts, short-circuit markets, and direct contact with consumers

The farmers surveyed are mostly self-employed, managing their farms directly by themselves, calling on seasonal labour when needed, and depending on the campaign: during the harvest of cereals, market garden crops (tomatoes, watermelons, etc.), etc. As shown in the graph below, only one of the 16 farmers surveyed belong to a farmers' group which it's an association of a number of farmers (maximum 100 farmers) in order to collaborate together for purchasing inputs, exchanging materials, dialogue with governmental institutes.

Figure 99: Farmers' status in El Krib, Tunisia

As mentioned above (paragraph related to the producer market characteristics and market strategies), there are no short marketing channels for cereals. Farmers prefer to hand over all their production to the collection centers run by the cereal's office.

As regard to the olive oil value chain the graph below shows that only one of the 15 farmers surveyed belong to a farmers' group.

Figure 100: Status of interviewed farmers in El Krib, Tunisia

However, all the farmers surveyed belong to the regional agricultural and Fisheries Union, which is a syndicate organization enabling them to access the subsidies and support provided by the government.

We also notice the number of informal relationships between the farmers surveyed:

- Seed donations/sales (mainly in scarcity periods),
- Mutual assistance during planting (soil preparation, borrowing farm equipment, etc.)
- Gathering and transport of olives to processing units,
- Harvesting and transport of cereals to collection centers, etc.

10.4.3.3 Motivation and Quality/value perception of producers

At this level, it is important to point out that the only motivation for the farmers surveyed to adopt agroecological practices lies in the fact that these practices enable them to improve soil quality (through the use of manure, crop rotations, etc.). However, these practices are not well recognized in Tunisia and even if the quality of agroecological products can be better, farmers are not motivated to explore this avenue, since the yields of agroecological crops are often lower than those from conventional agriculture.

In addition, even cereal collectors do not consider the adoption of agroecological practices as an opportunity for their activities (cereal collection and storage), since there are no specific measures for

these products and the purchase prices of cereals is the same, the same goes for the storage bonus granted to them.

The situation is similar for olive oil producers: processing units do not consider the adoption of agroecological practices as an opportunity for their activities, since there are no specific measures for these products.

10.4.3.4 *Barriers and opportunities to production and market access*

Concerning the supply of inputs, the main constraints encountered by the farmers surveyed are essentially:

- Seed availability (especially the last season) and poor quality (sometimes)
- Very high prices and unavailability of inputs
- The increase in production costs (Cost of Labour and various inputs)
- Poor and degraded soil (hence low yields)
- Limited access (sometimes impossibility) to financing the activity

Climate risks such as drought, lack of precipitation, hail, etc. also constitute increasingly accentuated constraints, limiting the development of cereal and olive oil farming.

10.4.3.5 *Interactions with other value chains*

Integrated farming systems, combining crop and livestock production, increase the quantity of products generated. They allow crop residues to be used to produce meat, milk and other goods, while manure is produced to improve the fertility and quality of the cultivated soil. From an economic perspective, the coordination of crop and livestock production provides a level of autonomy for the technical system and reduces dependence on input markets (Souissi et al., 2024).

The farming systems identified in Siliana show the interaction of cereals with other agricultural activities, in particular, livestock, forage crops, and fruit trees (mainly oil olives and almonds). This association of agricultural activities is justified by the fact that:

- farmers benefit from cereal residues, after threshing, for feeding and grazing their herds,
- the manure will be used by farmers as a soil improver, helping to maintain soil fertility and finally,
- fruit growing will enable them to improve their incomes.

10.4.3.6 *Agroecological diagnosis and potential*

The challenges facing cereal growing in El-Krib provide an opportunity for the value chain to switch to agro-ecology. Indeed, climate change (reduced rainfall, high levels of heat, drought, etc.), the non-availability of inputs (fertilizers, seeds, etc.) and their very high costs, as well as the deterioration in soil and groundwater quality, all encourage the adoption of agro-ecological practices that preserve the environmental and socio-economic conditions. Otherwise, Tunisia's olive oil sector is a cornerstone of its agricultural economy, with the country being one of the largest global producers and exporters of olive oil. The agroecological potential of Tunisia's olive oil value chain refers to the capacity of its natural resources, ecosystems, and agricultural practices to support and enhance the sustainable production of olive oil while maintaining or improving the health of its environment and rural communities.

Our investigation showed a set of practices that are already adopted by growers in El Krib, including mainly the use of manure, crop rotation, animal grazing, and the incorporation of Indigenous crops.

In addition, farmers are more aware of the need to adopt agro-ecological practices that promote better conditions and enable them to water and soil quality, and consequently their yields and production levels. The shift towards direct sowing (no-till), the combination of legumes (for nitrogen fertilization of the soil) and livestock (to take advantage of the manure) demonstrates this willingness to adopt agro-ecological practices.

10.4.4 Main recommendations for the reinforcement of agroecological potential in the selected value chains

Despite its important role in Siliana's agricultural farming system, and given its socio-economic impact, the cereal and olive oil value chains face many functional problems, in addition to the climatic risks that make farmer's work more difficult. Thus, farmers (mainly the smallest among them) are facing a range of issues when it comes to financing their activities, particularly in terms of input supplies. Added to this is the degradation of soil quality and water resources. In addition to the climatic hazards that make the job of the above-mentioned farmers more challenging, the two value chains suffer numerous functional issues despite their significant position in El-Krib's agricultural farming system and socioeconomic impact.

In order to build farmers' capacity and encourage them to move towards agroecology, we need to:

- Raise awareness and train farmers in good farming practices (use of manure, direct sowing, waste recycling, etc.)
- Facilitate the supply of seeds, plants and inputs (through micro-credit and payment arrangements)

- Promote agroecological products among collection centers and final consumers to guarantee opportunities for farmers and enhance the value of their products on the market.
- Increase awareness and provide farmers with training in appropriate agricultural techniques (use of manure, waste recycling, etc.) in order to increase farmers' capacity and motivate them to transition to agroecology.
- Encourage the sale of agroecological products to processors and end users in order to provide farmers with opportunities and raise the market value of their goods.

10.5 Conclusion and Recapitulation of Main Results

In Tunisia, where dryland areas predominate, the ongoing implementation of the Agroecology initiative provides the context for this study, which explores the drivers and barriers of agroecological transformation in this challenging environment. The research focuses on stakeholder engagement, to explore farmer perceptions. The study, conducted in Siliana El Krib Living Lab, involved questionnaires with various stakeholders of cereals and olive oil value chains. Findings highlight farmer s' potential in promoting sustainable farming, with clear goals, diversified systems, and collaborations. However, challenges such as input scarcity, water shortage, low income, and marketing must be addressed.

Results also indicate that the two selected value chain as having an interesting potential for agroecological transformation, but it faces constraints such as climate, lack of policy incentives, training, funding, and difficulty in adopting technical innovations. Despite these obstacles, key drivers for agroecological transition were identified. These include the compatibility of many agroecological practices with existing farmer capabilities, their cultural and economic benefits, and the positive outcomes for environmental sustainability and health.

In conclusion, to build resilience, all involved stakeholders must

- **Adopt Drought-Resistant Olive Varieties:** Invest in research to identify and propagate olive tree varieties that are more resistant to dry conditions and pests, ensuring long-term production even in arid environments.
- **Improve Irrigation Efficiency:** Implement water-efficient irrigation systems, such as drip irrigation, to optimize water use in olive orchards. Promote the use of rainwater harvesting systems and the recycling of water in farming.
- **Agroecological Practices:** Encourage the adoption of agroecological practices that enhance soil health and biodiversity, such as crop rotation, intercropping, organic farming, and mulching. These practices help preserve ecosystems and make farming more resilient to extreme weather conditions.

PART 2

Consumer behaviour analysis of agroecological value chains in North Africa

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PART 2. CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR ANALYSIS OF AGROECOLOGICAL VALUE CHAINS IN NORTH AFRICA

Part 2 Summary

Over the past few years, the increasing global demand for food that is healthy, sustainable, and ethically produced has triggered a shift in consumer behaviour, particularly in emerging nations where environmental and economic pressures intersect food security concerns. In North Africa, a region marked both by vast agricultural potential and socio-economic vulnerability, research on consumer behaviour has become critical to promoting sustainable consumption patterns and AE transitions. This part seeks to offer a more complete understanding of consumer awareness, environmental attitudes, and willingness to pay (WTP) for agroecologically produced food in five North African countries (Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Mauritania and Tunisia).

Through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and multiple linear regression models, this part highlights the key socio-economic and perceptual variables that shape consumer behaviour. Results reveal the effects of environmental concern, importance of AE knowledge, education, age and income levels on consumers' WTP behaviour. Through this deeper five-country assessment, this section reveals interesting insights for food processors, policymakers, and marketers who want to encourage more sustainable food systems in the region. It sheds light on not only the similarities, but also the main differences in attitudes among consumers, and points to country-specific drivers and barriers to be addressed in future policy and marketing efforts.

Chapter 11

Introduction and Context for Consumer Behaviour Assessment

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Chapter 11. Consumer behaviour assessment in North Africa

11.1 Introduction for Consumer Behaviour Assessment in North Africa

Predicted food consumption by 2050 is 50% higher, so there is great need to raise farm-to-fork production (Berners-Lee et al., 2018). Although, since intensive agriculture already harms earth system, productivity increases have to be in line with environmental objectives. Operating via biogeochemical cycling alteration, greenhouse gas release, severe biodiversity loss, and soil degradation particularly in North Africa by 45% (Ernst et al., 2024). Through pesticide and chemical residues in food products, conventional farming also has indirect harmful effects on human health (Pathak et al., 2022). As they are sustainable and flexible, food value chain especially food processing can offer protection and answers for the environmental and health concerns (Tsironi et al., 2021). According to (Pawlak & Kołodziejczak, 2020), agriculture is the primary industry where all the above listed problems intersect; so, innovative ideas must be applied in agricultural systems to guarantee food security and safeguard the environment. Agroecology is a method that examines all the various aspects for human, plants, animals, and environment, in addition to the interactions that occur in between, these lead to achievement of sustainability in environmental resources and food products (Altieri, n.d.; Chaudhary et al., 2023). Through integrated techniques that shortens several sectors, it helps SDGs. Apart from SDGs, AE works to achieve biological variety and aims to meet Paris climate accord targets (FAO, 2018).

Though there was a rise in food products lately, reduction of natural resources, population growth, and new diseases created a major issue that caused competition whereby richer people, particularly in developing nations, have more access to high quality and nutritious food than others (Fróna et al., 2019). Narrowing the focus to emerging nations like Near East and North Africa area based on (FAO, 2023), Food Policy Monitoring indicated in 2023 that almost 13% of the population (about 60 million people) were deemed as undernourished. Apart from the limited availability of sustainable healthy products, this is connected to many issues in the region influencing consumer behaviour. For instance, only 40,000 ha was certified as organic land in 2008 in Egypt, representing 1.1% of the total agricultural land (Mohamed & Shelaby, 2012). It only rose to 3% in 2021, emphasizing that most of the land belongs to large-scale farmers who export the majority of the output. The rest of the small or large-scale local farmers, therefore, have limited access to technology, market and knowledge required to carry out AEP (Mohamed & Shelaby, 2012).

North African countries, especially Tunisia, Morocco, Mauritania, Algeria, and Egypt, face challenges in adopting environmental stressors due to geographical limitations, the low adoption of sustainable agriculture and low access to technology (Requier-Desjardins et al., 2024). As a result, for decades stakeholders in the agri-food system of the region prioritized traditional practices of production to

increase productivity and profit (Stempfle et al., 2024). Such majority systems often rely on monoculture, high levels of mechanisation, intense application of agro-chemical inputs and large-scale mass production, all of which propel ignoring the sustainment of the environment and the need for food at future needs (Elouattassi et al., 2023).

These issues make it important to refocus on consumer needs regarding this type of products. Consumer behaviour is very important in North Africa because how people consume food impacts how food is processed, transported, and produced. By calling for a market for sustainably produced food, consumers can help catalyze a system-wide change to healthier, more sustainable ways of producing food, creating a market for these foods (Kennedy et al., 2023). First and foremost is to understand how can we characterize and incentivize shifts in food consumers toward agroecological products relative to their more strategic impact on food processing and sustainable development across North Africa, as AEP offer potential pathways to match these emerging demands.

11.2 Literature review for consumer behaviour towards agroecological products

The following literature review section reports the main findings of the systematic review conducted within the NATAE project (Deliverable D3.3), which focused on the nutritional benefits of AEP and their influence on consumer behaviour. The knowledge summarized here reflects key themes and evidence identified in 122 peer-reviewed studies reviewed in this deliverable.

Academic research has emphasized mainly in environmental and production outcomes, a growing area of literature addresses several relevant, still overlaps exist between AE and consumer behaviour. The literature review focuses largely on whether areas apply AEP that impact consumers' purchasing decisions, perceptions of nutritional quality, or health consciousness. The systematic literature review within D3.3 of the NATAE project shows that consumers are increasingly shifting towards food products that are sustainable, ethically made and health-promoting (Berki-Kiss & Menrad, 2022; Mehrabi et al., 2022; Radulescu, Violeta et al., 2012; Tsakiridou, Efthimia, Tsiamparli & Mattas, 2016). Moreover, consumers are increasingly turn away from conventional products and organic or sustainable products which they associate with higher nutritional value, environmental impact and high ethical production standards (Pereira et al., 2023). These changing preferences reflects not only on the personal values of consumers, but they also show a larger push for food systems that produce sustainable ecological and social outcomes.

The systematic literature review identified four broad thematic clusters in the literature:

- a. Consumer behaviour and decision-making process: emphasizing WTP, food preferences, and sociopsychological variables like educational level, income, and perceived value of the product (Mazzocchi et al., 2021; Rossi et al., 2023; Śmiglak-Krajewska et al., 2020).
- b. Sustainability and environmental concerns: highlight the connection between food choices and issues like climate change, biodiversity and carbon footprint (de Graaf et al., 2016; Gerini et al., 2016; Predieri et al., 2023; Stiles William, 2017; Tsakiridou et al., 2010).
- c. Health and environmental responsibility: emphasizing the interaction between health motivations and packaging perceptions in environmentally friendly consumption (Pais et al., 2022; Petrescu & Vermeir, 2019; Radulescu, Violeta et al., 2012; Tsakiridou, Efthimia, Tsiamparli & Mattas, 2016).
- d. Ethical consumption: responsible consumption, animal welfare, food security, fight against food waste, nutrition in the context of ethics of consumer choice (Berki-Kiss & Menrad, 2022; Ghvanidze et al., 2016; Sciarelli et al., 2021; Zander & Hamm, 2010)

Despite increasing consumer demand for sustainable food, the review also identifies key challenges to broader uptake of AE products, regarding the knowledge of availability, higher prices and the low public awareness of AE nutritional and environmental benefits (Srinivasan et al., 2024; van Bussel et al., 2022). The nutritional value of AEP, higher micronutrient content, lower chemical residues, and increased dietary diversity, are important factors which have an impact in consumer behaviour (Mahendra Wisnu W & Basrowi, 2024; Wang, 2024). The number of peer-reviewed articles that cited AEP was very small, suggesting a gap in terminology and awareness even within the academic literature.

In addition, a lot of previous studies indicated that demographic factors such as consumers age, gender and education have an important impact on food choices with regard to sustainability (Korte et al., 2023; Martinez et al., 2023; Wezel et al., 2018). Purchasers who are younger and more educated ones tend to express more preference for ethical and environmentally friendly products. Marketing effectiveness and eco-labeling also help to build confidence in consumers and at the same time influence purchase decisions (Galati et al., 2022; Heerman & Sheldon, 2022; Higgins et al., 2020; Jo et al., 2019).

From the review has emerged that there is a need for more research on consumers and AE products in order to better understand how AEP can better align with their preferences, mainly in particular in geographical areas with low presence such as North Africa. By integrating both the nutritional and environmental benefits of AEP into future policies and marketing interventions, we can begin to study more consumer demand for sustainable products, that show the way towards a food system that serves both human and plant health.

11.3 Objectives

Within this framework, this section aims primarily at assessing consumer behaviour as regards to AE products and sustainable food consumption in North African countries (Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, and Mauritania). Based on data generated in these five countries, the report seeks to unpack the main socio-demographic and perceptual drivers of consumer awareness, preference and WTP for agroecologically produced food. More precisely, the report also seeks to identify regional commonalities and divergences in consumer behaviour and the implications of those for food processing, marketing and policy across North Africa. Finally, this study intends to yield results that inform larger processes that may foster sustainable consumption patterns, agroecological transitions, and overall, resilience of food houses in the region.

Three main sub-objectives emerge based on the literature review in order to fully capture consumer trends and habits in the five participating countries of North Africa in the NATAE project. The first sub-objective is to investigate the extent to which the environmental pillar of sustainability and the depletion of natural resources concern consumers. At the same time, the social factor that aims to ensure a high standard of living must be studied, as well as the economic factor that aims to purchase and consume environmentally friendly products. Secondly, this study examines the extent to which, from the perspective of consumers, biodiversity and other sustainable practices influence their consumption decisions. The third objective is to examine whether food security aspects and beliefs about food safety influence the decisions of participating consumers.

Based on the aforementioned sub-objectives, three basic hypotheses were selected and examined in the context of consumer behaviour research: a) what are the main factors that influence consumer behaviour towards AE products, b) to what extent is environmental concern but also concern for their health a factor that influences the purchase of AE food and c) to what extent are consumers WTP a premium price to seek out and purchase AE products.

11.4 Methodology

11.4.1 Theoretical background

To design the appropriate questionnaire that would help to outline all the factors that influence North African consumers regarding the purchase and consumption of organic foods, the following models were used:

11.4.1.1 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), proposed by Ajzen (1991), which serves as one of the most widely used models for understanding and predicting human behaviour, mainly for understanding the consumer decision-making process (Ajzen, 1991). Based on this theory, a consumer's behaviour is directly influenced by their intentions, which in turn are shaped by their attitude towards a particular behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Figure 101). Therefore, this model was used to investigate consumers' intentions around AE products, their opinions and evaluations of these foods, and their confidence and ability to seek and purchase them. The questionnaire was designed to include the above in combination with the respondents' beliefs about social norms, their environmental attitudes, and the perceived ease or difficulty of purchasing AE foods. In this way, we will better understand what motivates consumer decisions, especially among consumers interested in switching from consuming conventional foods to consuming AE products.

Figure 101: Theory of Planned Behaviour

11.4.1.2 Model of Responsible Environmental Behaviour (REB)

The model of Responsible Environmental Behaviour (REB) is based on the fact that both cognitive (rational) and emotional reactions of consumers play a very important role in consumer behaviour (Goldman et al., 2020). Based on this model, consumers evaluate the products they will purchase based on logical reasoning (such as evaluating the price of the product, its nutritional value and the impact on the environment) but also on emotions that arise such as guilt, empathy, concern, etc

(Figure 102). The use of the model is important as it simplifies the consumer decision-making process regarding environmental protection and consumer concerns, ethical consumption and animal welfare and sustainability. The questionnaire included questions based on this model to examine rational and emotional stimuli simultaneously. For example, questions related to the health benefits and environmental impacts of using AE foods relate to the rational domain. Correspondingly, questions related to the emotional satisfaction of supporting local producers or anxiety about environmental degradation affect the emotional dimension. In this way, the reasons and factors that influence North African consumers towards or away from AE products are examined more comprehensively.

Figure 102: Model of Responsible Environmental Behaviour (REB)

11.4.1.3 Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) model

The Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) model attempts to examine all stimuli that come from both the external and internal environment of consumers and strongly influence their final consumer decision (Hetharie et al., 2019). More specifically, the external factors called stimuli are all the external information that consumers receive both from their social environment (friends, family, social groups), as well as from the various marketing strategies from the promotion of AE products. These external stimuli influence the second pillar of the SOR model, which is the organism, i.e. the consumer himself. At this stage, the influence of internal factors (demographic, psychological, cultural and social) is also observed, which equally influence their decisions as they affect the cognitive and emotional state of consumers. In the final stage of the model (the decision stage), a final consumer decision is made (choice of product, brand and point of purchase) and the reaction of consumers after the purchase is also examined (Figure 103). This model is particularly useful in the formulation of the questionnaire,

as all the stimuli that influence the formation of the final consumer decision are examined. The “organism” component includes internal reactions such as trust, perceived value of an environmental product or emotional intention, while the “response” focuses on the stated willingness to purchase or recommend such products. Based on the above, this model thus helps to capture the dynamic relationship between environmental indicators and consumer behaviour.

Figure 103: Stimulus Organism Response (SOR) model

11.4.2 Questionnaire design

The questionnaire used in this study consists of 45 questions and is structured in five distinct sections, each designed to capture critical dimensions of consumer behaviour related to AE products (Appendix G). The first section includes questions on the demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of consumers with 9 questions related to gender, age, education level, income and the number of people in the household. There is also a question in this section regarding whether consumers live in an urban, peri-urban or rural environment. These questions aim to group consumers according to and in

correlation with the answers they will give to the remaining categories of questions. The second section includes questions about the level of concern of respondents about various environmental issues. For example, participants were asked about their awareness of climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution and reduction of natural resources.

The next section (third) explores consumers' environmental attitudes in terms of how they perceive and emotionally react to the above environmental issues, while also exploring their intentions regarding the shift to the organic food market. The fourth section includes questions about agroecology, attempting to explore the participants' familiarity with organic and sustainable farming and their perceived benefits. This attempts to study the general knowledge of North Africans and their lack of information regarding agroecology. It should be noted that the following definition of agroecology is given in the questionnaire, given by the FAO (FAO, 2018), so that everyone can answer with knowledge of what it is about:

“Agroecology is the science of applying ecological concepts and principles to manage interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment for food security and nutrition. All over the world farmers already apply this approach, which has a fundamental pillar in traditional and local knowledge.”

Source: <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/knowledge/practices/en/>

The last section of the questionnaire explored the WTP a premium price for specific categories of AE products in relation to the corresponding conventional ones. This category of questions aims to assess the dynamics of the market sector for these products and how consumers' awareness of environmental protection issues is ultimately valued through their dietary choices. WTP varies depending on demographic, psychological and contextual factors and thus this section is crucial for the formulation of appropriate pricing strategies and policy-making (Hahsler, 2015).

Based on the related literature on the management of this type of research, a 5-point Likert scale was used for sections 2, 3 and 4 of the questionnaire (Nemoto & Beglar, 2013), while for WTP a scale of -20% to +20% was used for the different products. The questionnaire, after its design, was shared with the rest of the participants of the NATAE project and was then tested in a small focus group to check to what extent the questions are simple and understandable by the participants, and thus all necessary changes were made for its validation. Subsequently, it was translated from English, which was the original language of the design, into French and Arabic so that it could be more easily completed by the participants and was uploaded to the questionnaire design software Limesurvey.

11.4.3 Data collection

Then, training workshops were held in all Living Labs so that those who would be responsible and would collect the questionnaires by country would be properly informed and qualified. In these workshops, the questionnaire was demonstrated and training was provided on the methods of collecting the questionnaires, the stratification of the sample and the personal interview procedure so that the participants' answers were not influenced and the answers were not biased.

Before data collection, the following charts were developed for the representativeness of the sample by country based on the most recent census of their population. The aim was to ensure that the final sample to be collected would be representative of the adult population of each North African country according to age and gender.

Figure 104: Algeria's census

Figure 105: Egypt's census

Figure 106: Morocco's census

Figure 107: Mauritanian census

Figure 108: Tunisian census

For each country, a target of 500 completed questionnaires was set. The proportions by age group as well as the 1:1 ratio in the gender of the participants help in the more reliable generalization of the data while making it easier to monitor the progress of data collection by study country. Furthermore, it is easier to compare the results of the countries among themselves but also with the overall sample despite the fact that there were very small deviations in the census distributions of the different countries.

11.4.4 Data analysis

The primary analysis performed on the collected data was a descriptive analysis in the 5 countries of interest. This analysis mainly concerned the socio-economic data of the sample in order to have a clearer picture of the demographic characteristics of the respondents and to verify whether these correspond to the initial requirements. For example, a significant percentage of the respondents were concentrated in the age group 25-44 in all the countries under study, a fact that was in agreement with the data of the national population censuses. Descriptive statistics were initially performed on many of the following categories of questions as well as on the willingness to pay questions in order to draw some initial generalized conclusions about consumer habits. Descriptive statistics played a critical role in determining the distribution and central tendencies of the key variables, revealing preliminary patterns that were further explored through factor analysis and linear regression in the following phases of the research.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to group the variables into factors in order to obtain the most basic reasons that influence consumers in the AE products market. This analysis was used for the questions of the second, third and fourth units of the questionnaire to correlate the most relevant variables between them. PCA was carried out for both the total sample and the individual samples of each country, while previously a data suitability check was carried out for the implementation of this specific method. The suitability check was carried out by checking the KMO index and Bartlett's sphericity test. KMO values above 0.5 are considered satisfactory and the closer this value is to unity, the more suitable the sample is for PCA (IBM, 2019). In all samples, the KMO value was >0.6 indicating that all collected data were suitable for the specific analysis at a significance level <0.05 . Also, a Varimax rotation was applied to the data to enhance interpretability by maximizing the variance between the variables in each factor, while minimizing overlap with other factors (Abdi & Williams, 2010).

In addition, for each component of each sample, an interpretation was made based on the factor loading values of individual variables with values <0.4 being considered non-significant and removed from further analysis. Using PCA, the main factors influencing consumers per case study emerged, and these factors were then correlated with the demographic characteristics of the sample using linear regression analysis to derive more specific consumer groups (Jaadi, 2019).

To identify the factors influencing consumers' WTP for AE products, multiple linear regression analysis was also conducted with the samples' demographic data. The quality and explanatory power of the regression model were assessed using R-squared, adjusted R-squared and the significance of individual coefficients (p-values) (Gao, 2024). For a more targeted interpretation of the results and an understanding of the specific demographic groups that statistically significantly influence each factor, more specific inference tests were applied (Sharma, 2021). Specifically, one-way ANOVA was used

to test for statistically significant differences in WTP across more than two independent groups such as income or education levels. Similarly, independent samples t-tests were used for comparisons between two groups, such as gender (males vs. females) or respondents from rural and urban areas in relation to the factors or outcomes of the WTP.

Chapter 12

Consumer behaviour assessment for Algeria

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Chapter 12. Consumer behaviour assessment for Algeria

12.1 Demographic characteristics of the sample

The Algerian dataset collected a total of 552 valid responses from a nationally representative diverse sample. The sample included 49.3% male and 50.7% female participants, providing a nearly equal gender distribution. Age-wise, most respondents belonged to the 25–34 (24.3%) and 35–44 (24.5%) brackets, followed by 45–59 (22.1%). Younger (18–24) and older (60+) groups were also represented, comprising 14.5% and 14.7% of the sample respectively. In terms of employment status, most (58.7%) were employed, while 17% were unemployed, 13.4% were students, and 10.9% were retired. Out of this, 53.4% of the respondents specified that they were not satisfied with their average monthly income, while 41.7% were satisfied and only 4.9% reported themselves as being very satisfied. The sample was relatively well-educated: 27.5% were high school education, 25.7% had a bachelor's degree, and 35.7% received a master's or PhD. In terms of residential area, almost half (48.7%) of the participants lived in urban and, 31 and 20.3% in rural and peri-urban areas, respectively. Regarding household composition, 32.8% of respondents reported two adults living in their household, and 33.2 had no children, and 21.9% had one child. In Algeria, household size and structure are diverse with more than half the families composed of only a family with no children or a small family with one or more children (Table 26).

Table 27: Demographic characteristics of Algerian sample

Gender	N of answers	Valid percent
Male	272	49.3
Female	280	50.7
Age		
18-24	80	14.5
25-34	134	24.3
35-44	135	24.5
45-59	122	22.1
60+	81	14.7
Professional status		
Unemployed	94	17.0
Employed	324	58.7
Student	74	13.4
Retired	60	10.9
Average monthly income		
Not satisfactory	295	53.4
Satisfactory	230	41.7
Very satisfactory	27	4.9
Number of adult household member		
0	3	.5
1	28	5.1

2	181	32.8
3	104	18.8
4	121	21.9
5	64	11.6
6	35	6.3
7	11	2.0
8	4	.7
11	1	.2
Number of children in household		
0	183	33.2
1	121	21.9
2	119	21.6
3	76	13.8
4	41	7.4
5	9	1.6
6	3	.5
Your household live in		
Rural	171	31.0
Peri-urban	112	20.3
Urban	269	48.7
Educational level		
No formal education	13	2.4
Elementary school	48	8.7
High school	152	27.5
Bachelor	142	25.7
Master /PhD	197	35.7

12.2 PCA results

Prior to running the PCA, a correlation matrix was investigated to check the strength and nature of relationships between the likert scale variables. In this matrix, the values are replaced by Pearson correlation coefficients ranging from -1 to $+1$, where $+1$ indicates a strong direct association between the variables, -1 indicates a strong inverse association, and 0 indicates no linear association. As typically observed in behavioural research, the majority of variables were weakly to moderately positively correlated (as anticipated due to the multifaceted nature of consumer behaviour constructs).

For example, variables Q10. 2 and Q10. 3, showed an intermediary correlation ($r = 0.332$), and the correlations between Q10. 1 and Q10. 4 ($r = 0.027$) or Q10. 1 and Q10. 5 ($r = 0.074$) were significantly weaker. These weak correlations imply that the variables may tap into very different but complementary aspects of environmental attitudes or perceptions. Although this means that each component may explain less total variance, they are less likely to suffer from multi-collinearity, which is helpful for the regression analysis that follows.

This resulted in the determinant of the correlation matrix of 1.947×10^{-6} that is lower than the most often used level of warning of multicollinearity that is $0,00001$ (Shrestha, 2020). While this low determinant may raise concerns about singularity, or redundancy within the data, on its own it is not

cause to abandon the analysis. Moreover, the correlation matrix also confirms that all variables have been standardized, variance normalized to 1, which is a needed step to be able to compare variables and extract meaningful components through PCA (Gewers et al., 2018).

Table 28: Correlation matrix (Algerian sample)

Correlation	Correlation Matrix				
	Q10.1	Q10.2	Q10.3	Q10.4	Q10.5
Q10.1	1	.125	.084	.027	.074
Q10.2	.125	1	.332	.154	.188
Q10.3	.084	.332	1	.095	.011
Q10.4	.027	.154	.095	1	.496
Q10.5	.074	.188	.011	.496	1
Q10.6	.196	.095	.213	.084	.214
Determinant	1.947E-6				

In order to identify the latent dimensions that drive consumer behaviour in Algeria, PCA was performed on 34 Likert-scale items. The first reliability test achieved a Cronbach's alpha of 0.901, considered as excellent internal consistency and appropriateness for factor extraction. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was excellent at 0.890 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 6642.321$, $df = 561$, $p < 0.001$). These results verified that the item interrelations were sufficiently high to warrant PCA.

Table 29: KMO and Bartlett's test for Algeria's sample

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.890
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6642.321
	df	561
	Sig.	<.001

The communalities for most variables were above 0.5, indicating a good proportion of shared variance. A few variables (Q10. 6, Q10. 11, Q10. 13, and Q11. 1) had communality values lower than this threshold. However, they only changed the variance explained by 1%, so they were kept in the analysis to protect data integrity. Based on Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalues > 1), nine components were extracted. The above components cumulatively explained 59.56% of the total variance in the dataset. The rotated solution through Varimax rotation improved factor structure interpretability but did not change the factor structure.

Table 30: Total variance explained for Algeria

Initial eigen value	Extraction some of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings					
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9.010	26.499	26.499	9.010	26.499	26.499	4.224	12.423	12.423
2	2.083	6.127	32.626	2.083	6.127	32.626	3.586	10.547	22.970
3	1.658	4.877	37.504	1.658	4.877	37.504	2.382	7.007	29.976
4	1.495	4.396	41.899	1.495	4.396	41.899	2.311	6.798	36.774
5	1.400	4.117	46.016	1.400	4.117	46.016	2.062	6.064	42.838
6	1.326	3.900	49.916	1.326	3.900	49.916	1.666	4.900	47.738
7	1.185	3.485	53.401	1.185	3.485	53.401	1.493	4.391	52.129
8	1.086	3.194	56.595	1.086	3.194	56.595	1.397	4.109	56.238
9	1.009	2.968	59.562	1.009	2.968	59.562	1.130	3.325	59.562

Q11.4, Q12.3, and Q10.17 were eliminated after using the varimax rotation technique and examining the rotated component matrix as their factor loadings fell below 0.5. Then, each of the nine PCA-derived components was given a name. The first component, "Q.12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices," addresses AE practices in the survey and so indicates the degree of consumer awareness of AE activities. Used to gauge consumer attitudes on environmental protection, the second part has six questions including "Q. 10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment". Labeled "tradeoff between economic development and environmental protection," the third part consists of queries such "Q.10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth." Questions such "Q. 11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations" make up the fourth part, so it was called "Consumer viewpoints on environment's future". Referring to the people's involvement on environmental protection, the fifth component comprises three variables including "Q.10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants". The sixth component points out consumer behaviour toward locally produced food. Consumer awareness of environmental responsibility and solutions is determined by the seventh component, which is named for the two variables reflecting the same concept as "Q10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world". The eighth component was named based on three environmental awareness-related factors involved in it. The ninth component was named depending on one aspect connected to consumer knowledge of environmental concerns.

Table 31: PCA labelling for Algeria's sample

Principal Components
<p><u>Component 1: Consumer awareness about AE practices</u></p> <p>12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices 12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems 12.1. I am familiar with agroecological practices 12.9 I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility 12.12 I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming 12.5 I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources</p>
<p><u>Component 2: Environmental concerns</u></p> <p>12.10 I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating tree to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity 10.7 I am worried about global warming 10.8 In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss) 10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment 10.11 We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem 12.8 I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health</p>
<p><u>Component 3: Tradeoff between economic development and environmental protection</u></p> <p>10.16 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development. 10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth</p>
<p><u>Component 4: Consumer perspectives on environment's future</u></p> <p>11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations 10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations 12.2 I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture</p>
<p><u>Component 5: Consumer contribution for environmental protection</u></p> <p>10.5 The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us 10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants 11.1. Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem</p>
<p><u>Component 6: Consumer behaviour towards locally produced food</u></p> <p>10.15 Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment 12.6 I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment 11.3 I choose to purchase locally produced food</p>
<p><u>Component 7: Consumer environmentally responsible behaviour towards environment</u></p> <p>10.2 Science and technology can solve all environmental problems 10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world</p>
<p><u>Component 8: Actions related to environmental awareness</u></p> <p>11.2 When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable 10.13 Optimized use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources 12.7 I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices</p>
<p><u>Component 9: Environmental issues awareness</u></p> <p>10.1 Environmental problems are exaggerated</p>

The PCA results observed for the Algerian sample, as such, undermine interesting highlights on the various aspects of consumers regarding environmental and agroecological dimensions. However, given the diverse nature of psychological, behavioural and informational determinants of sustainable consumption, these components serve as evidence of the multicollinearity of attitudes in this scenario in our extract of 9 indicatives. The stability of the first three components (awareness of agroecological practices, environmental concern, and trade-off between economic development and environmental protection) indicates that these are the most reliable and significant dimensions in shaping consumer-oriented sustainability behaviour in the context of Algeria. Notably, the stability of education, living space, and professional status as explanatory variables for these subcomponents reinforces the notion that socio-demographic background is a key factor influencing individual approaches to environmental issues. Two components displayed slightly lower internal consistency than the others, but their conceptual significance (e.g., personal responsibility, local product attitudes) supports their retention within the tool, particularly given the ongoing development in this area within an emerging market. In sum, The PCA succeeded at reducing a complex dataset into relevant and understandable dimensions, which serve as a basis for targeted analysis and concrete policy or marketing actions in Algeria's transition towards agroecological and sustainable food systems.

12.3 Linear Regression analysis results

To understand the effect of socio-economic variables on the main factors yielded by PCA, multiple linear regression analyses were conducted for the Algerian sample. The PCA components were employed as the dependant variables, and the independent variables were age, sex, professional occupation, mean monthly income, household composition (adults and children), residential zone, and educational attainment.

The results, summarized in Table 31, show a number of statistically significant correlations:

Table 32: Correlation among PCA results and SE characteristics of Algerian sample

Socio -economic characteristics	Components								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Age	***					***	*		
Gender						*			
Professional status	**	***					**		

Average monthly income								*	
Number of adult household members			*					*	
Number of children in household									**
Your household live in:	***	**	*				*		
Educational level	*	***				*	*	***	

Consumer awareness of AEP were significantly influenced by age ($p < 0.001$), residential area ($p < 0.001$), professional occupation ($p < 0.01$), and education level ($p < 0.05$). This implies that older, more educated individuals who live in the city and who work professionally are more aware of AEP. Component 2 associated with professional status ($p < 0.001$), home neighborhood ($p < 0.01$), and level of education ($p < 0.001$), highlighting the role of both professional and educational environments in the development of environmental awareness.

Component 3 was statistically significant influenced by level of education ($p < 0.001$), reflecting that higher education is associated with greater preference for environmental sustainability over economic growth. None of the socio-economic variables were significant in the forth factor, suggesting a more equally held perspective toward long-term environmental responsibility. Aged and female respondents were more likely to show commitment to personal environmental responsibility (factor 5) which is influenced by age ($p < 0.001$) and sex ($p < 0.05$).

Component 6 is influenced by professional status ($p < 0.01$) and education ($p < 0.05$), underpinning the relationship between socio-economic engagement and place-based consumption choice. Component 7 is weakly correlated with the number of adults in the household ($p < 0.05$) and residential location ($p < 0.05$), suggesting some contextual variation in the attribution of responsibility for global environmental problems.

Actions related to environmental awareness (factor 8) is influenced by the number of adults ($p < 0.05$) and gender ($p < 0.05$), showing the minor contribution of household structure and gender towards pro-environmental actions. Component 9 is mostly influenced by education level ($p < 0.001$) and number of children in the household ($p < 0.01$). Those with higher education and more children in the household are more sensitive to general environmental matters. Overall, the analysis determines education to be the most stable and best predictor across the variables, followed by professional status, residential location, and age. The findings support the impact of socio-demographic context in shaping both environmental attitudes and behavioural predispositions of Algerian consumers.

12.4 Willingness To Pay results

The WTP analysis of Algerian consumers reveals a more general picture of readiness to support this food category. While they are not yet fully informed about AE products, a significant percentage of respondents were willing to pay more money than they usually pay to acquire them. AE olive oil, fruits and vegetables produced with AEP received the highest rates of WTP (up to +20%). On the contrary, products such as AE cereals and aromatic and medicinal plants showed comparatively lower WTP ratios, indicating either limited perceived added value or lower familiarity with the benefits of these products.

Demographic factors played an important role in shaping these WTP patterns. Education level had a statistically significant effect WTP for almost all products, with consumers with higher education levels reporting higher willingness to pay. WTP for organic fruit was further shaped by employment status and household composition (number of adults and children). Products such as meat and dairy products were associated with income satisfaction, reinforcing the idea that financial security plays a role in sustainable food choices. Regarding age, older consumers were more willing to pay for cereals, while employment status influenced preferences for products such as herbs and meat. While the percentage of WTP varies by product, the main conclusion is that improving consumer education and awareness is key to expanding the market for sustainable food systems.

12.5 Conclusions

The first case study highlighted the main components influencing Algerian consumers towards AE products, explaining 59.56% of the total variance. These elements mainly reflected environmental awareness, knowledge of AE products and support for locally produced foods. Organic awareness and environmental concern had the greatest influence. Age, educational level, occupation and place of residence are the most important demographic factors influencing these components. Older people with a high educational level and higher professional status show greater awareness for AE foods. Specifically, consumers over 45 years of age, especially those who are retired or live in urban areas, showed the strongest relationship with awareness of AE. Also, demographics play an important role in consumers' WTP. Education level was the most consistent demographic factor that statistically significantly affected almost all product categories. WTP for AE olive oil ($R^2 = 0.089$), organic fruits ($R^2 = 0.112$) and locally produced vegetables ($R^2 = 0.073$) were strongly influenced by education. In addition, factors such as employment status, household composition and income satisfaction were statistically significant for some products, such as dairy and meat. However, consumer awareness of sustainable foods remains limited among the general Algerian population, with over 50% of them not being sure whether they are aware of them. In conclusion, Algerian consumers show increasing

interest and positive attitudes towards sustainable foods, particularly among the more educated and financially stable consumers. However, limited product availability, lack of clear labeling, and low adoption of sustainable practices remain significant barriers.

Chapter 13

Consumer behaviour assessment for Egypt

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Chapter 13. Consumer behaviour assessment for Egypt

13.1 Descriptive statistics

500 consumers participated in the survey (447 valid), ensuring a representative sample of Egyptian consumers. The gender distribution was well balanced, with 50.9% male and 49.1% female respondents. The sample covered a wide range of age groups, with a big concentration in the younger age groups: 17.5% aged 20–24, 15.7% aged 25–29 and 11.4% aged 30–34. 33.2% of participants were under 30 years old, and older age groups, including those aged 55 and over, represented approximately 18.9% of the sample.

In terms of employment, the majority were employed (63.9%), followed by students (15.5%), retirees (11%) and unemployed (9.6%). In terms of income satisfaction, 48.9% of respondents said they were satisfied, while 43.5% were not satisfied and only 7.6% described their income as very satisfactory. In terms of housing distribution, most (76.7%) lived in urban areas, followed by 13.7% in suburban areas and 9.6% in rural areas. Family composition was: 27.4% had four adults in the household, while almost half of the respondents (49.1%) reported having no children and 22% had one child (Table 32).

Table 33: Demographic characteristics of Egyptian sample

Gender	Frequency	Valid percent
Male	227	50.9
Female	219	49.1
Age		
20-24	78	17.5
25-29	70	15.7
30-34	51	11.4
34-39	48	10.8
40-44	39	8.7
45-49	41	9.2
50-54	35	7.8
55-59	31	7.0
60-64	24	5.4
65+	29	6.5
Professional status		
Unemployed	43	9.6

Employed	285	63.9
Student	69	15.5
Retired	49	11.0
Average monthly income		
Not satisfactory	194	43.5
Satisfactory	218	48.9
Very satisfactory	34	7.6
Number of adult household member		
0	3	0.7
1	21	4.7
2	96	21.5
3	87	19.5
4	122	27.4
5	76	17.0
6	30	6.7
7	10	2.2
8	1	0.2
Number of children in household		
0	219	49.1
1	98	22.0
2	85	19.1
3	30	6.7
4	10	2.2
5	3	0.7
13	1	0.2
Your household live in		
Rural	43	9.6
Peri-urban	61	13.7
Urban	342	76.7
Educational level		
No formal education	5	1.1
Elementary school	8	1.8
High school	54	12.1
Bachelor	335	75.1
Master /PhD	44	9.9

13.2 PCA results

Two preliminary tests were conducted to confirm the sampling adequacy and factorability of the dataset. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy was very good and had a value of 0.875. Furthermore, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 5691.481$, $df = 561$, $p < 0.001$), supporting the assumption of meaningful correlations among variables, hence validating the application of PCA.

Table 34: KMO and Bartlett's test for Egypt's sample

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.875
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	.5691.481
	df	561
	Sig.	<.001

According to Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalues > 1), nine principal components were extracted from the data set. Collectively, these components accounted for 57.86% of the total variance, suggesting that a significant proportion of the variability in environmental and AE attitudes can be captured with these latent dimensions. A Varimax rotation was used to maximize interpretability of the component structure. Rotated solution: Spread the variance more evenly over the components, making each component more distinct.

Table 35: Total variance explained for Egypt

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial eigen value			Extraction some of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.357	24.580	24.580	8.357	24.580	24.580	4.568	13.436	13.436
2	3.378	9.936	34.516	3.378	9.936	34.516	3.164	9.305	22.742
3	1.920	5.648	40.164	1.920	5.648	40.164	2.635	7.751	30.493
4	1.358	3.994	44.157	1.358	3.994	44.157	2.046	6.018	36.511
5	1.217	3.580	47.737	1.217	3.580	47.737	1.990	5.852	42.362
6	1.190	3.499	51.236	1.190	3.499	51.236	1.817	5.344	47.706
7	1.142	3.358	54.593	1.142	3.358	54.593	1.570	4.618	52.324

8	1.052	3.093	57.687	1.052	3.093	57.687	1.452	4.271	56.596
9	1.011	2.975	60.661	1.011	2.975	60.661	1.382	4.066	60.661

Based on their factor loading characteristics, names have been given for every one of the nine PCA-derived components. For example, "Q10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations," the first component consists of eight questions meant to clarify consumer future views and attitudes toward the environment. Consumer awareness of farming techniques is evaluated in the second part by five questions including "Q12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems". Seven questions in the third and fourth parts are "Q12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices." Every question in both halves reflects the same concept, so they are classified as consumer awareness regarding AE practices. The fifth component has two questions with the same meaning, such "Q10.16 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development," so it was classified depending on which is more important, economic development or environmental protection. Labeled consumer behaviour toward locally produced food, the sixth component consists of factors such "Q11.3 I choose to buy locally produced food." The seventh component was named based on three values reflecting the same concept as this question "Q10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world "to determine consumer knowledge of environmental responsibility and solutions. The eighth component was named according to two environmental concern-related variables: "Q10.7 I am worried about global warming." Labeled according to two variables connected to consumer perceptions and environmental effect, the ninth component was Global warming concerns me. The ninth component was named based on two factors connected to determining the customer beliefs and environmental effect.

Table 36: PCA labelling for Egyptian sample

Principal Components
<p>Component 1: Consumer perspectives on environment's future</p> <p>10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations 10.5 The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us 11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations 10.11 We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem 10.17 We can accept changes in our lifestyles to protect natural resources 10.13 Optimized use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources 11.1. Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem 10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants</p>
<p>Component 2: Consumer awareness of farming practices</p> <p>12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems 12.9 I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility 12.8 I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health 12.12 I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming</p>

12.10 I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating tree to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity
Component 3: Consumer knowledge about AE practices 12.7 I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices 12.1. I am familiar with agroecological practices 12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices 11.2 When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable
Component 4: Consumer knowledge about AE practices 12.5 I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources 12.3 I believe that agroecological practices are beneficial for my health 12.2 I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture
Component 5: Tradeoff between economic development and environmental protection 10.16 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development. 10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth
Component 6: Consumer behaviour towards locally produced food 11.3 I choose to purchase locally produced food 12.6 I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment 10.15 Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment
Component 7: Consumer awareness of environmental responsibility and solutions 10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world 10.2 Science and technology can solve all environmental problems
Component 8: Consumer awareness about environmental problems 10.7 I am worried about global warming 10.8 In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss)
Component 9: Consumer beliefs and impact on the environment 10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment 10.1 Environmental problems are exaggerated

These principal components encapsulate a rich structure of Egyptian consumers' perceptions of the environment and their attitudes towards AEP. Consumer perspectives on the environment's future (Component 1) emerged as the strongest and most holistic factor combining forward-looking values and collective, as well as, lifestyle adaptation. By including statements around intergenerational equity, lifestyle change, and environmental education, however, it also appears a significant portion of Egyptian consumers possess a values-oriented vision of longer-term ecological health. This element reflect an implicit ethical component of consumer consciousness, encouraging conservation of natural resources not just as a necessity, but as a collective responsibility of society.

Components 2,3 and 4 provide a more technical understanding of sustainability that is grouped around different levels of consumer awareness and understanding of farming and AEP. These improve agricultural practices that are part of AE, including, crop rotation, cover crops, integration of livestock, and less use of agrochemicals. Another interesting aspect is that Component 4 focuses on health and sustainability outcomes, meaning AE has been recognized as helping not only the environment but as well as consumers' health. On the other hand, Components 5 and 6 indicate more behavioural preferences, like a willingness to prioritize environmental protection above economic

growth, and strong support for components 5 locally produced food, pointing to both ideological as well as action-oriented elements. The other components (7, 8 and 9) represent more global opinions about how responsibility is attributed, concern with the environment, and belief in human impact on it. These elements reflect a comprehensive framework of environmental awareness covering knowledge, concern, values and behaviour.

13.3 Linear Regression analysis results

Utilizing the nine components as dependent variables, multiple linear regression analyses were used to explore the sociodemographic determinants of the PCA components. The following independent factors were determined: age, sex, job status, median monthly income, number of members in household (adults and children), place of residence, education level. The results revealed numerous statistically significant relationships between consumer attitudes and environmental or AE profile (Table 36).

Table 37: Correlation among PCA results and SE characteristics of Egyptian sample

	Components								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Socio economic characteristics	-								
Age	.	.	***						***
Gender	.	.	.						
Professional status	.	.	.						
Average monthly income	.	.	.						
Number of adult household members	.	**	.						
Number of children in household	*	.	.						
Your household live in:	**	**	**						

Educational level	***	.	**					*	
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The strongest socioeconomic characteristic that influence most of the variables was the level of education, which was significantly associated with Component 1 ($p < 0.001$), Component 3 ($p < 0.01$), Component 4 ($p < 0.01$), and Component 9 ($p < 0.05$). These items were referred with consumers potential views on the future state of the environment, their awareness of AEP, and their views on environmental impacts, indicating that education is necessary to create environmental awareness and technical knowledge for sustainable practices.

Age also played a prominent role, most notably for factor 3 ($p < 0.001$) and factor 9 ($p < 0.001$), and they both pertaining to environmental knowledge and attitudes on human impact. Number of children marginally influence Component 1 ($p < 0.05$), whereas number of adult members in a household predicted Component 2 ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, Components 1, 2, and 3 were all significantly associated with area of residence (urban versus rural/peri-urban) ($p < 0.01$); this suggests that urban living could boost accessibility to environmental knowledge and more sustainable attitudes.

As shown in the same Table, none of the components were found to be statistically significantly affected by gender, employment status, or income, which might suggest that in Egypt environmental attitudes are less determined by occupation or income level, and are affected more directly by access to education and information. Age, education and living in urban area as the major determinants for Egyptian consumers' attitudes towards sustainability.

13.4 Willingness To Pay results

The WTP of AE products in Egypt varies significantly depending on the food category under study. More specifically, consumers are more willing to pay more for olive oil produced under AEP and locally produced fruits (up to 20% more money stated that they would pay about 40% of young highly educated consumers). This is followed by locally produced vegetables and cereals produced with AEP farming (about 30% of young people stated that they would pay +10% for these categories). On the other hand, WTP levels for organic dairy products and aromatic and medicinal plants under AEP were relatively low, possibly due to price sensitivity or lack of knowledge about their environmental benefits.

The demographic characteristics that mainly influence the WTP a premium price are educational level (mainly for locally produced fruits and vegetables). Consumers themselves are the ones who stated that they are more aware and have more knowledge about environmental concerns and sustainability. Therefore, environmental literacy plays a key role in influencing purchase decisions. Age and household size (especially the number of children) were also significantly associated with higher WTP

for some categories. There was a small effect related to income satisfaction and gender, suggesting that across all economic status or gender identity, there is potential for broad consumer engagement. With WTP ratios in Egypt indicating an early market for sustainable food, the effects of education and age suggest that communications and targets around WTP will have a broad and profound impact on this growing market.

13.5 Conclusions

However, Egyptians case study provides the most comprehensive exploration of the Egyptian consumer's behaviour regarding AE products, offering significant new insights into environmental awareness, knowledge of AEP, and WTP. PCA extracted nine principal components accounting for 60.66% of the total variance in attitudes and awareness. Socio-economic factors and especially education level, age, and place of residence molded core characteristics such as consumer perspectives on the environmental future, awareness of AEP, and concern about environmental issues. For example, highly-educated people and those living in rural regions but with higher education levels showed a stronger environmental attitude and AE awareness, suggesting that experience and contextual learning present in rural areas may lead to sustainability-oriented actions.

Interest peaked for fruit produced under AEP followed by AE olive oil and local vegetables, and WTP analysis revealed moderate WTP for AE products. In consumer decision-making, economic constraints are highlighted by the fact that only 5.4% are separating the income satisfaction levels of consumers ready to spend more and those who are not. Although professional status had a negative association, likely due to job insecurity and little disposable money available in Egypt, the regressions indicated a positive association between WTP and monthly income, number of adult members in the household and education levels. The majority indicated only a +10% WTP over conventional product prices, even as knowledge increased based on responses that mirrored the impact of previous inflation and currency devaluation.

However, Egyptian consumers have environmental concerns and knowledge of AEP, especially young, higher educated consumers and knowledgeable rural residents. Cost sensitivity and budget limitations, however, still restrict wider AE products acceptance. Affordability and product accessibility are areas that require focused education initiatives, government incentives, and policy support. Inhibiting this transition from consumers' intention to action, and informing a more sustainable and resilient food system that supports change in Egypt, will depend on initiatives to promote clear labeling, build trust, and integrate AE in food market.

Chapter 14

Consumer behaviour assessment for Morocco

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Chapter 14. Consumer behaviour assessment for Morocco

14.1 Demographic characteristics of the sample

In Morocco, 547 people were surveyed and after data cleaning, 513 valid responses were included in the analysis. The demographic profile is broadly representative in terms of age, gender, education, income and household structure. 55.8% of the sample was entirely male and 44.2% were female. The age distribution of the sample were respondents aged 25–34 (24.0%), followed by 45–59 (22.8%), 18–24 (19.7%), and 35–44 (17.9%), while 65 and above represented 15.6% of the sample (Table 37).

In terms of professional status, 58.7% were employed, 22% were students, 9.9% were unemployed, and 9.4% were retired, demonstrating a significant prevalence of active working-age population. In response to the question about satisfaction with income, 58.1 % of the respondents said they were satisfied with their income, 32.6% were dissatisfied, and only 9.4 % said they were very satisfied with their income. Participants from Morocco presented particularly high levels of educational attainment, with 62% holding a Master’s or PhD, and a further 23% holding a Bachelor’s degree. This correlates with the fact that a majority of respondents (77.2%) lived in urban areas, vis-a-vis 14.8% in peri-urban and only 8% in rural regions.

Household composition also varied. Most of the households had 2 to 4 adult members (25%: two adults; 20.3%: three adults; 20.5%: four adults). Lastly, the number of children per household differed, with 37.82% of households having no children, 24.43% with one child, and 24.76% with two children. This demographic structure indicates a relatively educated and urban-based population with moderate household sizes and satisfactory income, this shows a good sample for assessing consumer behaviour and awareness of AEP in Morocco.

Table 38: Demographic characteristics of Moroccan sample

Gender	N of answers	Valid percent
Male	286	55.8
Female	227	44.2
Age		
18-24	101	19.7
25-34	123	24.0
35-44	92	17.9
45-59	117	22.8
65+	80	15.6
Professional status		

Unemployed	51	9.9
Employed	301	58.7
Student	113	22.0
Retired	48	9.4
Average monthly income		
Not satisfactory	167	32.6
Satisfactory	298	58.1
Very satisfactory	48	9.4
Number of adult household member		
0	10	1.9
1	56	10.9
2	128	25.0
3	104	20.3
4	105	20.5
5	71	13.8
6	25	4.9
7	10	1.9
8	1	.2
9	1	.2
10	1	.2
12	1	.2
Number of children in household		
0	194	37.8
1	125	24.4
2	127	24.8
3	50	9.7
4	10	1.9
5	4	.8
6	1	.2
9	1	.2
10	1	.2
Your household live in		
Rural	41	8.0
Peri-urban	76	14.8
Urban	396	77.2

Educational level		
No formal education	10	1.9
Elementary school	14	2.7
High school	53	10.3
Bachelor	118	23.0
Master /PhD	318	62.0

14.2 PCA results

Before running PCA, a correlation matrix was examined, which indicated generally weak to moderate positive correlations among variables — typical of datasets pertaining to complex consumer behaviour. Although some correlations were relatively low, they also helped to reduce multicollinearity, and they also supported the use of PCA to summarize and interpret the data in a more limited and homogenous way.

The dataset obtained proved appropriate for factor analysis. The KMO measure was 0.897, which signifies excellent sampling adequacy, and Bartlett's test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 7984.790$, $df = 561$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that item correlations were adequate to justify PCA.

Table 39: KMO and Bartlett's test for Moroccan sample

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.897
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	7984.790
	df	561
	Sig.	<.001

Based on Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalues > 1), the PCA extracted seven main components, explaining a total of 61.18% of variance. Maximization of the loading of each variable on one component, and minimization of its loading on others, was achieved through application of a Varimax rotation, to aid in interpretability. This rotation better distributed variance across components and revealed evident thematic groupings.

The components themselves are a multidimensional realization of sustainability. The high means of awareness of AE practices, environmental concerns, and intention for supporting locally produced food was a noticeable outcome as these indicators demonstrate that the general public is becoming increasingly aware of the ecological farming and sustainable consumption. On the other hand, the inclusion of elements such as trust in labels, knowledge about environmental issues, and

responsibility attribution shows that Moroccan consumers are not only concerned about the environment, but that they also seem to be invested in assessing the framework that supports or goes against sustainable choices. These insights reveal a population that is an environmentally aware, and increasingly critical of the roles that institutions play in delivering change, something of relevance for policymakers and marketers hoping to scale-up agroecological transitions in Morocco.

Table 40: Total variance explained for Morocco

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial eigen value			Extraction some of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.833	25.978	25.978	8.833	25.978	25.978	6.081	17.884	17.884
2	4.308	12.672	38.650	4.308	12.672	38.650	4.376	12.871	30.755
3	2.137	6.286	44.936	2.137	6.286	44.936	2.484	7.307	38.062
4	1.586	4.666	49.602	1.586	4.666	49.602	2.167	6.375	44.437
5	1.544	4.541	54.142	1.544	4.541	54.142	2.101	6.181	50.618
6	1.269	3.732	57.874	1.269	3.732	57.874	1.876	5.516	56.134
7	1.123	3.304	61.178	1.123	3.304	61.178	1.715	5.044	61.178

Only one variable was eliminated after using the varimax rotation technique and examining the rotated component matrix: "Q.10.1. environmental problems are exaggerated" because of its low loading (<0.5) on all seven preserved components suggesting it did not significantly contribute to any factor. Each of the seven PCA components has been labeled. All queries regarding AEP "12.6 I think that eating locally produced food is good for the environment" are included in the first component. It shows how informed consumers are about AEP, including "Q.12.4. I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices".

Consumer knowledge of several environmental issues is measured in the second part by eight questions including "Q.10.7. I am concerned about global warming". Both the third and fifth factors have seven questions like "Q.11.4. I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices". These questions show consumer views on the future of the environment. The questions in these two parts were both called "Consumer Perspectives on the Future of the Environment" since they thematically correspond. Focusing on the trade-off between economic growth and environmental protection, the fourth component poses questions such "Q.10.16. environmental protection is more essential than economic development". Labeled "Consumer behaviour towards locally produced

food," the sixth component has two factors: "Q.11.3. I choose to purchase locally produced food." At last, the seventh component was called "Consumer perspectives of locally produced food on the environment" as both variables in this component emphasised the environmental effect of local food consumption.

Table 41: PCA results for Moroccan sample

Principal Components
<p>Component 1: Consumer awareness about AE practices</p> <p>12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices</p> <p>12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems</p> <p>12.9 I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility</p> <p>12.8 I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health</p> <p>12.1. I am familiar with agroecological practices</p> <p>12.5 I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources</p> <p>12.10 I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating tree to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity</p> <p>12.2 I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture</p> <p>12.12 I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming</p> <p>12.3 I believe that agroecological practices are beneficial for my health</p> <p>12.7 I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices</p>
<p>Component 2: Consumer awareness about environmental problems</p> <p>10.5 The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us</p> <p>10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants</p> <p>10.7 I am worried about global warming</p> <p>10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment</p> <p>10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations</p> <p>10.13 Optimized use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources</p> <p>10.8 In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss)</p> <p>10.17 We can accept changes in our lifestyles to protect natural resources</p>
<p>Component 3: Consumer perspectives on environment's future</p> <p>11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations</p> <p>11.1. Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem</p> <p>11.4 I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices</p>
<p>Component 4: Trade-off between economic development and environmental protection</p> <p>10.16 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development.</p> <p>10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth</p> <p>10.11 We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem</p>
<p>Component 5: Consumer perspectives on environment's future</p> <p>10.14 The benefits of technology are greater than its harmful side effects</p>

<p>10.2 Science and technology can solve all environmental problems</p> <p>10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world</p> <p>10.12 Since natural resources (such as sun, wind, and water) can never be exhausted, energy will never run out on this planet</p>
<p>Component 6: Consumer behaviour toward locally produced food</p> <p>11.2 When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable</p> <p>11.3 I choose to purchase locally produced food</p>
<p>Component 7: Consumer perspectives of locally produced food on the environment</p> <p>10.15 Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment</p> <p>12.6 I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment</p>

The PCA of the Moroccan dataset indicates that the 7 components identified provide good thematic coverage of sustainability-related behaviours and beliefs. Consumer awareness about AEP (Component 1) was the strongest component consisting of eleven items that indicate conceptual and practical awareness of AE techniques. This cluster suggests that Moroccan consumers and particularly those with advanced education or exposure to the sustainability discourse have a fairly developed understanding of AE, including concepts from crop diversification to soil health to the environmental advantages of marginally reducing agrochemical application.

Component 2, “Consumer awareness about environmental problems”, increases the environmental awareness in the sample. It integrates both emotional concern (i.e., fear for loss of global biodiversity, global warming, etc) and a feeling of personal accountability, demonstrating that awareness is not only passive but can be action-oriented as well. The multiple components concerning future-oriented thinking (components 3 and 4), environmental protection and growth in economic development (component 5), together describe a heterogeneous picture of awareness where environmental and climate values meet environmental responsibility. Additionally, Components 6 and 7, both of which pertain to consumer behaviour and attitudes toward consuming locally produced food, suggests that localism in food is becoming a significant environmental strategy among Moroccan consumers. These parts reveal that it values not just the environmental ethic of local production but practical habits such as eco-friendly packaging decisions.

14.3 Linear Regression analysis results

The regression analysis investigated the influence of various socio-economic factors on the factors identified in the PCA. The results demonstrate that in general, the key drivers influencing consumer

behaviour and environmental attitudes in Morocco were seen as education level, age, gender and the profession rank.

For the four dimensions with favorable correlations, educational degree emerged as a consistent and significant factor: i. component 1 $p < 0.01$, ii. Component 3 $p < 0.001$, iii. component 4 $p < 0.001$ and iv. Component 5 $p < 0.001$. This means more educated individuals are much more likely to have greater understanding and concern over sustainability, understand the trade-offs between economic and environmental goals, and faith in research and solutions based on policy.

Another significant factor influencing two factors is consumers' age, which is correlated highly with Component 1 ($p < 0.05$) and Component 3 ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that older customers tend to be more aware about environmental issues, and more informed with regard to AE practices. In contrast, gender is statistically significantly associated with Component 3 (Environmental perspectives on environment's future, $p < 0.01$) and Component 4 ($p < 0.05$). This implies that gendered social roles may influence sensitivity to the environment and views on development versus conservation.

Component 1 was significantly impacted by professional status ($p < 0.001$), meaning that people who worked were more likely to report knowledge of AE methods. Although monthly income and household size showed no significant associations for the present context, surprisingly, the type of residence (urban vs rural) was only associated with Component 6 ($p < 0.01$), suggesting some behaviour concern for the local produced food. Results highlight education as the strongest socio-economic factor influencing most of PCA components affirming the necessity of targeted educational campaigns and policies considering demographic and professional sectors in Morocco.

Table 42: Correlation among PCA results and SE characteristics of Moroccan sample

Socio economic characteristics	Components						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Age	*		***				
Gender			**	*			
Professional status	***						
Average monthly income							
Number of adult household members							

Number of children in household							
Your household live in:						**	
Educational level	**			***	***		

14.4 Willingness To Pay results

Key findings of the analysis of Moroccan consumers' WTP for AE and locally produced food products showed a broadly positive attitude to sustainable consumption although more negatively towards AE products compared to locally-produced products. Consumers seem to value staple food and fresh food items that they can consider healthy and sustainable as those with the highest WTP proportions included AE olive oil, organic fruits, and locally produced vegetables. In comparison, aromatic plants, medicinal herbs, and cereals were reported with lower WTP levels, probably due to less perceived health or environmental benefits or lower degree of acquaintance with the product.

These WTP patterns were significantly influenced by demographic characteristics. The most consistent predictor of WTP across almost all products was educational level, with the strongest effect for AE olive oil followed by organic fruits and locally produced vegetables. This is also important for building the market demand for sustainable food, and environmental knowledge. Employment status and age affected WTP for particular categories as employed consumers and older respondents were more likely to show WTP a premium for AE meat and cereals. Remarkably, income satisfaction had little effect, suggesting educated consumers are motivated by environmental awareness. In conclusion, Moroccan consumers exhibit a motivation towards support for AE products that could be enhanced by extending the frame of reference beyond health, quality, and trust. Policymakers and producers can leverage these insights to devise pricing mechanism and promotional activities that are in synchrony with the expectations of and limitations of Morocco's most responsive consumer segments: educated, employed and urban living consumers.

14.5 Conclusions

The Moroccan case study shows that environmental awareness and consumer demographics significantly influence consumer habits and decisions. Of the 7 factors of the PCA (explaining 61.18% of the total variance), awareness of both agroecology and environmental issues is the most important. It is also interesting to note that the regression study revealed complex views, as age significantly influenced awareness of AE (factor 1), while education level, gender and employment status had significant positive effects on awareness components.

The study revealed encouraging signs of market readiness for AE products in terms of WTP, especially among older and more educated consumers. While income and occupational level also influenced preferences for locally produced dairy and vegetables, age was the main factor influencing WTP for AE grains, olive oil and meat. Older consumers, for example, would be more willing to pay for sustainable options perhaps due to increased environmental and health awareness. However, especially for younger or lower-income populations, the high prices of these products remain a problem. These findings somewhat fit with previous research that highlights the influence of quality, pricing and availability on sustainable purchasing behaviour of Moroccan consumers. Overall, the results indicate an increasing focus on sustainability among Moroccan consumers, especially where knowledge of local and agroecological food systems is supported by education and urban residence. However, further behavioural changes are hindered by structural barriers such as unequal access to information, poor labeling systems, and low affordability.

Chapter 15

Consumer behaviour assessment for Mauritania

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Chapter 15. Consumer behaviour assessment for Mauritania

15.1 Demographic characteristics of the sample

The sample from Mauritania included 322 valid respondents and had a varied demographic structure. The age distribution was slightly well structured according to the last census (28.9% aged 25–34; 23.3% aged 45–59; 22.3% aged 35–44; 20.2% aged 18–24, and 5.3% aged 60+).

Professionally, over half (54.7%) were in employment, 19.5% were students, and 19.9% were retired, which is likely a reflection of extended family structures or early retirement. Just 5.9% were unemployed. 50% of the sample reported their income was not satisfactory, while 45.3% satisfied, and 4.7% reported their income as very satisfactory.

Two adults were reported in most households (54.2%) and the majority had no children (37.5%); however, a considerable proportion had 1–2 children (50.2% combined). The vast majority of the population was urban (83.8%), while only 14.9% were rural. Regarding educational background, a large percentage of respondents was at least high school graduates (36.3%), while 28.3% had a bachelor's degree and 17.7%, a master's or PhD, and 17.7% had attended only elementary school or had no formal education. The higher level of education and urban concentration of this population allows to host a meaningful panel analysis of perceptions and behaviours regarding environmental sustainability and agroecological practices in Mauritania.

Table 43: Demographic characteristics of Mauritanian sample

Gender	N of answers	Percentage
Male	100	31.1
Female	222	68.9
Age		
18-24	65	20.2
25-34	93	28.9
35-44	72	22.3
45-59	75	23.3
60+	17	5.3
Professional status		
Unemployed	19	5.9
Employed	176	54.7
Student	63	19.5
Retired	22	19.9
Average monthly income		
Not satisfactory	161	50
Satisfactory	146	45.3
Very satisfactory	15	4.7
Number of adult household member		

1	48	15.6
2	168	54.2
3	51	16.3
4	43	13.9
Number of children in household		
0	117	37.5
1	75	24
2	81	26.2
3	26	8.5
4	11	3.5
5	4	1.2
Your household live in		
Rural	48	14.9
Peri-urban	4	1.3
Urban	270	83.8
Educational level		
No formal education	28	8.7
Elementary school	29	9
High school	117	36.3
Bachelor	91	28.3
Master /PhD	57	17.7

15.2 PCA results

A PCA to examine underlying patterns in consumer behaviour and attitudes towards the environment was performed on 34 Likert-scale questions. The analysis had the purpose of identifying the primary latent dimensions that summarize consumer perceptions about agroecology and sustainability. KMO and Bartlett's Test Sample adequacy was excellent as KMO value was 0.958 with acceptable threshold value of 0.6. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was also statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 10,052$; $df = 561$; $p < 0.001$), suggesting that there were adequate correlations in the dataset between variables to validate PCA.

Table 44: KMO and Bartlett's test for Mauritanian sample

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.958
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10.052
	df	561
	Sig.	<.001

Referring to the total variance explained after running the PCA, we were left with 4 principal components (eigenvalues > 1). They accounted for 68.1% of the total variance together:

Table 45: Total variance explained for Mauritania

Component	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	18.27	53.74	53.74
2	2.14	6.28	60.02
3	1.67	4.9	64.92
4	1.07	3.15	68.07

From PCA results obtained from Mauritanian sample a clear and persuasive depiction of how consumers in the country are following environmental and AE challenges has been emerged. Component 1 corresponds to “Environmental attitude and knowledge of AE practices”, which is very broad and dominant with numerous aspects of environmental values, environmental natural resource conservation concern, and strong knowledge of AEP. As these items include questions like “Protecting the environment should be a higher priority” and “I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals” it also shows that this component mixes ethical as well as knowledge dimensions. It is indicative of a highly engaged environmental worldview, in which consumers associate ecological quality with lifestyle change, biodiversity protection and health outcomes. Component 2, termed “attitude toward local food and packaging type”, revolves around concrete consumer behaviours (preference for recyclable packaging and support of locally produced food) signaling movement from rather abstract concern to actual purchasing behaviours. This behavioural variability also suggests that Mauritanian consumers care about environmental issues, but they act on that concern in ways that are affordable and convenient beforehand

Component 3 shows belief in the power of science and technology, and externalizes responsibility for environmental issues to richer countries, and is labelled “Perceptions on Environmental Issues”. This kind of global and institutional zoom out may point to both trust in macro-level solutions, but also a carefree disinterest for individual responsibility. In contrast, Component 4, “awareness of environmental issues”, captures some optimistic perceptions, like the belief that “environmental problems are exaggerated” or that “renewable resources never will run out.” These viewpoints may indicate gaps in environmental knowledge or conflicting narratives surrounding climate urgency and technological optimism. In combination, these elements provide evidence that although Mauritanian consumers may be well aware of and concerned with environmental and AE issues on a conceptual level.

Table 46: PCA results for Mauritania

Principal Components
<p>Component 1: Environmental attitude, knowledge of AE practices</p> <p>10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants</p> <p>10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations</p> <p>11.4 I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices</p> <p>12.3 I believe that agroecological practices are beneficial for my health</p> <p>10.15 Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment</p> <p>10.5 The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us</p> <p>11.1 Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem</p> <p>11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations</p> <p>10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth</p> <p>12.2 I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture</p> <p>10.17 We can accept changes in our lifestyles to protect natural resources</p> <p>10.11 We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem</p> <p>10.8 In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss) am worried about global warming</p> <p>12.5 I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources</p> <p>12.6 I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment</p> <p>10.9 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development</p> <p>10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment</p> <p>10.3 Optimised use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources</p> <p>12.10 I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating trees to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity</p> <p>12.12 I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming</p> <p>12.9 I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility</p> <p>12.8 I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health</p> <p>12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems</p> <p>12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices</p>
<p>Component 2: Attitude towards local food and packaging type</p> <p>11.2 When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable</p> <p>12.1 I am familiar with agroecological practices</p> <p>12.7 I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices</p> <p>11.3 I choose to purchase locally produced food</p>
<p>Component 3: Perceptions on environmental issues</p> <p>10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world</p> <p>10.2 Science and technology can solve all environmental problems</p>
<p>Component 4: Awareness of environmental issues</p> <p>10.1 Environmental problems are exaggerated</p> <p>10.14 The benefits of technology are greater than its harmful side effects</p>

10.12 Since natural resources (such as sun, wind, and water) can never be exhausted, energy will never run out on this planet

15.3 Linear Regression analysis results

Linear regression analysis on the sample of Mauritanian consumers showed several statistically significant differences between the four factors and demographics. Age, educational level and occupational class are the most important of these influencing characteristics. Age ($p < 0.001$), average monthly income ($p < 0.01$), region of origin ($p < 0.05$) and education level ($p < 0.001$) all had significant effects on Component 1 (Environmental attitudes and knowledge of AEP). This means that older individuals, more educated individuals with higher satisfaction with monthly income and urban residence are more likely to have strong environmental values and a greater understanding of SA practices.

Also, age ($p < 0.001$), average monthly income ($p < 0.001$), area of residence ($p < 0.01$) and education level ($p < 0.001$) all revealed statistically significant differences with Component 2 (Attitudes towards local food and packaging). This shows that the higher educational level of consumers but also their satisfaction with their income lead them mainly to more sustainable consumption decisions and to the search for recyclable food packaging.

Furthermore, age ($p < 0.05$), area of residence ($p < 0.05$) and education ($p < 0.05$) all had statistically significant effects on Component 3 (Perceptions on environmental issues). Younger consumers, those who live in urban areas and those who are less educated associate the development of technology and other global issues with environmental protection issues. Finally, regarding the fourth component, gender ($p < 0.001$) and area of residence ($p < 0.05$) are the demographic factors that significantly influenced it. More specifically, it seems that male consumers and rural residents have more doubts that there is an urgent need for environmental protection and declare themselves less aware of sustainability issues compared to women and urban consumers. In general, among Mauritanian consumers, education, gender, income, and place of residence influence their consumer decisions regarding the adoption of AEP.

Table 47: Correlation among PCA results and SE characteristics of Mauritanian sample

Socio-economic characteristics	Components			
	1	2	3	4
Age				
Gender				***
Professional status	***	***	*	
Average monthly income	**	***		

Number of adult household members				
Number of children in household				
Your household live in :	*	**		*
Educational level		***	*	

15.4 Willingness To Pay results

A large percentage of Mauritanian respondents (96.3%) stated that they are willing to purchase products that promote AEP. However, the results regarding the WTP extra for the purchase of these products differ depending on the specific socioeconomic characteristics of the consumers. Income and educational level influence more the willingness of Mauritanian consumers to pay for AE and locally produced foods. Respondents who claimed "satisfactory income" showed the highest positive correlation ($r = 0.14$), implying that those who are financially stable are more likely to purchase sustainably produced products. Those with a master's or PhD degree also showed a slightly positive correlation ($r = 0.09$), thus supporting the importance of education in promoting environmental responsibility and informed purchasing behaviour.

Although the difference between the gender responses is small, men are more willing to pay for AE food products ($r = 0.09$). Those who live in urban areas were somewhat less willing to pay for these products ($r = -0.14$), which is interesting given the trend observed in other countries outside of North Africa. Households with more adults or children were also weakly negatively associated with WTP, suggesting that financial constraints can affect the ability or WTP more for sustainable goods. Mauritanian WTP trends show that, while increased family size and urban living may create barriers, economic satisfaction and better education remain important factors in enhancing sustainable consumer behaviour.

15.5 Conclusions

This chapter examined Mauritanian consumer behaviour towards AE products and showed that there is generally a basic understanding of environmental concerns among the population. Mauritania generally shows good awareness and support for AE practices, but economic and informational barriers to wider consumer adoption persist. The most concerned consumers about sustainability and environmental protection are older consumers, more educated consumers, and income-satisfied consumers. Four main components emerged from the PCA analysis of the sample results. The most important and primary factor is the environmental attitudes and knowledge of consumers on AE, environmental responsibility and awareness of environmental issues. This factor explains more than 53% of the total variation, a fact that further strengthens its importance.

From the correlation of the factors with the demographic characteristics of the sample, it emerged that gender, place of residence but also level of education and monthly income satisfaction play the most important role, influencing almost all the factors. Although almost 96.3% of respondents stated that they would buy products with the AE label, socioeconomic factors influenced their actual willingness to pay (WTP) more for them. People with a higher educational level and a satisfactory income are more willing to pay for AE foods of all categories. Finally, families with a greater number of adult and minor members have less WTP extra, showing that family status is also an important factor influencing consumer decisions and choices.

Chapter 16

Consumer behaviour assessment for Tunisia

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Chapter 16. Consumer behaviour assessment for Tunisia

16.1 Demographic characteristics of the sample

Out of the 530 responses received, 521 of those responses were found to be valid for the purposes of this study following data cleaning procedures and included strong representation on key demographic indicators. 52% respondents were female and 48% were male and there was a significant age range in the sample, and the most frequent age groups both comprised over 12% of the sample (20–39 years). Older age categories (45–64 years) were also notably represented, suggesting a well-rounded demographic composition. Most of the participants who responded were employed (65.5%), 13.4% were students, 11.1% (retired), 10% (unemployed). In terms of the level of income satisfaction, 60.5% were satisfied, 33.8% were dissatisfied and only 5.8% took account of their income as high. It indicates a sample dominated by middle incomes and reasonably content with their economic circumstances.

The data also confirmed that nearly half (47.4%) of the participants' households had no children, suggesting a growing trend towards having nuclear families, with the majority of the households having two adults (42.4%). Educational level was: 39.3% of respondents held a bachelor's degree and 32.1% held a master's or PhD, while only 4% had no formal education. In terms of geography, 73.7% of the respondents (72% of the respondents) were living in urban areas, 18% in rural areas and 8.3% in peri-urban areas. Such distribution reflects the urban-centric nature of modern Tunisian society, but it still pulls in rural voices. In summary, demographics provide a solid groundwork for understanding consumer perception and attitude toward AE and environmental sustainability.

Table 48: Demographic characteristics of Tunisian sample

Gender	N of answers	Valid percent
Male	250	48.0
Female	271	52.0
Age		
20-24	67	12.9
25-29	64	12.3
30-34	64	12.3
35-39	64	12.3
40-44	54	10.4
45-49	52	10.0
50-54	49	9.4
55-59	37	7.1
60-64	27	5.2
65+	43	8.3
Professional status		
Unemployed	52	10.0

Employed	341	65.5
Student	70	13.4
Retired	58	11.1
Average monthly income		
Not satisfactory	176	33.8
Satisfactory	315	60.5
Very satisfactory	30	5.8
Number of adult household member		
0	5	1.0
1	47	9.0
2	221	42.4
3	98	18.8
4	99	19.0
5	36	6.9
6	12	2.3
7	2	.4
8	1	.2
Number of children in household		
0	247	47.4
1	109	20.9
2	123	23.6
3	36	6.9
4	4	.8
5	2	.4
Your household live in		
Rural	94	18.0
Peri-urban	43	8.3
Urban	384	73.7
Educational level		
No formal education	21	4.0
Elementary school	45	8.6
High school	83	15.9
Bachelor	205	39.3
Master /PhD	167	32.1

16.2 PCA results

A PCA was performed on 34 Likert-scale items that were measured from the Tunisian sample in order to explore deeper underlying structures in participants' attitudes and knowledge surrounding AEP and environmental issues. The suitability of the dataset for PCA was also demonstrated by a KMO value of 0.957, above the recommended threshold of 0.6; thus, the sampling adequacy and factorability were confirmed. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was also significant ($\chi^2 = 13707.00$, $df = 561$, $p < 0.001$), indicating adequate correlations between variables to factor extraction.

Table 49: KMO and Bartlett's test for Tunisian sample

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.957
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	13707.100
	df	561
	Sig.	<.001

Total variance explained PCA based on Kaiser's criterion (eigenvalues > 1) yielded six components, which explained 69.73% of the total variance. Using a Varimax rotation to maximize the distance between components helped us achieve better interpretability of factors by minimizing the cross-loadings, so that the thematic structure of each component would be as clear as possible.

Table 50: Total variance explained for Tunisia

Total Variance Explained									
Initial eigen value				Extraction some of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
Component	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	15.471	45.503	45.503	15.471	45.503	45.503	8.841	26.002	26.002
2	2.971	8.739	54.243	2.971	8.739	54.243	5.949	17.498	43.499
3	1.976	5.811	60.054	1.976	5.811	60.054	3.546	10.429	53.929
4	1.212	3.566	63.620	1.212	3.566	63.620	1.924	5.658	59.587
5	1.074	3.159	66.779	1.074	3.159	66.779	1.877	5.519	65.106
6	1.003	2.951	69.730	1.003	2.951	69.730	1.572	4.624	69.730

Labels have been given for every one of the six components that have emerged from PCA after using the varimax rotation technique and examining the rotated component matrix. The first component explains the degree of consumer awareness about AE practices by including all questions connected to AE practices such "Q.12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices." Nine questions make up the second part; "Q. 10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment" among them helps to gauge consumer attitudes toward environmental protection. Labeled "Consumer awareness toward environment," the third part contains queries including "Q.10.1 Environmental problems are exaggerated". Reflecting "Consumer awareness of environmental responsibility and solutions," the fourth component has questions such "Q. 10.3 Rich countries are responsible for

solving the environmental problems of the world". Labeled "Consumer perspectives on environment's future," the fifth component comprises two variables: "Q.11.1. Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem". Labeled "Consumer behaviour towards environmental protection," the sixth component is based on three variables reflecting the same concept including "Q.11.4 I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices."

Table 51: PCA results for Tunisian sample

Principal Components
<p><u>Component 1: Consumer awareness about AE practices</u></p> <p>12.12 I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming</p> <p>12.9 I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility</p> <p>12.10 I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating tree to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity</p> <p>12.11 I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems</p> <p>12.8 I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health</p> <p>12.5 I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources</p> <p>12.2 I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture</p> <p>12.3 I believe that agroecological practices are beneficial for my health</p> <p>12.4 I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices</p> <p>12.1. I am familiar with agroecological practices</p> <p>10.8 In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss)</p> <p>12.7 I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices</p> <p>12.6 I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment</p>
<p><u>Component 2: Consumer attitudes toward environmental protection</u></p> <p>10.16 Environmental protection is more essential than economic development.</p> <p>10.17 We can accept changes in our lifestyles to protect natural resources</p> <p>10.9 Environmental protection is more important than economic growth</p> <p>10.11 We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem</p> <p>10.15 Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment</p> <p>10.13 Optimized use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources</p> <p>10.10 There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations</p> <p>10.14 The benefits of technology are greater than its harmful side effects</p> <p>10.6 Human activity is damaging for the environment</p>
<p><u>Component 3: Consumer awareness toward environment</u></p> <p>10.1 Environmental problems are exaggerated</p> <p>10.7 I am worried about global warming</p> <p>10.12 Since natural resources (such as sun, wind, and water) can never be exhausted, energy will never run out on this planet</p> <p>10.4 Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants</p> <p>10.5 The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us</p>
<p><u>Component 4: Consumer awareness of environmental responsibility and solutions</u></p>

10.3 Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world 10.2 Science and technology can solve all environmental problems
<u>Component 5: Consumer perspectives on environment's future</u> 11.1. Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem 11.5 Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations
<u>Component 6: Consumer behaviour towards environmental protection</u> 11.2 When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable 11.3 I choose to purchase locally produced food 11.4 I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices

Results from the Tunisian dataset based on the PCA results indicate a multidimensional and integrated perception of consumers awareness and behaviour towards environmental sustainability and agroecological practices. Component 1, named “Consumer Awareness about AEP”, is the most detailed, grouping many variables that capture not only technical knowledge about AE (i.e. cover crops, crop rotation, livestock integration, reduced use of agrochemicals), but also interest on biodiversity and local food systems. AE was thought of by Tunisian consumers as a broad, health- and environment-centered approach to food production, given strong association with health benefits, environmental policy knowledge and locally produced food.

“Consumer attitudes toward environmental protection”, Component 2 represents a dimension where most respondents strongly agree that natural resources should be protected, environmental health should be given greater priority compared to economic growth. The same factor shows that consumers are willing to change their lifestyles to ensure a sustainable future (e.g., buy fewer products, buy only from sustainable companies). The fact that there are such statements from consumers, the human impact on the environment and responsibility suggests that there is an ethical basis for environmental concern in Tunisia.

The rest factors help to solidify the depth of public perception. Component 3 examines general environmental awareness, as they combine emotional responses such as fear of global warming and individual responsibility. Component 4 emphasizes questions of who is responsible for making and solving the world’s environmental problems, particularly through the lens of whether wealthy and/or scientific solutions are the solution to environmental degradation. Components 5 and 6 reflect more operational and prospective actions that are observed by others, including support for public education, sustainable purchasing, and willingness to practice AE principles. Such a layered structure reflects a significant development of environmental consciousness among Tunisian consumers, encompassing awareness, concern, moral responsibility, and behavioural intention as important variables.

16.3 Linear Regression analysis results

The six principal components retrieved from our PCA in Tunisian sample were subsequently tested in regard to socioeconomic characteristics using regression analysis. The results showed that the educational level was the most stable variable, the most influential as it was able to significantly predict three factors as follows: Component 1 (General Awareness of AE Practices, $p < 0.001$), Component 2 (attitudes toward environmental protection; $p < 0.001$), Component 3 (Environmental knowledge, $p < 0.001$). These findings show the importance of education in both determining environmental concern and knowledge about AEP. Higher frequencies of awareness and knowledge of environmental and sustainability issues were associated with consumers who had formal education, which are in agreement with the results of previous case studies that analyzed this particular region.

Place of residence (urban, rural, peri-urban) also significantly affected both Component 3 ($p < 0.001$) and Component 6 ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that urban consumers may be more aware of sustainable behaviours, like buying locally produced food. Average monthly income ($p < 0.01$ for Component 4 and $p < 0.05$ for Component 6) suggests that economic comfort is conducive to practical involvement in environmentally- friendly choices.

Results confirm that education is a leading determinant of environmental and agroecological awareness levels in Tunisia, whilst income and urban living conditions increase the consumer ability to adopt sustainable behaviours. These findings point to integrated educational and policy approaches that address less aware and lower affordability segments, facilitating the movement from pro-environmental attitude to behaviour change at scale.

Table 52: Correlation among PCA results and SE characteristics of Tunisian sample

Socio -economic characteristics	Components					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Age						
Gender	*					
Professional status		*				
Average monthly income	**					**
Number of adult household members						
Number of children in household						
Your household live in :			***			**
Educational level	***	***	***			

16.4 WillingnessTo Pay results

Results from Tunisia's case study indicate a high level of consumer acceptance of AE and locally produced food products with significant differences depending on food category. The largest proportions of consumers, who were willing to pay a premium were observed for AE olive oil, organic fruit, and locally- produced vegetables, suggesting that consumers prioritize products associated with typical consumption, health characteristics and natural methods of production. On the contrary, cereals, aromatic and medicinal plants, and dairy products had a lower average WTP, probably because of low awareness of their environmental impacts or price sensitivity in these categories.

WTP behaviour was significantly influenced by demographic variables. That shows in the case of AE olive oil, organic fruits, and locally produced vegetables that environmental and health awareness influence sustainable purchasing behaviour, whereas, educational level was the most stable factor that influence for most products. Age had positive effects as well, older consumers were more willing to pay for sustainable products such as cereals and meat. At more significant expense items (like dairy and meat), WTP was influenced by income level, suggesting that while values may affect many consumer decisions, affordability still serves as an obstacle for many consumers. Remarkably, the number of children in the household was linked to higher WTP for a few product categories, possibly reflecting a concern about family health and food quality. The Tunisian case study demonstrates important potential in growing AE markets, particularly for well-educated, urban living and older consumers.

16.5 Conclusions

In the Tunisian case study, the most important factor influencing consumers in the context of AE is consumer awareness of environmental conservation. Education level also plays the most important role in this study compared to other demographic factors, showing that consumers with tertiary education are generally more informed, more involved and more willing to adopt sustainable consumption practices. Furthermore, there are statistically significant differences in the responses given by consumers from urban and rural areas, with the latter being more aware of environmental protection issues.

With greater preferences for products such as olive oil and organic fruits, WTP findings revealed a modest tendency among Tunisian consumers to pay a premium for AE and local products – typically no more than 10% above the base price. The regression study, however, revealed that most socioeconomic factors did not significantly predict WTP for specific key items. Overall, discrepancies

between knowledge, attitudes and actual behaviour are observed among Tunisian consumers. Ultimately, although Tunisia has laid a good foundation for environmental awareness, changing consumer behaviour towards more sustainable behaviour – especially through WTP for AE products – requires a multi-faceted strategy.

PART 3

Framing social acceptability of agroecological combinations in North Africa

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PART 3. FRAMING SOCIAL ACCEPTABILITY OF AGROECOLOGICAL COMBINATIONS IN NORTH AFRICA

Part 3 Summary

A thorough review of the literature related to the social acceptability concept of environmentally friendly practices and innovations was conducted. This review provided valuable insights about the available frameworks and methodologies for assessing social acceptability in a very wide range of areas of innovations including agriculture. Based on this literature review helped to differentiate between two related concepts, i.e., acceptability and acceptance. Accordingly, the final methodology for assessing the social acceptability of AEPs was prepared. This methodology included the design of a generic model of the social acceptability framework of AEPs. This model served as the foundation for identifying the variables to measure the components of the suggested conceptual framework for the social acceptability of AEPs and their contextual setting. A list of these variables was prepared and incorporated into the design of the questionnaires to be used in the field data collection of the subsequent assessments and surveys. Training sessions on the developed methodology were conducted for the project Living Labs in three countries: Egypt in September 2024, and Mauritania and Tunisia in February 2025. For Morocco, a session is planned for April 2025, and for Algeria, a PhD candidate from the NATAE project will be handling the social acceptability component of the two Living Labs.

Chapter 17

Assessing Social Acceptability of AEP Combinations

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Chapter 17. Assessing Social Acceptability of AEP Combinations

17.1 Introduction

The core endeavour of the NATAE project is to support the main actors in the food production system in North African (NA) countries to transform these into sustainable farming systems. This process addresses some long-standing systems and hence needs enough time and tedious efforts. Thus, it should be based on introducing some alternative innovative combinations of agroecological practices (AEPs) to the farmers which proved they suit their conditions and context from all perspectives. The suitability of such AEPs and their combinations would encourage farmers to adopt and apply these AEPs in their fields.

However, the alternative packages to be recommended should have clear advantages for the actors compared with the existing ones to be accepted and maintained. Such acceptance cannot be sustained unless it is supported by several other partners within and outside the local community who are concerned the final product to perpetuate. Hence, the transformation process requires constructive societal dialogue to reconfigure the networks of relationships among concerned actors to reach a socially accepted approach to change. Nevertheless, this process of transition, especially if it needs deep changes in the existing structures, requires a smooth fusion of the alternative solutions that are most relevant to the territorial context (Sachet, et al., 2021) from the environmental, social, economic, technical, and cultural dimensions. Yet, it is worth mentioning that the traditional culture, including religion, the value system, and heritage in the NA region affect the practices accepted in a wide range of fields. Farming practices in food production systems are no exception in this regard. Thus, the social acceptability of any technical, institutional, and behavioural changes to be recommended is crucial to the establishment of clear transition pathways toward the adoption of AE practices and products in sustainable food systems.

The previous conditions have attracted attention to the concept of social acceptability which gained an early interest in many technical fields, especially in Information Technology (IT) products and applications, and renewable energy projects. This was due to the social constraints encountered when introducing new technologies to customers and communities. This situation was also found valid in the case of introducing new technologies in the agricultural development projects associated with the trials to apply the Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) and the family farming approaches by the FAO and other international development agencies.

In their valuable review study, Busse and Siebert (2018) introduced a very wide range of definitions of social acceptability that need further analysis to adopt the one that is more suitable for NATEA and its specific objectives. One of the definitions to be considered is the one introduced by Shindler and

Brunson (2004), which defined SA as a judgment that people make about whether an action, attribute, or condition is considered preferable to possible alternatives. Yet, a further review of the literature has indicated that many advocates of the concept have referred to the need to differentiate between social acceptability as a process and social acceptance as an outcome (Busse & Siebert, 2018). In the context of the planned activities of NATAE this differentiation and adoption of the two concepts seem logical and needed. They would be more suitable for a proxy longitudinal study, i.e. before and after the experimentation (Gordon, et al., 2014) of the recommended AEPs. Accordingly, there is a need to differentiate between social acceptability and social acceptance (Busse & Siebert, 2018) in our task which will help identify the difference between the purpose of the first SA assessment survey and the second one planned after the experimentation phase in the LLs. Intensive reading of these differences that will be reflected in the design of the variables, their measures, and data collection tools is needed before finalizing the design of the data collection tools. This process was started by the team already and is going on now.

As mentioned in the ToR of this task, Gendron (2014), mentioned that SA is a collective evaluation rather than an individual position, in the sense that the judgment of acceptability contributes to and affects the social dynamics likely to forge and transform it. Thus, the author stresses that social acceptability is primarily determined by shared values and beliefs while acknowledging that individual preferences also play a decisive role in shaping this collective judgment.

On the other side, social acceptability is influenced by the social dynamics that include changes that might happen in the network of relationships among experts, decision-makers, and civil society that reflect the viability of this dynamic. Furthermore, as civil society has become more active, it has more capacities to contribute to more relevant decisions locally by mobilizing its own experts and expertise. As a result, social acceptability is shaped by complex socio-economic and cultural interactions, in which value systems, beliefs, experience, and scientific knowledge play important roles in shaping the future.

Yet, in the context of NATAE overall objectives, the methodology that would be recommended should consider the multidimensionality, multipolarity, and complexity of the social acceptability concept and its application under diversified contexts. For that reason and based on the early review of the literature and planned interaction with the LLs' leaders, a blend of methods and tools will be reviewed and analyzed to check their suitability for the local conditions and the benefits to be gained by the concerned community where each LL is located (Cowell, Bristow, & Munday, 2011). Furthermore, the diversity of the environmental, socioeconomic, technical, administrative, and cultural conditions of the selected LLs will require the construction of a flexible and multidimensional conceptual framework/model that would ensure using of suitable methods and participatory tools for performing the Social Acceptability Survey under different contexts. This approach would allow comparability of

the results at the territorial level. This criterion is needed to reach and recommend strategic options derived from the participatory assessments for AE transition under diversified conditions and contexts.

Hence, exploring a comprehensive conceptual framework of social acceptability that is suitable for the diversified context is a key criterion in investigating the main variables/factors that would facilitate or hinder the social acceptability of agroecological practices. This framework should help operationalization, and the quantification of the related measures needed to bring changes in the related factors existing in reality. This is one of the main functions of the review of literature activity of the SA team.

In addition, the methodology to be recommended for the SA survey should be based on a framework that supports the use of a complementary package of tools rather than one or limited tools. Each tool has its privileges and shortcomings but using a blend of methods and tools will help complementarity and comprehensiveness of the gathered information and data. However, these tools will depend, primarily, on the actual conditions prevailing in each LL territory, the community of farmers concerned, the institutional structure, the concerned stakeholders, and the related AE packages recommended.

17.2 The Literature Review and suggested approaches for the SA assessment

17.2.1 Literature review

To select and recommend specific approaches and tools for the fulfillment of the task of social acceptability assessment, it was mandatory to review related literature to facilitate reaching a relevant conceptual framework and model for action first. This task needed a lengthy process of search of the materials published about the social acceptability of innovations whether in the field of agroecology or any other field of new technologies. All members of the SA team contributed to this task which resulted in collecting of the materials listed in Annex H.

The review process relied on the collected materials as well as the theoretical analyses of the concept of Social Acceptability from various social, psychological, and technical perspectives. This process will help prepare a review of the literature paper that the team plans to publish later.

However, careful review and analysis of the appropriate items of the published materials have shown that we have to consider the following aspects for the Social Acceptability concept. First, we have to differentiate between two very close concepts; social acceptability and social acceptance. The major differences between the two are related to the time sequence of occurrence, the complexity of the structure of the related conceptual framework, and the nature of action. Social acceptability comes first before the experimentation of the innovation while social acceptance comes next to the

experimentation process. Second, the social acceptability conceptual framework is more complex than that related to social acceptance, Third, social acceptability is concerned with the social process and social action among different partners and stakeholders while social acceptance is more related to the outcome of the process itself at the community and actors' level. In brief, social acceptability is concerned with the willingness to act while social acceptance is more concerned with the behavioural action, i.e. adoption and implementation of specific practices. Yet, a detailed discussion and analysis of the two concepts will be included in the review paper to be published later.

The SA team discussed the applicability and the advantages and disadvantages of applying the different research methods and designs for this study including the with/without, and the pre/post designs. The pros and cons for each design were discussed with the background of the overall objectives of NATAE project in consideration. Therefore, the SA team excluded the "with and without" design for several reasons, including the need to identify resembling areas that have the same environmental, socioeconomic, technical, administrative, and cultural conditions of the selected LLs, which require time, effort, and data to perform territorial diagnosis in order to choose these resembling areas.

A pre-post (before/after) design is considered more adequate when taking into consideration the intervention required through the experimentation component of the project, the timeframe of actions, the efforts needed, and the financial resources available. This design would allow, as well, independent researchers to adopt the NATAE project methodology to conduct their studies under their diversified local, regional, and national conditions. This approach requires applying the survey at two points in time. First, the survey will be conducted on a sample of the LLs' producers before the actual implementation of the AE practices to assess the degree of SA that producers hold due to their exposure to training and awareness dissemination by the LL leaders and project experts. Second, the survey will be applied to the same respondents, as much as we can, after the actual implementation of the AE practices; i.e. the experimentation.

17.2.2 Suggested approaches for the SA assessment

Based on the review of literature, it was found that the concept of social acceptability was widely used in a very wide range of technical areas where new innovations and products are generated for public and individual uses. Nevertheless, the proposed methodology for assessment of the SA of AEPs and their combinations will use a mix of methods to perform task 3.3. The quasi- experimental design will be the main method to be applied to assess the relationship between the social acceptability dimensions and the contextual factors and variables that are suggested to be in relationship with these dimensions before and after the NATAE intervention. The quantitative method will be the main

option for preparing the measures of these variables and selecting the data collection and the related statistical analysis tools. Meanwhile, the qualitative method will be fully incorporated into the recommended mix of methods. Yet, it is worth mentioning that identifying the Social Acceptability survey before the experimentation process could be considered the main source of the baseline data for the experimentation phase while the Social Acceptance survey will be the source of output/outcome evaluation of the experimentation process.

Table 53: The quasi-Experimental design of the SA assessment surveys

Survey Design								
Survey	Living Lab Location and round of data							Type of Data
Social Acceptability	LL1.1	LL2.1	LL3.1	LL4.1	LL5.1	LL6.1	LL7.1	Baseline
Intervention (Experimentation Phase)								
Social Acceptance	LL1.2	LL2.2	LL3.2	LL4.2	LL5.2	LL6.2	LL7.2	Post Evaluation

Design: Mohamed Nawar

The Table 52 mentioned above indicates that several types of needed analyses of data and situations will be available to serve the overall objectives of NATAE. For instance, a horizontal level of comparative analysis among all living labs will be available separately before or after the intervention. In addition, a vertical type of analysis at each living lab level before and after the intervention will also be available. These kinds of comparative analyses are needed to reach some general conclusions that are necessary for building public policy recommendations.

Nevertheless, in case of the need for a more rigorous research design to help in better attribution and causation of the sources of change in the second survey, it is recommended to use a control group design at least of small samples. The use of the experimental/control, i.e. with/without group design along with the before/after design is likely to contribute to more meaningful results. Yet, it poses a more complex design of the surveys and more burden, i.e. time and effort on the local teams of the LLs which will need the full involvement of all partners in each LL in making the proper decision.

In addition, the assessment of the farmers' SA of the newly recommended packages of the AE practices will need to use both the participatory approach and the experimental design of the research needed. By participatory approach we mean the actual involvement of the targeted groups, i.e. the

farmers and concerned stakeholders in the selection and approval of the measures of the SA-related variables and data collection tools as well as providing the field data. When dealing with research design we have the choice between two options, either to use any of the alternative experimental/control group designs or the before/after design. Each option has its advantages and disadvantages. However, the complexity of the first option is concerned with two aspects, the first is related to the difficulty of ensuring a selection of a community/territory similar to the community/territory of the concerned LL before the intervention in addition to being able to ensure that the sole source of change between the two areas is the introduction of the AEPs in the LL area and the absence of that factor in the control area. The second will be the problem of attribution and causation of any difference between the experimental and control areas that will need a very delicate handling to separate the effect of the intervention on the measured variables if any change is captured. Yet, in the case of adopting the second option the problem of attribution and causation of the possible change of the measured variables persists.

In addition to the constraints mentioned, we have to consider the LLs' capacity to understand and help them face the challenges of applying the first option. Hence, the SA team suggests an early discussion of this issue with the LLs' leaders to reach a scenario that could be adopted by all concerned partners. This will be followed with a thorough training of the field data collectors on the customized tools of data collection, once we agree upon the final versions of these customized tools. An initiative to reach this agreement took place during the Tunis consortium event last April/May through the meeting with leaders of the LLs in Mauritania and Tunis, and the distribution of situational analysis data collection tools Annex I to them. A follow-up with the leaders of the LLs in the above-mentioned two regions in addition to the colleague in Morocco took place immediately after the Feast in June. Only the Tunisian colleague responded by explaining the stage their LL is going through. For collecting the data for both social acceptability and social acceptance surveys from the farmers, a pretested questionnaire will be applied with personal interviews with the selected sample of farmers in each LL. This will need an agreement on the sampling technique to be used in all LLs to ensure compatibility without jeopardizing the diversity of conditions in the LLs.

Yet, based on the suggested conceptual framework of Social Acceptability and its generic model presented in Figures 109-110, the first version of this structured questionnaire is attached in Annex J. It includes all measures related to the dimensions of the concept as well as the contextual factors and variables suggested to affect social acceptability from the farmers' point of view.

Figure 109: The Draft Generic Model of Social Acceptability Conceptual Framework

Figure 110: Draft Model of the Social Acceptance Conceptual Framework

In addition, collecting the field data related to the contextual variables at the community level that were included in the generic model of SA will use both desk work and Focus Group discussion meetings (FGM) techniques. These FGMs will involve representatives of all concerned stakeholders in each LL. A checklist of the questions to be raised in the FGMs will be prepared ahead of and customized for each LL to guide the activities planned for each LL.

17.2.3 Sampling

Since the survey will be applied under diversified socioeconomic, environmental, and cultural contexts uniformity of the unit of study under these conditions should be maintained, as much as it possible, to allow comparability. The SA team will try to benefit from both the farm typology study and the socioeconomic territorial diagnostic analyses performed by other WGs in the identification of comparable units of study under these diversified contexts. Initially, the farm household, regardless of the farm type, is suggested to be the unit of study in the SA assessment survey. The source of information related to this unit will be the operator/holder whether he/she is the owner or a tenant. The most important is to conduct personal interviews with the decision maker or an informed respondent at that level.

Selection of the cases to be studied in each LL should ensure the representation of all LL members of all types with their relative weight in the LL in the sample structure. This means, initially, using the random sampling techniques in the selection process of these cases. However, the LLs' territories might have heterogeneous structures regarding the actors' farming systems, cropping structures, farm size, farming practices, irrigation techniques, harvesting practices, and marketing avenues. Therefore, to maintain a realistic representation of the LLs' population, in the statistical sense, a quota or proportional random sampling technique might be suggested in the LLs that are characterized by a clear heterogeneity of its structure of farm types.

Hence, a clear overview of the LL structure from the farm typology and the socioeconomic characteristics of LL communities' perspectives is mandatory for the sampling process.

Determination of the size of sample in each LL will be based on some of the well known applications like the following one: <https://www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator.html?type=1&cl=90&ci=5&pp=50&ps=35330&x=Calculate>

17.2.4 Suggested Tools of field data collection

To ensure applicability of needed comparisons regarding the producers' degree of SA of the AEPs among all LLs the methodology is intended to be generic. This would allow adaptability to the different conditions in all selected LLs and their territories. Therefore, a structured form of the data collection tools was designed to satisfy the comparability criterion.

For the main tool of collecting the field data from the farmers a structured questionnaire that include all the measures of the dimensions and contextual factors and variables in model of SA was prepared.

Structure of the questionnaire attached in Appendix J includes the following;

Section 1: Farmers' socio-economic characteristics:

Section 2: Farm characteristics

Section 3: Social Acceptability related Variables; AEPs' information, knowledge, risk assessment, and attitudes)

Section 4: Stakeholder Analysis

Section 5: Capacity building and Incentives Section 6: Social Capital (Trust)

By the end of the questionnaire, there will be an open-ended section for the data collectors to register their comments on the process of field data collection which would help capture the constraints during that process. The attached version of the questionnaire is being translated into Arabic.

However, the customized questionnaire will be subject to a pretest on small numbers of farmers in the nearby territories to reach the final form of the customized questionnaire. This final form which all partners should approve will be used in the training session of the field data collectors. These training sessions will follow the implementation of the two workshops of the farmers and the representatives' boards and will be agreed upon by each LL leader and to provide the facilities and logistics needed for this pivotal activity.

Following the training, the national teams in the selected LLs will apply the SA survey tools under with monitoring of the SA senior expert and his team. The collected data will be processed and managed locally in a manner agreed upon in advance to ensure the best opportunity for comparability of these data from all LLs' sites (Pre-survey). Before this process the SA team will ensure that the data entry of all collected field data in all LLs is manipulated in a unified method, i.e, using the same kind of datasheet files, like Excel, and a unified data file structure that could be transferred to the SPSS package data files that the SA team will use in data analysis. Guidance from the SA team side will be available to all LLs concerned personnel to ensure uniformity in this regard.

One of the components of the SA generic model is the stakeholder analysis where there will be a need to identify the role of each partner in supporting the implementation of the AEPs and their combinations at the farm level according to the farming system they belong to (Teixeira et al, 2018) and in light of the farming typology. Identifying these roles will need focus group discussion meetings to be organized in each LL. This stage cannot be undertaken before the full selection of the suitable

AEPs and their combinations for each LL and implementation of the two workshops of the farmer workshop and the Living Lab representatives' board workshop.

17.2.5 Statistical analysis of collected field data

Once the data processing is completed the entire SA team will work on the analysis of these data according to a specific plan and report structure to be prepared upon agreement with NATEA PMC. The report's structure will be designed to answer all the questions necessary to lead to an action plan for transforming the food and farming systems towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly practices and products in general and in the concerned territories in specific. Meanwhile, this will lead to reaching conclusions for the post-experimentation design in each LL as well as shedding light on a number of research and policy questions that would suit each territory and its context. It is worth mentioning that preparation of the statistical tools needed for immediate data entry and data clearance using the SPSS was established.

Currently, fieldwork for the social acceptability component of the study is running throughout several areas. This section of the study aims to grasp how local communities view and interact with agroecological techniques from a social and cultural perspective. A follow-up report set for release in November 2025 (Deliverable 4.7) will give the results together with a more in-depth study of consumer behaviour, including aggregated data from the whole sample and a cross-country comparison across the five North African countries. This report will offer more understanding of the reasons, preferences, and social dynamics shaping consumer decisions in many different geographical settings as well as the acceptance of agroecology.

General Conclusion

General Conclusion

Analysing agroecological value chains could be regarded as more than added value to products in the different stages of the supply chain emerging from agroecological and sustainable practices. Given the strong socio-economic place given by agroecology to influence the empowerment and livelihoods of producers, then agroecological value chains are to consider the marketability and income production of products particularly from small producers and their recognized qualities. Such dynamics are important to consider in a context like that of North Africa where vulnerability is increasing at multiple levels such as environmental, social, and economic. North Africa is a region subjected to growing climatic shocks, water stress, and degradation of natural resources particularly the soil and biodiversity. Population growth, poverty, and gender disparities add socio-economic challenges to the growing needs for food and food security that tend to influence policy towards intensive farming and increase in production. While the recognition of agroecology is underway and signs of its infiltration is starting to appear among local actors, especially with the support of civil society and research institutions, the building of knowledge around the larger value chains and food systems is yet to be developed.

This deliverable consists of an analysis of the potential of agroecological value chains in seven territories in five North African countries including Algeria, Egypt, Mauritania, Morocco, and Tunisia. It is developed under the framework of the Horizon Europe NATAE project, Task 3.2. The production of this deliverable was led by the CIHEAM-IAMM in close collaboration with the local partners of CARI, CREAD, GRDR, ENAM, INAT and one external expert for Egypt. Data collection and primary analysis was conducted by local partners following the methodology, questionnaires and outline provided by the task leader resulting in seven distinct reports for each of the studied territories. After that, a transversal analysis was produced synthesizing the findings while highlighting common observations and trends, barriers and challenges, and finally describing an overall insight on the potential of emergence of agroecological value chains in such contexts.

Results show a multitude of observations that emerge with common trends on one hand, and with some direct specificities linked to specific territories on another. Overall, on-farm practices, which are being analysed in more depth in other project deliverables, are seen to be market by small-scale farm sizes which many today still rely on chemical inputs and have limited access to quality seeds or agroecological alternative inputs. Yet, some agroecological practices are registered consisting of for example intercropping, water-saving techniques, and organic fertilization, but are often applied out of necessity in effort to reduce costs and not out of adoption of practices. Additionally, weak infrastructure is noticed in the majority of territories in storage, transportation, and overall logistics which lead to significant losses and add high costs especially for small producers thus restricting their access to markets. In fact, market access in North Africa generally and in the analysed territories

specifically show a mix of subsistence agriculture and market-oriented production trends. The former is more common in more 'family-like farms' such as in Morocco's Meknes and Algeria's Tizi Ouzou regions where producers prioritise self-consumption and sell surplus produce. For the latter, limited resources and logistical capacity push producers to rely on intermediaries that handle bulk purchases, transportation and ensure market access. These are the cases seen mostly in Egypt's Luxor, Morocco's Meknes, and Mauritania's PK-17. However, economic return in such cases is compromised and producers attain prices lower than market average to ensure selling; one of the consequences of limited collective action and bargaining power.

Only rare exceptions exist such as in the case of Algeria's oasis and peri-oasis region in Laghouat and mountains in Tizi Ouzou where short circuit consumption are found to be revolving around family and community networks mainly for medicinal and aromatic plants, olive oil, and dates, but is based on limited quantities and strong producer-consumer trust system. For Tunisia's Siliana region, the state-regulated value chains provide secure linkages with certified actors of the value chain therefore reducing the risks related to ensuring of markets and price disparities for olive oil and cereals. Yet, fluctuations in prices are strongly reported and relate to global price trends and those emerging from national and climate-related contexts. In Mauritania's PK-17, being a peri-urban territory near the capital Nouakchott, the involvement of the state and regional authorities shows that accessibility to small-scale farming could be attained in an urban environment, and with the existence of specialized markets, added-value return is possible. Yet, this remains accessible only to 'elite' consumers and not the average general public.

Other forms of marketing as direct contact between producers and consumers does exist around North Africa and take the shape of weekly (or periodic) open markets as *souks*. Yet, the issue remains in the limited small quantities capable of being dispatched through such arenas, providing only a partial sale whereas producers tend to prefer to ensure the selling of their entire production quantities. On another hand, probably one of the bigger findings is evidence of clear vertical linkages between actors rather than a horizontal integration inclusive of collective work. Self organization of producers such as in cooperatives remains limited in the studied territories, with most producers acting individually and relying on vertical relationships with markets or intermediaries. Yet, some successful examples are reported mostly in women-led cooperatives. This is the case for example of the mountainous agrosystem in Skoura, Morocco's Boulemane region, where women-led cooperatives are growing in their efforts to facilitate land access for medicinal and aromatic plants cultivation along olive groves of family members, mainly spouses. Such efforts are found interesting given women's weak access to property rights, one of the major challenges for women in agriculture over North Africa mainly due to legislative gaps and socio-cultural norms.

Another example from Algeria's Tizi Ouzou mountains also demonstrate successful collective efforts involving women in the foraging, cultivation and value addition of medicinal and aromatic plants, further highlighting the potential of such a value chain on the socio-economic level and in local short circuits. Moreover, in such short-circuit contexts, the consideration of formal added value tools such as certification are not seen to be as potentially effective where personal or community networks are at the basis of accessing the local market.

Overall awareness and knowhow around formal certification remain in fact highly variable between territories and many primary producers and local actors around North Africa are becoming increasingly aware of the benefit held by certification especially in enhanced marketability. However, certification remains unaffordable and inaccessible by the majority for multiple reasons chiefly due to the unaffordability of certification prices, absence of clear differentiation, and/or weak understanding and knowledge around the system. Possible alternatives could entail initiatives such as the Participatory Guarantee System (PGS) which is a form of community-based guarantee system that has shown some pilot successes in countries as Morocco even if it remains informal to date. Thus, one of the questions to be raised is on the suitability of capitalizing on the successes and lessons learned from experiences of the PGS and therefore its applicability to other contexts in efforts to provide an alternative to conventional certification systems. Other local concepts such as the *beldi* could also be worth exploring in their cultural heritage component that such products embody along with their reputation in being produced following natural methods and processes. Such products could potentially offer alternative value addition, as opposed to conventional certification, that are based on tradition and community habits therefore maintaining a strong link with the socio-cultural identity of localities. As such, a preserving of traditional practices could be framed in a suitable pathway for agroecological products which many times transcends to practices mastered by women especially in food processing and preservation.

This is an essential trail to consider as a means of encouraging and empowering the participation of women in the economic cycle and in collective groups especially since gender disparities still prevail today. Across North Africa, women play a significant role in agriculture, but their participation today remains largely limited to unskilled manual labor. Despite irregular initiatives in enhancing their employment (as in sun-drying in Luxor, Egypt), their roles in the sector is characterised by minimal decision-making power, leadership, or access to resources and property rights. Today, the majority of countries in North Africa lack any proper inclusivity for women particularly in land ownership and relevant legislation thus marginalizing women as landowners, seen to be less than 5-6% in Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia. This is why initiatives that revolve around women in leadership roles, as in the MAPs sector in Skoura Morocco and Tizi Ouzou Algeria, are important. Their promising results showcase pilot successes in accessing of resources and information, attain enhanced market

participation, and therefore hold a strong potential for the socio-economic inclusion and enhancement of livelihoods.

Consumer behaviour assessment tries to understand in depth the factors that influence North African consumers (Algerians, Egyptians, Moroccans, Mauritians and Tunisians) in terms of the choice and consumption of AE products. At the same time, the socio-economic factors that influence each component were studied as well as the WTP extra for specific categories of AE and locally produced foods. The results of the study show that there are several similarities in consumer trends in the five countries, however, there are also very significant differences in consumer habits.

The level of education is one of the most important factors that determine knowledge about AE foods and sensitivity to environmental issues. Consumers who have a higher level of education are more concerned about issues such as climate change and biodiversity loss and are more willing to pay extra for sustainable goods. Age is another important factor influencing consumer decisions, especially in the cases of Algeria and Egypt. Older consumers in these countries are associated with higher levels of environmental awareness. The same applies to consumers who are satisfied with their monthly income in Mauritania and Egypt. Occupational status and place of residence equally influence consumer decisions. Area of living usually had more access to knowledge but not always the highest WTP.

The order of appearance of the factors differs from country to country, indicating different priorities that drive consumer decision-making. For example, for Moroccan consumers it is more important to acquire knowledge about agroecological practices, while for Tunisians this concern appears only among consumers with a higher educational level. Also, many consumers in all countries strongly associate sustainable agriculture with better human health in addition to environmental protection. However, in some settings - such as Mauritania and Tunisia - beliefs about technology improve environmental problems and doubts about the seriousness of environmental concerns also emerged. Regarding the WTP findings, they were generally positive in most countries, with consumers want to support AE foods. However, when asked whether they were willing to pay more money to obtain them, the answers varied. In general, it can be said that North African consumers are more willing to pay for olive oil, fruits and vegetables. In contrast, cereals and aromatic medicinal plants produced according to AEP were not as popular with consumers. As expected, larger household size and lower income were associated with lower WTP. This is particularly evident in Egypt and Mauritania.

Based on the different beliefs that emerged from the parties involved in the supply chain, different environmental needs and concerns arise that differentiate the possibility of transitioning towards the adoption of agroecological practices by region. Many small farmers in different regions know or already apply certain agroecological practices mainly in the olive oil, date and cereal value chains. However, it seems that these practices are either not fully supported or are not completely applicable.

Among the most common problems noted is the structural fragility of the group organization. Often at prices much lower than their real value, most producers work alone and depend on intermediaries to reach the markets, selling their harvest. The lack of strong cooperatives or producer organizations hinders their access to better markets, loans, inputs or training and weakens their bargaining power. Cooperatives are sometimes weak or inactive even when they exist. At the same time, some extreme points were observed, particularly in MAP value chains, where women's groups were able to develop more socially inclusive and economically viable models, thus demonstrating how collective action can promote both production and agroecological principles.

Although it can be useful for creating new markets and increasing income, certification remains inaccessible to most smallholders. Formal certification methods are considered costly, complex and remote from the reality of local producers. It is common for producers to be unaware of the processes or advantages of growing agroecological products. Even when they do, they usually lack the financial and institutional support to participate in certification schemes. Although still developing and not yet widely adopted or recognised by national authorities, alternatives such as PGS provide a more accessible and community-based type of quality assurance.

The study of consumer behaviour reveals a promising but cautious trend. Across all research locations, people show a growing interest in organic, healthier, locally produced foods. Many people view goods associated with agroecology favourably, particularly those linked to cultural or historical customs. Largely due to affordability and a lack of knowledge about agroecological practices and their benefits, this enthusiasm does not necessarily translate into purchasing activity. Consumers have difficulty understanding what agroecology means. Without the appropriate labelling or credible promises, they rely primarily on personal connections and local markets to purchase food. Although still small in size and unable to leverage highly organized or established agroecological markets, this trust-based approach works effectively in small food supply chains.

Laghouat's focus was on dates and olive oil. Producers there struggle with low market prices, easier access to inputs, and express concerns about water shortages. Many depend on informal marketing and traders, which reduces their profits. The olive oil industry is fragmented and lacks a coordinated and more collective effort. Both the olive oil and MAPs value chains in Tizi-Ouzou revealed greater community participation, especially among women in MAP projects, which showed encouraging group models despite poor formal structures. Consumers in both regions have confidence in local and traditional products. At the same time, their knowledge of AEP and food labels is minimal. Most purchases are made through direct relationships or trust in the local market. When goods are perceived as locally produced or healthy, there is a WTP more, and this mainly concerns more educated consumers with a relatively satisfactory monthly income, while age and gender do not change the results much.

MAPs and tomatoes were examined in Luxor's LL. While MAPs are grown on a smaller scale and are usually sold without processing or branding, the tomato industry is dominated by monoculture and the use of mainly chemical inputs. Producers sell to traders and/or local markets, so there is a high dependence on them. Access to premium markets and value addition are limited. Although many consumers do not distinguish between agroecological and conventional products, interest in natural and traditional products, especially MAPs is growing. Price remains the determining factor influencing consumers' decisions. Certification and labeling is not widely understood, and purchases are made based on knowledge and perceived quality.

The study in Mauritania focused on turnips and onions in a peri-urban setting. Smallholders struggle to obtain inputs, infrastructure and consistent markets. Almost all depend on traders and there is no organized group structure. Although not methodically, agroecological techniques are used informally. Consumers prioritize cheapness and rely heavily on local markets. Knowledge of organic farming or agroecology is quite low. Trust in known suppliers shapes purchasing choices more than any idea of sustainable or environmental agriculture.

Existing traditions and a high demand for local quality make the olive oil and MAP industries in Boulemane particularly promising for the agroecological transition. Cooperatives are still underdeveloped and formal accreditation is uncommon. Onion and mint farmers in Meknes use various techniques, but land fragmentation and market dependence are significant obstacles. Producers are not very well coordinated. Consumers associate local, traditional goods with excellence and show a strong preference for them. Awareness of agroecological ideas, meanwhile, is growing and consumers seem to recognize the benefits of sustainable and agroecological products. Many, especially the more educated middle-aged consumers, also report a high willingness to pay extra to buy them.

The olive oil and cereals sectors were examined for the case of Tunisia. Cereal producers suffer from poor teamwork, limited processing capacity and market instability. Although assistance for sustainable techniques is still lacking, olive oil production is better organised. Producers are aware of ecological limits, but environmental conditions such as insufficient rainfall create difficulties. Especially for olive oil, consumers are increasingly concerned about local products and food quality. Although there is a desire to pay more for quality, knowledge of agroecological or certified systems is lacking. Most purchases are made in conventional markets, where trust and reputation are paramount.

Overall, when assessing the agroecological practices within the value chains identified in the reports, they are seen to contribute to the 10 elements of agroecology (FAO, 2018): Diversity: Practices include crop rotations, intercropping, and manure use to enhance soil fertility; Synergies: include intercropping in olive and date farming, integrating livestock for weed control, and using organic fertilizers in agroforestry systems; Efficiency: sun-drying, drip irrigation, composting, and integrated

pest management improve cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability in agriculture; Co-creation and Sharing of Knowledge: some farmers, especially women, share innovations through cooperatives, which strengthens market positions and facilitates direct sales; Human and Social Values: Women play key roles in harvesting and processing, and cooperatives help enhance economic opportunities; Culture and Food Traditions: some products serve as both food and medicine, linked to cultural identity; Circular and Solidarity Economy: repurposing crop residues for compost or animal feed.

These show that there are multiple considerations to be equated. Many value chains rely on informal governance, with recommendations to strengthen collective action through collective organizations to enhance bargaining power. The recommendations stress the importance of fostering entrepreneurship, improving infrastructure, and supporting collective actions. Policies should consider promoting sustainable practices that are economically performant, alongside recognition by consumers and markets of the added value linked to agroecological products, as these are essential for fostering long-term success. Circular economy principles and solidarity networks can help reduce costs and environmental impact while strengthening value chains.

Special emphasis should also be placed on community development and women's empowerment. As such, some questions could be raised in relation to developing the emergence of agroecological of agroecological value chain potential in North Africa. A particularly important point for policy considerations would be in identifying trade-offs in what is believed as incompatibilities between food security objectives, which are usually linked with increased productions and yields with decreased import dependency, and sustainability objectives integrating agroecological principles linked to decreased use of inputs. In fact, some misalignment exist today with what is being applied. On one hand, many public policy strategies around North Africa clearly state integrating more environmentally-friendly objectives related to agricultural practices, environmental sustainability, management of natural resources, preservation of biodiversity and others. Yet, evident cases show that multiple national strategies remain clearly in support of subsidies to conventional chemical inputs without provide any direct support to the accessing of alternative inputs and machinery which are more agroecological. On another hand, a similar paradox emerges between strategies aligning with environmental sustainability and export. In fact, increased export objectives enter in the national strategies of multiple countries in North Africa such as in Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia. The question raised is how export value chains could align with efforts made to reduce environmental impact under agroecological principles with increased food miles and the entering international shipping processes; a similar state in which organic production is produced and traded today.

Ultimately, what is certain is that multiple factors need to be well-developed and functioning in synergy to improve the emergence of agroecological value chains in North Africa. These span from the

structuring and dissemination of public information and awareness around agroecology to drive demand and supply trends upward together, along with the capacity building of primary producers in adopting new practices and in understanding their benefits. Availability of markets and their access remains of the essential components to consider since. If there are no accessible markets for farmers, then transitioning to agroecology will not have a concrete driver for farmers to change their habits of production, possibly requiring more effort, only to achieve the same (or even less) outcome. The driver, being the market and its returns, should be encouraging enough to them and concretised in tangible added value that could stimulate a change in production modes. Self organization capacities and participatory governance structures are another main factor that places small producers at their center, provides the ability to engage in decision-making and networking, and therefore in achieving an autonomous ownership for directing a trajectory towards agroecological transitions of local food systems. It is important to recognize that fostering adoption also depends heavily on a supportive enabling environment. This includes factors such as public policies and institutional frameworks, secure property rights, access to credit, active civil society involvement, and other supportive mechanisms in addition to product differentiation.

The results from both the producer and consumer perspectives highlight, when taken together, the requirement for an enabling environment that supports agroecological value chains not only with technical training or financial resources but also with trust-building, cultural relevance, and social organization. Top-down policies will not ensure North Africa's agroecological transition. Local, inclusive projects are needed that empower both ends of the chain — improving the conditions for producers to operate sustainably and successfully and fostering informed demand among consumers who value agroecological foods.

The convergence of both studies highlights that while the potential for agroecological value chains is real, coherent actions need to be supported – organizing producers, reducing dependence on intermediaries, increasing awareness and trust in agroecological products, and promoting inclusive governance – especially with regard to women and marginalized groups. These results offer a solid basis for guiding future policies and interventions to support sustainable, equitable, and culturally connected food systems in North Africa.

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Appendixes

Appendixes

Appendix A. Short questionnaire for the nomination of value chains

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Guiding questions under NATAE Task 3.2 to be addressed to Living Lab Leaders prior to the organisation of bilateral meetings to identify existing Value Chains

Instructions

These questions have been prepared by the CIHEAM IAMM team responsible for the Task 3.2 under the NATAE project (Evaluating and strengthening the integration of AE value chains). These questions aim to guide the discussion planned with each of the Living Lab leaders as a way to help select two specific products (value chains) of interest in each territory.

We thank you in advance for your responses.

For your questions and return of responses:

- T3.2 leader: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

Partner institute name:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Date of filling responses:

Click or tap to enter a date.

Name of respondent:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Date of bilateral meeting with T3.2 leader, if known:

Click or tap to enter a date.

Name of Living Lab:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Q1. What are the specific* priority products you think should be studied in the territory of your corresponding Living lab and why? Please rank them from most to least important, explain the reasons why, and their main market scales.

Rank (by importance)	Main agricultural / agri-food product	Main reason(s)	Main market(s)
1	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____
2	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____

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3	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____
4	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____
5	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____
6	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> Regional <input type="checkbox"/> International <input type="checkbox"/> National Comments: _____

*List specific products rather than categories. For example: potatoes instead of vegetables.

Q2. Do you know any products produced in your area that are certified or reputable?
 (Certification may be in the form of official or non-official form).

- Yes, please explain Click or tap here to enter text.
 No

Q3. Which specific products would you nominate to be analysed under the NATAE project T3.2, and why? *You can choose up to two products:*

Nominated Product (Value Chain) nb.1:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Main reasons for this nomination:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Nominated Product (Value Chain) nb.2 (if any):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Main reasons for this nomination:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Thank you for your time

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Appendix B. Questionnaire for primary producers

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NATAE Task 3.2 Questionnaire

Targeted Value Chain Actors

Primary Producers in the Living Lab (add living lab name)

Value Chains of (add value chains selected)

INTRODUCTION

This questionnaire is prepared under the scope of the NATAE project Work Package 3 Task 3.1 (Evaluating and strengthening the integration of AE value chains). It is aimed at primary producers, i.e., farmers, in the six Living Lab territories under the project (in Mauritania, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco and Egypt). Responses collected from participants will help in building the understanding on the mapping, characteristics, and dynamics of the identified value chain from an agroecological perspective. This includes the capacity assessment of producers to become involved in systems that add value to their products following agroecological practices. The aim is to identify and analyse the priority value chains on which to focus development efforts, so as to guarantee their economic, environmental and social sustainability, in line with the main principles of agroecology. It also provides information on the value chain's mode of governance (collaborative or not), the distribution of the resulting benefits (equitability); autonomy/independence (financially, seeds, etc.); the know-how in place (cultural aspect); the farm's resilience (income diversity); and social performance (example: inclusion of women, people with disabilities, etc.).

This task is being led by the CIHEAM-IAMM. Findings under this task shall be consolidated in a Value Chain Analysis and Diagnosis Report and will be submitted to the Leader of the Work Package 3, the University of Thessaly, to be joined with the final Deliverable.

INSTRUCTIONS

Data collectors are requested to follow the below steps before starting any interview with the participant.

Step 1: Fill consent forms

You are provided with a standardized consent form which should be read and filled with the participant, including an introduction to the NATAE project.

Step 2: Introduce the project and objective of this questionnaire

Data collectors may use the above scope to introduce the participant to the specific objective of this questionnaire. General information on the NATAE project is found in the consent form.

Step 3: Start voice recording

Step 4: Start the interview and fill the questionnaire

For your questions

- T3.2 lead researcher: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate researcher: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

Disclaimer

This project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement no. 101084647. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. For the associated partner in the NATAE project, this work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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INTERVIEWER DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Contact information (phone/email):** _____
- **Date of interview:** _____
- **Name and country of the living lab:** _____

PARTICIPANT DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Address:** _____
- **Contact information (phone):** _____
- **Age:** _____ **Gender:** F M
- **Level of education:**
 - No formal education Primary Secondary
 - Higher education
- **Value Chain Product(s):** _____
- **Number of years of activity in this value chain:** _____
- **Participant Status:**
 - Independent Primary Producer
 - Member of a co-operative
 - Other, please specify _____
- **Registration Status**
 - Registered _____
 - Not registered
- **Type of land tenure:**
 - Land-owned Land rented Other, please specify _____
- **Role in the facility (if applicable for large operations):**
_____ (e.g., owner, partner, employee, etc.)

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Section 1 Overview of the participant's activity

Q1. Can you please introduce your business activity (including non-agricultural activity)?

Q2. *Do you apply or promote agroecological practices (that are environmentally friendly)? *For example: reduced of water consumption, reduced application of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, use of green energy or packaging, waste reduction, application of biological control, organic farming practices, etc.*

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q3. Do you have employees and/or do you recruit seasonal workers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Just me	<input type="checkbox"/> Me and my family	<input type="checkbox"/> Number of full-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of part-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of seasonal workers _____
----------------------------------	---	--	---	--

Q4. Regarding the family workforce, how many women are there? And what are their activities?

Q5. What is the main occupation(s) of employees and seasonal workers, if any?

Main occupation of employees: _____

Main occupation of seasonal workers: _____

Q6. What is the share (%) of women in the total number of employees and the total number of seasonal workers?

Share of women in total number of employees _____%

Share of women in the total number of seasonal workers _____%

Q7. What are their main activities? And are they decision-making positions?

Q8. Are there any employees with disabilities or undergoing rehabilitation / reintegration?

<input type="checkbox"/> Disabled Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> In Rehabilitation Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---	-----------------------------

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Q9. What is the average age range of employees and seasonal workers?

Average age: _____

Q10. On what basis are employees and seasonal workers compensated?

Q11. List the main products you produce (including animal products), and the estimated volume (tonne/year) for each product:

Section 2 Overview of the participant's activity in the value chain of this study

Q12. What makes you proud of your production? Example: quality, respect for the environment, autonomy, heritage, etc.

Q13. What is the total surface area of your farm and the share (%) of the area dedicated to the product(s) in the value chain ?

Total area under cultivation: _____ (hectares)
Surface area dedicated to the product of the value chain: _____ (%)

Q14. What is the average total production (tonnes/year) of the farm, and the share (%) of the production of the value chain product?

Production season: starts _____ and ends _____
Average size of production of the farm (total production; all products combined):
_____ (tonnes / year)
Value chain product production : _____ %

Q15. *How much do you estimate the volume of your losses per year from the post-harvest stage to the marketing stage? What are the reasons for these losses (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold goods, etc.)?

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Estimated loss of value chain product: _____ % of production

Reasons:

Q16. If you are a member of a cooperative, what is the share (%) of your production in this value chain that you dedicate to the cooperative?

Production dedicated to the cooperative: _____ %

Comments: _____

Q17. Do you sell primary products and/or process products? If you are processing (transforming), what is the % of fresh products that is being processed and into which product(s)?

<input type="checkbox"/> Primary Products	<input type="checkbox"/> Processed products
	% of fresh products being processed: _____
	List of processed products: _____

Q18. For processed products, do you have your own processing facilities, or do you use a processing company (ask for contact)?

Q19. What percentage of your total value chain production (specific product) that is being marketed?

Percentage of value chain production marketed: _____ %

Q20. For the part of the production that is not marketed, what is it used for? (Self-consumption, donations, etc.)

Q21. * Do you have by-products being generated from your production, if so, list these products and what they are used for?

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Q22. *Do you apply one or more of the following practices for the value chain of this study? Please check all that apply:

<input type="checkbox"/> Produce your own compost or manure	<input type="checkbox"/> Planned landscape for enhanced exosystemic services such as reforestation, natural habitat restoration, windbreaks, soil erosion control, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/> Apply purchased compost or manure	<input type="checkbox"/> Incorporated native crops
<input type="checkbox"/> Recycle or treat wastewater	<input type="checkbox"/> Applied crop rotation, how many _____
<input type="checkbox"/> Use green energy (e.g., solar panels) or bioenergy (e.g., biogas)	<input type="checkbox"/> Practiced agroforestry: integrating crop production and trees
<input type="checkbox"/> Use crop residues for other purposes (if yes, explain _____)	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal grazing
<input type="checkbox"/> Use drip irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/> Included crop and livestock systems
<input type="checkbox"/> Use of non-crop plants for ecological functions as water conservation, pest management, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Alley cropping with trees

Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q23. What qualities/values do you explain to your customers to promote the sale of your product?
Example: organoleptic qualities (taste), nutritional qualities (health), freshness, support for local production, respect for the environment, preservation of culinary heritage, solidarity, etc.

Q24. Is entering your products to the market profitable for you? Please explain your answer.

Q25. Considering your total turnover (all farm products combined), what is the share (in %) generated by the products of the value chain in this study?

Q26. Are you having difficulty finding outlets and accessing the market for the selling of your products? Please explain your answer.

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Q27. Are there competitors who sell the same product as you? If so, what are the effects of this competition on your business and what steps are you taking to deal with these competitors?
 Explain your answer

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	-----------------------------

Q28. In your opinion, what are the characteristics (qualities, prices, varieties, etc.) that differentiate your product from other producers?

Q29. Do you know what a 'certification' process entails? If so, how did you learn this?

Q30. Would you like to engage in a certification process (organic label, GPS, etc.)? Explain your answer.

Q31. Has your market activity grown in the last 5 years? If so, how?

Yes increased, explain _____

Remained stable, explain: _____

No decreased, explain: _____

Q32. Have your profits increased in the last 5 years? If so, by how much?

< 10% 10% to 30% 30% to 50% > 50% No growth

Section 4 Supply of production inputs in the value chain of this study

Q33. Do you use local or imported plants and/or seeds? And how do you source them? Explain your answer.

Local seeds/seedlings	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	Method of supply _____
-----------------------	------------------------------	-----------------------------	---------------------------

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Imported seeds/seedlings	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	Method of supply _____
--------------------------	------------------------------	-----------------------------	---------------------------

Q34. Who are your main suppliers for the production inputs (seeds, seedlings, fertilizers, compost, etc.) that you use in your agroecological (or similar) practices?

Type of Input Purchased	Supplier	Contact information

Q35. What are your main constraints for the supply of these inputs?

--

Section 5 Markets and marketing channels of the value chain being studied

• UNPROCESSED PRODUCTS

Q36. Where do you market your products of the value chain and at what estimated quantities of the total being sold?

Type of market (e.g., wholesale, intermediate, farmer's market, etc.)	Market location (local, regional, national)	Average distance in km	Estimated percentage of the quantity from total sales (%)	Estimated selling price (precise currency)	Contact information
<input type="checkbox"/> Intermediaries/middlemen					
<input type="checkbox"/> Wholesalers					
<input type="checkbox"/> Farmers' shops					
<input type="checkbox"/> Specialized shops (organic, etc.)					
<input type="checkbox"/> Farmers' markets, open markets, etc.					

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<input type="checkbox"/> Direct Farm Sales					
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g., relational network, friends, family, etc.) _____					

Q37. Are your marketing channels different depending on the varieties you produce? Explain your answer.

Q38. What elements do you take into account when choosing your marketing channels (e.g., price attained, transportation / logistics, etc.)?

Q39. Which of the above types of marketing channels is/are the most important to you and why? Explain your answer.

Q40. Is it important for you to diversify your marketing channels? Explain your answer.

Q41. For the options not chosen above, please explain why you do not seek them?

Q42. What is your main mode of transportation to market your products (e.g., personal van or rental, collective with other producers, other.)? Is it different depending on the marketing channels mentioned in the table above? Explain your answer.

Q43. What is the percentage of your transportation costs in relation to your selling price for each marketing channel listed in the table above?

Estimated transportation costs: _____ % of the selling price

Q44. *Describe the packaging (e.g., plastic bags, cardboard, recycled materials, etc.) that you use for each marketing channel listed in the table above.

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Q45. Where do you procure the inputs for the packaging of your products: packaging, labels, etc.?

Q46. What are your main constraints for the supply of packaging inputs (packaging, labels, etc.)?

• PROCESSED PRODUCTS

Q47. Where do you sell your (processed) products of the value chain and at what estimated quantities of the total being sold?

Type of market (e.g., wholesale, intermediate, farmer's market, etc.)	Market location (local, regional, national)	Average distance in km	Estimated percentage of the quantity from total sales (%)	Estimated selling price (precise currency)	Contact information
<input type="checkbox"/> Intermediaries/ middlemen					
<input type="checkbox"/> Wholesalers					
<input type="checkbox"/> Farmers' shops					
<input type="checkbox"/> Specialized shops (organic, etc.)					
<input type="checkbox"/> Farmers' markets, open markets, etc.					
<input type="checkbox"/> Direct Farm Sales					
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g., relational network, friends, family, etc.) _____					

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Q48. What elements do you take into account when choosing your marketing channels (e.g., price, transport, etc.)?

Q49. Which of the above types of marketing channels is/are the most important to you and why? Explain your answer.

Q50. Is it important for you to diversify your marketing channels? Explain your answer.

Q51. For the options not chosen above, please explain why you do not seek them?

Q52. What is your main mode of transportation to market your products (e.g., personal van or rental, collective with other producers, other.)? Is it different depending on the marketing channels mentioned in the table above? Explain your answer.

Q53. What is the percentage of your transport costs in relation to your selling price for each marketing channel listed in the table above?

Estimated transportation costs: _____ % of the selling price

Q54. *Describe the packaging (e.g., plastic bags, cardboard, recycled materials, etc.) that you use for each marketing channel listed in the table above.

Q55. Where do you procure the inputs for the packaging of your products: packaging, labels, etc.?

Q56. What are your main constraints for the supply of packaging inputs (packaging, labels, etc.)?

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• FOR BOTH PROCESSED AND UNPROCESSED PRODUCTS

Q57. When you sell in short circuits (farmers' shops, farmers' markets, farm sales, etc.), what is the profile of the consumers of your products, rural and/or urban?

Q58. What are the advantages of marketing in short circuits compared to other marketing channels?

Q59. What are the constraints and risks of marketing in short circuits?

Q60. Are you able to sell your products to urban consumers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain how and where: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No, explain why: _____
---	--

Q61. Does the selling price vary depending on whether you sell in an urban or non-urban market? If so, what are the reasons? And how much do you estimate this difference to be?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes Price higher by: _____ % Price lower by: _____ % Reasons: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q62. Are you the sole decision-maker when it comes to the choice of market/marketing channels?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No, explain: _____
------------------------------	---

Q63. Apart from short supply chains (direct consumer sales), what types of arrangements do you follow to market your products (formal, informal, verbal, other, etc.)?

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Q64. Who sets the selling prices of your products? Explain your answer.

Q65. What element(s) do you take into account when calculating the selling price of your products?

Q66. How would you describe your relationships and bargaining power with your customers (wholesalers, retailers, etc.)?

Q67. Do you think these relationships are transparent (access to price information, etc.) and trustworthy? Explain your answer

Q68. What measures would you propose to improve your bargaining power?

Q69. Do you see changes in prices during the same production season? If so, what are the reasons and consequences of this variation?

Q70. For the same product, how would you evaluate your selling price in relation to:

Other products produced conventionally:	
<input type="checkbox"/> Inferior	<input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated difference in percentage: _____ %
Other certified products (organic, participatory guarantee systems, etc.), indicate the type of certification: _____	
<input type="checkbox"/> Inferior	<input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated difference in percentage: _____ %

Q71. Do you think you are sufficiently informed about the characteristics of consumer demand (quality requirements, price, etc.)?

Q72. Do you usually participate in cultural events through your product? For example: community and social events, cultural promotion or educational events, etc.

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<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	-----------------------------

Section 6 Governance and organization

Q73. Are there any laws or regulations that you must comply with to market your products?

Q74. What motivates you to grow and market this product? (e.g., subsidies, certifications that improve the selling price, membership in a cooperative, etc.)

Q75. Are you a member of a collective structure/organization? If so, what type of structure (cooperative, union, etc.) and for what type of activities? (e.g., collection, marketing, etc.)

Q76. Do you have informal relationships with other producers or actors that facilitate your activities (e.g., harvesting, transportation, marketing, etc.) and the exchange of information? Explain your answer.

Section 7 Challenges, risks and opportunities of the value chain studied

Q77. What are the main obstacles and weaknesses you face in your production and marketing business?

Q78. Are there sources of support that contribute or could help alleviate these challenges? (e.g., government support, extension services, private support, etc.)

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, which ones: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No, explain
---	--------------------------------------

Q79. What are the main risks you face and what are you doing to reduce them?

Q80. Does your farming activity alone allow you to achieve financial independence?

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<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No, explain: _____
------------------------------	---

Q81. Do you think there are any current or future opportunities in the business of marketing agroecological products?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain	<input type="checkbox"/> No, explain: _____
---------------------------------------	---

Q82. Do you think that consumers are willing to pay a premium price for agroecological products and that there is market potential for agroecological products? Explain your answer.

--

Q83. What are your future plans for this type of production?

--

* Refers to questions that relate to agroecological assessment

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Appendix C. Questionnaire for intermediaries

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NATAE

Fostering agroecology transition in North Africa through multi-actor evaluation and networking

NATAE Task 3.2 Questionnaire

Draft Questionnaire under NATAE Task 3.2

Version of April 30, 2024

Targeted Value Chain Actor
Intermediaries and/or collectors

INSTRUCTIONS

Data collectors are requested to follow the below steps before starting any interview with the participant.

Step 1: Fill consent forms

You are provided with a standardized consent form which should be read and filled with the participant, including an introduction to the NATAE project.

Step 2: Introduce the project and objective of this questionnaire

General information on the NATAE project is found in the consent form.

Step 3: Take photos of the available products with a focus on packaging and labels

Step 4: Start the interview and fill the questionnaire

For your questions

- T3.2 lead researcher: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate researcher: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

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INTERVIEWER DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Contact information (phone/email):** _____
- **Date of interview:** _____
- **Name and country of the living lab:** _____

PARTICIPANT DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Address:** _____
- **Contact information (phone):** _____
- **Age:** _____ **Gender:** F M
- **Level of education:**
 - No formal education Primary Secondary
 - Higher education
- **Value Chain Product(s):** _____
- **Number of years of activity in this value chain:** _____
- **Type of structure:**
 - Private Cooperative Start-up Other, please specify _____
- **Role in the facility (if applicable for large operations):**
_____ (e.g., owner, partner, employee, etc.)

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Section 1 Overview of the participant's activity

Q1. Can you please introduce your business activity (including non-agricultural activity)?

Q2. *Do you apply agroecological practices (that are environmentally friendly)? *For example: reduced of water consumption, use of green energy (solar panels, etc.) or packaging, waste reduction/recycling, application of biological control, organic farming practices, etc.* Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q3. Do you have employees and/or do you recruit seasonal workers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Just me	<input type="checkbox"/> Me and my family	<input type="checkbox"/> Number of full-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of part-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of seasonal workers _____
----------------------------------	---	--	---	--

Q4. What is the main occupation(s) of employees and seasonal workers, if any?

Main occupation of employees: _____

 Main occupation of seasonal workers: _____

Q5. What is the share (%) of women in the total number of employees and the total number of seasonal workers?

Share of women in total number of employees _____%
 Share of women in the total number of seasonal workers _____%

Q6. What are the main activities of women? And are they decision-making positions? Describe and comment

Q7. Are there any employees with disabilities or undergoing rehabilitation?

<input type="checkbox"/> Disabled Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> In Rehabilitation Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---	-----------------------------

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Q8. List the main products you market and for each product, what is the estimated volume (Ton/year)? Describe and comment

Section 2 Overview of the participant's activity in the value chain of this study

Q9. Do you only market products (from the value chain studied) from agroecological practices (or similar, i.e. environmentally friendly practices) or also products (from the value chain studied) from conventional agricultural practices? Describe and comment

Q10. If you market both products (from the value chain studied) from agroecological practices (or similar i.e. environmentally friendly practices) and products (from the value chain studied) from conventional agricultural practices, what is the % distribution in the annual volume you market?

NOTE: THE REMAINDER OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE APPLIES ONLY TO AE PRODUCTS

Q11. What is the annual volume you market? (Tons/year)

Annual marketed volume of the value chain product: _____ (Tonnes/year)

Comments:

Q12. What percentage of the value-chain product(s) do you market in relation to your total annual turnover? Describe and comment

Percentage of value chain product marketed in relation to total turnover/year: _____ %

Marketing season: start on _____ and end on _____

Q13. *How much do you estimate the volume (in %) of your losses/waste per year until the marketing stage? Describe and comment

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Estimated loss/waste of value chain product: _____ % of volume traded
(tonnes/year)

Q14. What are the reasons for these losses/waste (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold items, etc.) and the impacts on your business? Describe and comment

Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q15. What qualities/values do you explain to your customers to promote the sale of your product?
Example: organoleptic qualities (taste), nutritional qualities (health), freshness, support for local production, respect for the environment, preservation of culinary heritage, solidarity, etc. Describe and comment.

Q16. Is marketing your products profitable for you? Describe and comment

Q17. Are you having difficulty finding outlets, accessing the market for the sale of your products? Describe and comment.

Q18. Are there competitors who sell the same product(s) as you? If so, which ones? Describe and comment

Q19. What are the effects of this competition on your business and what measures are you taking to face your competitors? Describe and comment

Q20. In your opinion, what are the characteristics (quality, price, varieties, etc.) that differentiate your product(s) from those of your competitors? Describe and comment

Q21. Do you sell products with certifications? Describe and comment

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<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: What type of certification: _____ What are the benefits of certification? <input type="checkbox"/> Improvement in the selling price: by how much _____ % <input type="checkbox"/> Reputation / recognition <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ Do you encounter any constraints? (If applicable) _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q22. Has your business grown in the last 5 years? If so, how?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain: <input type="checkbox"/> Decreasing, explain: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth Explain
---	---

Q23. Have your profits increased in the last 5 years? If so, by how much?

<input type="checkbox"/> < 10%	<input type="checkbox"/> 10% to 30%	<input type="checkbox"/> 30% to 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> > 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth, stable	<input type="checkbox"/> Decreased (specify by how much in %)
--------------------------------	-------------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------	--	---

Section 4 Governance and organizational factors

Q24. Are there any laws or regulations that you must comply with to sell your products? If so, are these rules binding? Describe and comment

Q25. Are you a member of a collective organization, interprofessional organization or another organization? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q26. Do you participate in networks or networking activities with, for example, producer groups, consumer networks? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

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Section 5 Supply Methods for the Value Chain Studied

Q27. Do you buy directly (i.e. without intermediaries) from local producers? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes Total number of producers: Annual Total Volume (tonnes): Advantages of this method of supply:	<input type="checkbox"/> No, why? _____
---	--

Q28. From which main profiles of local producers (e.g. small family farms, medium/large producers, etc.) do you get your supplies directly? Estimate the number of producers per profile. Describe and comment

Q29. What are the main criteria you take into account when sourcing directly from local producers (quality, price, quantity, others)? Describe and comment

Q30. If you source directly from local producers, on the basis of which elements is the price negotiated? and what is the main type of transaction (e.g. buying, selling on commission, other)? Describe and comment

Q31. If you source directly from local producers, do you take care of the harvest (standing purchases), transport, other functions? Describe and comment

Q32. If you source directly from local, what type of agreement (written contract, informal verbal agreement, other) do you follow and for what reasons? Describe and comment

Q33. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership (e.g. production contract) with the local producers from whom you source directly? If so, what does this collaboration consist of and what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q34. What type of suppliers **other than local producers in direct supply** do you work with for your supply? (e.g. producer, cooperative, collector, intermediary, etc.) Describe and comment

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Type of Provider	Number	Location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Volume share (%) of total supply	Type of transaction (e.g. purchase, standing purchase, commission sale, other, etc.)	Average purchase price/kg (specify currency)

Q35. What are your purchasing criteria and are they different depending on the type of supplier (listed in Table Q 34)? Describe and comment

Q36. What elements do you take into account when setting the purchase price? Are these elements different depending on the type of supplier? Describe and comment

Q37. Is your purchase price different depending on the type of supplier? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q38. How does the purchase price vary during the season, and are there other factors that affect the price variation? Describe and comment

Seasonal variation:

Purchase price: minimum: _____ maximum: _____ reason: _____

Other factors: _____

Q39. If you buy from producers through another intermediary instead of sourcing directly, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q40. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership with your suppliers? If so, which ones and what does this collaboration consist of, what are the advantages? Describe and comment

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Q41. For each type of supplier, do you have supply constraints (e.g. volume, quality, regularity of supply, price, etc.)? Describe and comment

Section 6 Logistics and Participant Loss/Waste in the Value Chain Studied

Q42. For each type of supplier (listed in Table Q 34), do you cover transport? If so, what modes of transport do you use? Describe and comment

Q43. Do you have your own means of transport or do you use logistics providers/intermediaries?

Q44. What is the estimated share (in %) of your transport costs in relation to your selling price? Describe and comment

Estimated transport costs: _____ % of the selling price

Q45. Do you take care of the storage of the products? If so, do you have your own storage facilities or do you use logistics providers? And what is the estimated cost (in %) in relation to your selling price? Describe and comment

In-house Logistics Provider

Type(s) of owned storage units: _____

Provider's storage unit type(s): _____

Estimated storage costs: _____ % of the sale price

Q46. Do your suppliers (listed in the table in Q34) have storage facilities? If so, what type of storage unit do they use (cold stores, etc.)? Describe and comment

Q47. What measures do you recommend to reduce your losses/waste? Describe and comment

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Q48. Do you have any constraints in logistics? If so, what do you recommend to lift these constraints?
 Describe and comment

Section 7 Markets and marketing channels in the value chain studied

Q49. What are your main types of customers (other wholesalers, restaurateurs, retail stores, etc.)?
 Describe and comment

Type of customer	Customer location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Share (%) in value of total sales	Average selling price/kg (specify in currency)	Coordinates

Q50. What are the purchasing criteria (specific quality, price, quantity, etc.) of your customers (listed in Table Q53) and are they different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q51. What elements do you take into account when setting the sale price? Are these elements different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q52. Is your selling price different depending on the type of customer? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q53. For the same product, how would you rate your selling price in relation to: Describe and comment

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Other products of conventional agriculture: <input type="checkbox"/> Lower <input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %
Other certified products (organic, Participatory Guarantee Schemes, etc.), indicate the type of certification: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> Lower <input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %

Q54. What elements do you take into account when choosing your customers (distance, price, means of transport, other) Describe and comment

Q55. Which of the types of customers are the most important to you? Describe and comment

Q56. Is it important for you to diversify your customers? Describe and comment

Q57. Are you the only decision-maker when it comes to customer choice? Describe and comment

Q58. If you sell directly to consumers, what are their main buying criteria? (e.g. price, quality, freshness, local product, other.) Describe and comment

Q59. What is the average selling price per kg (specify currency) when selling directly to consumers? And what is the % of this marketing channel in your total sales in value? Describe and comment

Q60. Is this selling price higher, lower or similar to other types of customers (listed in Table Q 53) Describe and comment

Q61. If you sell directly to consumers, what do you see as the main advantages and constraints of this marketing channel? Describe and comment

Q62. *For each type of customer (mentioned in Table Q49) what packaging (wooden crates, plastic crates, recycled materials, etc.) do you use? Describe and comment

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Q63. Do you have any constraints when it comes to sourcing packaging? Describe and comment

Section 8 Challenges, risks and opportunities of the participant in the value chain studied

Q64. What are the main constraints, risks, challenges (access to markets, organizational, other) that you face in your business? What measures are you taking to reduce them? Describe and comment

Q65. Are there sources of support that help you or could help you with the challenges you face? (e.g., government support, private support, etc.) Describe and comment

Q66. Do you think there are current or future market opportunities for agroecological (or similar) products? Describe and comment

Q67. If so, in your opinion, what are the levers/actions to be implemented to encourage the promotion of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q68. Do you think that your suppliers and customers are aware of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q69. Do you have any future plans for this type of product? Describe and comment

* Refers to questions that relate to agroecological assessment

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Appendix D. Questionnaire for wholesalers

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NATAE

Fostering agroecology transition in North Africa through multi-actor evaluation and networking

NATAE Task 3.2 Questionnaire

Draft Questionnaire under NATAE Task 3.2

Version of April 30, 2024

Targeted Value Chain Actor

Wholesalers

INSTRUCTIONS

Data collectors are requested to follow the below steps before starting any interview with the participant.

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Step 2: Introduce the project and objective of this questionnaire

General information on the NATAE project is found in the consent form.

Step 3: Take photos of the available products with a focus on packaging and labels

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For your questions

- T3.2 lead researcher: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate researcher: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

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INTERVIEWER DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Contact information (phone/email):** _____
- **Date of interview:** _____
- **Name and country of the living lab:** _____

PARTICIPANT DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Address:** _____
- **Contact information (phone):** _____
- **Age:** _____ **Gender:** F M
- **Level of education:**
 - No formal education Primary Secondary
 - Higher education
- **Value Chain Product(s):** _____
- **Number of years of activity in this value chain:** _____
- **Type of structure:**
 - Private Cooperative Start-up Other, please specify _____
- **Role in the facility:** _____ (e.g., owner, partner, employee, etc.)

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Section 1 Overview of the participant's activity

Q1. Can you please introduce your business activity (including non-agricultural activity)?

Q2. *Do you apply agroecological practices (that are environmentally friendly)? *For example: reduced of water consumption, use of green energy (solar panels, etc.) or packaging, waste reduction/recycling, application of biological control, organic farming practices, etc.* Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____ _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	-----------------------------

Q3. Do you have employees and/or do you recruit seasonal workers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Just me	<input type="checkbox"/> Me and my family	<input type="checkbox"/> Number of full-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of part-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of seasonal workers _____
----------------------------------	---	--	---	--

Q4. What is the main occupation(s) of employees and seasonal workers, if any?

Main occupation of employees: _____

 Main occupation of seasonal workers: _____

Q5. What is the share (%) of women in the total number of employees and the total number of seasonal workers?

Share of women in total number of employees _____%
 Share of women in the total number of seasonal workers _____%

Q6. What are the main activities of women? And are they decision-making positions? Describe and comment

Q7. Are there any employees with disabilities or undergoing rehabilitation?

<input type="checkbox"/> Disabled Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> In Rehabilitation Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---	-----------------------------

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Q8. How much do you estimate the total annual volume marketed (all products combined) by your business?

Total volume traded: _____ (tonnes/year)

Q9. List the main products you market and for each product, what is the estimated volume (Ton/year)? Describe and comment

Section 2 Overview of the participant's activity in the value chain of this study

Q10. Do you only market products (from the value chain studied) from agroecological practices (or similar, i.e. environmentally friendly practices) or also products (from the value chain studied) from conventional agricultural practices? Describe and comment

Q11. If you market both products (from the value chain studied) from agroecological practices (or similar i.e. environmentally friendly practices) and products (from the value chain studied) from conventional agricultural practices, what is the % distribution in the annual volume you market?

NOTE: THE REMAINDER OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE APPLIES ONLY TO AE PRODUCTS

Q12. What is the annual volume you market? (Tons/year)

Annual marketed volume of the value chain product: _____ (Tonnes/year)

Comments:

Q13. What percentage of the value-chain product(s) do you market in relation to your total annual turnover? Describe and comment

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Percentage of value chain product marketed in relation to total turnover/year: _____ %
Marketing season: start on _____ and end on _____

Q14. *How much do you estimate the volume (in %) of your losses/waste per year until the marketing stage? Describe and comment

Estimated loss/waste of value chain product: _____ % of volume traded
(tonnes/year)

Q15. What are the reasons for these losses/waste (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold items, etc.) and the impacts on your business? Describe and comment

Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q16. What qualities/values do you explain to your customers to promote the sale of your product?
Example: organoleptic qualities (taste), nutritional qualities (health), freshness, support for local production, respect for the environment, preservation of culinary heritage, solidarity, etc. Describe and comment.

Q17. Is marketing your products profitable for you? Describe and comment

Q18. Are you having difficulty finding outlets, accessing the market for the sale of your products? Describe and comment.

Q19. Are there competitors who sell the same product(s) as you? If so, which ones? Describe and comment

Q20. What are the effects of this competition on your business and what measures are you taking to face your competitors? Describe and comment

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Q21. In your opinion, what are the characteristics (quality, price, varieties, etc.) that differentiate your product(s) from those of your competitors? Describe and comment

--

Q22. Do you sell products with certifications? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: What type of certification: _____ What are the benefits of certification? <input type="checkbox"/> Improvement in the selling price: by how much _____ % <input type="checkbox"/> Reputation / recognition <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ Do you encounter any constraints? (If applicable) _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q23. Has your business grown in the last 5 years? If so, how?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain: <input type="checkbox"/> Decreasing, explain: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth Explain
---	---

Q24. Have your profits increased in the last 5 years? If so, by how much?

<input type="checkbox"/> < 10%	<input type="checkbox"/> 10% to 30%	<input type="checkbox"/> 30% to 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> > 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth	<input type="checkbox"/> Decreased (specify by how much in %)
--------------------------------	-------------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	---

Section 4 Governance and organizational factors

Q25. Are there any laws or regulations that you must comply with to sell your products? If so, are these rules binding? Describe and comment

--

Q26. Are you a member of a collective organization, interprofessional organization or another organization? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

--

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Q27. Do you participate in networks or networking activities with, for example, producer groups, consumer networks? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Section 5 Supply Methods for the Value Chain Studied

Q28. Do you buy directly (i.e. without intermediaries) from local producers? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes Total number of producers: Annual Total Volume (tonnes): Advantages of this method of supply:	<input type="checkbox"/> No, why? <hr style="border: 0; border-top: 1px solid black; margin-bottom: 10px;"/>
---	---

Q29. From which main profiles of local producers (e.g. small family farms, medium/large producers, etc.) do you get your supplies directly? Estimate the number of producers per profile. Describe and comment

Q30. What is the average distance in Km of these local producers from whom you buy directly? Describe and comment

Q31. What are the main criteria you take into account when sourcing directly from local producers (quality, price, quantity, others)? Describe and comment

Q32. What is the volume (tonnes/year) of your supply from local producers in direct supply? What is the share (%) of your total supply (by volume)? Describe and comment

Q33. If you source directly from local producers, on the basis of which elements is the price negotiated? and what is the main type of transaction (e.g. buying, selling on commission, other)? Describe and comment

Q34. What is the average purchase price/kg (specify currency) from these local producers?

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Q35. If you source directly from local producers, do you take care of the harvest (standing purchases), transport, other functions? Describe and comment

Q36. What type of agreement (written contract, informal verbal agreement, other) do you follow and for what reasons? Describe and comment

Q37. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership (e.g. production contract) with the local producers from whom you source directly? If so, what does this collaboration consist of and what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q38. What type of suppliers **other than local producers in direct supply** do you work with for your supply? (e.g. producer, cooperative, collector, intermediary, etc.) Describe and comment

Type of Provider	Number	Location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Volume share (%) of total supply	Type of transaction (e.g. purchase, standing purchase, commission sale, other, etc.)	Average purchase price/kg (specify currency)

Q39. What are your purchasing criteria and are they different depending on the type of supplier (listed in Table Q 38)? Describe and comment

Q40. What elements do you take into account when setting the purchase price? Are these elements different depending on the type of supplier? Describe and comment

Q41. Is your purchase price different depending on the type of supplier? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

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Q42. How does the purchase price vary during the season, and are there other factors that affect the price variation? Describe and comment

Seasonal variation:

Purchase price: minimum: _____ maximum: _____ reason: _____

Other factors: _____

Q43. If you buy from producers through an intermediary instead of sourcing directly, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q44. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership with your suppliers? If so, which ones and what does this collaboration consist of, what are the advantages? Describe and comment

Q45. For each type of supplier, do you have supply constraints (e.g. volume, quality, regularity of supply, price, etc.)? Describe and comment

Section 6 Logistics and Participant Loss/Waste in the Value Chain Studied

Q46. For each type of supplier (listed in Table Q 38), do you cover transport? If so, what modes of transport do you use? Describe and comment

Q47. Do you have your own means of transport or do you use logistics providers/intermediaries?

Q48. What is the estimated share (in %) of your transport costs in relation to your selling price? Describe and comment

Estimated transport costs: _____ % of the selling price

Q49. Do you take care of the storage of the products? If so, do you have your own storage facilities or do you use logistics providers? And what is the estimated cost (in %) in relation to your selling price? Describe and comment

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In-house Logistics Provider

Type(s) of owned storage units: _____

Provider's storage unit type(s): _____

Estimated storage costs: _____ % of the sale price

Q50. Do your suppliers (listed in the table in Q38) have storage facilities? If so, what type of storage unit do they use (cold stores, etc.)? Describe and comment

Q51. What measures do you recommend to reduce your losses/waste? Describe and comment

Q52. Do you have any constraints in logistics? If so, what do you recommend to lift these constraints? Describe and comment

Section 7 Markets and marketing channels in the value chain studied

Q53. What are your main types of customers (other wholesalers, restaurateurs, retail stores, etc.)? Describe and comment

Type of customer	Customer location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Share (%) in value of total sales	Average selling price/kg (specify in currency)	Coordinates

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Q54. What are the purchasing criteria (specific quality, price, quantity, etc.) of your customers (listed in Table Q53) and are they different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q55. What elements do you take into account when setting the sale price? Are these elements different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q56. Is your selling price different depending on the type of customer? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q57. For the same product, how would you rate your selling price in relation to: Describe and comment

Other products of conventional agriculture: <input type="checkbox"/> Lower <input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %
Other certified products (organic, Participatory Guarantee Schemes, etc.), indicate the type of certification: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> Lower <input type="checkbox"/> Similar <input type="checkbox"/> Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %

Q58. What elements do you take into account when choosing your customers (distance, price, means of transport, other) Describe and comment

Q59. Which of the types of customers (listed in Table Q 53) are the most important to you? Describe and comment

Q60. Is it important for you to diversify your customers? Describe and comment

Q61. Are you the only decision-maker when it comes to customer choice? Describe and comment

Q62. Do you sell your product(s) directly to consumers? If so, why? How and where (e.g. rural market, urban market, other)? Describe and comment

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Q63. If you sell directly to consumers, what are their main buying criteria? (e.g. price, quality, freshness, local product, other.) Describe and comment

Q64. What is the average selling price per kg (specify currency) when selling directly to consumers? And what is the % of this marketing channel in your total sales in value? Describe and comment

Q65. Is this selling price higher, lower or similar to other types of customers (listed in Table Q 53) Describe and comment

Q66. If you sell directly to consumers, what do you see as the main advantages and constraints of this marketing channel? Describe and comment

Q67. *For each type of customer (mentioned in Table Q53) what packaging (wooden crates, plastic crates, recycled materials, etc.) do you use? Describe and comment

Q68. Do you have any constraints when it comes to sourcing packaging? Describe and comment

Section 8 Challenges, risks and opportunities of the participant in the value chain studied

Q69. What are the main constraints, risks, challenges (access to markets, organizational, other) that you face in your business? What measures are you taking to reduce them? Describe and comment

Q70. Are there sources of support that help you or could help you with the challenges you face? (e.g., government support, private support, etc.) Describe and comment

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Q71. Do you think there are current or future market opportunities for agroecological (or similar) products? Describe and comment

Q72. If so, in your opinion, what are the levers/actions to be implemented to encourage the promotion of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q73. Do you think that your suppliers and customers are aware of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q74. Do you have any future plans for this type of product? Describe and comment

* Refers to questions that relate to agroecological assessment

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Appendix E. Questionnaire for retailers

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NATAE Task 3.2 Questionnaire

Draft Questionnaire under NATAE Task 3.2

Version of April 30, 2024

Targeted Value Chain Actor

Retailers (specialist shops, open-air markets, supermarkets, etc.)

INSTRUCTIONS

Data collectors are requested to follow the below steps before starting any interview with the participant.

Step 1: Fill consent forms

You are provided with a standardized consent form which should be read and filled with the participant, including an introduction to the NATAE project.

Step 2: Introduce the project and objective of this questionnaire

General information on the NATAE project is found in the consent form.

Step 3: Take photos of the available products with a focus on packaging and labels

Step 4: Start the interview and fill the questionnaire

For your questions

- T3.2 lead researcher: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate researcher: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

Disclaimer

This project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement no. 101084647. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. For the associated partner in the NATAE project, this work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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Estimated loss/waste of value chain product: _____ % of volume traded
(tonnes/year)

Q14. What are the reasons for these losses/waste (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold items, etc.) and the impacts on your business? Describe and comment

Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q15. What qualities/values do you explain to your customers to promote the sale of your product?
Example: organoleptic qualities (taste), nutritional qualities (health), freshness, support for local production, respect for the environment, preservation of culinary heritage, solidarity, etc. Describe and comment.

Q16. Is marketing your products profitable for you? Describe and comment

Q17. Are you having difficulty finding outlets, accessing the market for the sale of your products? Describe and comment.

Q18. Are there competitors who sell the same product(s) as you? If so, which ones? Describe and comment

Q19. What are the effects of this competition on your business and what measures are you taking to face your competitors? Describe and comment

Q20. In your opinion, what are the characteristics (quality, price, varieties, etc.) that differentiate your product(s) from those of your competitors? Describe and comment

Q21. Do you sell products with certifications? Describe and comment

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Section 1 Overview of the participant's activity

Q1. Can you please introduce your business activity (including non-agricultural activity)?

Q2. *Do you apply agroecological practices (that are environmentally friendly)? *For example: reduced of water consumption, use of green energy (solar panels, etc.) or packaging, waste reduction/recycling, application of biological control, organic farming practices, etc.* Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe <hr style="border: 0; border-top: 1px solid black; margin-top: 5px;"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	-----------------------------

Q3. Do you have employees and/or do you recruit seasonal workers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Just me	<input type="checkbox"/> Me and my family	<input type="checkbox"/> Number of full-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of part-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of seasonal workers _____
----------------------------------	---	--	---	--

Q4. What is the share (%) of women in the total number of employees and the total number of seasonal workers?

Share of women in total number of employees _____%
Share of women in the total number of seasonal workers _____%

Q5. What are the main activities of women? And are they decision-making positions? Describe and comment

Q6. Are there any employees with disabilities or undergoing rehabilitation?

<input type="checkbox"/> Disabled Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> In Rehabilitation Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---	-----------------------------

Q7. How much do you estimate the annual turnover (all products combined) of your business?

Q8. Do you have multiple points of sale? Describe and comment

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Section 2 Overview of the participant's activity in the value chain of this study

Q9. What is the annual volume you market? (Tons/year)

Annual marketed volume of the value chain product: _____ (Tonnes/year)
Comments:

Q10. What percentage of the value-chain product(s) do you market in relation to your total annual turnover? Describe and comment

Percentage of value chain product marketed in relation to total turnover/year: _____ %
Marketing season: start on _____ and end on _____

Q11. *How much do you estimate the volume (in %) of your losses/waste per year? And what are the reasons for these losses (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold items, etc.) and the impacts on your business? Describe and comment

Estimated loss/waste of value chain product: _____ % of volume traded (tonnes/year)

Q12. What are the reasons for these losses/waste (lack of storage facilities, cold chain, unsold items, etc.) and the impacts on your business? Describe and comment

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Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q13. What qualities/values do you explain to your customers to promote the sale of your product?
Example: organoleptic qualities (taste), nutritional qualities (health), freshness, support for local production, respect for the environment, preservation of culinary heritage, solidarity, etc. Describe and comment.

--

Q14. Is marketing your products profitable for you? Describe and comment

--

Q15. Are you having difficulty selling your products? Describe and comment.

--

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Q16. Are there competitors who sell the same product(s) as you? If so, which ones? Describe and comment

Q17. What are the effects of this competition on your business and what measures are you taking to face your competitors? Describe and comment

Q18. In your opinion, what are the characteristics (quality, price, varieties, etc.) that differentiate your product(s) from those of your competitors? Describe and comment

Q19. Do you sell products with certifications? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: What type of certification: _____ What are the benefits of certification? <input type="checkbox"/> Improvement in the selling price: by how much _____ % <input type="checkbox"/> Reputation / recognition <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ Do you encounter any constraints? (If applicable) _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q20. Has your business grown in the last 5 years? If so, how?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain: <input type="checkbox"/> Decreasing, explain: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth Explain
---	---

Q21. Have your profits increased in the last 5 years? If so, by how much?

<input type="checkbox"/> < 10%	<input type="checkbox"/> 10% to 30%	<input type="checkbox"/> 30% to 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> > 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth, stable	<input type="checkbox"/> Decreased (specify by how much in %)
--------------------------------	-------------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------	--	---

Section 4 Governance and organizational factors

Q22. Are there any laws or regulations that you must comply with to sell your products? If so, are these rules binding? Describe and comment

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Q23. Are you a member of a collective organization, interprofessional organization or another organization? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q24. Do you participate in networks or networking activities with, for example, producer groups, consumer networks? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Section 5 Supply Methods for the Value Chain Studied

Q25. Do you buy directly (i.e. without intermediaries) from local producers? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes Total number of producers: Annual Total Volume (tonnes): Advantages of this method of supply:	<input type="checkbox"/> No, why? <hr style="border: 0; border-top: 1px solid black; margin-bottom: 10px;"/>
---	---

Q26. From which main profiles of local producers (e.g. small family farms, medium/large producers, etc.) do you get your supplies directly? Estimate the number of producers per profile. Describe and comment

Q27. What is the average distance in Km of these local producers from whom you buy directly? Describe and comment

Q28. What are the main criteria you take into account when sourcing directly from local producers (quality, price, quantity, others)? Describe and comment

Q29. What is the volume (tonnes/year) of your supply from local producers in direct supply? And what is the share (%) of your total supply (by volume)? Describe and comment

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Q30. If you source directly from local producers, on the basis of which elements is the price negotiated? and what is the main type of transaction (e.g. buying, selling on commission, other)? Describe and comment

Q31. What is the average purchase price (specify currency) from these local producers?

Q32. If you source directly from local producers, do you take care of the transport, other functions? Describe and comment

Q33. What type of agreement (written contract, informal verbal agreement, other) do you follow and for what reasons? Describe and comment

Q34. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership (e.g. production contract) with the local producers from whom you source directly? If so, what does this collaboration consist of and what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q35. What type of suppliers **other than local producers in direct supply** do you work with for your supply? (e.g. producer, cooperative, collector, intermediary, etc.) Describe and comment

Type of Provider	Number	Location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Volume share (%) of total supply	Type of transaction (e.g. purchase, standing purchase, commission sale, other, etc.)	Average purchase price/kg (specify currency)

Q36. What are your purchasing criteria and are they different depending on the type of supplier (listed in the Table above)? Describe and comment

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Q37. What elements do you take into account when setting the purchase price? Are these elements different depending on the type of supplier? Describe and comment

Q38. Is your purchase price different depending on the type of supplier? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q39. Are there other factors that affect price variation? Describe and comment

Q40. What profile of producers do you mainly work with (e.g. small family farms, medium/large producers, producers' cooperatives, etc.), and estimate the number of producers? Describe and comment

Q41. If you buy from producers through an intermediary instead of sourcing directly, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q42. Do you have a collaboration/partnership with your suppliers? If so, which ones and what does this collaboration consist of, what are the advantages? Describe and comment

Q43. For each type of supplier (listed in the table above) do you have any supply constraints (e.g. volume, quality, regularity of supply, price, etc.)? Describe and comment

Section 6 Logistics and Participant Loss/Waste in the Value Chain Studied

Q44. For each type of supplier (listed in the table above), do you pay for transport? If so, what modes of transport do you use? Describe and comment

Q45. Do you have your own means of transport or do you use logistics providers/intermediaries?

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Q46. What is the estimated share (in %) of your transport costs in relation to your selling price?
Describe and comment

Estimated transport costs: _____ % of the selling price

Q47. Do you take care of the storage of the products? If so, do you have your own storage facilities or do you use logistics providers? And what is the estimated cost (in %) in relation to your selling price? Describe and comment

In-house Logistics Provider

Type(s) of storage units: _____

Estimated storage costs: _____ % of the sale price

Comments: _____

Q48. Have you implemented actions to reduce your losses/waste? Describe and comment

Q49. What measures do you recommend to reduce your losses/waste? Describe and comment

Q50. Do you have any constraints in logistics (transport, storage, other)? If so, what do you recommend to lift these constraints? Describe and comment

Section 7 Markets and marketing channels in the value chain studied

Q51. What are your main types of customers (consumers, professional customers e.g. restaurants, other)? Describe and comment

Type of customer	Customer location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Share (%) in value of total sales	Average selling price/kg (specify in currency)

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Q52. What are your customers' purchasing criteria (specific quality, price, quantity, etc.) (listed in the table above) and are they different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q53. What elements do you take into account when setting the sale price? Are these elements different depending on the type of customer? Describe and comment

Q54. Is your selling price different depending on the type of customer? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q55. For the same product, how would you rate your selling price in relation to: Describe and comment

Other products of conventional agriculture:

Lower Similar Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %

Other certified products (organic, Participatory Guarantee Schemes, etc.), indicate the type of certification: _____

Lower Similar Superior / Estimated Percentage Difference: _____ %

Q56. Which of the types of customers are the most important to you? Describe and comment

Q57. What are their main consumer purchasing criteria? (e.g. price, quality, freshness, local product, reputation of your point of sale, other.) Describe and comment

Q58. What is the profile of consumers? Describe and comment

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<input type="checkbox"/> Urban, <input type="checkbox"/> peri-urban, <input type="checkbox"/> tourist, <input type="checkbox"/> Other: Comments:
<input type="checkbox"/> Socio-professional category: Comment:

Q59. What are consumers' reasons for buying?

Q60. How would you assess the purchasing power of consumers? Describe and comment

Q61. *For each type of customer (mentioned in the table above) what packaging (wooden crates, plastic crates, recycled materials, etc.) do you use? Describe and comment

Q62. Do you have any constraints when it comes to sourcing packaging? Describe and comment

Section 8 Challenges, risks and opportunities of the participant in the value chain studied

Q63. What are the main constraints, risks, challenges (access to markets, organizational, other) that you face in your business? What measures are you taking to reduce them? Describe and comment

Q64. Are there sources of support that help you or could help you with the challenges you face? (e.g., government support, private support, etc.) Describe and comment

Q65. Do you think there are current or future market opportunities for agroecological (or similar) products? Describe and comment

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Q66. If so, in your opinion, what are the levers/actions to be implemented to encourage the promotion of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q67. Do you think that customers are aware of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q68. Do you have any future plans for this type of product? Describe and comment

* Refers to questions that relate to agroecological assessment

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Appendix F. Questionnaire for processing facilities

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NATAE

Fostering agroecology transition in North Africa through multi-actor evaluation and networking

NATAE Task 3.2 Questionnaire

Draft Questionnaire under NATAE Task 3.2

Version 23/07/ 2024

Targeted Value Chain Actor

Food Processors

INSTRUCTIONS

Data collectors are requested to follow the below steps before starting any interview with the participant.

Step 1: Fill consent forms

You are provided with a standardized consent form which should be read and filled with the participant, including an introduction to the NATAE project.

Step 2: Introduce the project and objective of this questionnaire

General information on the NATAE project is found in the consent form.

Step 3: Take photos of the available products with a focus on packaging and labels

Step 4: Start the interview and fill the questionnaire

For your questions

- T3.2 lead researcher: Fatima EL HADAD-GAUTHIER, elhadad@iamm.fr
- T3.2 post-doctorate researcher: Rita JALKH, jalkh@iamm.fr

Disclaimer

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INTERVIEWER DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Contact information (phone/email):** _____
- **Date of interview:** _____
- **Name and country of the living lab:** _____

PARTICIPANT DETAILS

- **First/last name:** _____
- **Address:** _____
- **Contact information (phone):** _____
- **Age:** _____ **Gender:** F M
- **Level of education:**
 - No formal education Primary Secondary
 - Higher education
- **Value Chain Product(s):** _____
- **Number of years of activity in this value chain:** _____
- **Type of structure:**
 - Private Cooperative Start-up Other, please specify _____
- **Role in the facility:** _____ (e.g., owner, partner, employee, etc.)

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Section 1 Overview of the participant's activity

Q1. Can you please introduce your business activity (including non-agricultural activity)?

Q2. *Do you apply agroecological practices (that are environmentally friendly)? *For example: reduced of water consumption, use of green energy (solar panels, etc.) or packaging, waste reduction/recycling, application of biological control, organic farming practices, etc.* Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, describe _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
---	-----------------------------

Q3. Do you have employees and/or do you recruit seasonal workers?

<input type="checkbox"/> Just me	<input type="checkbox"/> Me and my family	<input type="checkbox"/> Number of full-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of part-time employees _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No. of seasonal workers _____
----------------------------------	---	--	---	--

Q4. What is the main occupation(s) of employees and seasonal workers, if any?

Main occupation of employees: _____

 Main occupation of seasonal workers: _____

Q5. What is the share (%) of women in the total number of employees and the total number of seasonal workers?

Share of women in total number of employees _____ %
 Share of women in the total number of seasonal workers _____ %

Q6. What are the main activities of women? And are they decision-making positions? Describe and comment

Q7. Are there any employees with disabilities or undergoing rehabilitation?

<input type="checkbox"/> Disabled Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> In Rehabilitation Nb. _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	---	-----------------------------

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Q8. What type of processing do you carry out (drying, preserves, etc.) Describe and comment

Q9. What processing equipment do you have (traditional, modern, etc.)? Describe and comment

Q10. What is your total processing capacity (all products combined) (Tons)? Describe and comment

Q11. What is the total volume (all products combined) that you process (Tons/year)? Describe and comment

Q12. List the main products you process and for each product, what is the estimated volume (Ton/year)? Describe and comment

Section 2 Overview of the participant's activity in the value chain of this study

Q13. What is the annual volume you process of the value chain product specifically? (Tons/year) Describe and comment

Q14. *How much do you estimate the volume (in %) of your losses/waste per year compared to the total volume (tonnes) processed? Describe and comment

Estimated loss/waste of value chain product: _____ % of total volume processed (tonnes)

Q15. What are the reasons for these losses/waste (lack of storage facilities, cold chain and conservation, technological constraints, etc.) and the consequences on your business? Describe and comment

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Section 3 Perception of the marketing activity by the participant in the value chain studied

Q16. What types of processing do you carry out (drying, canning, etc.)? Describe and comment

Q17. Is your processing business profitable for you? Describe and comment

Q18. Are you having trouble finding customers? Describe and comment

Q19. Are there competitors who are processing the same product(s) as you? If so, who/what are these competitors? Describe and comment

Q20. What are the effects of this competition on your business and what measures are you taking to deal with it? Describe and comment

Q21. In your opinion, what are the characteristics of your business that differentiate you from your competitors? Describe and comment

Q22. Do you process products with certifications? Describe and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes: What type of certification: _____ What are the benefits of certification? <input type="checkbox"/> Improvement in the selling price: by how much _____% <input type="checkbox"/> Reputation / recognition <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ Do you encounter any constraints? (If applicable) _____	<input type="checkbox"/> No
--	-----------------------------

Q23. Has your business grown in the last 5 years? If so, how?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, explain:	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth
<input type="checkbox"/> Decreasing, explain: _____	Explain

Q24. Have your profits increased in the last 5 years? If so, by how much?

<input type="checkbox"/> < 10%	<input type="checkbox"/> 10% to 30%	<input type="checkbox"/> 30% to 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> > 50%	<input type="checkbox"/> No growth	<input type="checkbox"/> Decreased (specify by how much in %)
--------------------------------	-------------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	---

Section 4 Governance and organizational factors

Q25. Are there any laws or regulations (e.g. sanitary quality) that you must comply with in your processing activity? If so, which ones? Are these rules binding? Describe and comment

Q26. Do you have any certifications, quality standards? If so, what are the advantages/constraints of these certifications/standards for you? Describe and comment

Q27. Are you a member of a collective organization? interprofessional organization or another organization? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q28. Do you participate in networks or networking activities with, for example, producer groups? If so, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Section 5 Logistics and Participant Loss/Waste in the Value Chain Studied

Q29. Do you handle the storage of the products (raw and/or after processing)? If so, do you have your own storage facilities? Describe and comment

Q30. What measures do you recommend to reduce your losses/waste? Describe and comment

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Q31. As part of your processing activity, do you use by-products? If so, how (e.g. animal feed, compost, other) and does this recovery provide you with income? If not, why don't you value your by-products? Describe and comment

Q32. Do you have any constraints in the logistics field? Yes, what are they and what do you recommend to alleviate these constraints? Describe and comment

Section 6 Participant's customers in the value chain studied

Q33. Are you processing on behalf of producers? Describe (type of producers) and comment

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes Total number of producers: Annual total volume (tonnes):	<input type="checkbox"/> No, why? <input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>
---	--

Q34. If you work with local producers, what is their profile (e.g. small family farms, medium farms, large producers, etc.)? Estimate the number of producers according to the profile.

Q35. What is the average distance in Km of these local producers?

Q36. What is the volume (tons/year) that you process for local producers? And what is the share (in %) of this volume in the total volume you process? Describe and comment

Q37. On the basis of what criteria do you set the cost of processing for local producers? Describe and comment

Q38. What is the average cost/kg of processing (specify in foreign currency) for local producers?

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Q39. What types of packaging do you use (recycled packaging, etc...)?

Q40. Do you take over transport and/or other functions for local producers? Describe and comment

Q41. What type of agreement (written contract, informal verbal agreement, other) do you have with local producers? Describe and comment

Q42. Do you have a specific collaboration/partnership with local producers? If so, what does this collaboration entail and what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Q43. Who are your customers **other than the local producers** for whom you process their products? (producers, producer cooperatives, wholesalers, etc.)

Type of customer	Customer location (local, regional, national)	Avg. distance. (Km)	Volume (tonnes)	Share (%) in value of total turnover	Processing cost /kg (specify in currency)	Transaction Type (written agreement, informal, etc.)

Q44. What elements do you take into account when selecting your types of clients (listed in Table Q.43)? Describe and comment

Q45. Which of the types of customers (listed in the table above) are the most important to you? Describe and comment

Q46. Is it important for you to diversify your customers? Describe and comment

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Q47. Is your processing cost different depending on the type of customer? If so, what are the reasons? Describe and comment

Q48. If you package the products, is the packaging different for different customers (listed in Table Q.43)?

Q49. Does the cost of processing vary over the course of the season, and are there other factors that affect this price variation? Describe and comment

Seasonal variation:

Purchase price: minimum: _____ maximum: _____ reason: _____

Other factors: _____

Q50. Do you have a collaboration/partnership with your clients (listed in Table Q.43)? If so, which ones and what does this collaboration involve, what are the benefits? Describe and comment

Section 7 Challenges, risks and opportunities of the participant in the value chain studied

Q51. What are the main constraints, risks, challenges (access to markets, organizational, other) that you face in your business? What measures are you taking to reduce them? Describe and comment

Q52. Are there sources of support that help you or could help you with the challenges you face? (e.g., government support, private support, etc.) Describe and comment

Q53. Do you think there are current or future market opportunities for agroecological (or similar) products? Describe and comment

Q54. If so, in your opinion, what are the levers/actions to be implemented to encourage the promotion of this type of product? Describe and comment

Q55. Do you think that consumers are aware of this type of product? Describe and comment

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Q56. Do you have any future plans for this type of product? Describe and comment

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Appendix G. Questionnaire for consumer behaviour assessment

QUESTIONNAIRE

Determining Awareness about AgroEcological practices

Agroecology is the science of applying ecological concepts and principles to manage interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment for food security and nutrition. All over the world farmers already apply this approach, which has a fundamental pillar in traditional and local knowledge.

Source: <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/knowledge/practices/en/>

PART I: Demographic Characteristics

1. Age:
2. Gender: Male Female Other
3. Work status: Unemployed Employed Student Retired
4. Average monthly income : Not satisfactory , Satisfactory , Very satisfactory
5. Number of adult household members
6. Number of children in household:
7. Country of origin:
8. Your household live in: Rural area , Peri urban area Urban area
9. Educational Level:
No formal education 1
Elementary school graduate 2
High school graduate 3
Bachelor Degree 4
Master/ PhD Degree 5

PART II:

10. Environmental issues

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about problems related to environmental issues 1 = Totally disagree, 2= Disagree 3 = Neutral, 4= Agree, 5 = Totally agree

10.1	Environmental problems are exaggerated	
10.2	Science and technology can solve all environmental problems	
10.3	Rich countries are responsible for solving the environmental problems of the world	
10.4	Protecting the environment should be a higher priority for inhabitants	
10.5	The protection of the natural environment can be achieved by each of us	
10.6	Human activity is damaging for the environment	
10.7	I am worried about global warming	
10.8	In general, I am worried about the decrease of plants, trees and species on Earth (biodiversity loss)	
10.9	Environmental protection is more important than economic growth	
10.10	There is a high need to protect natural resources for next generations	
10.11	We should consider the environment's impact prior to addressing any problem	
10.12	Since natural resources (such as sun, wind, and water) can never be exhausted, energy will never run out on this planet	
10.13	Optimised use of water and energy is important for the sustainable use of natural resources	
10.14	The benefits of technology are greater than its harmful side effects	
10.15	Consuming locally produced food can be beneficial for the natural environment	
10.16	Environmental protection is more essential than economic development.	
10.17	We can accept changes in our lifestyles to protect natural resources	

11. Environmental attitude

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

1 = Totally disagree, 2= Disagree 3 = Neutral, 4= Agree, 5 = Totally agree

11.1.	Educating the public about the environment can help to solve environmental problem	
11.2	When I buy a product, I assess the type of packaging and choose the one that is recyclable	
11.3	I choose to purchase locally produced food	
11.4	I am willing to adopt environmentally friendly agricultural practices	
11.5	Natural resources should be saved for the benefits of future generations	

12. Agroecological practices

Please answer the following questions, using the 1-5 scale, with 1 = Totally disagree, 2= Disagree 3 = Neutral, 4= Agree, 5 = Totally agree

112.1.	I am familiar with agroecological practices	
12.2	I believe agroecological practices are important for sustainable agriculture	
12.3	I believe that agroecological practices are beneficial for my health	
12.4	I know about the environmental benefits of agroecological practices	
12.5	I believe that agroecology can improve the quality of natural resources	
12.6	I believe that consuming locally produced food is beneficial for the environment	
12.7	I am aware of policies or programs in my country/region that promote or support agroecological practices	
12.8	I believe that crop rotation contributes to soil health	
12.9	I am aware of the role of cover crops in reducing soil erosion and improving soil fertility	
12.10	I believe that planting more trees on farms, an integrating trees to crop cultivation will contribute to enhance soil quality, & plants and animal diversity	
12.11	I am aware of the benefits of integrating livestock into cropping systems	
12.12	I am aware of the benefits of reducing agrochemicals usage in farming	

12. Willingness to pay

12.1 Are you willing to support agroecological practices via purchasing foodstuff certified as such?

YES NO

12.2 Taking into account the type of products you usually buy, please answer if you would pay more or less, for the following:

Product	Willingness To Pay				
	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Cereals produced under agroecological practices	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Olive oil produced under agroecological practices	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Locally produced vegetables	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Locally produced dairy products	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Meat products produced under agroecological practices	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Organic fruits	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Locally produced fruits	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%
Aromatic and medicinal plants and essential oils under agroecological practices	-20%	-10%	0	+10%	+20%

Thank you for your time!

Appendix H: List of published materials related to Social Acceptability

- Adamsone-Fiskovica, A., & Grivins, M. (2024). Understanding the potential of sustainability turn in farming: review of sociotechnical adoption factors of agri-environmental cropping practices. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 39, e16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170524000085>
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Appendix I: Questionnaire for Living Lab leaders

Interview with the Living Labs Leaders

Date: May 2nd 2024

Leader Name:

Affiliation:

Contact infos:

- E-mail:
- Phone:
- Address:
- Other:

Preparatory Arrangements

The farmers' workshop was completed on...../.../.....=

Is the report available? Yes () No ()

The board representatives' workshop was completed on...../.../.....

Is the report available? Yes () No ()

The diagnostic analysis report conclusion.

.....
.....
.....
.....

Data about the lab.

Location.

Area in hectares.

Number of farms.....nd farmers.....

Average area of the farms in the LL (The typology if done?).....hectares

List the AEPs recommended and selected in the two workshops (by crop or other measure) and at each of the following levels):

- At farm
- At value chain
- At LL level

Practice	Description	Level		
		Farm	Value Chain	L.L.
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				
5.				
Other				

Partners committed to contribute to implementation of the experimentation phase.

- 1.....
- 2.....
- 3.....
- 4.....
- 5.....
- 6.....

Role of each partner in the experimentation phase.

Partner #	Role	Notes

Date and duration of the awareness campaign (AC) provided to the farmers.

Who delivered that awareness campaign?

Has any partner attended the AC?

Topics covered in the AC:

-
-
-
-

Information related to the respondents

Total number of the farmers at the Territory level.....

Total number of the farmers in the living lab level.....=

Total number of the farmers in the living lab attended/exposed to the AC.....=

How many farmers could be met to fill the questionnaire (Excluding all those who Exposed to the Awareness campaign.....

The duration, date and time suitable to interview the farmers to respond to the survey?

- Duration..... days
- Date: ././.
- Time: Noon () / afternoon() / in the field () / Else- Mention

Data Collection and Manipulation

How many field-data collectors could be recruited?.....

Their previous experience in data collection: None () immature () fair () Good ()
Very High ()

How many of them are familiar with data processing using either SPSS or Excel sheets?.....

How many could be trained for using new data management application(s)?

Appendix J: Questionnaire of SA assessment Survey

1. Location of living lab:.....The farmer's name (Optional).....

Section (1): Farmers' socio-economic characteristics:

2. Age:years

3. Gender: Male Female

4. Formal years of education:

5. Average monthly expenditures of household.....(identify currency)

6. Which of the following sources of income are applicable to you?

Source	%	Source	%
1) cropping		2) Government assistance	
3) livestock		4) Labor in other farms	
5) Off-farm activities		6) Rentals	
7) Overseas transactions		8) In-kind aids	
9) Investments		10) Other, please specify	
11) Pension			

Respondent can select more than one option with mentioning the percentage of income from each source

7. To what extent do your current income covers your needs.....

1) Not adequate	2) Adequate	3) Highly adequate
-----------------	-------------	--------------------

8. To what extent do you feel secured with your current income

1) Not secured	2) Secured	3) Very secured
----------------	------------	-----------------

9. Number of household members:

10. Household family type:

1) nuclear	2) compound	3) extended
------------	-------------	-------------

11. Do you have a secondary job besides agriculture: yes no → 13
 12. If yes, please specify:.....

13. For how long have you practiced agriculture? years

14. Have you ever received any support from any NGOs, research, or governmental agencies/ programs? yes no → Part 2

15. If yes, please specify the kind of support (e.g., financial, technical, material, etc.) and source (e.g., NGO) :

NGO		Government	
Source	kind of support	Source	kind of support

Secion (2): Farm characteristics:

16. Area of the farmland (in hectare):

Owned:.....	Rented:.....	Other:
Please specify any other types of tenure and size		

17. Which crops do you cultivate the last 2/3 years?

Summer		Winter		Perennials	
Crop	Area	Crop	Area	Crop	Area
.....
.....
.....

18. Farm Labor (in number)?

Type	Family		Waged	
	Males	Females	Males	Females
Permanent				
Casual (l/d)				
Seasonal (l/d)				

19. Do you have any type of livestock that are considered important enterprise on your farm? Yes No → 21

20. If yes, please specify,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,,

Type	Number
Dairy	
Beef	
Sheep	
Pigs	
Poultry	
Other	

21. To what extent do you engage your household members in any decisions related to your farming activities? Rarely () Occasionally () Frequently ()

22. Please specify soil type of the farm (Please Specify).
Clay () Silt () Sand () Loam () Chalk () Other ()

23. What is your estimate of the average annual cost of agricultural activities in your farm per hectare the last year?

24. Which of the following sources of your financial expenditure on agricultural activities are applicable to you (please mention the contribution of each source in %)

Source	%	Source	%
1) Cropping		2) Government subsidy	
3) Livestock		4) Working in other farms	
5) Off-farm activities		6) Rentals	
7) Overseas transactions		8) Bank loans	
9) Contracted farming		10) In kind aids (grants)	
11) Investments		12) Other, please specify	
13) Pension			

Respondent to select more than one option with with a total of 100% from all sources

25. Do you have any specific support of your farming activities right now from any program/project? Yes No → 27

26. If yes, specify

27. Please specify your current farming practices per crop

Crop	Farming Activity					
	Land Preparation ¹	Fertilization ²	Irrigation ³	Weeding ⁴	Pest Control ⁵	Harvesting ⁶
Crop 1:						
Crop 2:						
Crop 3:						
Crop 4:						

- (1) Mechanisation/manual labor in land preparation
- (2) Chemical/organic (composting) fertilizers
- (3) Surface/sprinkler/drip irrigation or rain fed
- (4) Chemical/biological/manual/integrated weed control
- (5) Chemical/biological/manual/integrated pest control
- (6) Mechanisation/manual labor in harvesting

28. How much of your production is used for the following purposes?

Purpose	Percentage of crop* production %					
	Crop 1	Crop 2	Crop 3	Crop 4	Crop 5	Crop 6
Family consumption						
Local market						
External market						

*could be plant (field crop/vegetable), horticulture, or animal production

29. Which of the following practices did you implement in your farm the last two seasons?

Crop	AEPs												
	Crop Rotation	Crop Association	Raised Bed Cultivation	Water Source Management	Biological Control of Pests and Diseases	Composting	Integrated Pest Management	Organic Fertilizers	Phytosanitary Treatments Based on Natural Products	Crop and Livestock Integration	Agroforestry	Adoption of Salinity Resistant Varieties	Other, specify

30. How much time do you take to reach your farm from your home?.....hour

Section (3): Social acceptability: AEPs' Information, knowledge, risks and attitude regarding AEP.

31. Sources and accessibility to AE agricultural information:

Information About	Accessible yes=1 No=0	Source (Radio, tv, social media, official websites, extension agents, other (please specify)	Frequency How often do you access this info? (per year)
Best Inputs prices			
Best inputs suppliers			
Best time for planting			
Weather forecast			
Best harvesting time			
Best market channels			
Best market prices			
Higher yield seed varieties			
Government/ NGO programs			

32. To what extent do you rate the Suitability, credibility, and sufficiency of AE agricultural information? (On a scale from 1 up to 3)

Information	Sufficient to answer your worries.	Credible (trustful)	Suitable	Conflicting with other sources/ inconsistent
Best Inputs prices				
Best inputs suppliers				
Best time for planting				
weather forecast				
Best harvesting time				
Best market channels				
Best marketing prices				
Higher yield seed varieties				
Government/ NGO programs				

33. **(Risk assessment) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (On a scale from 1 up to 5)**

(Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Statement	Score
1. Avoiding using agrochemicals represents a risk to me (yield drop).	
2. The recommended AEP package would increase the cost of your farm's activities.*	
3. Implementing the recommended practices requires more labors.*	
4. Implementing the recommended practices requires more effort and time to manage weeds and pests.*	
5. Adopting AEP requires dealing with different stakeholders from outside my already existed trusted network	
6. Access to the market of AE products is not easy for me	

34. **(knowledge) To what extent do you agree with the following statements?**

(On a scale from 1 up to 5) (Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Practice	Related knowledge	Score
Crop rotation: the succession of crops grown on the same plot of land.	1. Reduces the spread of disease and parasites.	
	2. preserves soil fertility and therefore increases productivity	
	3. ensures that crops are always present on the plot, helping to curb the development of undesirable weeds and reduce soil erosion.	
	4. allows you to optimize the input of compost according to your needs.	
Crop association (intensefication): Several plants are put together to support each other.	5. Sowing certain other plants helps scare away pests.	
	6. Combining plants helps improve the health of another plant.	
	7. Combining "legumes" with another plant helps add nitrogen to the soil.	
	8. There are companion plants that reinforce each other.	
	9. Combining strong-smelling ornamental plants helps repel insect pests from neighboring plants	
	10. There are companion plants that helps shade another plant.	
Crop and livestock integration: production of	11. Using animal waste as fertilizers helps increase soil fertility	

fodder, recycling animal waste to produce fertilizers, and using animal energy (tillage, transport, extraction, processing of agricultural products).	12. Using animal waste as fertilizers helps reach greater self-sufficiency	
	13. Using organic animal fertilizers helps avoid greenhouse gas emissions linked to the use of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers	
	14. Using Agricultural and forestry produce for fodder helps reaching greater self-sufficiency	
	15. Using Agricultural and forestry produce for fodder helps reaching better nutritional quality.	
	16. Utilizing farm animals in agricultural activities (e.g., tillage and transportation) helps reduce hired labors and costs	
Agroforestry: the planting, maintenance, and use of trees/hedges in the fields and reforestation.	17. Planting trees in the field helps improving water availability (groundwater capture, protection against erosion, shading to limit evapotranspiration	
	18. Planting trees in the field has no effect on soil fertility*	
	19. Agroforestry has no role in combating climate change *	
Soil and water conservation: soil cover and protection practices (keeping crop residues on the surface, catch crops, mulching), organic matter burial practices (manure, crop residues), trough and half-moon cultivation practices, contour sowing practices.	20. The mentioned practices have no effect on climate change (carbon storage)*	
	21. The mentioned practices have no effect on soil fertility*	
	22. The mentioned practices help control erosion	
Biological control: other alternatives to pesticides, including Phyto-stimulant (stimulating plants' natural defenses against diseases and pests), Repellent (making cultivated plants undesirable to their predators), and Biocides.	23. Using biological control is not healthy*	
	24. Using biological control is harmful to the environment*	
	25. Biopesticides are only preventive products that can't cure crops after infections with aphids, pests, or mites*	
Farm-saved seeds: mass selection of seeds, seed cultivation and conservation, exchanges between farmers, experimentation with new species and varieties.	26. Seeds production help reduce seed purchases.	
	27. Seeds production guarantees a healthy origin.	
	28. Seeds production helps select a well-adapted variety to your environment.	
<p>*Adverse scoring: totally agree = 1, agree = 2, neutral = 3, disagree=4, totally disagree=5</p> <p>The statements listed in these questions are all derived from the NATAE's D7.3, use only the AE practices applied in the surveyed LL.</p>		

35. (Attitude) To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the AEP package recommended in your living lab?

(On a scale from 1 up to 5) (Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Dimension	Statement	score
Cognition	1. When needed, information related to market prices, opportunities to sell crops, planting/harvesting techniques are not accessible*	
	2. When needed, required trainings to implement agroecological practices are available.	
	3. There are available markets (buyers, collectors, traders, consumers) for the agroecological crops.	
	4. There are available suppliers for the required inputs (seeds, fertilizers, etc.).	
	5. There are partners (input suppliers, buyers, extensions workers, agricultural cooperatives) are ready to support you during your farm transitioning.	
	6. The available markets of agroecological products are accessible to me.	
	7. If needed, labors are available.	
Affection	8. The long-term benefits worth all the initial difficulties that I would encounter.	
	9. On the long-term, the benefits expected from transitioning to AE agriculture are higher than the paid costs.	
	10. Agro-ecological crops have competitive advantage over conventionally grown crops in the market.	
Intentional behavior	11. The initial costs will be increased but I can afford them.	
	12. Despite the long-term benefits I would receive, I'm not intended to implement these practices.*	
*Adverse scoring: totally agree = 1, agree = 2, neutral = 3, disagree=4, totally disagree=5		

Local NGOs - - -									
International NGOs - - -									
Agricultural bank - - -									
Traders - - -									
Other agencies (please specify) - - -									

Section (5): Capacity building and conditional incentives

37. (capacity building) To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

(Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Statement	score
1. I have received different types of trainings (demonstration fields, field schools, workshops) on AE transitioning.	
2. These training involved different types of demonstrating materials (posters, pictures, drawings)	
3. The discussions during these trainings/workshops were suitable to my needs.	
4. I was able to express myself freely during these meetings	
5. These trainings enhanced my market skills.	
6. These trainings enhanced my agricultural behavior	
7. These trainings enriched my knowledge about AE polices and regulations in my territory	
8. These trainings helped me build linkages with other farmers	
9. These trainings helped me build linkages with different stakeholders (extension workers, suppliers, sellers, academics, etc.,)	

38. (conditional incentives) Do you expect getting any of the following benefits during your AE transitioning? Yes = 1, No= 0

Incentives	Rating
1. Subsidized loans	
2. Grants	
3. Tools	
4. Cost sharing arrangements	
5. Price guarantees	
6. inputs	
7. free services	

39. (institutional arrangements) To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (On a scale from 1 up to 5) (Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Statement	score
There are national policies supports agroecological transitioning.	
There are sufficient provision of AE-related extension services	
The national policies mainly focus on increasing food production and sufficiency through conventional agriculture. *	
There are NGO programs supports your transitioning.	

The national policies do not support farmers*	
The state integrates different stakeholders from market, NGOs, farmers, government to support agroecological transitioning	
There are entities offers a certification for agroecologically produced crops	
National polices integrates information and communication technology into extension services	
Farming published documents are transparent regarding the AE-related data	
*Adverse scoring: totally agree = 1, agree = 2, neutral = 3, disagree=4, totally disagree=5	

Section (6): Social trust

40. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

(Totally disagree = 1, disagree= 2, neutral= 3, agree= 4, totally agree= 5)

Stakeholder	This stakeholder has a good reputation	I choose to deal with this stakeholder because I trust him	I deal with this stakeholder because there is no other alterative	I will never deal with this stakeholder again. (would you please explain why?)
Input suppliers				
Research institute				
Farm cooperative associations				
Governmental entities				
Extension workers				
Local NGOs				
International NGOs				
Agricultural bank				
traders				

Other (please specify)				
------------------------	--	--	--	--

41. Are there any of your neighbors who has already committed to agroecological practices? Yes () No () End
42. In case of yes, has this encouraged you to try AEP in your own farm? Yes () No ()

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